

- PhD dissertation -

Disruptive financing innovation: an analysis of financing fintech services to
SMEs and LMEs in Germany

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Declaration

I declare that the work undertaken for this PhD dissertation as well as the writing of the final dissertation was done by myself.

This PhD dissertation has not been submitted for another comparable academic award.

Title of Dissertation:

Disruptive financing innovation: an analysis of financing fintech services to SMEs and LMEs in Germany

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Abstract

In a widely used context, fintechs can be considered as an enabling disruptive innovation in financial services and markets. Germany is the second largest fintech market in Europe after the UK. Fintechs that provide financing services with financial return for the investors are crowdlending, crowdinvesting, and factoring platforms. These kinds of fintechs are defined as financing fintechs. The overall aim of this research is to critically examine the potential disruptive innovation threat of financing fintechs that provide services to small-and-medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in Germany to traditional banks. After the conduction of a narrative literature review, this research is based on a qualitative multi-method approach. Financing fintech is a new phenomenon, which implies that the topic is relatively unexplored. Therefore, to gain an in-depth understanding and a holistic picture of the topic to evaluate the potential disruptive innovation, a qualitative approach was selected. First, based on a total population sampling strategy, the business model of 21 financing fintechs that provide services to SMEs in Germany was appraised in depth by the material of the financing fintechs' web-presences and the application of a qualitative content analysis. Second, ten semi-structured expert interviews with executive managers of large mid-sized companies (LMEs) which have an annual turnover between 50 and 500 mn€ were conducted to critically explore and evaluate to which extent the service of financing fintechs is a substitute for traditional banking services to LMEs in Germany. Disruptive innovation is a theory that shows how entrants can disrupt incumbents by either creating new markets or reshaping existing markets – the technology itself is less intrinsically disruptive in character, rather it is the business model that enables the disruptive impact. First, the entrants serve low-end or non-customers, while finally as the performance improves, they serve mainstream customers. The incumbents do not consider the entrants as threat until the disruption is in its final stage because the entrants firstly serve the less-attractive customers. In case the entrant's service or product is a substitute for the incumbent's service or product, it can be a critical disruption which can finally lead to a liquidation of the incumbent. LMEs can be considered as mainstream customers because the traditional banks' major focus is not on smaller SMEs, which are the least profitable customers. The results show that although there are indications of a disruptive innovation, the disruptive innovation is limited due to structural reasons in the business model of financing fintechs and the services required from the executives of LMEs in Germany – especially higher transaction costs and information asymmetries and the risk of sending negative signals disable the substitution.

Key words: Fintechs, Financial Innovations, Alternative Finance, Strategic Management, Traditional Banking, Small-and-Medium-Sized Corporates, Empirical Studies.

JEL-Classifications: D22, G20, M13.

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1 Introduction

The purpose of this chapter is to provide background information of the research topic under study and to present the research problem, aim, questions, objectives, and scope. Additionally, it outlines the research methodology and methods to achieve the research aim and objectives and to answer the research questions. The structure of this study is also illustrated.

1.1 Background and research problem and aim

In 1994, Bill Gates, co-founder of Microsoft, supposedly said that “banking is necessary, banks are not” (Filkorn, 2015). Today, traditional banks face different challenges such as low margins due to the low interest environment, higher regulatory requirements due to the financial crisis in 2007-2009, a changing customer behaviour due to the technology development, and new financial providers like fintechs and bigtechs that enter the market (European Banking Authority, 2018; Financial Stability Board, 2017; Nicoletti, 2017; Paulet & Relano, 2017).

Fintechs are newly founded technology-driven companies that provide financial services and products (Dorfleitner, Hornuf, Schmitt, & Weber, 2016). The terminology is a neologism that originates from finance and technology (Gomber, Koch, & Siering, 2017; Puschmann, 2017; Tiberius & Rasche, 2017). Currently, there is no universal academic definition of fintech (Dorfleitner et al., 2016). The Financial Stability Board defines fintech “as technology-enabled innovation in financial services that could result in new business models, applications, processes or products with an associated material effect on the provision of financial services” (2017, p. 7). Schueffel analysed different databases in order to find a definition that contains the major commonalities in more than 200 academic studies (2016). According to Schueffel, a fintech is “a new financial industry that applies technology to improve financial activities” (2016, p. 1). The term describes the connection of mainly internet-based technologies with established business activities of the financial industry. In contrast, bigtechs imply large technology-driven companies that initially started in other industries like Amazon, Apple, Facebook or Google and then started financial activities on the payment market and by now also partly enter the financing market (Basel Committee of Banking Supervision, 2017; Demertzis, Merler, & Wolff, 2018).

According to Dorfleitner et al., fintechs can be categorised by the following four segmentations: Financing, asset management, payment services, and others (2016). The financing segmentation can be divided into two segments. The first is crowdfunding and the second is loans and factoring. Crowdfunding can be further divided into variants with and without financial return to the investors (European Commission, 2014). Donation-based crowdfunding means there is no financial return to the investors, whereas reward-based crowdfunding includes a compensation in the form of a non-

monetary return, e.g. a pre-emption right to buy the company's product. Crowdlending and crowdfunding can be considered as crowdfunding with financial return to their investors (Kirby & Worner, 2014). The second segment of financing is loans and factoring. The former means the fintech platforms arrange loans between borrowers and traditional banks. Factoring, also known as invoice trading, is related to the sale of accounts receivable through online platforms. Asset management can be split into four following segments: Robo advise, social trading, personal financial management, and investments and banking. Payment services consist of cryptocurrency and blockchain and alternative payment services. The last segmentation contains other fintech services that are not related to financing, asset management, or payment services. This includes services linked to insurance services and searching and comparison platforms. Furthermore, there are fintechs offering technology solutions for banks or other financial service providers (Dorfleitner et al., 2016). The segmentations are illustrated by figure 1. However, there can also be different segmentations and terminologies. Fintechs that provide insurance related services are also known as insurtechs, and fintechs that provide regulatory services for banks are known as regtechs (Alt, Beck, & Smits, 2018).

Figure 1: Segmentation of fintechs

Source: Own illustration based on Dorfleitner et al. 2016, p. 11

The Basel Committee on Banking Supervision consider fintechs as growing competition to traditional banks (2017). They argue that especially due to the adoption of new technologies, which lower the barriers to entry in the financial services market, fintechs represent a strategic risk for traditional banks. However, as shown previously, the services of fintechs are wide-ranging in scope

while the segment of financing fintechs represents a high strategic risk for traditional banks due to the phenomenon of disintermediation (Dorfleitner et al., 2017; European Banking Authority, 2015). This implies the substitution of financial intermediaries like banks by direct interactions between investors and borrowers through a platform (Dorfleitner et al., 2016). Crowdfunding platforms are two-sided marketplace business models that provide a matching service between two sides of the market (Belleflamme & Lambert, 2014; Belleflamme, Omrani, & Beitz, 2015; Pur, Huesig, Mann, & Schmidhammer, 2014). Factoring platforms also provide a direct matching between a company and investors who buy the account receivables (Dorfleitner, Rad, & Weber, 2017).

There are successful and competitive two-sided marketplace business models in non-financing markets. For example, Booking Holdings Inc. is the provider of booking.com, which is a platform to book accommodations online. Including the further platforms Kayak, Priceline, Agoda, Rentalcars, and OpenTable the stock market capitalisation of Booking Holdings Inc. is 81.495 bnUS\$ (Bloomberg, 2019a; Booking Holdings Inc., 2018). Airbnb is not listed on the stock market but evaluated at 38.000 bnUS\$ (Forbes, 2019). In contrast, the market capitalisation of Hilton Worldwide Holdings Inc. that manages a portfolio of hotels and resorts is 28.972 bnUS\$, and the market capitalisation of Marriott International Inc. that also manages a portfolio of hotels and resorts is 47.468 bnUS\$ (Bloomberg, 2019b, 2019c).

However, the strategic impact of financing fintechs on traditional banks depends on whether or not the services are substitutes for traditional banking services (European Commission, 2015). In case the services are not substitutional, the strategic impact is reduced. There are indications that the services of financing fintechs can be a substitute for traditional banking services in the retail segment (Ghose et al., 2016; Noeth et al., 2014; Wolfe & Yoo, 2017). Not solely for consumers but also for SMEs (small-and-medium-sized enterprises), financing fintechs could be a substitute for traditional banking services (Blohm, Leimeister, Wenzlaff, & Gebert, 2013; Dimler, Peter, & Karcher, 2018; Gierczak, Bretschneider, Haas, Blohm, & Leimeister, 2016; Yan, Yu, & Zhao, 2015). For SMEs that have difficulties to access traditional financial sources, financing fintechs might be an alternative. The higher competition could bring benefits for the SMEs (European Commission, 2016).

There are different studies that indicate that financing fintechs serve SMEs, which are not attractive for traditional banks. Blohm et al. argue that crowdfunding platforms serve companies which cannot be efficiently served by traditional banks, especially due to the low loan volumes (2015). Maier found that the average funding volume of 409 SMEs on one crowdlending platform in Germany was 73 k€ while the average turnover of the companies was 1.4 mn€ (2016a). Dorfleitner,

Kapitz, and Wimmer found that of 85 SMEs on four crowdfunding platforms in Germany, the average funding volume was 143 k€ while the average turnover was 220 k€ (2014). Primarily due to the higher information asymmetries between the bank and the SME, the higher unit costs for banks, and the higher risks for banks, SMEs have more difficulties in accessing bank loans than large companies and small SMEs have more difficulties than larger SMEs (Fouché et al., 2016; Grunow & Figgenger, 2006; Schwartz, 2016; Seehausen, 2014).

Since these SMEs are not attractive for traditional banks, it might be that they do not consider financing fintechs as a strategic threat. As the findings of Dorfleitner et al. show that the most German banks do not consider fintechs – generally fintechs, not specifically financing fintechs – as a threat (2016). According to the disruptive innovation theory, incumbents often fail competing disruptive innovation because they do not consider it as disruption. First, the entrants serve low-end customers, which are not attractive for the incumbents, or non-customers, which are not served at all. Then, they improve their performance, which means functionality and reliability of the product or service, and serve mainstream customers and disrupt the incumbents. For example, when Netflix started its business in 1997, it was not attractive to the Blockbuster’s mainstream customers who typically rented new releases on impulse. The delivery through mail by Netflix took several days. However, as the technology allowed to change its business model to streaming video over the internet, it finally became attractive to Blockbuster’s mainstream customers (Christensen & Raynor, 2003; Christensen et al., 2015, 2004). Therefore, there is a strategic risk for traditional banks that financing fintechs are a disruptive innovation.

In order to evaluate the success of companies, different theories can be applied. For example, the market-based view, which is subjected to the structure conduct performance paradigm, implies that a company’s success mainly depends on the competitive market structure (Porter, 1980). According to Porter, strategic positioning means “performing different activities from rivals, or performing similar activities in different ways” (1996, p. 3). In contrast, the resource-based view implies the company’s success mainly depends on the internal resources of the company (Barney, 1986). In this context, the disruptive innovation theory can be considered as a more radical approach which can lead to destruction of competitors (Tiberius & Rasche, 2017). In a widely used context, fintechs can be seen as enabling disruptive innovation in financial services and markets (Peat, Kelly, & Broby, 2017).

The overall aim of this research is to critically examine the potential disruptive innovation threat of financing fintechs that provide services to small-and-medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in Germany to traditional banks.

1.2 Research questions and objectives

As explained in the previous section, financing fintechs constitute a potential disruptive innovation threat to traditional banks. The outcome of the evaluation of the disruptive innovation threat is especially relevant for executives of traditional banks in order to define their strategy. In case financing fintechs are a disruptive innovation threat, the business of traditional banks is at risk while rational decisions of the executives lead to the failure, which is the dilemma in the disruptive innovation theory (Christensen, 1997). Furthermore, the results can be relevant for the executives of financing fintechs in order to define their strategy and for consultancies who advise traditional banks or fintechs. Additionally, as fintechs could have a strategic impact on the traditional banking system, regulatory authorities such as the Basel Committee on Banking Supervision and European Banking Authority are interested in this topic (2017; 2015). The German Ministry of finance is also interested in the evaluation of the impact of fintechs on the traditional banking system (Dorfleitner et al., 2016). The outcome can help the regulatory authorities to define steering mechanisms.

In order to achieve the research aim, three different research questions have to be answered, whereas the third question is answered by the results of the previous questions. The first research question is as follows:

- 1) What defines the business model of financing fintechs, i.e. crowdlending, crowdinvesting, and factoring platforms that provide services to SMEs in Germany?

The business model is essential for the evaluation of the disruptive innovation of entrants (Christensen & Raynor, 2003; Johnson, Christensen, & Kagermann, 2008). As basis for the evaluation of the disruptive innovation threat, the business models of financing fintechs that provide services to SMEs in Germany have to be understood in depth. The results can be used as basis for the evaluation whether the services of financing fintechs can be a substitute for traditional banking services. Based on the literature review, two studies were identified that defined the process of crowdinvesting platforms in Germany. Hagedorn and Pinkwart split the general process of crowdinvesting into seven phases (2016), while Beck defined five similar phases (2017). However, these studies do not include all relevant aspects of a two-sided marketplace business model, and for the other two segments, there are no similar studies. Furthermore, the BaFin, which is the national regulatory authority in financial issues, describes some legal issues for crowdlending and crowdinvesting platforms (2017a, 2017b). However, this information does not provide an in-depth understanding of the business models. The contribution to knowledge of this research question is an in-depth understanding of the business model of financing fintechs that specifically provide

services to SMEs in Germany – the specific contribution to academics and practice is stated in chapter seven.

The second research question is as follows:

- 2) In a critically exploratory and evaluative way, to which extent is the service of financing fintechs a substitute for traditional banking services to LMEs (large mid-sized companies) in Germany?

Whether or not a disruptive innovation is critical depends especially on whether the entrants' services or products are complements to or substitutes for the incumbents' services or products (Christensen & Raynor, 2003; Rafii & Kampas, 2002). Based on the literature review, three studies were identified that evaluated whether the services can be a substitute for traditional banking services in Germany. Blohm et al. conducted a Delphi-Study with experts from crowdfunding platforms, academics, banks, consultancy companies to find the importance of crowdfunding platforms for start-ups, SMEs, and large companies (2015). However, there is no clear direction for the SME market, for the future development of crowdfunding, and no in-depth understanding of the quantitative results. Additionally, the expert round did not include executives of LMEs. Maier conducted a survey to SMEs that applied for a funding on a crowdlending platform in Germany to quantitatively evaluate the advantages and disadvantages of crowdlending relative to traditional banking (2016a, b). However, the study consists of pre-defined aspects, which should be a disadvantage in relatively unexplored topics, provides not an in-depth understanding of the reasons behind the evaluation, and were addressed to SMEs and not LMEs, which can be considered as mainstream customers of traditional banks. Dorfleitner et al. collected and analysed data of four crowdfunding platforms to find whether crowdfunding can be a substitute for traditional banking services for SMEs (2014). However, this study does not provide an in-depth understanding of whether or not the services can be a substitute and does not consider aspects from executives of LMEs.

The contribution to knowledge of this research question is an in-depth understanding to which extent the service of financing fintechs is a substitute for traditional banking services specifically to LMEs in Germany – the outcome is that it cannot be a substitute. The specific contribution to academics and practice is also stated in chapter seven.

Based on the results of the previous research questions and the application of the disruptive innovation theory, the third research question can be answered in order to achieve the research aim:

- 3) To what extent are financing fintechs that provide services to SMEs in Germany a disruptive innovation threat to traditional banks?

The literature review shows in chapter three different studies which include the strategic impact of fintechs on traditional banks. Navaretti et al. analysed theoretically the impact (2018), while the Basel Committee on Banking Supervision defined five scenarios to describe the possible impact of fintechs on traditional banks (2017). Brandl and Hornuf conducted a network analysis on contractual link data between banks and fintechs to analyse the reactions of traditional banks (2017), while Dorfleitner et al. sent a questionnaire to 9 traditional banks and 33 smaller, innovative banks in order to request their fintech related activities (2016). However, these studies do not include the application of the disruptive innovation theory based on empirical data. By answering this final research question, the research aim should be achieved – the specific contribution to academics and practice is also stated in chapter seven.

Table 1: Evaluation of research questions based on FINER criteria

Criteria	Evaluation
Feasible	Based on the attendance of different workshops and discussions with other researchers, the approach seemed to be feasible in terms of scope, time, money, and expertise.
Interesting	Fintech is a widespread topic in press. This implies that it is an interesting topic for different kind of groups including fintechs, traditional banks, and customers who consume financing services.
Novel	The results of the narrative literature review show a research gap meaning this research contributes to novel information.
Ethical	Under ethical aspects, the conduction of the research is not critical. There is no physical or mental risk. Confidentiality of data and anonymisation of the experts are assured.
Relevant	The results are relevant for different parties. First, for traditional banks to evaluate the potential disruptive threat of financing fintechs and potentially to adjust their business models. Second, for financing fintechs to evaluate their market position and potentially to adjust their business models. Third, consultants who strategically advise traditional banks or financing fintechs. Fourth, for the government and regulatory authorities to have a deeper understanding of the impact of financing fintechs on traditional banks. Fifth, for other researchers it can be useful for further studies. More details are explained in chapter seven.

Source: Own illustration

The FINER criteria can be applied to check the quality of the research questions. FINER means feasible, interesting, novel, ethical, and relevant (Hulley, Cummings, Browner, Grady, & Newman, 2007). In table 1, the evaluation is illustrated.

In order to answer the main research questions, the author of this research seeks the following three major objectives that are derived from the research questions:

- 1) To qualitatively appraise in depth the business model of financing fintechs, i.e. crowdlending, crowdinvesting, and factoring platforms that provide services to SMEs in Germany.
- 2) To critically explore and evaluate to which extent the service of financing fintechs is a substitute for traditional banking services to SMEs in Germany.
- 3) Based on the results of the previous objectives, to qualitatively evaluate the disruptive innovation threat of financing fintechs that provide services to SMEs in Germany to traditional banks.

1.3 Research scope

As previously shown, the services of fintechs are wide-ranging in scope (Dorfleitner et al., 2017). Due to the phenomenon of disintermediation, and hence the high strategic impact of financing fintechs on traditional banks (Dorfleitner et al., 2017; European Banking Authority, 2015), financing fintechs are in the scope of this research. As mentioned above, crowdlending and crowdinvesting relate to the category of crowdfunding with financial return to the investors (Dorfleitner et al. 2016). Since of the other two segments of crowdfunding there is no interest payment or another monetary return to the investors, they are not in the scope of this research – this is not comparable with the services of traditional banks. The category loans of the segment loans and factoring is also not in the scope of this research because there are traditional banks involved which finally originate the loan – the platform is just an intermediary (Dorfleitner et al. 2016).

Within the European Union, crowdfunding is restricted by the national regulatory authorities (Belleflamme & Lambert, 2014). Member states adapt their regulatory frameworks to the local markets which results in different rules and therefore, in different business models (European Commission, 2016). This is also applicable for factoring platforms (BaFin, 2009). According to the disruptive innovation theory, regulatory authorities can have an essential role in shaping the context for both the entrants and incumbents (Christensen et al., 2004). Therefore, a single country has to be considered with common regulatory requirements. The scope of this research is limited

to the German market due to the following reasons: first, Germany has the largest economy in Europe (World bank, 2019), and the largest fintech market in Europe after the United Kingdom (UK) (Hddad & Hornuf, 2016). This implies that economically Germany is an essential market in general and for fintechs in specific. Second, the German financing fintech market shows high growth rates: the total volume of crowdlending and crowdinvesting increased from 116 mn€ in 2014 to 416 mn€ in 2017 (Ziegler et al. 2019; Zhang, Ziegler et al., 2016). The factoring volume increased from 500 mn€ in 2015 to 720 mn€ in 2016 (Dorfleitner, Hornuf, Schmitt, & Weber, 2016, 2019). As shown in chapter three, of the total volume, the largest share after factoring is crowdlending to consumers. However, crowdlending to business has the highest growth rate (Dorfleitner et al., 2016; Zhang et al., 2016). Increasing growth rates can be a signal of disruptive innovation, while the actual market size of the entrants is not essential (Christensen & Raynor, 2003). Third, in contrast to the UK, Germany has a bank-based system, which is characterised by a close relationship, the so-called house-bank-model (Behr & Schmidt, 2016; Paulet & Relano, 2017). Since financing fintechs operate more on hard information based on a transactional-based approach (Navaretti et al., 2018), for financing fintechs it might be more difficult to substitute traditional banking services in Germany. However, this has to be deeper analysed. Fourth, as already mentioned, the findings of Dorfleitner et al. show that the most German banks do not consider fintechs as a threat (2016), which could imply a disruptive innovation. Fifth, the German government is also interested in the impact of fintechs on the traditional banking system (Dorfleitner et al., 2016).

Furthermore, the scope is limited to financing fintechs that provide services to SMEs. Since companies have a higher need for more complex financial solutions than consumers (Renker, 2005), the market entry barrier of financing fintechs into the retail banking sector might be lower than in the corporate banking sector. In the retail sector, it is clearer that the services of financing fintechs can be a substitute for traditional banking services (Ghose et al., 2016; Noeth et al., 2014; Wolfe & Yoo, 2017), while the topic is more unexplored in the SME sector (Moritz & Block, 2016). Additionally, as mentioned, financing fintechs currently serve SMEs which should not be attractive for traditional banks, which implies a potential risk of a disruptive innovation in case the entrants move up-market and serve the mainstream customers of traditional banks. Regarding the quantitative definition of the IfM Bonn, the definition of a SME implies a maximum annual turnover of 50 mn€ and that the company has not more than 499 employees (2017). Of all German companies, 99.6% are SMEs, which make 35.4% of the total turnover of all companies (Guenterberg, 2012). According to the IfM Bonn, large companies are companies that have an annual turnover higher than 50 mn€ and employees more than 499 (2017). Of all German companies, 0.4% are large companies, which make 64.6.4% of the total turnover (Guenterberg, 2012). For large companies, crowdfunding is likely no substitute for traditional banking services

(Blohm et al., 2015). Large companies have more complex financing needs, switch more often between different banks and forms of financing instruments, and have access to capital markets (Fouché et al., 2016; Renker, 2005). However, there is also a category in between: The KfW Banking Group defines a company as SME if the annual turnover is not higher than 500 mn€ (Schwartz, 2016; Zimmermann, 2017), and the definition of Grunow and Figgenger for a medium-sized company also includes a threshold of 500 mn€ (2006). Of all companies in Germany, 0.35% are companies with an annual turnover between 50 and 500 mn€ (Zimmermann, 2017). These companies can be defined as large mid-sized companies (LMEs). Since small SMEs are not attractive for traditional banks while large companies have a need for more complex financing solutions, switch more often between different banks and instruments with direct capital market access, LMEs can be considered as mainstream customers.

1.4 Summary of research methodology and methods

In order to answer the research questions, the research consists of a secondary and primary research. As recommended for qualitative research, the secondary research consists of a theoretical and conceptual framework of definitions, theories, and conceptions that are relevant to achieve the research objectives and a narrative literature review to give an overview of the current state of research and to show the research gap (Merriam & Tisdell, 2016). The primary research consists of a business model analysis based on a documentary research and expert interviews with executive managers of LMEs as illustrated by figure 2.

Figure 2: Overview of overall research approach

Source: Own illustration

The objective of the documentary research is to qualitatively appraise in depth the business model of crowdlending, crowdfunding, and factoring platforms that provide services to SMEs in Germany. This includes the first qualitative evaluation of the disruptive innovation threat of financing fintechs to traditional banks. Based on the results, the expert interviews can be conducted

with executive managers of LMEs in Germany to critically explore and evaluate to which extent the service of financing fintechs is a substitute for traditional banking services. This includes the second qualitative evaluation of the disruptive innovation threat of financing fintechs to traditional banks. Since both are qualitative studies, it is a multi-method approach (Saunders, Lewis, & Thornhill, 2009). In contrast, a mixed method consists of an integrative quantitative and qualitative research, while triangulation means that the results of the same subject are checked by different methods to compensate the limitations of each method (Creswell, 2014; Flick, 2007). More details about the methodology and methods are explained in chapter four.

1.5 Structure of thesis

In order to answer the research questions, the research is structured into seven chapters that are described in the following. After the introduction in chapter one, chapter two provides theoretical and conceptual frameworks. In chapter three, the existing literature of financing fintech related studies is illustrated and the research gap examined by a narrative literature review. Chapter four provides a detailed description of the research philosophy and methodology and the methods applied. Chapter five provides the results of the primary research consisting of the documentary research in order to qualitatively appraise in depth the business model of crowdlending, crowdinvesting, and factoring platforms. Chapter six provides the results of the primary research consisting of the expert interviews in order to critically explore and evaluate to which extent the service of financing fintechs is a substitute for traditional banking services to LMEs in Germany. Chapter seven provides the overall conclusion. Figure 3 illustrates the structure of the research.

Figure 3: Overview of structure of research

Source: Own illustration

2 Theoretical and conceptual frameworks

In order to achieve the research aim and objectives and to answer the research questions, the following theoretical and conceptual frameworks are required. Based on these frameworks, issues are identified that are related to the research objectives. The linkage between each issue addressed through these sections to the respective research objective is also explained and illustrated in the summary and conclusion section. These issues are also used as basis for the definition of the deductively defined categories of the category systems of the documentary research and the expert interviews and as basis for the discussion and evaluation of the research results. This chapter includes existing theories, concepts, and definitions which are not directly related to the topic of fintechs, while chapter three contains all relevant financing fintech related studies. Again, as recommended for qualitative research, the secondary research should consist of a theoretical and conceptual framework of theories, concepts, and definitions that are relevant to achieve the objectives and a literature review to give an overview of the current state of research and to show the research gap (Merriam & Tisdell, 2016).

2.1 Relevant theories and concepts

2.1.1 Disruptive innovation theory

2.1.1.1 Explanation of disruptive innovation theory

The issue addressed in this section is to show what disruptive innovation implies and how entrants can disrupt incumbents, which is relevant to evaluate the disruptive innovation threat of financing fintechs to traditional banks.

In 1995, Bower and Christensen used the term disruptive technology by describing the disruptive process in the disk drive industry and by explaining a method for executive managers for identifying and cultivating disruptive technologies. Christensen further explained why rational decisions of executive managers can lead companies to fail and what they can do to the dilemma (1997). In 2003, Christensen and Raynor replaced the term disruptive technology with disruptive innovation because the technology is less intrinsically disruptive or sustaining in character, rather it is the business model that enables the disruptive impact. "Disruption is a theory: a conceptual model of cause and effect that makes it possible to better predict the outcomes of competitive battles in different circumstances" (Christensen & Raynor, 2003, p. 55).

There is a distinction between sustaining and disruptive innovations. Sustaining innovations are improvements of existing services or products in established markets like airplanes that fly farther, computers that process faster, and cellular phone batteries that last longer. Online banking was

also a sustaining innovation to make banking faster and more convenient. The platform business model of Uber, which provides a mobile application that connects consumers who need rides with drivers who are willing to provide them, can also be considered as sustaining innovation because it directly served mainstream customers instead of firstly serving low-end or non-customers (Christensen & Raynor, 2003; Christensen, Raynor, & McDonald, 2015). Sustaining innovations can be radical or incremental in character. The former is at the end of the continuum like the move from black-white to colour television, while the latter is less radical like a caller identification in communication (Christensen, Scott, & Roth, 2004). “Most innovations are not disruptive. Many of the most important and most profitable innovations are sustaining innovations that take a good service or product and make it better” (Christensen et al., 2004, p. 270).

In contrast to sustaining innovations, disruptive innovations introduce a new value proposition and either create new markets or reshape existing markets. There are two kinds of disruptive innovations: New-market and low-end. Additionally, there are four kinds of customers, and two kinds of companies (Christensen & Raynor, 2003; Christensen et al., 2015).

The companies can be split into incumbents and entrants. The incumbents are established companies with proofed services or products. They have acquired a significant market share over the years and further develop their existing services or products. The entrants are companies that enter the market without past success and organisational constraints and trying to seize disruptive opportunities. The entrants may not necessarily be start-ups because they can also come from other industries of incumbents (Christensen & Raynor, 2003; Christensen et al., 2015).

The customers can be split into high-end, low-end, mainstream, and non-customers. High-end customers, the most profitable customers, are undershot, meaning those requirements are not sufficiently met. They buy the existing service or product, but they are not fully satisfied and wish for further performance improvements for which they are willing to pay more. Performance means functionality and reliability. Signals of high-end costumers are that they are willing to pay more for a higher service or product performance. High-end customers create opportunities for incumbents to profitably introduce sustaining innovations. Low-end customers, the least profitable customers, are overshot, meaning those requirements are overly met. As the incumbent continuously launches further performance improvements of the service or product instead of satisfying solely the functional requirements, a growing number of customers no longer use the service or product in its entirety, and they are not willing to pay for further improvements. It is a consequence of a company's inability to profitably differentiate its products or services. From the customer's perspective the services or products are often too complex and expensive. Low-end customers

create opportunities for entrants to change the market by low-end disruption. Mainstream customers are the major customers who are in between the high- and low-end customers. Non-customers do not, or only to a limited extent, consume the existing service or product. They have a job that needs to be done, but there is no existing market serving them (Christensen & Raynor, 2003; Christensen et al., 2015, 2004).

The new-market disruption can occur when characteristics of existing services or products limit the number of potential customers or force consumption to take place in an inconvenient way. The new-market disruption overcomes the barriers of non-customer to consumption through a relatively simple and affordable service or product that allows for solving problems. This means a job needs to be done, but an adequate solution does not exist. An example of new-market disruption is Ebay. Ebay established a new online market that enables owners of collectibles to sell off things that they do not longer need. Another example is Apple's iPhone. First, it was a sustaining innovation within the smart phone market. However, the later growth can be explained by a new-market disruption within the personal computer market as the primary access point to the internet. The iPhone's success was not solely based on product improvement but also on the introduction of a new platform business model that matches application developers with phone users. The entrants' challenges are to overcome non-consumption, not to overcome incumbents. The performance of the services or products of the entrants on the dimensions that are valued by mainstream customers is lower. However, as their performance improves, they become good enough to pull customers out of the incumbent market. At the beginning by serving low-end customers, and finally, by serving mainstream customers. The new-market disruption does not enter into the mainstream market, it rather pulls customer out into the new market because the customers find it more convenient to use the new service or product. Since the entrants compete against non-consumption, the incumbents do not consider the entrants as threat until the disruption is in its final stages. At first, the incumbents move up-market. For a time, they replace the low-margin revenues that entrants serve with higher-margin revenues from sustaining innovations (Christensen & Raynor, 2003; Christensen et al., 2015, 2004).

The low-end disruption is related to the most unprofitable customers for incumbents in the lower market segment. Their needs are overshoot because the supply of the incumbents exceeds their requirements. Therefore, the service or product is too expensive in relation to what they want to have. They use the service or product because it is the solely available alternative. The probability that those customers are switching to an offer with a lower price is high. The entrants have lower-cost business models than the incumbents. In contrast to the incumbents, the entrants often approach a non-integrated organisation with outsourcing to partners. The entrants are not

considered as a threat by the incumbents as they lose no or limited sales to the entrants and assume that they will not be competitive in the mainstream markets. An example of low-end disruption is Amazon, by starting to be a competitor only to traditional bookstores. Another example is Netflix. When Netflix started its business in 1997, it was not attractive to the Blockbuster's mainstream customers who typically rented new releases on impulse. The delivery through mail by Netflix took several days. However, as the technology allowed to change its business model to streaming video over the internet, it finally became attractive to Blockbuster's mainstream customers. Since the entrants compete against low-end customers, the incumbents do not consider the entrants as a threat until the disruption is in its final stages. As in the new-market disruption, first, the incumbents move up-market. For a time, they replace the low-margin revenues that entrants serve with higher-margin revenues from sustaining innovations (Christensen & Raynor, 2003; Christensen et al., 2015, 2004).

The disruption can also be a hybrid of the new-market and low-end disruption. Entrants can serve non-customers and low-end customers. McDonald's made it so inexpensive and convenient to eat out that they created a new market in the eating-out industry (Christensen & Raynor, 2003). The disruptive innovation model is illustrated by figure 4.

Figure 4: Theory of disruptive innovation

Source: Own illustration based on Christensen & Raynor 2003, p.44; Christensen et al. 2015, p. 4

The vertical axis represents the service or product performance, while the horizontal axis represents time. The solid lines represent the company improvement trajectories meaning how services or products become better over time. The dotted lines represent the customer demand trajectories meaning the customers' willingness to pay for performance. Since entrants of the new-market disruption serve non-customers, the performance measures are different to the existing market (Christensen & Raynor, 2003; Christensen et al., 2015).

For both the new-market and low-end disruption, asymmetry of motivation and skills allow entrants to enter the market. Asymmetry of motivation occurs when one company wants to do something that another company specifically does not want to do, and asymmetry of skills occurs when one company's strength is another company's weakness. Factors like market size and prospect for growth, general industry attractiveness, attractiveness of specific business models within that industry, and the level of competition determine the motivation. Asymmetry of skills can also be defined as the capability to obtain resources that are transmitted into a business model, and finally, services or products are offered to customers. First, entrants enter behind a shield of asymmetric motivation by serving customers that appear to the incumbents to be either undesirable or non-existing. Additionally, the relatively small market size to the incumbents' markets is unattractive for incumbents. Second, entrants follow their own improvement trajectory to move up-market. In the beginning entrants typically undershoot their customers' needs, while through improvements the entrants move up-market. Incumbents also move up-market by sustaining innovation to serve their high-end customers who are the most profitable ones. Third, entrants utilise the advantage of asymmetry of skills. Since of the increasing volume, the entrants cannot be ignored any more by the incumbents. By moving up-market, the entrants develop skills to increase the performance. The incumbents can still face barriers in terms of motivation, and they might not have the skills that are required (Christensen et al., 2004).

Disruptive innovation takes place within a certain context. Regulatory authorities can have an essential role in shaping the context for both the entrants and incumbents. Authority's action can be asymmetric, meaning it creates motivation for one group, while simultaneously diminishing it for another. This also includes that entrants cannot move up-market due to regulatory barriers (Christensen et al., 2004).

Usually, incumbents win in sustaining innovation. As this strategy means making a better service or product that they can sell for higher profit margins to their best customers, the incumbents' priority is to compete with sustaining innovation. Hence, the incumbents prefer to invest their limited resources in sustaining innovation. Additionally, their processes and resources are designed to

compete with those types of innovations. However, incumbents often fail in the face of disruptive innovations because they do not consider it as a disruption. They focus on their mainstream and high-end customers, ignore non-customers and low-end customers and invest where profits are most attractive. They are not motivated to defend the new or low-end markets that the entrants find attractive. Moving up-market and avoiding less profitable services or products is preferred by executive managers in order to reduce a negative effect on their profitability and company value. For an incumbent that does not move up-market, it might be difficult to differentiate its service or product against competitors whose cost structure is comparable (Christensen & Raynor, 2003; Christensen et al., 2015, 2004). “This ultimately means that in doing what they must do, every company prepares the way for its own disruption. This is the innovator's dilemma” (Christensen & Raynor, 2003, p. 43). The incumbents listen to their mainstream or high-end customers, give them the service or product performance they are looking for, and finally, they are threatened by the disruptive innovation their customers led them to ignore, while entrants take advantage of asymmetry of motivation and skills. Incumbents often quantify the size of the market rather than to understand the customer (Christensen & Raynor, 2003; Christensen et al., 2015).

Disruption is not a fixed point; it is rather a process that takes time. Complete substitution of the service or product, if it comes at all, may take decades. The fact that disruption can take time supports the explanation why incumbents frequently overlook disruptive innovations. At the point at which the entrants serve the mainstream customers, it is often too late for the incumbents because the entrants already dominate the market (Christensen & Raynor, 2003; Christensen et al., 2015, 2004). Nevertheless, “disruption is an ongoing force that is always at work—meaning that disruptors in one generation become disrptees later” (Christensen & Raynor, 2003, pp. 48–49).

The disruptive innovation theory shown in this section explains how entrants can disrupt incumbents, which can be used for the evaluation of the disruptive innovation threat of financing fintechs to traditional banks. However, it does not explain how the disruptive innovation threat can be evaluated ex-ante, which is explained in the following section.

2.1.1.2 Ex-ante analysis of disruptive innovation and possible actions in response

The issue addressed in this section is to show concepts of how the disruptive innovation threat of entrants can be evaluated ex-ante, which is relevant to evaluate the disruptive innovation threat of financing fintechs to traditional banks.

“Incumbent firms that take action when data shows a downturn in their core businesses take action too late. The only signal to take timely action is sound theory” (Christensen et al., 2004, p. 42). An incumbent that is confronted with innovation has firstly to identify whether it is a sustaining or disruptive innovation. In case of sustaining innovation, the incumbent is possibly at an advantage, and thus there is no significant threat. In case of disruptive innovation, the incumbent has to define whether or not it is critical. If it is critical, then the incumbent has to prioritise the disruption, and has to define respective actions (Christensen et al., 2015, 2004).

In order to identify disruptive innovation, the first question is whether the customers that are served by entrants are low-end customers who are overshot or non-customers who are not or only to a limited extent consuming the existing service or product. Additionally, the question is whether the disruptive innovation is against all incumbents within one industry. If not, then the entrants will probably not win (Christensen & Raynor, 2003). Furthermore, the market size is less relevant than the growth rates. Increasing growth rates can be a signal of disruptive innovation, while the market size is not essential. The disruptive innovation brings relative advantages to low-end or non-customers such as lower price, more convenience, or simplification. Due to its performance limitation, mainstream and high-end customers who are already consuming the existing or potentially competing service or product of the incumbents will reject the new service or product (Christensen et al., 2004). Additionally, a signal can be that entrants’ business models generate revenues in a different way, and the entrants have a modular structure implying a non-integrated organisation that is based on outsourcing of components and subsystems. The modular structure can also be seen as specialisation (Christensen & Raynor, 2003; Christensen et al., 2004).

Whether or not a disruptive innovation is critical depends especially on whether the entrants’ services or products are complements to or substitutes for the incumbents’ services or products. If the services or products are substitutes, it can lead to total elimination of the incumbents, while complements are possibly more likely leading to minor revenue losses (Christensen & Raynor, 2003; Rafii & Kampas, 2002).

Two services or products are substitutes if they satisfy equal needs, and thus can be replaced with each other (Evans, 2011). Hence, the services or products are in competition with each other (Piekenbrock & Henning, 2013). Perfect substitutes can be used in exactly the same way, while imperfect substitutes refer to services or products that cannot. The latter has a lower level of substitutability but also a positive cross elasticity of demand which means if an increase in price of one service or product increases the demand of the other service or product. In contrast, complementary services or products are jointly used in consumption with a negative cross elasticity

of demand. Perfect complements are services or products that have to be consumed with another service or product with a fixed proportion like one to one, while imperfect complements are qualitatively equal but less intense. Services or products are imperfect complements if they are not perfect complements and if an increase in price of one service or product decreases the demand for the other service or product (Arnold, 2008; Gilbert, 2018).

Figure 5: Perfect substitutes and complements

Source: Own illustration based on Piekenbrock & Henning, 2013; Arnold, 2008

Perfect substitutes and complements are illustrated by figure 5. In economics, the indifference curve implies a combination of two services or products that provide the customer with equal levels of value. However, “the extent to which goods are complements or substitutes still depends on our subjective judgment about their ability to satisfy the same pressing needs” (Evans, 2014, p. 15). After the identification and evaluation of whether or not the disruptive innovation is critical, the incumbent has to prioritise it, which includes resource allocation (Christensen & Raynor, 2003). The actions which have to be defined depend on the stage of disruptive innovation and the incumbent’s strategy (Christensen et al., 2004).

Rafii and Kampas defined six stages between the start and the success of a disruption (2002). The disruption can fail during any stage. The stages are illustrated by figure 6. First, the entrant enters a foothold market by serving non-customers or low-end customers. Second, the entrant enters the mainstream market by overcoming entry barriers. Third, the entrant begins to attract mainstream customers, often by offering lower performance for a lower price. Fourth, mainstream customers switch if their switching costs are not substantial. Fifth, the incumbent retaliates if it becomes aware of a pending disruption. Nevertheless, the incumbent can also abandon the market if profitability levels are not worth defending. Sixth, the incumbent is displaced to some degree, which can range

from minor revenue losses to liquidation. This depends primarily on whether the entrant's service or product is a complement to or substitute for the incumbent's service or product.

Figure 6: Illustration of stages for evaluation of disruptive innovation

Source: Own illustration based on Rafii and Kampas 2002

The incumbent's strategy can be to cede or compete the market. The former implies that the incumbent leaves the market to the entrant to focus on its high-end costumers. In order to compete, the incumbent can modify its core service or product or introduce a new service or product to serve low-end or non-customers (Christensen et al., 2004). For the latter the incumbent can set up an autonomous company with a different business model including a different cost structure and decision-approval process. The set-up of an autonomous company can reduce the asymmetry of motivation and skills. In case of a separate company, the new business is not affected by the incumbent's overhead costs, which allows more leeway to move up-market with a lower price. The business of the new company should be considered as an opportunity without projecting highly profitable figures in the future for resources that are required in the present. The focus should be on low-end customers or non-customers and not on the mainstream customers. Therefore, based on the autonomous company, there should be different sales channels which are not competing with sustaining innovations that are probably more attractive for salespersons.

Additionally, the company should have a modular structure implying a non-integrated organisation that is based on outsourcing of components and subsystems. In contrast to the theory that non-core competencies should be outsourced, in this context, it depends on the kind of customers that are targeted (Christensen & Raynor, 2003). Due to outsourcing, the company can introduce services or products faster without having to redesign the whole organisation. The company can combine and match components from outsourcing partners in order to flexibly respond to specific customer needs. Additionally, due to outsourcing, the fixed costs can be lower, which can cause lower prices. Although standard interfaces with outsourcing partners increase compromise in terms of performance, it should not be an issue because the customers are overshot. In contrast, for sustaining innovation a relative advantage is a vertically integrated organisation that controls the manufacture of all critical components of the system. The assembly of standardised components reduces the degree of manufacture freedom, which reduces the performance possible. However, whereas integration at one point was a relative advantage, it later becomes a relative disadvantage. This is a gradual process when the performance gap (performance is below the mainstream customer demand trajectory) is becoming a performance surplus (performance is above the mainstream customer demand trajectory) (Christensen & Raynor, 2003; Christensen et al., 2004). Another strategy is to acquire the entrant (Christensen et al., 2004).

The six stages of Rafii and Kampas (2002) and the further aspects mentioned in this section can be used to evaluate the disruptive innovation threat of financing fintechs to traditional banks. However, since traditional banks can react after each stage to defend the potential disruptive innovation, the financing fintechs can adjust their business models between the stages, and the stages mainstream customer attraction and mainstream market entry can be merged (both imply that mainstream customers are served), the stages can be adjusted – the evaluation is illustrated in the overall conclusion of this research.

2.1.2 Information asymmetry and principal agent theory

The issue addressed in this section is to explain how traditional banks reduce the information asymmetry, which is a result of the principal agent relation. This is relevant for the appraisal of the business model of financing fintechs and the evaluation of whether the services of financing fintechs can be a substitute for traditional banking services.

The principal-agent relation means the separation of ownership and control and represents a kind of contract in which one or more principals delegate decision making authority to an agent (Jensen & Meckling, 1976). The agents are able to take actions that impact the principals. The principal-

agent theory's assumption is that information asymmetries between the principal and the agent exist. Additionally, both the principal and agent behave opportunistically, and the advantage for the principal depends on the behaviour of the agent. Regarding financing transactions without financial intermediaries, investors can be considered as principals and borrowers as agents. In case of a financial intermediary in between, the financial intermediary acts as the agent for the investors and simultaneously as the principal for the borrowers as illustrated by figure 7 (Grethe, 2010; Zemke, 1995).

Figure 7: Principal-agent (P-A) relation with and without financial intermediary

Source: Own illustration based on Zemke 1995, p. 50 and Grethe 2010, p. 61

The principal-agent relation causes problems which can be split into ex-ante and ex-post. Ex-ante means before both parties of a transaction enter into a contract, while ex-post means after the contract is concluded. Adverse selection is an ex-ante problem which was first described by Akerlof in 1970 (Belleflamme & Lambert, 2014; Grethe, 2010). Akerlof described that buyers cannot distinguish between high and low quality due to information asymmetry which causes lower prices for high-quality products. This phenomenon discourages high-quality sellers and encourages low-quality sellers. Finally, only low-quality products remain (1970). "In general, information asymmetry means one party to a transaction has more or superior information than the other party, resulting in an imbalance of power in transactions" (Fabozzi & Drake, 2009, p. 111). In a financing transaction this means that the borrower knows more about its investment opportunities than the investor (Greenbaum, Thakor, & Boot, 2016). Adverse selection implies that a borrower with a high credit risk attempts to overstate its creditworthiness to potential investors to appear like a low credit risk borrower. Only the borrower itself knows its true creditworthiness. The investor does not know or cannot evaluate the creditworthiness and requires an average interest rate, while the borrower

with a low credit risk does not borrow at higher interest rates. Finally, only high credit risk borrowers remain (Greenbaum et al., 2016).

Moral hazard is described as ex-post problem. "Moral hazard is a problem that arises when one person, called the agent, is performing some task on behalf of another person, called the principal. If the principal cannot perfectly monitor the agent's behaviour, the agent tends to undertake less effort than the principal considers desirable" (Mankiw, 2016, p. 452). Therefore, the term moral hazard refers to the risk of an inappropriate behaviour by the agent. Regarding financing transactions, this can mean that the borrower takes a high risk to increase the profit, while the bank takes a disproportionate share of the downside risk.

The information asymmetry can be reduced. The signalling theory implies that a higher-informed party (signaler or agent) sends a quality signal to the less-informed party (receiver or principal) to reduce information asymmetry (Block, Hornuf, & Moritz, 2018). Spence applied the theory to the labour market to demonstrate how job applicants can use their higher education as effective signals to reduce their potential employers' information deficits (1973). For signals to be effective, they need to be observable because otherwise they would not be perceived by the receiver, and they need to be costly, otherwise they would be too easy to fake or imitate. The costs include the implementation costs of sending a quality signal and the risks costs, meaning penalty costs of sending a false signal (Vismara, 2018). The sender intentionally sends positive signals to information outsiders to cause a reaction by the receiver, for example, the investment in a company (Block et al., 2018). A signalling equilibrium occurs when the sender signals honestly, the receiver trusts that information, and the signal's expectations are confirmed through experience (Spence, 1973). The effectiveness of signals can be increased by frequently sending signals (Block et al., 2018). The advantage of financial intermediaries is that they can evaluate signals more accurate and efficient than individual investors (Boscia & Salvo, 2009).

Additionally, financial intermediaries can reduce information asymmetry through the activities of screening, contracting, and monitoring (Berger & Udell, 1998). In order to reduce adverse selection, financial intermediaries can collect data of the borrower over time. This can include soft information which can be gained in a relationship between the financial intermediary and the borrower (Ekpu, 2016; Everett, 2015). Additionally, adverse selection can be reduced by specialised skills in screening, processing, and interpreting credit information. If individual investors have adequate skills to evaluate information, they could also reduce adverse selection. However, due to duplicated screening it is not efficient, which implies multiple individual investors doing the same

screening and evaluation, while a financial intermediary evaluates the creditworthiness once and can reuse the information (Greenbaum et al., 2016).

Additionally, financial intermediaries can reduce moral hazard by contractual activities like covenants and by requiring a collateral or a personal guarantee (Boscia & Salvo, 2009; Ekpu, 2016; Jiménez & Jesús, 2004). This also includes frequently monitoring the borrower's financial conditions and intervening in operating strategy when necessary (Greenbaum et al., 2016). The function as principal for the investors can be seen as the biggest advantage of financial intermediaries. Due to specialisation and economies of scale effects, they screen, select, evaluate, and monitor borrowers better and more cheaply than individual investors (Grethe, 2010).

As shown in this section, traditional banks reduce the information asymmetry. For the appraisal of the business model of financing fintechs and for the evaluation whether the services can be a substitute for traditional banking services, it has to be evaluated whether financing fintechs also reduce the information asymmetry.

2.1.3 Transaction cost theory

The issue addressed in this section is to explain how traditional banks reduce the transactions costs, which is relevant for the appraisal of the business model of financing fintechs and the evaluation of whether the services of financing fintechs can be a substitute for traditional banking services.

Coase used the term transaction cost by explaining when certain activities are performed within companies or on the market (1937). It implies that obtaining a service or product costs more than the price of the service or product. Williamson further developed the theory of transaction costs (1981, 1985). Transaction costs can be split into ex-ante and ex-post. The former is related to activities that occur before the contract is conducted such as searching, informing, and negotiating, while the latter is related to activities that occur after the contract is agreed such as controlling, enforcing, adjusting.

Due to the process known as financial intermediation whereby banks take funds from depositors and provide loans to borrowers, traditional banks reduce the transaction costs (Girasa, 2016). The process of financial intermediation includes the transformation functions. "The transformation process performed by banks means that banks themselves enter into contractual agreements with other market participants and change the size, maturity and risk structure of the underlying financial contracts" (Janssen 2009, p. 17). The lot size transformation implies matching different

volumes of capital providers and capital seekers. Banks take a large number of investments with small volumes from investors and provide larger volumes to borrowers or vice versa (Hartmann-Wendels et al., 2007).

The maturity transformation implies to bridge the gap between capital providers that want to invest for short-term and capital seekers that want to borrow for long-term. Banks have liabilities like deposits that have a shorter maturity than their assets like loans to borrowers (Ison & Wall, 2007). If there are not enough new deposits, funding issues for the bank can occur (Hartmann-Wendels et al., 2007). Additionally, in case of holding long-term assets financed by short-term liabilities, there is an interest rate risk. According to the liquidity premium theory, investors prefer short-term over long-term investments because a shorter maturity means higher liquidity. They are willing to hold long-term investments if compensated by a premium (Madura, 2016). Without a liquidity premium, there would be no incentive for financial intermediaries to engage in maturity transformation (Greenbaum et al., 2016). Furthermore, the maturity transformation can be supported by secondary markets (Hartmann-Wendels et al., 2007).

The risk transformation implies to match capital providers with capital seekers that have divergent risk preferences. Banks take deposits as liabilities with low risk for their investors and provide loans to borrowers with higher risk. This principle is primarily based on the portfolio diversification and the banks' equity (Hartmann-Wendels et al., 2007). The assumption is that the size in unit is too small for investors to diversify their investments like banks (Greenbaum et al., 2016). If an unexpected risk occurs, the bank covers the loss by its equity (Hartmann-Wendels et al., 2007). For depositors within the European Union, banks that qualified as credit institutions have a deposit guarantee according to section 2 of directive 2014/49/EU.

Based on financial intermediaries, the number of contractual agreements, and hence the transactions costs can be reduced. This is illustrated by figure 8. In case of n borrowers (capital seekers) and m investors (capital providers), the transaction costs can be reduced from $n \times m$ to $n + m$ if each transaction is equal in its costs and m and n is higher than two. In case of no financial intermediary, there are $n \times m$ contractual agreements, while the number is $n + m$ with a financial intermediary (Hartmann-Wendels et al., 2007). Additionally, since financial intermediaries are specialised in their transactions, the transaction costs can be reduced (Grethe, 2010; Hazard et al., 2016). "They turn information into knowledge, which then flows into the financial services" (Auge-Dickhut et al., 2016, p. 77). This includes the evaluation of the creditworthiness and the monitoring of the borrower (Boscia & Salvo, 2009).

Figure 8: Simplified illustration of financial markets with and without intermediation

Source: Own illustration based on Hartmann-Wendels et al. 2007, p. 112

As shown in this section, traditional banks reduce the transaction costs. For the appraisal of the business model of financing fintechs and for the evaluation of whether the services can be a substitute for traditional banking services, it has to be evaluated whether financing fintechs also reduce the transaction costs.

2.1.4 Capital structure theories – static trade-off versus pecking order theory

The issue addressed in this section is to show how the capital structure decisions of executives might be driven, which is relevant to evaluate what financing fintech segment is more or less disruptive. As already mentioned, financing fintechs include factoring, crowdlending, and crowdinvesting platforms. Factoring implies internal financing, crowdlending implies debt-based crowdfunding, and crowdinvesting implies mezzanine-based crowdfunding.

The modern capital structure theories are based on the capital structure irrelevance theory of Modigliani and Miller (Schneider, 2010). Based on their theory and further aspects by other authors, the static trade-off theory was developed. In contrast to the static trade-off theory, based on first ideas of Donaldson (1961), Myers and Majluf developed the pecking order theory (1984). The static trade-off and pecking order theory are the most established theories because they explain the capital structure decisions of companies in a holistic view (Schneider, 2010).

According to the capital structure irrelevance theory of Modigliani and Miller, “the average cost of capital to any firm is completely independent of its capital structure and is equal to the capitalization rate of a pure equity stream of its class” (Modigliani & Miller, 1958, pp. 268–269). If the value of a levered company that has a higher debt-to-equity ratio is higher, the investor sells its shares, takes a private loan, and buys shares of the unlevered company with the same fraction of

shares to the total shares and the same leverage on its portfolio level. The investor proceeds a premium which will be diminished by the market mechanism. The shares of the levered company are sold, while the shares of the unlevered company are bought, which finally leads to an equilibrium. If the value of the unlevered company is higher, the investor sells its shares, buys shares of the levered company with proportion S_l / V_l and invests in debt securities with proportion D_l / V_l , where S_l is the equity value, V_l the company value, and D_l the debt value of the levered company. On the investor's portfolio there is a premium which finally leads to an equilibrium. The assumptions of their theory are the absence of taxes, bankruptcy costs, information asymmetries, and the existence of perfect capital markets without transaction costs (Modigliani & Miller, 1958).

However, the reality of capital markets might be different from the assumptions of the theory. The existence of banks should imply that the markets are imperfect as described in chapter 2.2.1. Therefore, the financing structure could be relevant for companies. While Modigliani and Miller underestimated the tax impact in the first publication, in 1963 they revised the evaluation of the tax impact on the average cost of capital. Since interests on debt can be deducted from the company's income, and thus reduce the net taxable earnings, the usage of debt decreases the average cost of capital. In 1988, Miller mentioned, "showing what doesn't matter can also show, by implication, what does" (p. 100). Based on the revision of the tax impact, the static trade-off theory was developed (Schneider, 2010). Robichek and Myers showed that the theory of Modigliani and Miller excluded the bankruptcy costs (1966). Bankruptcy costs are related to the company's probability of bankruptcy. The higher the leverage, the higher the probability of bankruptcy. The finding of Kraus and Litzenberger was the trade-off between the tax advantages and bankruptcy cost (1973). The market value of a levered company is equal the value of an unlevered company, plus the present value of the corporate tax advantage, and minus the present value of the bankruptcy costs. The optimal capital structure is when the marginal tax advantages of debt are equal to the marginal costs of bankruptcy. The optimum is illustrated by figure 9. This means the company defines a target debt-to-equity ratio and gradually moves toward it (Myers, 1984).

Figure 9: Optimal capital structure in static trade-off theory

Source: Own representation based on Myers 1984, p. 577 and Raßhofer 2010, p. 5

In 1976, Jensen and Meckling integrated the principal-agent theory into the capital structure theory (1976). Again, the principal-agent relation means the separation of ownership and control and represents a kind of contract in which one or more principals delegate decision making authority to an agent. The principals are the equity and debt investors, while the agent is the company's management. Since on both sides opportunistic behaviour can be expected, monitoring and bonding mechanisms can be established. Monitoring means the implementation of control and incentive mechanisms, while bonding means self-commitments by the agent. Even in case of the implementation of these mechanisms, there are residual losses due to an opportunistic behaviour. Therefore, the principal-agency costs are the sum of the monitoring and bonding costs and the residual losses. Rational principals expect a decrease of the company value by the principal-agency costs. The higher the volume of both external debt and equity, the higher the principal-agency costs. The principal-agency costs for external equity can be decreased by a higher leverage. The principal-agency costs for external debt can be decreased by a lower leverage. Considering this, the optimal capital structure is the leverage in which the company's principal-agency costs are at minimum. According to the authors, in case these costs are significant, the static trade-off theory should be extended by these costs.

In contrast to a target debt-to-equity ratio, the pecking order theory implies that companies follow hierarchy rules. Companies prefer internal financing over external financing and regarding external financing, debt over mezzanine and mezzanine over equity. In this theory there is no target debt-to-equity structure because there are two kinds of equity, internal and external, one at the top of the pecking order and one at the bottom. The theory is based on information asymmetries between the management and the investors. Besides the information asymmetries, the capital markets are

perfect, the management acts on the interest of the existing shareholders, and new capital issues are related to new investors. In case the management issues equity for an investment opportunity, the intrinsic value of the equity differs from the market value because the management only knows the true value of the net present value of the investment opportunity and the true value of the equity. The intrinsic value reduced by the market value means whether the equity is under- or overvalued. The objective of the management is to maximise the intrinsic value of the existing equity shareholders. If the inside knowledge is unfavourable meaning the intrinsic value is smaller than the market value, the management will always issue. If the inside knowledge is favourable, meaning the intrinsic value is larger than the market value, the management may dismiss a positive net present value of an investment opportunity rather than issue undervalued equity. The management issues equity when the true value of the net present value of the investment opportunity is equal to or larger than the amount by which the new equity is undervalued, meaning

$$y \geq \Delta N$$

where

y = true value of the net present value of the investment opportunity

ΔN = N_1 minus N

N = market value of new issued equity, when issued

N_1 = intrinsic equity value.

However, in case the management acts in this way and the investors know this, the issue of equity causes negative signals to the existing and new shareholders. The costs of the possibility that the company decides not to issue, and thus dismisses a positive present value of the investment opportunity can be avoided by internal financing. In case there are no internal financing sources available, debt is preferred over equity (Myers, 1984; Myers & Majluf, 1984). Generally, the rule is to “issue safe securities before risky ones” (Myers, 1984, p. 584). If the equity is undervalued (if $\Delta N > 0$) and y is less than the amount by which the new equity is undervalued ($y \leq \Delta N$), the company can take debt to realise y . The absolute value of ΔN is less if a debt is issued rather than equity, and thus the company value can be increased with less dilution of the true value of the existing shareholders. If the management has favourable information (if $\Delta N > 0$), it will prefer to issue debt over equity. In contrast, if the management has unfavourable information (if $\Delta N < 0$), it will prefer to issue equity over debt. However, since the investors know how the management acts, they would avoid buying equity unless the company has already exhausted its debt capacity. Therefore, investors force companies to follow the pecking order (Myers, 1984; Myers & Majluf, 1984). Since there is no target debt-to-equity ratio, the theory consists of hierarchical rules for financing decision making (Schneider, 2010).

The static trade-off and pecking order theories could explain which financing fintech segment is more or less disruptive. In case the LMEs follow the pecking order theory, factoring platforms might have a higher disruptive potential than the other segments since they are related to internal financing. However, in case the LMEs follow the static trade-off theory, crowdlending might have a higher disruptive potential because it is a debt-based financing source. These aspects are further discussed along the results of the expert interviews.

2.1.5 Lending technology concepts and SME financing limitations

The issue addressed in this section is to explain what the lending technologies of traditional banks imply, which is relevant for the appraisal of the business model of financing fintechs and the evaluation of whether the services of financing fintechs can be a substitute for traditional banking services. Additionally, it addresses the issue what obstacles SMEs have in accessing traditional banking services, which can provide indications that financing fintechs serve low-end or non-customers, which is relevant to evaluate the disruptive innovation threat.

There are two major lending technologies that are defined as transactional and relationship lending (Bolton, Freixas, Gambacorta, & Mistrulli, 2013; Ekpu, 2016). Transactional lending is primarily based on hard information and single transactions, while relationship lending is based on soft and hard information and focuses on long-term relationships (Bolton et al., 2013; Ferretti, 2016).

Hard information is quantifiable and can be easily transmitted into the bank's decision process (Carbo-Valverde & Rodríguez-Fernández, 2016). This includes annual reports, cash flow statements, forecast of key figures like turnover, bank account data, and further figures from the borrower. Soft information consists of qualitative information (Reichling et al., 2005). This can be management quality, reliability, life situation of owner, strategic objectives of the company, and the risk appetite of management (Schwartz et al., 2017). In contrast to hard information, soft information is not easily quantifiable and cannot be easily transmitted into the bank's decision process (Carbo-Valverde & Rodríguez-Fernández, 2016).

Transactional lending is solely based on scoring models which consist of hard information and statistical approaches. Any qualitative variable is converted to a numerical value (Ferretti, 2016). There is an automated decision approval that increases the objectivity and decreases the flexibility (Ekpu, 2016). In contrast, relationship lending means the bank invests effort to obtain information of the customer. Based on multiple interactions with the same customer over time and cross products, the bank evaluates its profitability. Due to the relationship, information asymmetry can

be reduced. Therefore, those banks are interested in keeping a long relationship with their customers (Fouché et al., 2016). Relationship lending requires also human input and subjective evaluation (Ekpu, 2016). In case of a decentralised hierarchy of the bank, the soft information flow is higher, and the relationship is more intense than in a centralised hierarchy. Large banks tend to have hierarchical organisational structures with more layers. Therefore, large banks are less efficient in making relationships than small banks (Ekpu, 2016; Stein, 2002).

The banking system in Germany is a bank-based system (Paulet & Relano, 2017). It is characterised by a close relationship, the so-called house-bank-model (Behr & Schmidt, 2016). A relationship bank (house-bank) is characterised by a long-term relationship with its customer. The customer conducts most of the businesses and transactions through its relationship bank. Due to informational advantages through the long-term relationship, the customer typically expects that the relationship bank will provide a loan in difficult times as well (Dimler et al., 2018).

Norden found that long-term, exclusive, and cross-product synergy-creating bank relationships are likely to result in higher loan volumes and better interest rates (2015). Long-term implies repeated interactions between the bank and the borrower. The longer the relationship, the higher the soft information. Exclusive means the extent to which a company concentrates its borrowing on a single bank. The information can be complete, more accurate, and easier to interpret. Although exclusive banks might take advantages of their monopoly position, there can be beneficial loan conditions. Cross-product synergy means the scope of the financial services provided by the bank that can be used for information production. Informational synergies for commercial banks are the simultaneous provision of lending, deposit taking, and payment transaction services (Norden, 2015). "Account activity helps significantly to predict future borrower defaults approximately one year in advance, and serve as a basis for banks' loan pricing, credit limit management, and loan loss provisioning" (Norden & Weber, 2009). However, since fintechs leverage on technology, both big data and machine learning could be used to decrease information asymmetries and to evaluate the creditworthiness of borrowers (Cummins, Lynn, Mac an Bhaird, & Rosati, 2019; European Banking Authority, 2018; Navaretti et al., 2018).

Since SMEs are opaquer than larger companies, the lending to SMEs relies more on relationships with house-banks (Fouché et al., 2016; Gischer, Herz, & Menkhoff, 2012; Grunert & Norden, 2012). Although they are depending more on relationship lending, they have more difficulties in accessing traditional banking services. SMEs have more difficulties in accessing bank loans than large companies and small SMEs have more difficulties than larger SMEs (Schwartz, 2016; Seehausen, 2014). Andrieu, Staglianò, and Van der Zwan found that it is more likely that a larger and older SME

receives a bank loan than a smaller and younger SME (2017). Additionally, it is more likely that a bank charges a younger and informationally opaque SME higher interest rates than an established SME (Ekpu, 2016). Furthermore, due to the Basel requirements, loan provisions to SMEs are limited (Pahnke, Schroeder, Leonhardt, & Wiedemann, 2015; Udell, 2015). According to the Basel requirements, the higher the risk of the loan, the more regulatory capital has to be hold by the bank. This can cause higher interest rates and higher collateral requirements. The equity ratios of smaller SMEs are lower than of larger SMEs. Therefore, it is more difficult to receive a bank loan for smaller SMEs (Seehausen, 2014). In Germany, the equity ratio is a relevant figure in order to evaluate the leverage of the company (Reichling et al., 2005). The equity ratio is the relation of the equity to the total capital. The higher the equity ratio, the more stable the company, the more independent of other financial sources, and the better the company's creditworthiness (Woehe, Bilstein, Ernst, & Haecker Joachim, 2013). According to the KfW Banking Group, the average equity ratio of SMEs increased from 18.4% in 2002 to 29.7% in 2015, whereas the ratio of middle companies increased from 21.8% to 33.4%, of small companies from 15.0% to 31.3%, and of micro companies from 14.9% to 20.9%. It can be seen that in each year the ratio of middle companies is higher than of small companies and of small companies higher than of micro companies (Schwartz, 2016). The figures are summarised in table 2.

Table 2: Equity ratios of German SMEs

Equity ratios of SMEs in Germany			
in %	2002	2008	2015
SME total	18.4%	25.4%	29.7%
Micro	14.9%	19.8%	20.9%
Small	15.0%	23.9%	31.3%
Middle	21.8%	29.0%	33.4%

Source: Own illustration based on data from Schwartz 2016

Additionally, since smaller companies have lower turnovers, they have less diversification, and thus a higher volatility in turnover (Grunow & Figgner, 2006). Furthermore, based on the increasing banking regulations and the low interest environment, it is difficult for banks to cover the transaction costs for low loan volumes (Schwartz, 2016). The creditworthiness evaluation and the monitoring by the bank contain fixed costs. Since smaller companies have smaller investment volumes, they face higher costs per unit. The unit cost of funding decreases with an increase in investment volume (Fouché, Neugebauer, & Uthemann, 2016). This is also the reason why traditional factoring and mezzanine providers typically have minimum turnover requirements. In case of a relatively low loan volume, banks often avoid high efforts to reduce information asymmetries (Nohtse, 2012). Since SMEs partly have fewer reporting requirements, banks can face

higher information asymmetries (Schwartz, 2016). SMEs tend to be informationally opaque (Mercieca, Schaeck, & Wolfe, 2009; Navaretti, Calzolari, & Pozzolo, 2015). Therefore, often the interest rates and the collateral requirements are higher (Schwartz, 2016).

The results of this section show that SMEs depend more on relationship lending as they are opaquer than larger companies. However, primarily due to the higher information asymmetries, unit costs, and risks, traditional banks focus on larger companies rather than smaller ones. Due to these financing obstacles, financing fintechs might be a residual financing option for SMEs, which could be an indication for a disruptive innovation.

2.2 Relevant definitions

2.2.1 Traditional banking and banking landscape in Germany

The issue addressed in this section is to show what the definition of traditional bank implies and how the banking landscape in Germany is, which is relevant since this research focuses on the impact of financing fintechs on traditional banks in Germany.

“It is through a country’s financial system that entities with funds allocate those funds to those who have potentially more productive ways to deploy those funds” (Fabozzi and Drake 2009, p. 111). The process of allocating funds from capital providers to capital seekers does not always work directly. Under conditions that make it difficult to interact directly, the financial system founded financial intermediaries (Fabozzi & Drake, 2009). Financial intermediaries provide services in imperfect markets that are characterised by transaction costs and information asymmetries (Haas, Blohm, & Leimeister, 2014; Hartmann-Wendels, Pfingsten, & Weber, 2007). Based on an organised market with financial intermediaries, these costs can be reduced (Fabozzi & Drake, 2009; Van Hoose, 2010). According to the modern theory of financial intermediation, the existence of banks is explained by the presence of the market imperfection (Boscia & Salvo, 2009).

Commercial and investment banks are financial intermediaries (Fabozzi & Drake, 2009). The primary service of commercial banks consists of providing loans, accepting deposits, and further services like payment transaction services (Gomez, 2010; Hartmann-Wendels, Pfingsten, & Weber, 2007). The most corporate customers of commercial banks do not have access to equity or debt capital markets. The service of investment banks consists of assisting companies and institutions to raise equity or debt on capital markets, giving advice in transactions like mergers and acquisitions, purchasing and selling securities either on own book or on behalf of their customers, and offering asset management to manage customers’ funds (Hartmann-Wendels et al., 2007; Iannotta, 2010).

While commercial banks generate interest and commission income, investment banks generate commission and trading income (Massari, Gianfrate, & Zanetti, 2014). Investment banks act as a financial intermediary in the broader sense by supporting trading activities on financial markets. Commercial banks engage in lot size, maturity, and risk transformation (Hartmann-Wendels et al., 2007).

In Germany, there is no obligation to separate commercial banking from investment banking (Hartmann-Wendels et al., 2007). Germany is the home of universal banking (Heffernan, 2005). Universal banks provide both commercial and investment banking services (Berger, Molyneux, & Wilson, 2015). Corporate banking consists of commercial and investment banking services (Mueller, 2011). Corporate banking can be considered as every kind of financial solution for companies (Renker, 2005).

Traditional banking refers to the process known as financial intermediation whereby banks take funds from depositors and provide loans to borrowers (Girasa, 2016). Furthermore, traditional banks operate through physical branches (Colombo, 2017). However, they also have other channels like teller machines, call centres, and online banking including mobile banking via smartphones (Dapp, 2014). In contrast to traditional banks, direct banks, also defined as online banks, exclusively provide their services through online channels without branches (Auge-Dickhut, Koye, & Liebertrau, 2016). The service of the latter is typically more limited (Hartmann-Wendels et al. 2007). Neo banks, also defined as challenger banks, provide their services primarily via smartphones (Basel Committee of Banking Supervision, 2017).

The German banking landscape is a three-pillar system differing in terms of ownership. There are private, cooperative, and public saving banks. Private banks are owned by private shareholders and their major objective has always been to make profit. Cooperative banks are owned by their members and their major focus today is also to make profit. Public saving banks are owned by public bodies like municipalities, associations, and federal states and their major focus today is also to make profit (Hartmann-Wendels et al., 2007).

In order to operate as a bank within the euro area, a banking licence is required. In this research a bank is the synonym for the regulatory definition of a credit institution according to section 1 of the German Banking Act (KWG). The activity of a credit institution contains the ability to take deposits or other repayable funds from the public and to provide loans. According to section 4 of the Single Supervisory Mechanism (EU Regulation 1024/2013), the European Central Bank and the related

national authority are responsible for providing and withdrawing the banking licence. In Germany, it is the BaFin.

In this section, it is shown what traditional bank implies. In this research, traditional bank implies a bank with a banking licence that takes deposits and provides loans and therefore, provides a lot size, maturity and risk transformation, and that has physical branches to serve the customers. However, there are no specific differences considered between private, cooperative, and public saving banks.

2.2.2 Traditional financing instruments

2.2.2.1 *External equity financing*

Financing sources can be split into internal, which means to generate funds by turnover or restructuring the company's assets, and external, which means the funds come from outside (Pape, 2015). Regarding the rights and obligations, the maturity, and the risks and opportunities, financing instruments can be split into equity, debt, and mezzanine financing instruments (Pape, 2015; Reichling, Beinert, & Henne, 2005). The issue of this sub-section and the following sub-sections is to show what the traditional financing instruments such as traditional bank loans, factoring, and mezzanine imply, which is relevant to evaluate whether the services of financing fintechs can be a substitute for traditional banking services.

Since external equity investors take the full investment risks and opportunities, they have an influence on the company's executive management (Spremann, 2010). The risk implies to be liable for the company's liabilities that is at least the amount of investment, the participation in losses, the unlimited maturity, and to have no collateral (Pape, 2015). In case of capital companies, the investors' liabilities are limited to the amount invested, while in case of private companies, the investors' liabilities are not limited (Grunow & Figgner, 2006). The opportunities imply the unlimited participation in profit and the full proportional participation in an increase of company value (Pape, 2015).

2.2.2.2 *Traditional bank loans*

Since debt investors do not take the full investment risks and opportunities, the influence on the company's executive management is limited (Spremann, 2010). Debt has a limited maturity and is repaid independently of the company's profit. Short-term loans are not longer than one year (Brigham & Ehrhardt, 2017). Typically, long-term loans are not longer than 10 years. Generally,

short-term loans are used for working capital, while long-term loans are used for fixed assets (Schulz, 2010). In the event of insolvency, bank loans have a higher seniority than subordinated loans (Pape, 2015; Staroßom, 2013).

Collateral is related to an asset that is pledged to a secured bank loan. In case of a secured bank loan and a default event of the borrower, the bank can legally claim the asset. Otherwise, the bank's claim is solely based on the recourses that are offered by the country's legal system (Megginson, Smart, & Lucey, 2008). For example, companies can pledge marketable securities, land and buildings, equipment, inventory, and accounts receivable as collateral (Brigham & Ehrhardt, 2017). The kind of legal entity can also be relevant. In case of default of a private company, the bank can recourse against the personal and business assets, while in case of a capital company, the bank can exclusively recourse against the business assets. In SME lending a personal guarantee can also be required, which means the bank can recourse against the entire personal assets of the owner or executive manager of the company if a default occurs (Ekpu, 2016).

The bank loan contract can also contain covenants that oblige the company to fulfil certain rules (Vernimmen, Quiry, Dallochio, Le Fur, & Salvi, 2014). The covenants can be split into covenants that discourage undesirable behaviour, encourage desirable behaviour, keep collateral valuable, and covenants that oblige the borrower to provide certain information. Covenants that discourage undesirable behaviour can be restrictions to undertake risky investments or to use the funds of the loan solely for specific activities like purchasing defined equipment. Covenants that encourage desirable behaviour can be specifications to hold certain assets relative to the company's value to keep its net worth high. Covenants that keep the collateral valuable can be restrictions to keep the collateral in good conditions. Covenants that oblige the borrower to provide information can be the provision of quarterly accounting and income reports (Ekpu, 2016).

The interest rate can be fixed for the full term or variable that is regularly adjusted based on a reference rate such as the inter-bank rates EURIBOR or LIBOR. The interest rate depends on the credit risk that consists of the expected loss and the cost of capital for the unexpected loss, the refinancing costs, and the administration costs (Ekpu, 2016; Gruetzemacher & Theis, 2010).

The repayment can be based on a bullet structure meaning the repayment is at the end of maturity, while the interest is paid during the term. The annuity structure means the total payment including repayment and interest is constant over the term of the loan. At the beginning, the share of the interest payment is relatively high and the repayment of the loan relatively low. This is changing vice versa during the term. The balloon structure means a part of the repayment is repaid during

the term and the remaining part at the end of maturity, while the interest is paid during the term. There are also other kinds of repayments like the repayment with a holiday period adjusted to specific cash flows of a project or roller-coaster with irregular repayments (Coyle, 2002).

2.2.2.3 Traditional factoring

Traditional factoring means that a company which has a claim against its customer sells its account receivable to a traditional factoring provider (BaFin, 2009; Pape, 2015). In Germany, traditional banks like public saving, cooperative, and the big private banks either directly or indirectly provide factoring services by a specialised subsidiary (Bundesverband der Deutschen Volksbanken und Raiffeisenbanken e.V., 2018; CommerzFactoring, 2018; Deutsche Factoring Bank GmbH & Co. KG, 2018; Merl, 2008; PB Factoring GmbH, 2018; Reichling et al., 2005; UniCredit Bank AG, 2018).

Due to simplification reasons, in the following the factoring provider is defined as the bank and the company as the borrower. The steps of factoring are illustrated by figure 10.

Figure 10: Steps of factoring as financing instrument (notification factoring)

Source: Own presentation based on data from Pape 2015

The borrower makes a purchase agreement with its customer and delivers the product on credit. This means the company provides a trade credit to its customer. After the bank evaluated the creditworthiness of the borrower and especially the borrower's customer, the borrower and the bank agree on a factoring contract. Based on the contract, the company sells its accounts receivable to the bank and receives the advance payment in return reduced by the factoring costs. Finally, in case of notification factoring, the bank claims the account receivable against the borrower's customer and receives the funds. Generally, the bank does not buy individual accounts receivable;

instead by fulfilling certain criteria, it buys a portfolio of accounts receivable. Based on the portfolio, the bank takes diversity effects to reduce the credit risk (BaFin, 2009; Pape, 2015).

Factoring can have three functions that depend on the contract. The financing function means the borrower receives the funds in advance. The credit insurance function means the transfer of the credit risk from the borrower to the bank. The service function means the transfer of services like accounting of accounts receivable and dunning processes from the borrower to the bank. Regarding the credit insurance function, factoring can be split into non-recourse and recourse factoring. The former means the bank takes the credit risk of the borrower's customer, while the latter means the credit risk is kept by the borrower. Furthermore, factoring can be split into non-notification and notification factoring. The former means the borrower sells its accounts receivable to the bank without communication to its customer, while the latter means the customer is informed about the factoring contract and has to directly transfer the funds to the bank (BaFin, 2009; Pape, 2015).

The costs depend on the factoring functions. The financing costs are mainly based on the market interest rates for bank overdrafts. In case of non-recourse factoring, there is an additional risk cost that is primarily based on the creditworthiness of the borrower's customer. Typically, the bank charges the borrower for the creditworthiness evaluation, and in case of further services there are additional costs (BaFin, 2009; Pape, 2015).

Factoring is a financing instrument that is congruent with the company's turnover. This means the financing resources increase with an increase in turnover. Therefore, it can be used for growth ambitions (Dimler et al., 2018). Factoring is often an alternative for traditional bank loans, for example, to finance working capital (Merl, 2008; Tolkmitt, 2007). It can be used to meet trade credits or to provide trade credits to customers (Harms, 2010). Factoring can also increase the equity ratio, and thus the creditworthiness by reducing debt through the funds which became available (Dimler et al., 2018; Schulz, 2010).

2.2.2.4 Traditional mezzanine instruments

Depending on the national practices, there are different definitions of mezzanine. Mezzanine capital has characteristics of both equity and debt (Reichling et al., 2005). Therefore, it is also defined as hybrid financing. Depending on the different characteristics, mezzanine can be split into debt or equity mezzanine. In case it has more debt character, it is debt mezzanine, otherwise it is equity mezzanine (Nohtse, 2012).

Mezzanine can be used for companies in the growth phase to bridge temporary financing needs without the provision of voting rights for project financing or for acquisitions and buyouts (Grunow & Figgenger, 2006; Jetter, 2008; Keuper & Sikora, 2011). It can also be used for companies that do not receive bank loans. This might be the case if the company has insufficient collaterals or a low equity ratio (Reichling et al., 2005). Based on mezzanine instruments, the creditworthiness can be improved for debt financing (Decker & Ziese, 2005). However, the acceptance of mezzanine as equity depends on the bank's rating approach (Grunow & Figgenger, 2006).

The maturity of equity instruments is unlimited, of debt limited, and of mezzanine in between, which can include certain cancellation rights. The characteristics of the financing instruments are illustrated by figure 11.

Figure 11: Characteristics of financing instruments

Source: Own illustration based on Jetter 2008, p. 138

The cost of equity consists of the participation in profit and an increase of the company value. The cost of debt consists of the interest payments (Jetter, 2008). The cost of mezzanine can consist of both an interest and variable payment. The latter can be a non-equity, equity, or virtual-equity kicker. The non-equity kicker means there is an additional interest payment that depends on the success of the company based on defined reference values and thresholds. For example, an additional interest payment of 8% can be paid if the profit is more than 500 k€. The equity kicker means there is the right or option to convert debt into equity shares. The virtual-equity kicker is between and enables a participation in company value without having equity shares. The investment is treated like equity based on the virtual-equity kicker component. The calculation of the company value is contractually defined (Staroßom, 2013). In case of losses, equity investors fully participate, while debt investors do not. In mezzanine it depends on the contract. The

participation in losses can be agreed (Jetter, 2008). In case of insolvency, equity is subordinated, while debt is not. In mezzanine it depends on the contract (Nohtse, 2012). Finally, equity investors have voting and control rights, while debt investors can define certain covenants. In mezzanine it depends on the contract (Jetter, 2008).

In Germany, subordinated loans (Nachrangdarlehen), typical silent partnerships (typische stille Gesellschaft), convertible bonds (Wandelanleihe), and option bonds (Optionsanleihe) are debt mezzanine, while untypical silent partnerships (atypische stille Gesellschaft), participation rights (Genussrechte), and participation certifications (Genussscheine) are equity mezzanine (Bieg, Kußmaul, & Waschbusch, 2015; Pape, 2015). These financing instruments have different risk levels as shown by figure 12. The higher the risk for the investor, the higher the capital cost rate for the borrower. Debt instruments have the lowest, while equity the highest risk. In between are equity and debt mezzanine (Reichling et al., 2005; Seehausen, 2014).

Figure 12: Risk level and capital cost rate of financing instruments

Source: Own illustration based on Seehausen 2014, p. 242

Subordinated loans are unsecured loan agreements. In case of default, the claims are subordinated to senior debt (Grunow & Figgner, 2006). In case a non-equity kicker is included, it is a subordinated profit-participating loan (partiarisches Nachrangdarlehen). Typically, loss participation is not defined. In Germany, the legal base for subordinated loans is section 488 at seq. of the German Code of Civil (BGB). The conditions like the interest payment, repayment structure, and the right of cancellation can be individually agreed. Typically, the investor has information rights like receiving quarterly reports about the business development and conducting on site visits (Staroßom, 2013). The maturity of subordinated loans is usually between 5 and 10 years. Typically, investors are banks or other institutional investors (Staroßom, 2013).

In case of typical silent partnerships, the investor participates in the company's equity. However, it is an undisclosed partnership implying the investor's rights and obligations are legally obliged between the investor and the company and not externally to third parties. In Germany, the legal base of silent partnerships is section 230 to 236 of the German Commercial Act (HGB) (Grunow & Figgenger, 2006). The participation in the company's profit is legally obliged, while a loss participation that is limited to the value of the investor's equity can be agreed. Typically, a fixed interest rate and a non-equity kicker are agreed (Staroßom, 2013). According to section 233 of the German Commercial Act (HGB), the investor has a control right that consists of the validation of the annual report accuracy through accessing the business records. The exit of an investor includes a claim on the nominal value repayment (Bieg et al., 2015; Pape, 2015). Typically, institutional investors invest in typical silent partnerships, the volume ranges between 50 k€ and 10 mn€, and the maturity ranges between 5 and 10 years (Grunow & Figgenger, 2006).

Convertible bonds are fixed-income securities with a right to convert debt into equity, while option bonds, also known as warrant bonds, are fixed-income securities with an additional right to buy equity of the company (Grunow & Figgenger, 2006). Since both are not relevant in this research, they are not further described.

Both participation rights and certifications are agreements that contain certain obligations and rights. Participation rights are not securitised, while participation certifications are securitised. Therefore, the former is related to private and the latter to public mezzanine (Bieg et al., 2015; Pape, 2015). Private mezzanine has smaller volumes, individual contracts, and no secondary markets (Reichling et al., 2005). Since there is no legal definition, there is a leeway to define the rights and obligations, especially the economic conditions. It can include a fixed interest and a non-equity kicker. Typically, the loss participation is limited to the investor's nominal value (Bieg et al., 2015; Pape, 2015). The investor has certain information and control rights. In case of standardised agreements, the volume ranges between 5 and 15 mn€ and the maturity between 5 and 10 years. However, there are also maturities up to 30 years. Typically, institutional investors invest in participation rights and certifications (Grunow & Figgenger, 2006; Staroßom, 2013).

In contrast to a typical silent partnership, the investor of an untypical silent partnership participates in an increase of the company value (Bieg et al., 2015; Pape, 2015). Additionally, the investor has more rights including voting rights. Therefore, the investor has an active role in strategic and operative issues. The information, control, and voting rights depend on the contract. The cost of capital can consist of a fixed interest, a variable payment depending on the success of the company

like a participation in profit and a participation in an increase of the company value (Grunow & Figgener, 2006).

Traditional banks provide program mezzanine to SMEs that typically consists of standardised participation rights, silent partnerships, or subordinated loans (Keuper & Sikora, 2011; Merl, 2008; Nohtse, 2012; Von Haller, 2008). The economic conditions consist of a fixed interest rate and a variable component (Halt, Donch, Stiles, & Fesnak, 2017; Nohtse, 2012; Starořom, 2013). The variable payment to the investors typically depends on the companies' profits and the equity that is available. In contrast to traditional bank loans, for banks it is an off-balance sheet transaction (Keuper & Sikora, 2011; Merl, 2008; Nohtse, 2012; Von Haller, 2008). The construction of program mezzanine is illustrated by figure 13.

Figure 13: Procedure of program mezzanine

Source: Own presentation based on data from Nohtse 2012

Banks provide advisory and sales services, while the provision of the capital is through a special purpose vehicle (SPV). The SPV is initiated by the bank, while the administration of the SPV is conducted by an independent fund management. Additionally, the securitisation procedure involves a trustee who represents the interests of the investors. The SPV refinances the provision of mezzanine capital through collateral debt obligations (CDO). A portfolio of claims is securitised in different tranches to investors. The probability of default of the whole portfolio and the tranches are evaluated by a rating agency. Based on the agency's rating, the interest rate is defined. The fixed interest and variable payments are transferred from the company to the SPV during the entire term, while the repayment is at the end of the maturity. The tranches are based on a waterfall principle meaning there are different tranches in which higher tiered investors receive payment first, while lower tiered investors receive payment after the higher tiered investors are paid in full. The tranches are split into senior, mezzanine, and equity. From the interest and variable payments

that are paid by the companies, first the administration costs of the SPV are covered. Then, the defined interests for the senior tranches followed by the mezzanine and equity tranches are covered. In case of no payment, for example due to an insolvency, the interest payment to the equity tranche is suspended to build up the repayment volume for the higher tiered tranches. In case that not enough funds are available to repay the nominal volume to the investors, the lower tiered tranches take the losses at first (Nohtse, 2012).

For mezzanine program it is required to publish a prospectus to the investors. Typically, due to the complex structure and the information that is required of each company, the prospectus consists of 158 to 355 pages (Nohtse, 2012). During the period, the SMEs continually provide information about their business development (Keuper & Sikora, 2011). Further covenants can also be defined (Jetter, 2008). In contrast to standardised programs, there are also individualised contracts. The cost of the latter is higher because of the effort of individual requirements and negotiations (Keuper & Sikora, 2011).

This sub-section and the previously sub-sections showed what financing options companies have especially through traditional banks, and what characteristics they have. These results can be used for the definition of the deductively defined categories of the category systems of the documentary research and the expert interviews and to discuss the results.

2.2.3 SMEs and LMEs in Germany

The issue addressed in this section is to show what the definitions of SME and LME imply, which is relevant since this research consists of an appraisal of the business model of financing fintechs that provide services to SMEs and interviews with executives of LMEs.

There are different definitions of a SME or the so-called “Mittelstand” in Germany (Grunow & Figgner, 2006). According to the Centre for Small-and-Medium-Sized Business Research (IfM Bonn), there is a qualitative definition that considers the ownership and management of the company and a quantitative definition that considers the number of employees and turnover (2017). In Germany, the so-called “Mittelstand” is often used as synonym for “KMU” (Welter, May-Strobl, Wolter, & Guenterberg, 2014). Literally, “Mittelstand” means a mid-sized company, while “KMU” would mean a small-and-medium-sized enterprise (SME). In Germany, “Mittelstand” is often associated with the source of innovation, growth, and employment (Goeke, 2008).

According to the qualitative definition of the IfM Bonn, a company is defined as mid-sized company if up to two persons, or their family relatives, hold at least 50% of the company's shares and the persons are in the company's executive management. According to the IfM Bonn, mid-sized companies and owner- and family-managed companies are synonyms. Regarding the quantitative definition, the IfM Bonn defined three categories for a SME: Micro, small, and middle companies. The thresholds of the quantitative definition according to the IfM Bonn are illustrated in table 3.

Table 3: Quantitative definition of SME based on IfM Bonn

	Number of employees		Annual turnover	
SME in total	≤ 499	AND	≤ 50 mn €	
Micro	≤ 9	AND	≤ 2 mn €	
Small	≤ 49	AND	≤ 10 mn €	
Middle	≤ 499	AND	≤ 50 mn €	

Source: Own presentation based on IfM Bonn 2017

Micro companies do not have more than 9 employees and 2 mn€ in annual turnover. Small companies do not have more than 49 employees and 10 mn€ in annual turnover. Middle companies do not have more than 499 employees and 50 mn€ in annual turnover (IfM Bonn, 2017). The quantitative definition of the IfM Bonn is different from the definition of the EU commission. The EU commission's definition according to the recommendation 2003/361 includes the balance sheet value and the number of employees of middle companies is 249 at most (European Commission, 2003).

In total, 3,647 k companies existed in Germany in 2014. Thereof, 3,249 k (89.0%) micro companies, 307 k (8.4%) small companies, 76 k (2.2%) middle companies, and 15 k (0.4%) large companies existed. Large companies are companies that are larger than middle companies. This means of all German companies, 99.6% were SMEs. The total turnover of all companies was 6,236 bn€. Thereof, 577 bn€ (9.3%) related to micro companies, 674 bn€ (10.8%) to small companies, 953 bn€ (15.3%) to middle companies, and 4,032 bn€ (64.6%) to large companies. This means 35.4% of the total turnover was allocated to SMEs. The total number of employees who are subjected to the social insurance contribution was 28,101 k. Thereof, 3,934 k (14.0%) related to micro companies, 5,223 k (18.6%) to small companies, 7,280 k (25.9%) to middle companies, and 11,665 k (41.5%) to large companies. This means 58.5% of all employees worked in SMEs (Guenterberg, 2012). Based on these figures, also shown in table 4, it can be derived that SMEs are relevant especially in terms of number of companies and employees.

Table 4: Split in % by kind of company in Germany

Company split in Germany (SME definition IfM)						
Kind of company	Number of companies		Total turnover		Total employees	
	# in k	in %	# in bn€	in %	# in k	in %
Total	3,647	100.0%	6,236	100.0%	28,101	100.0%
SME total	3,632	99.6%	2,204	35.3%	16,437	58.5%
Micro	3,249	89.0%	577	9.3%	3,934	14.0%
Small	307	8.4%	674	10.8%	5,223	18.6%
Middle	76	2.2%	953	15.3%	7,280	25.9%
Large	15	0.4%	4,032	64.6%	11,665	41.5%

Source: Own presentation based on data from Guentenberg 2012

However, there are also other definitions. Banks have their own definitions (Duhnkrack, 2006). In order to differentiate between large companies and SMEs, the definitions of banks also often include turnover, number of employees, and balance sheet value (Decker & Ziese, 2005). The KfW Banking Group defines a company as SME if the annual turnover is not higher than 500 mn€ (Schwartz, 2016; Zimmermann, 2017). Grunow and Figgenger defined also a threshold of 500 mn€ (2006). According to Grunow and Figgenger, small companies are companies with less than 5 mn€ in annual turnover and less than 5 mn€ in balance sheet value. Mid-sized companies have an annual turnover between 5 and 50 mn€ and a balance sheet value between 5 and 25 mn€. Large mid-sized companies (LMEs) have an annual turnover between 50 and 500 mn€ and a balance sheet value between 55 and 200 mn€. According to the SME definition of the KfW Banking Group that includes companies up to 500 mn€ in annual turnover, 99,95% are SMEs. The majority of those SMEs is related to the service industry. 30.5% of the SMEs are related to services to businesses, 16.6% to services to consumers, 17.4% to trade, 10.3% to construction, 7.3% to manufacturing, 4.9% to transportation and communication, 4.1% to financial services, 3.1% to catering, and 5.9% to other industries (KfW Banking Group, 2015).

As shown in this section, there are different definitions of SME and LME. However, financing fintechs that provide services to SMEs might apply other definitions. For the sample definition of the interviews with executives, LMEs are defined as companies with an annual turnover between 50 and 500 mn€. Additionally, the industry allocation can be used for the sample selection.

2.2.4 The business model

2.2.4.1 General definition of the business model

The issue addressed in this section is to show what the definition of business model implies, which is relevant for the appraisal of the business model of financing fintech. Additionally, the business model is essential for the success of disruptive innovations of entrants and failures of incumbents (Christensen & Raynor, 2003; Johnson, Christensen, & Kagermann, 2008).

According to the existing literature, business models can be defined in different ways (Andreini & Bettinelli, 2017). The model implies simplified reflection of reality. Therefore, from a simplified perspective the business model means how a company undertakes its business (Tiberius & Rasche, 2017). According to Kotler, Berger, and Bickhoff, “a business model is a fairly recent attempt to formulate a simplified description of a company’s strategy” (2016, p. 47). Baden-Fuller and Morgan define the business model as “the logic of the firm, the way it operates and how it creates value for its stakeholder” (2010, p. 158). According to Teece the business model “reflects management’s hypothesis about what customers want, how they want it, and how the enterprise can organize to best meet those needs, get paid for doing so, and make a profit” (2010, p. 173).

Johnson et al. defined four interrelated components which relate to a business model: Customer value proposition (CVP), key processes, key resources, and profit formula as illustrated by figure 14 (2008).

Figure 14: Business model – four interrelated components

Source: Own illustration based on Johnson et al., 2008, p. 5

According to the authors, the CVP is the most relevant component and implies to create value for the customers. Customer value takes the perspective of a company's customers, considering what they want and believe that they get from buying and using a service or product. The customers' perceptions typically involve a trade-off between what customers receive and what they have to give up (Woodruff, 1997). The value can be communicated to the customers or can be an implicit promise. The CVP helps customers to perform a job that needs to be done. In this context, job means a fundamental problem in a given situation that needs a solution. The company needs a fundamental understanding of the job and has to design and deliver the respective solution to its customer target group. The more relevant the job is to the customer, the better the company's solution relative to existing alternatives, and the lower the price, the greater the CVP (Johnson et al., 2008; Payne, Frow, & Eggert, 2017).

The key processes mean the company's operational and managerial processes in order to deliver the value to the customer in the way it can be successfully repeated and increased in scale. The key resources are the company's key assets such as people, technology, products, and facilities that are required to deliver the value to the targeted customer (Johnson et al., 2008).

The profit formula means how the company creates value for itself while providing value to the customer. This primarily implies the revenue model and the cost structure (Johnson et al., 2008). Revenue refers to the company's pricing strategy which implies what services or products are priced in what way. In a simplified definition, the price multiplied by quantity is the revenue. There are different ways to split revenues, for example, usage-dependent and usage-independent and direct and indirect revenue. Usage-dependent revenue is generated with each use, while usage-independent is generated regardless of the usage. Direct revenue refers to the company's primary operations, while indirect revenue refers to any revenue arising from sources other than the primary operations (Kotler et al., 2016).

Costs can be split into fixed and variable. The former is independent and the latter depended on the level of services or products produced by the company (Taussig & Akron, 2017). Economies of scale are the cost advantages that companies obtain due to their increase in scale. The unit costs decline with increasing scale. Large companies experience economies of scale effects. Economies of scope imply lowering average cost by producing more types of services or products. This can be caused by, for example, management structures and systems consolidated at a single point instead of presence in each segment or subsidiary. The emergence of learning effects, which bring corresponding cost benefits, is reflected in the experience curve. The experience curve effects refer

to unit costs to cumulative volume. Therefore, these effects are also available to smaller companies that have been active in the market a long time (Kotler et al., 2016).

Larger companies often simultaneously implement several different business models to deliver value to different markets. This means the company has a portfolio of different business models (Sabatier, Mangematin, & Rouselle, 2010).

As shown in this section, there is not just one definition of business model. Since the four interrelated components of Johnson et al. (2008) provide a comprehensive picture with different aspects, they can be used to qualitatively appraise the business model of financing fintechs. However, since financing fintechs have a two-sided marketplace business model (Belleflamme & Lambert, 2014; Dorfleitner, Rad, & Weber, 2017), there are further aspects which have to be considered.

2.2.4.2 Definition of the two-sided marketplace business model

The issue addressed in this section is to show what the definition of a two-sided marketplace business model implies, which is relevant for the appraisal of the business model of financing fintechs.

A two-sided marketplace business model is based on a platform that brings together two sides to enable direct interactions between them (Eisenmann, Parker, & Alstyne, 2006; Hagiu & Wright, 2014). Therefore, it can also be defined as platform business model, which inherently rely on independent actors to co-create value (Taeuscher & Laudien, 2018). The platform provides infrastructure and governance (Eisenmann et al., 2006).

In contrast to traditional value chains, which move from left to right (left of the company is cost, while right is revenue), on a platform the costs and revenues can be on both sides (to the left and right) because it can serve distinct groups of actors. The platforms can be physically located such as malls that bring together consumers and sellers (Eisenmann et al., 2006). They can also be digital, for example, Uber in transportation, Airbnb in accommodation, and Lending Club in finance (Taeuscher & Laudien, 2018). Intermediaries can choose to function as a marketplace on which suppliers sell their products to buyers or as a reseller which implies that the intermediary buys products from suppliers and resells them to buyers. The former is a platform business model (Hagiu & Wright, 2014). This is illustrated by figure 15.

Figure 15: Intermediary – Reseller versus marketplace function

Source: Own illustration based on Hagiu and Wright 2014, p. 184

The network effect of platforms implies that the actors are attracted or unattracted to each other. Attracting implies positive network effects where an increasing number of actors makes it more valuable, while unattractive implies negative network effects where an increasing number makes it less valuable. Additionally, the network effects can be one-sided or cross-sided (Eisenmann et al., 2006). The former are within-group effects that imply that the benefit of network participation to an actor depends on the number of other network actors within the same side, while the latter are cross-group effects that imply that the benefit of network participation to an actor depends on the number of other network actors on the other side (Belleflamme et al., 2015). Due to the network effects, successful platforms that surpassed a critical mass in terms of number of participants on both sides enjoy increasing returns to scale (Eisenmann et al., 2006), while platforms that do not reach a critical mass will probably fail (Blohm et al., 2015). Return to scale describes the change of the rate of increase in output relative to the associated increase in input, under the ceteris paribus assumption. In constant return to scale, there are the same change percentages in both output and input. In decreasing return to scale, the input has a higher percentage of change than the output, while in increasing return to scale, the output has a higher percentage of change than the input (Taussig & Akron, 2017). The outcome of positive network effects is often a winner-takes-it-all result especially when the costs of affiliating with multiple platforms are high for network actors and the demand for differentiated features is limited (McIntyre & Srinivasan, 2017). In order to increase the network effect, platforms often subsidise one side (Eisenmann et al., 2006).

According to Tauscher and Laudien (2018), two-sided digital marketplace business models fulfil the following criteria: First, these platforms match independent actors from a demand and supply side via a digital platform, whereas it is not necessarily required that the actors are related to different groups. The actors may participate in the market on both sides, the demand and supply

side. Second, these actors enter direct interactions with each other. Third, the platforms provide a frame for transactions without a substantial produce or trade of the service or product.

As shown in this section, in two-sided marketplace business models three different parties are involved – the actors from demand, the actors from supply, and the platform – which should be considered for the appraisal of the business model of financing fintechs.

2.2.5 Brief definition of big data analytics and machine learning

This issue addressed in this section is to show what the definitions of big data analytics and machine learning imply. This is relevant for the appraisal of the business model of financing fintechs and the evaluation of whether the services of financing fintechs can be a substitute for traditional banking services since financing fintechs could use these technologies to create soft information and therefore, to reduce the information asymmetries.

Big data and machine learning are widespread topics in the press (Shalev-Shwartz & Bend-David, 2014; Witten, Frank, Hall, Pal, & Kaufmann, 2017). This can be contributed to the promotional initiatives by leading technology companies who invested in building the market, but also to the fact that unlike former times the techniques are being deployed to solve real-world problems (Gandomi & Haider, 2015; Rebala, Ravi, & Churiwala, 2019).

Big data analytics can be considered as a synonym to big data (Dorfleitner & Hornuf, 2018). Big data consists of three following dimensions: Volume, variety, and velocity. The first refers to the magnitude of data. Big in terms of data volume is relative and varies by factors such as time and type of data. Therefore, the threshold for big data volume definition depends on the industry. Variety refers to the structural heterogeneity of the data. This can be split into structured, semi-structured, and unstructured data. Structured data refers to tabular data found in spreadsheets or relational databases, while unstructured data refers to data that lacks a structural organisation like text, images, audio, and video. In between is semi-structured data that does not conform to strict standards like extensible mark-up language (XML), which is a textual language for exchanging data on the internet. Velocity refers to the rate at which data are created and the speed at which it should be analysed. Due to the proliferation of digital devices such as smartphones and sensors, the demand for real-time analytics is increasing. The value of big data is given when companies can leverage on evidence-based decision making (Gandomi & Haider, 2015). “The availability of big data, retrieved from various data sources, with different data formats and sizes, can provide a more complete picture of a borrower” (Yan et al., 2015, p. 6). “Big data means that all information about

the customer can be used in real time for the precise analysis of customer behaviour, to derive the correlation between results and behaviour, and thus to make perfectly tailored predictions and cluster formations by using all available data sources” (Auge-Dickhut et al., 2016, p. 23).

Machine learning is a core technique of artificial intelligence (Aziz & Dowling, 2019; European Banking Authority, 2018; Ryll et al., 2020). Artificial intelligence is a term formed by socio-behavioural rationales of human capabilities – principally, expectations that machines could emulate human cognition and behaviour (Ryll et al., 2020). Machine learning can be described as the change of a system resulting from an interaction with its environment (Ryll et al., 2020). “A system interacts with its environment in such a way that the structure of the system changes, in turn transforming its interaction with its environment, creating an iterative process” (Ryll et al., 2020, p. 16). Machine learning is achieved by a self-learning algorithm, which is a program that allows computers to learn from the input available to them. Learning means to convert experience into knowledge or expertise (Shalev-Shwartz & Bend-David, 2014). Machine learning can have similarities with and differences from statistics (Bzdok, Altman, & Krzywinski, 2018; Witten et al., 2017). However, there are different definitions and philosophical discussions about the meaning of machine learning (Witten et al., 2017; Shalev-Shwartz & Bend-David, 2014).

Generally, machine learning can be divided into three categories: supervised, unsupervised, and reinforcement (Arslanian & Fischer, 2019). In supervised machine learning there is a clear objective outlined, and the data is structured and labelled by humans (Arslanian & Fischer, 2019). Labelled data means that the right answer to a question related to data is known, while unlabelled means it is not known. The self-learning algorithm is provided with a set of labelled data points while it has to learn the key characteristics within each data point in the dataset to determine the answer. The next time the self-learning algorithm is provided with a new data point, it should be able to define the right answer based on the key characteristics (Rebala, Ravi, & Churiwala, 2019). In unsupervised machine learning, there is only input data, and it is wished to learn more about the structure of the data (Aziz & Dowling, 2019). The self-learning algorithm is provided with a set of unlabelled data and is allowed to identify clusters or groups of similar items or similarity of new item with existing group (Rebala, Ravi, & Churiwala, 2019). Reinforcement machine learning is different from the aforementioned categories in that it is based on an action-response model (Ryll et al., 2020). The external environment is continuously changing, and the response from the machine has to consider the changed environment. The learning has to result in the machine sensing the external environment and selecting an action based on its own state and the external environment, with the aim of maximizing a specific pre-defined objective (Rebala, Ravi, & Churiwala, 2019).

Machine learning uses data that is already available in a database (Witten et al., 2017). It provides advantage especially when leveraging with big data (European Banking Authority, 2018). The idea is to have computer programs that scrutinize databases automatically, seeking regularities or patterns (Witten et al., 2017). Based on machine learning, the loan decision process can be supported (Witten et al., 2017). Navaretti et al. argue that big data and machine learning may complement or replace relationship banking by the possibility of relying on a large set of data that is explored with powerful computers and algorithms that explore, learn, and identify patterns (2018). “Improving pattern recognition with machine learning, for example in text and verbal communication, could complement (or perhaps replace) this human activity” (Navaretti et al., 2018, p. 11). Since fintechs leverage on technology, both big data and machine learning could be used to decrease information asymmetries and to evaluate the creditworthiness of borrowers faster and more accurately, and possibly also in cases where conventional data is not available (Cummins, Lynn, Mac an Bhaird, & Rosati, 2019; European Banking Authority, 2018; Navaretti et al., 2018). However, an issue in machine learning can be the availability of suitable data and that the self-learning algorithm is not transparent, which can cause regulatory compliance issues (Aziz & Dowling, 2019).

As shown in this section, based on big data analytics and machine learning, soft information might be produced to reduce the information asymmetry. For the appraisal of the business model of financing fintechs and for the evaluation whether the services can be a substitute for traditional banking services, these aspects have to be evaluated.

2.3 Summary and conclusion

In order to achieve the research aim and objectives and to answer the research questions, the theoretical and conceptual frameworks are required. Based on these frameworks, issues are identified that are relevant for this research. The deductively defined categories of the category systems of the documentary research and the expert interviews are also constructed on these issues. Furthermore, the results of the documentary research and the expert interviews are discussed and evaluated along these issues. The linkage between each issue, which is represented through the sections, to the research objectives is illustrated by figure 16.

Figure 16: Linkage between theoretical and conceptual frameworks to research objectives

Source: Own source

The disruptive innovation theory relates to the third research objective. Disruptive innovation is a theory that shows how entrants can disrupt incumbents by either creating new markets or reshaping existing markets. Whether or not a disruptive innovation is critical depends especially on whether the entrants' services or products are complements to or substitutes for the incumbents' services or products. The concept of the disruptive innovation theory can be applied to evaluate the disruptive innovation threat of financing fintechs that provide service to SMEs in Germany to traditional banks.

The understanding and application of the theories which are related to the transaction costs and information asymmetries are relevant for the first and second research objective as traditional banks reduce the information asymmetries and transaction costs. For the appraisal of the business model of financing fintechs and for the evaluation of whether the services can be a substitute for traditional banking services, it has to be evaluated whether financing fintechs also reduce the information asymmetries and transaction costs.

The capital structure theories such as the static trade-off and pecking order theories are relevant for the second and third research objective since they explain how executives' decisions of the selection of financing instruments might be driven. First, these theories can be applied in the interviews with the executives to check whether their decisions are driven as defined in the

theories. Second, it can be evaluated which segment of financing fintechs, i.e. crowdlending, crowdinvesting, or factoring platforms is more or less disruptive in character.

The concepts of the two different lending technologies and the illustration of the SME financing limitations to traditional financing are relevant for all research objectives. First, for the appraisal of the business model meaning which lending technology is applied by the financing fintechs and second, whether this technology can be a substitute for traditional banking services for LMEs. Third, the financing limitations of SMEs can support the evaluation of the disruptive innovation as SMEs can be considered as low-end or non-customers.

The definitions of traditional banking and the banking landscape in Germany are related to the third research objective since this research focuses on the impact of financing fintechs on traditional banks in Germany.

The definitions of the traditional financing instruments are relevant for the second research objective. As mentioned, the disruptive innovation is critical especially when the entrants' services or products are substitutes for the incumbents' services or products. Therefore, the traditional banking instruments such as traditional bank loans, traditional factoring, and traditional mezzanine have to be understood to evaluate whether the services of financing fintechs can be a substitute – crowdlending platforms provide loans, crowdinvesting platforms provide mezzanine instruments, and factoring platforms provide factoring.

The definition of SME is relevant for the first research objective as it includes the appraisal of the business model of financing fintechs that provide services to SMEs, while the definition of LME is relevant for the second objective as it includes interviews with executives of LMEs. However, both are also relevant for the third research objective as the disruptive innovation theory differentiates between low-end and mainstream customers. Nevertheless, financing fintechs that provide services to SMEs might apply other definitions. For the sample definition of the interviews with executives of LMEs, the definition of LME can be applied.

The definitions of the business model and the two-sided marketplace business model are relevant for the first research objective. Although there are different definitions, in this research the aspects of the two-sided marketplace business model can be applied to analyse the business model of financing fintech – it implies different aspects for the borrower, investors, and the platform. Furthermore, the four interrelated components, customer value proposition (CVP), key processes,

key resources, and profit formula, can be applied to qualitatively appraise in depth the business model of financing fintechs.

The definitions of big data analytics and machine learning are relevant for the first and second research objective. Since SMEs are often informationally opaque, relationship banking can be an advantage for SMEs. In case financing fintechs leverage on technology such as big data and machine learning, the information asymmetries might also be reduced. Therefore, for the appraisal of the business model and the evaluation to which extent the service of financing fintechs is a substitute for traditional banking, these aspects have to be evaluated.

3 Narrative literature review of financing fintech related studies – examination of research gap

The purpose of this chapter is to present the studies that are related to financing fintechs to provide an overview of the existing literature and to show the research gap. The studies in this chapter support the understanding of this research and provide a basis for the conduction of this research. This includes that the studies are used as basis for the definition of the deductively defined categories in the category systems of the documentary research and the expert interviews and as basis for the discussion and evaluation of the research results. The narrative literature review is thematically structured which is described in the next section.

3.1 Approach of narrative literature review

In order to provide a comprehensive overview of the current state of research and to illustrate the research gap, the method of a narrative literature review can be used (Baumeister & Leary, 1997; Green, Johnson, & Adams, 2006). The narrative literature review includes the summary and evaluation of studies associated to a particular topic. In contrast, the focus of a systematic literature review is solely on one specific subject (Onwuegbuzie & Frels, 2016). Since this research is based on a qualitative multi-method approach, a narrative literature review is applied. The objective is not to test hypotheses.

To provide a comprehensive overview of the topic of financing fintechs, the narrative literature review is thematically structured. First, the market volume development is illustrated to show the actual relevance of financing fintechs. Second, the different financing fintechs, i.e. crowdlending, crowdinvesting, and factoring platforms are defined, and their business model characteristics are described – the results are used as basis for the definition of the deductively defined categories of the category systems of the qualitative content analyses to appraise in-depth the business models of financing fintechs that specifically provide services to SMEs in Germany. Third, studies are summarised that relate to the question whether or not the service of financing fintechs is a substitute for traditional banking services for companies in Germany – the results are used as basis for the definition of the deductively defined categories of the category system of the expert interviews to explore and evaluate to which extent the service of financing fintechs is a substitute for traditional banking services to LMEs in Germany. Fourth, literature is illustrated that is related to the strategic impact of fintechs on traditional banks and the reactions of traditional banks. Fifth, a forecast of the financing fintech market volume is shown. Finally, in the summary and conclusion chapter, the research gap is explicitly illustrated.

The procedure of a narrative literature review should include the definition of the selection criteria, the definition of the search terms and databases, and the documentation of the search process (Green et al., 2006). First, the selection criteria were defined. Below the criteria (C) and the related rationales (R) are shown to select the relevant studies to provide a comprehensive overview of the current state of research:

- C1: Solely literature that is related to one of the themes mentioned above. R1: Based on these themes, the current state of research and the research gap can be illustrated. Especially the results of theme two, three, and four are used as basis for the primary research.
- C2: Theoretical and empirical studies. R2: In order to illustrate a comprehensive picture of the current state of research and to have a basis for the primary research, both kinds of studies are relevant.
- C3: Quantitative and qualitative studies. R3: In order to illustrate a comprehensive picture of the current state of research and to have a basis for the primary research, both kinds of studies are relevant.
- C4: Literature in German and English. R4: Since the research scope is the German market, literature in German is also relevant.

Since countries adapt their regulatory framework to the local markets which results in different rules and therefore, in different business models (European Commission, 2016), for the identification and illustration of the research gap, solely empirical studies from Germany and official legal requirements from the German regulator are considered. Additionally, since the research gap is specifically related to each research question, as shown in the summary and conclusion section, theme two, three, and four are particularly relevant to identify and illustrate the research gap.

Second, the key terms for the search were defined. The key terms are illustrated by figure 17. The key terms are small-and-medium-sized company and SME as an acronym, traditional bank and traditional financing provider as a synonym, Germany, and fintechs. The service of fintechs can be described as alternative finance. As already mentioned, this research focuses on crowdlending, crowdinvesting, and factoring platforms. Crowdlending and crowdinvesting are related to crowdfunding (Dorfleitner, Hornuf, Schmitt, & Weber, 2017). The synonyms of crowdlending are marketplace lending, peer-to-peer lending, and P2P lending (European Banking Authority, 2015). The synonym of crowdinvesting is equity-based crowdfunding (European Commission, 2015; Hornuf & Neuenkirch, 2017). Factoring platforms can also be described as online or platform invoice trading (Dorfleitner, Rad, & Weber, 2017).

Figure 17: Illustration of key terms for narrative literature review

Source: Own source

Third, based on the key terms and logical connections, the following databases were searched. UWS One Search, Google Scholar, EBSCO Business Source Premier, and GVKPlus (German union catalogue via HAW). These databases were selected because they cover a wide range of journals. The initial search procedure for each database including the key terms, logical connections, date of search, and the number of results is illustrated in appendix A. Additionally, based on a track and trace approach, further studies were identified. In the next chapter the results are illustrated.

3.2 Results of literature review

3.2.1 Development of financing fintech market volume

Zhang, Ziegler et al. (2016) and Ziegler et al. (2019) analysed the financing fintech market in Germany based on surveys which were a part of surveys to financing fintechs in European countries excluding the UK. The former was conducted from May to June 2016 to 273 financing fintechs, while the latter was conducted from May to November 2018 to 269 financing fintechs. The data was partly enriched by secondary sources like annual reports, press releases, and other public data. In Germany, the total financing fintech volume without factoring increased from 65 mn€ in 2013 to 595 mn€ in 2017. Thereof, 416 mn€ is related to crowdlending to consumers and businesses and to crowdfunding, while 179 mn€ is related to other categories such as donation-based and reward-based crowdfunding and crowdfunding for real estate – the latter categories are not further considered because they are not in the scope of this research.

The figures are illustrated by figure 18. The volume of crowdlending to consumers increased by 803% from 36 mn€ in 2013 to 325 mn€ in 2017 while the CAGR (compound annual growth rate) was 73%. In the same period, the volume of crowdinvesting ultimately increased by 18% from 17 mn€ to 20 mn€, while in between it decreased from 30 mn€ in 2014 to 24 mn€ in 2015 and from 47 mn€ in 2016 to 20 mn€ in 2017 – the CAGR was 4%. The volume of crowdlending to business was firstly measured in 2014 with 6 mn€, which ultimately increased by 1,083% to 71 mn€ in 2017, while in between it decreased from 49 mn€ in 2015 to 23 mn€ in 2016 – the CAGR was 278%. According to Dorfleitner, Hornuf, Schmitt, and Weber, the factoring volume in Germany was measured in 2015 with 500 mn€, which increased by 44% to 720 mn€ in 2016 (2016, 2019).

Figure 18: Development of financing fintech market in Germany

Source: Own illustration based on data from Dorfleitner, Hornuf, Schmitt, & Weber 2016, 2019; Ziegler et al. 2019; Zhang, Ziegler et al. 2016

Dorfleitner et al. considered the sum of investments in 2015 of business angels (650 mn€) and venture capital funds (450 mn€) as potential market for crowdinvesting (2016). This implies that crowdinvesting is no substitute for traditional bank loans. Considering these volumes and the actual crowdinvesting volume in 2015 as potential market, the market share is 2.1%. However, for established SMEs crowdinvesting might also be an alternative to traditional banking (Demary, Hornik, & Watfe, 2016). The total loan volume to SMEs in Germany for investments was 62,200 mn€ in 2015 (Schwartz, 2016). Considering this volume and the actual volume of crowdlending to business in 2015 as potential market, the market share is 0.08%. Dorfleitner et al. considered the total factoring volume of 210,000 mn€ in 2015 of traditional factoring providers as potential market for factoring platforms (German Factoring Association, 2015; Dorfleitner et al., 2016). Considering

this volume and the actual volume of factoring platforms in 2015 as potential market volume, the market share is 0.24%.

In comparison to other countries, the market volume in Germany is small. As already mentioned, in the UK, the financing fintech market volume increased from 670 mn£ in 2013 to 6,190 mn£ in 2017 (Zhang, Ziegler et al., 2018). In the same period, the financing fintech market volume in the United States of America (US) increased from 4,400 mnUS\$ to 42,810 mnUS\$ (Ziegler, Johanson, King et al., 2018) and in China from 6,000 mnUS\$ to 358,000 mnUS\$ (Ziegler, Johanson, Zhang et al., 2018). Of the worldwide crowdfunding volume, 98% is related to crowdfunding with financial return and thereof, 96%-points to crowdlending (Rau, 2017).

As shown in this section, the current market is relatively small in Germany. However, as mentioned in chapter two, according to the disruptive innovation theory, the market size is less relevant than the growth rates (Christensen et al., 2004). Therefore, the high growth rates might be an indication that financing fintechs are a disruptive innovation.

3.2.2 Definition and business model characteristics of financing fintechs

3.2.2.1 Crowdfunding

Crowdfunding describes the use of small amounts of funds, obtained from a large number of individual or professional investors, to finance a project, business, or personal loan through an online web-based platform (Kirby & Worner, 2014). At the beginning of crowdfunding, it was mainly used to finance various types of artists like musicians, film creators, and journalism (Moritz & Block, 2016). The idea of crowdfunding is not new because Mozart and Beethoven have already financed concerts and publications of new music manuscripts via advance subscriptions from interested parties (Hemer, 2011). Based on crowdfunding, a borrower can raise external financing from a large audience through an open call on the internet (Ahlers, Cumming, Guenther, & Schweizer, 2015; Belleflamme, Lambert, & Schwiabacher, 2014). Crowdfunding platforms do not borrow from capital providers (investors), neither do they pool and lend money to capital seekers (borrowers) on their own book; instead they provide certain functionalities and perform as electronic matching market (Haas et al., 2014). Crowdfunding platforms are two-sided marketplace business models that provide a matching service between two sides of the market (Belleflamme & Lambert, 2014; Belleflamme et al., 2015; Pur et al., 2014). These platforms serve distinct groups of customers that need each other. Each group depends on the participation of the other group (Belleflamme & Lambert, 2014). Crowdfunding does not provide a one-to-one matching but a one-to-many matching because a funding requires more than one investor (Belleflamme et al., 2015).

“The concept of crowdfunding is rooted in the broader concept of crowdsourcing, which refers to using the crowd to obtain ideas, feedback, and solutions to develop corporate activities” (Belleflamme et al., 2014, p. 587). The crowd can be considered as anyone with access to the internet (Mwila, 2012), or those internet users that obtain knowledge about the funding (Gossel, Bruentje, & Will, 2016). Since crowdfunding is published online, it can be used to send signals to the market. This can be considered as an additional instrument to increase the company’s representation (Leboeuf & Schwienbacher, 2018). Analogous to the idea of crowdsourcing, feedback of potential investors can be received to improve or validate the business idea (Blohm et al., 2015; Gierczak et al., 2016). However, there is a legal risk, which means the idea that is published on the crowdfunding platform can be reproduced (European Banking Authority, 2015). This can have negative effects on intellectual property protection, especially for knowledge-based business models and on bargaining with potential suppliers (Agrawal, Catalani, & Goldfarb, 2014). To reduce the risk, the information that is published to the investors should not be too detailed and the core service or product should be ready for the market (Hagedorn and Pinkwart 2016).

Network effects in crowdfunding can occur in a cross-sided or one-sided way. The former is between companies and investors, while the latter is between companies themselves or investors themselves. The possible network effects are illustrated by figure 19.

Figure 19: Possible network effects in crowdfunding

Source: Own illustration based on data from Belleflamme et al., 2015

In the first case, positive network effects can arise as more investors on the platform may attract more companies (more investors imply a greater funding volume), which in turn can attract even more investors (more companies imply a greater investment variety). However, there can also be

cases of negative network effects where investors are more attracted by a platform with a smaller number of borrowers because this increases the probability that any given funding will achieve a required threshold. In the second case, also two opposing effects can occur: Positive network effects can arise as more investors can make it more attractive for others to join the platform because fundings are more likely to be funded. However, more investors can also mean more competition for a limited number of investment opportunities. The effects are negative among borrowers: A borrower, for any given number of investors, is likely to find it more difficult to obtain the required funds if there are more competing fundings (Belleflamme et al., 2015).

Crowdfunding platforms often focus on specific niches, for example start-ups or SMEs (Gierczak et al., 2016; Zetzsche & Preiner, 2018). For SMEs crowdfunding can be an alternative to traditional banking (Dorfleitner & Hornuf, 2018). As mentioned, donation-based crowdfunding, reward-based crowdfunding, crowdlending, and crowdinvesting are related to crowdfunding, whereas the latter two segments are related to crowdfunding with financial return. However, crowdfunding platforms cannot always be clearly assigned to one model. “What is important is the contractual design of the particular business model and not its name or its purely formal allocation to one of the four crowdfunding models” (BaFin, 2017b). Within the European Union, crowdfunding is restricted by the national regulatory authorities (Belleflamme & Lambert, 2014). Member states are tailoring their regulatory frameworks to the local markets which results in different rules (European Commission, 2016).

3.2.2.2 Crowdlending

This section and the following sections of chapter 3.2.2 show the definition of crowdlending, crowdinvesting and factoring platforms and their general business model characteristics, which implies not only literature that is related to the German market. This provides an overview of their business model characteristics and provides a basis for the definition of the deductively defined categories of the documentary research. For the illustration of the research gap, solely literature related to the German market is considered – this is shown by table 8 in the summary and conclusion of this chapter.

The European Banking Authority defines crowdlending as “open calls to the wider public by fund seekers through a third party, typically an online platform, to raise funds for a project or for personal purposes, in the form of a loan agreement, with a promise to repay with (or in certain cases without) interest. The fund raisers may include individuals, start-up companies or existing SMEs that are seeking an alternative means of funding, rather than the traditional credit market”

(2015, p. 8). Crowdlending can be understood as a form of debt-based crowdfunding (Fenwick, McCahery, & Vermeulen, 2018). Crowdlending can also be defined as peer-to-peer lending or marketplace lending (European Banking Authority, 2015; European Commission, 2016). Crowdlending to business means individual or professional investors directly lend to a company (European Commission, 2016).

After the borrower has applied for funding, the platform selects the funding based on due diligence. This can include the identification of the borrower, checking of the borrower's eligibility for a loan, and creditworthiness evaluation (European Commission, 2016). The creditworthiness evaluation is either directly conducted by a credit investigation company or by the platform's own risk management. In case the platform has its own risk management, it is often based on input from a credit investigation company. The level of the interest rate is typically driven by the creditworthiness and maturity (Dorfleitner et al., 2016; Sixt, 2014).

Crowdlending platforms are diverse in their matching mechanisms which bring investors and borrowers together (Cumming & Hornuf, 2017). The matching mechanism depends also on the regulatory system (European Commission, 2016). One mechanism is that the funding is published on the platform and the borrower defines the interest rate and maturity. Then, investors can screen the funding and decide whether or not they want to invest their funds (European Banking Authority, 2015). Another mechanism is that the funding is published on the platform and the borrower defines the maturity and the platform defines the interest rate based on a creditworthiness evaluation. Then, the investors can screen the funding and can decide whether or not they want to invest (Kaefer, 2016). In case more funds are available than the defined funding limit, the first-come, first-serve principle can be applied (Hagedorn & Pinkwart, 2016). It means an overall funding limit, which is typically larger than the minimum threshold, is set, and in case the limit is reached, there is no further option to invest (Hornuf & Schwienbacher, 2015a). Another mechanism is that the funding is published on the platform, the maturity is defined by the borrower, and the interest rate is defined in an auction in which the investors bid between themselves to offer the lowest interest. Another mechanism is that the investors provide funds to the platform and define certain preferences like risk level and interest rate. Then, the platform itself allocates the funds to the borrowers (European Banking Authority, 2015). The latter can also be defined as an auto-bid mechanism (Zhang et al., 2016). However, the studies mentioned above, do not show the explicit matching mechanisms of crowdlending platforms that provide service to SMEs in Germany.

The most platforms follow the all-or-nothing principle meaning a funding threshold is set at the beginning of the funding. In case the threshold cannot be raised within a pre-defined period, the funds pledged by the investors are given back (Gierczak et al., 2016). This implies that the planned returns of the funding can solely be delivered in case the full required funds are available. In contrast, some platforms apply the keep-it-all-principle, which means the collected funds can be kept by the borrower irrespective of whether or not the funding threshold is reached. The latter is typically used in crowdfunding without financial return (Gierczak et al., 2016).

The predominant motivation of crowdfunding platforms, especially of those offering crowdfunding with financial return, is to make profit. Therefore, their objective is to maximise the number and volume of successful fundings. This requires a high scale of investors, borrowers, and high-quality fundings. The platforms have an incentive to attract a high share of media attention to increase the network effects (Agrawal et al., 2014; Beck, 2014). Due to the network effects, and hence the possible winner-takes-it-all results, the pressure to grow as platform can increase the adverse selection (Navaretti, Calzolari, Mansilla-Fernández, & Pozzolo, 2018).

The most platforms have a fee-based revenue structure (Navaretti et al., 2018). The fee paid to the platform depends on the type of instrument, the platform, and additional services (European Commission, 2016; Hagedorn & Pinkwart, 2016; Kirby & Worner, 2014). There might be interest income for the in-between period in which the investors provided funds to the platform for a funding to the point the funds are passed to the borrowers (Belleflamme et al., 2015). The platforms can charge borrowers for the publication of the funding on their platforms, for consultancy services, for each funding transaction, or a fixed fee for the usage of the platform. Borrowers can also be charged in case of succeeding the funding volume (Beck, 2014). The fees can also be categorised in one-off and annual fees (Kaefer, 2016). The platform could charge borrowers and investors. Some platforms charge both sides, others charge solely one side (Evans, 2011). Since the participation of one group is conditioned on the participation of the other group, platforms often subsidise the more elastic side (Belleflamme et al., 2014; Navaretti et al., 2018). Investors can be charged for screening investment opportunities, for investment support, for each funding transaction, or by a fixed fee for the usage of the platform. They can also be charged in case of succeeding the total investment volume (Beck, 2014) or by another fee which depends on the borrower's performance (Zetzsche & Preiner, 2018). The platforms have different pricing strategies. Once the market has consolidated, the pricing strategies may change (Belleflamme et al., 2015). However, the studies mentioned above, do not show the explicit fees and interest rates of crowdlending platforms that provide service to SMEs in Germany.

The loans in crowdlending can be secured or unsecured with a collateral (European Commission, 2016). The maximum volume without the provision of a prospectus is 2.5 mn€ according to section 2a of the German Investment Act (VermAnlG). Any kind of prospectus for financing instruments has to be approved by the BaFin. The BaFin charges 6.5 k€ for the approval procedure (BaFin, 2018). However, due to the related legal and accounting effort for creating and approving the prospectus, the costs for the borrower are significantly higher (Cumming & Johan, 2013; Hahn, 2014). Since investors are less informed without a prospectus, regulators weigh the risk of less informed investors against the costs of creating a prospectus, and hence discouraging the company to raise capital (Cumming & Johan, 2013). In Germany, the major crowdlending platforms offer loans between 6 and 60 months (Harms, Klaue, Burkhardt, Seitz, & Spezzano, 2017; Maier, 2016a). Borello, De Crescenzo, and Flavio assume that the existence of secondary markets can be relevant for the future development of crowdfunding (2015). The major crowdlending platforms offer loans with an annuity structure (Harms et al., 2017; Maier, 2016a).

Depending on the country's specific regulations, the platform works either with or without a bank to originate the loan. The model without a bank means the contract is directly between the investors and the borrower, while the platform supports the whole process (European Commission, 2016; Kirby & Worner, 2014). The other model is a cooperation with a bank. In Germany, in order to originate the loan, the involvement of a bank that has a banking licence according to section 32 of the German Banking Act (KWG) is required (BaFin, 2017b; Dorfleitner et al., 2016). The platform acts as intermediary. There are two mechanisms, whereas the first steps are equal. The first mechanism is illustrated by figure 20.

Figure 20: Process loan origination in crowdlending with direct resale

Source: Own illustration based on BaFin, 2017

After the funding is uploaded to the platform by the borrower, the investors can invest. Then, the first mechanism means that the bank directly resells the loan claim in the form of partial claims to the investors. This process is also arranged by the platform (BaFin, 2017b).

The second mechanism means that the bank resells the full claim of the loan agreement to an intermediary that is 100% owned by the crowdlending platform. Afterwards, the intermediary resells the claim in the form of partial claims to the investors. The second mechanism with an intermediation is illustrated by figure 21.

Figure 21: Process loan origination in crowdlending with intermediation resale

Source: Own illustration based on BaFin, 2017

As shown in chapter two, traditional banks reduce the transactions costs. Based on these mechanisms illustrated by figure 20 and 21, it can be identified that crowdlending causes more transactions than traditional bank loans. However, for a deeper evaluation, the specific contractual agreements between the parties have to be considered.

Before the bank originates the loan, the borrower's identity has to be verified (European Commission, 2016). According to the directive 2015/849/EU of the European Union in conjunction with the German anti-money laundering act (Geldwäschegesetz), verifying a customer's identity when accepting a new customer is required in finance to fulfil the know-your-customer obligations (Arner, Zetsche, Buckley, & Barberis, 2019). In case of a company, it also needs the name of the company, the kind of legal entity, the trade registry number if available, and the identity of the person who represents the company. Authentication is the verification of a claimed characteristic of an entity, for example, the verification of a person's identity. The authentication can be conducted by the person's knowledge, the ownership of a physical object, or by a biometric element (Bender & Kuegler, 2016). Based on these literature review, the existing literature does

not show how crowdlending platforms verify the borrower's identity, which is also relevant to understand the business model.

The partial resale of the claim from the bank or intermediary to the investor is a capital investment according to section 1 of the German Investment Act (VermAnlG). Therefore, a prospectus is required. However, there is an exemption of the obligation to provide a prospectus of crowdfunding including crowdlending according to section 2a of the VermAnlG if the volume does not exceed 2.5 mn€ (BaFin, 2017b). Additionally, for the exemption, the investment volume of individual investors is limited. Each individual investor is limited to invest 1 k€ in one funding. If the individual investor owns assets that are available of at least 100 k€, the individual investor can invest 10 k€ in maximum. This limitation is similar to the Jumpstart Our Business Startup Act (JOBS) in the United States in order to protect the investors (Cunningham, 2012; Hornuf & Schwienbacher, 2017).

In both mechanisms that are described above, the crowdlending platform itself or the intermediary owned to 100% by the platform does not provide banking services according to the German Banking Act (KWG) or payment services according to the German Payment Services Supervision Act (ZAG) due to the cooperation with a bank (BaFin, 2017b). The bank can also be defined as white-label (Paul et al., 2016). The service of these banks can be defined as banking as a service (BaaS) or banking as a platform (BaaP) (Brandl & Hornuf, 2017). However, crowdlending platforms may be pursuant to the German Industrial Act (Gewerbeordnung) or to the German Securities Trading Act (WpPG). The supervisory provisions that might be relevant have to be proved for each individual case (BaFin, 2017b).

3.2.2.3 Crowdinvesting

In contrast to crowdlending, crowdinvesting does not consist of a senior debt agreement (BaFin, 2017a; Hornuf & Schmitt, 2017). Crowdinvesting is also known as equity-based crowdfunding (European Banking Authority, 2015). According to the BaFin, crowdinvesting is either related to the participation in the future profit of the company or an investment related to a security (2017). The participation can also be in turnover or in an increase of the company value (Dorfleitner, Kapitz, & Wimmer, 2014; European Commission, 2014).

Hagedorn and Pinkwart split the general process of crowdinvesting into application, screening and selection, contracting, roadshow, subscription, holding, and exit phase (2016). The application phase means the borrower applies to the platform for the publication of a funding. The screening and selection phase means the platform screens and selects the application by simplified due

diligence. Due diligence can include the identification of the borrower and a creditworthiness evaluation or business model validation. The contracting phase means the platform defines together with the borrower the financing instrument, the economic conditions, and the matching mechanism. The roadshow phase means the platform publishes the funding to the investors with a business plan, a business description, an image video, or other material. The subscription phase means the matching mechanism to bring together the investors and the borrower. There are different matching mechanisms. One mechanism is that the funding is published on the platform with defined economic conditions and maturity for the public. Then, the investors can screen the funding and can decide whether or not they want to invest. This mechanism is based on the first-come, first-serve mechanism. Another mechanism is an auction mechanism in which investors provide bids for the investment. The holding phase means the borrower frequently informs the investors with information such as annual reports or quarterly business development. Finally, the exit is due with the expiration of the holding period if no automatic prolongation was agreed (Hagedorn & Pinkwart, 2016).

Beck also defined five similar phases (2017). First, the borrower applies with a description of the idea, a short business plan, or also with a detailed business plan, and the platform selects the funding. Second, after a positive selection, the borrower creates the documents required like a detailed business plan. Third, after the platform checked the documents, the contractual agreement is defined. This also includes the funding volume and the length of publishing period to the investors. The latter is often defined by the platform and typically varies between 40 and 60 days. Fourth, the funding is published to the investors. During this period registered investors can invest by clicking an investment button. For the registration the investors might need a tax identification number or other requirements might be needed. For the fund flows between the parties a third party like a payment service provider with a separate bank account (assigned to the funding) can be involved. Fifth, the borrower applies the funds and regularly informs the investors about its business development. The reporting scope and frequency are defined in the contract. Additionally, the borrower regularly transfers the funds that are agreed in the contract like interest payment or participation in the company's success to the investors.

The different phases of Hagedorn and Pinkwart (2016) and Beck (2017) do not consider all relevant aspects of a two-sided marketplace business model. For an in-depth understanding of the business model of financing fintechs, different aspects of each party – borrower, investors, and platform – have to be considered.

Due to the regulatory framework in Germany, mezzanine instruments are used (Beck, 2014). For the transfer of equity shares of a GmbH (limited liability company), the involvement of a civil law notary is necessary according to section 15 of the German Limited Company Act (GmbH Gesetz). Due to the large number of investors and their small investment volumes in crowdinvesting, it is not used. In contrast, for the transfer of shares of a stock company, a civil law notary is not required. However, there is the requirement to publish a prospectus if the volume exceeds 100 k€ according to section 3 of the German Securities Prospectus Act (WpPG). Additionally, the founding of a stock company is related to higher costs. In case of a private company (full liability company), the cost and administrative effort can be less than the efforts related to capital companies. However, it can be assumed that investors do not invest in case they are liable for the company's liabilities. Therefore, in order to participate investors in profit, revenue, or in an increase of the company value, mezzanine instruments are used (Beck, 2014; Dorfleitner et al., 2016). This is the reason why it is termed as crowdinvesting rather than equity-based crowdfunding (Hornuf & Schmitt, 2016). While in early contracts the investors were forced to partially participate in company losses, in the meantime it has been abolished (Dorfleitner et al., 2017; Dorfleitner et al., 2014). In contrast, in the UK the participation in equity shares of a limited liability company is possible through platforms like Crowdcube or Seedrs (Hornuf & Schwiendbacher, 2015b).

In Germany, the instruments are subordinated loans, subordinated profit-participating loans, typical and untypical silent partnerships, and participation rights. These instruments can include returns like equity shares but have limited or no voting and control rights (Hagedorn & Pinkwart, 2016; Hornuf & Schmitt, 2017).

Typically, crowdinvesting contracts do not have any voting rights for the investors (Kloehn, Hornuf, & Schilling, 2016). In contrast to other European crowdinvesting platforms, the instruments in Germany are not securitised (Rossi & Vismara, 2017). In the past, crowdinvesting platforms switched from silent partnerships and participation rights to subordinated profit-participating loans because for the latter there was no obligation to provide a prospectus if the volume exceeded 100 k€. However, currently there is the same exemption according to section 2a of the VermAnlG if the volume does not exceed 2.5 mn€ as described in the chapter of crowdlending (BaFin, 2017a; Dorfleitner et al., 2016). The Small Investor Protection Act is an Omnibus Act that defines the exemption in section 2a of the VermAnlG. Nevertheless, if no prospectus is required, the borrower must prepare an investment information sheet (Vermögensanlagen-Informationsblatt), which is a short information sheet for the investors, and must submit it to the BaFin (BaFin, 2017; European Commission, 2016). Typically, the platform does not provide investment advisory services (Hagedorn & Pinkwart, 2016).

Partly, the company value is calculated by the platform based on the business plan (Dorfleitner et al., 2014). A business plan is a written document that describes the business model of the company (Staroßom, 2013). The calculation of the company value can be relevant for the investors in order to measure the participation in an increase of the company value. The most platforms do not publish their methods for the calculation. It can be assumed that they apply different multiples and discounted cash flow methods (Dorfleitner et al., 2014). As technology and online networks continue to develop, professional investors like business angels and venture capitalists are starting to invest in crowdfundering fundings (Lambert, Ralcheva, & Roosenboom, 2018).

Crowdfundering platforms do not need a banking licence. However, other licences might be required according to the German Industrial Act (Gewerbeordnung), German Banking Act (KWG), German Payment Services Supervision Act (ZAG), German Securities Trading Act (WpPG), or the German Capital Investment Act (KAGB). The supervisory provisions that might be relevant have to be proved for each individual case (BaFin, 2017a).

3.2.2.4 Factoring platforms

Factoring platform means that based on a platform, companies can sell their accounts receivable with less requirements than traditional factoring such as no turnover requirements (Dorfleitner et al., 2017; Dorfleitner, Rad, & Weber, 2017; Zhang, Baeck, & Collins, 2014). In contrast to traditional factoring, on factoring platforms companies can place individual accounts receivable for sale (Nicoletti, 2018). The company can upload an account receivable, and after the platform has verified it, the investors can buy it. The price of the account receivable can be either defined by the platform or by an auction mechanism (Dorfleitner, Rad, & Weber, 2017). The investors can be individuals or professionals (Wardrop, Zhang, Rau, & Gray, 2015). Typically, the investors are professional investors like institutions or high net worth individuals (European Commission, 2016).

According to section 1 subsection 1a of the German Banking Act (KWG), a company that purchases ongoing accounts receivable on the basis of standard agreements with recourse or non-recourse commercially or on a scale which requires commercially organised business operations that includes a financing function, is required to have a licence from the BaFin (BaFin, 2009).

Based on the results shown above, it can be seen that factoring platforms are the least studied segment of financing fintechs. Therefore, especially regarding factoring platforms, a deeper understanding of the business model is required.

3.2.3 Financing fintechs as substitute for traditional banking for companies in Germany

Based on the literature review, different studies are identified that relate to the question whether or not for companies in Germany the service of financing fintechs is a substitute for traditional banking services.

In order to estimate whether crowdfunding is a complementary service to or substitutional service for traditional banking, Blohm et al. conducted a Delphi-study with experts from 21 February 2014 to 17 April 2014 (2015). The first interview round contained 70 and the second 47 experts from academic disciplines, banks, consultancy companies, and crowdfunding platforms. The results are as follows. 51% of the experts assume it is very likely that in Germany in 2020 crowdfunding will be an important financing source for start-ups, 36% assume it is likely, 11% it is unlikely, and 2% it is very unlikely. 6% of the experts assume it is very likely that in Germany in 2020 crowdfunding will be an important financing source for SMEs, 36% assume it is likely, 57% it is unlikely, while no expert assumes it is very unlikely. Regarding large companies and multinational groups, no expert assumes it is very likely or likely, while 36% assume it is unlikely and 64% it is very unlikely. Additionally, 47% of the experts assume it is very likely that the crowdfunding platform market in Germany will be consolidated, 40% assume it is likely, 13% it is unlikely, while no expert assumes it is very unlikely. Furthermore, 19% of the experts assume it is very likely that companies like Google and Facebook will provide crowdfunding services, 64% assume it is likely, and 17% it is unlikely. Since such companies have a large scale of data of their users, this can be an advantage to offer crowdfunding. Regarding regulation, 64% of the experts assume that the regulation will not influence the success of crowdfunding, while 36% assume it will negatively influence it. The argument of the former is that further regulatory requirements potentially increase trust and quality, which can support the establishment of crowdfunding as alternative financing source. In table 5 the major results are summarised. Based on the results, the authors argue that at least until 2020 crowdfunding can be considered more as a complementary service. Currently, crowdfunding platforms serve companies which cannot be efficiently served by traditional banks, especially due to the low loan volumes. This is also reflected in the fees charged from the platforms – on average the fee is 10% of the funding volume. However, the authors argue that the crowdfunding market has a high potential to further increase. Therefore, they are not sure whether crowdfunding could become a mass product in the future, which could lead to a substitution for traditional banking.

Table 5: Expert estimations of crowdfunding market in 2020

n = 47 Statements to German market	Number of responses of experts in %			
	Very likely	Likely	Unlikely	Very unlikely
Crowdfunding will be an important financing source for start-ups in Germany in 2020	51%	36%	11%	2%
Crowdfunding will be an important financing source for SMEs in Germany in 2020	6%	36%	57%	0%
Crowdfunding will be an important financing source for large companies and multinational groups in Germany in 2020	0%	0%	36%	64%
Crowdfunding platforms will consolidate	47%	40%	13%	0%
Bigtechs like Google and Facebook will provide crowdfunding service	19%	64%	17%	0%

Source: Own illustration based on data from Blohm et al., 2015

The results from Blohm et al. (2015) can provide a first indication, however, there is no clear direction of the importance of crowdfunding for SMEs and no clear direction of the importance of crowdfunding in the future. Additionally, it does not provide insights of executives of LMEs and no in-depth reasons why crowdfunding can or cannot be a substitute for traditional banking services. Furthermore, as already mentioned in chapter two, the definition implies that complements have to be consumed together with a fixed proportion. Although it finally depends on the subjective judgment to which extent services are complements or substitutes, crowdfunding cannot be a complement because both crowdfunding and traditional banking services can be separately consumed. A price increase of crowdfunding would not decrease the demand of traditional banking services. Solely the service of crowdlending platforms and the white-label banks in terms of banking licence are perfect complements because the process of crowdlending requires a banking licence. Theoretically, crowdlending, crowdinvesting, and factoring platforms can be a substitute for traditional banking because there is an exchange of funds against an obligation to repay the funds plus an additional payment or to transfer claims of an account receivable.

In order to analyse the motives to use crowdlending and advantages and disadvantages of crowdlending relative to traditional banking, Maier conducted a survey to SMEs which applied for a loan at Fundingcircle (2016a). Fundingcircle is a crowdlending platform that provides services to SMEs in Germany. Of the 104 participants, 52% received funds and 48% did not receive funds. The data was enriched with 409 SME data sets from the platform's total financed loans. Of the 409 SMEs, the average turnover was 1.4 mn€, the number of employees 17, the loan volume 73 k€, and the average age of the company 13 years. Based on pre-defined categories, the participants were

asked to evaluate their motives why they are interested in crowdlending. The figures are summarised in table 6.

Table 6: Evaluation of motives of participants for crowdlending based on Maier, 2016a

n = 100 +2 fully agreement, -2 fully rejection	Pre-defined categories	Level of agreement/ rejection
Strongest motives	Fast financing solution	+1.3
	Flexible financing solution	+1.0
	Cheaper financing solution	+0.5
Mid field motives	Dissatisfaction with own bank	+0.4
	Financing diversification	+0.1
	Difficulties to receive funds elsewhere	-0.1
Weakest motives	Interested in fintechs	-0.3
	Other reasons	-1.0
	Avoid record in SCHUFA	-1.5

Source: Own illustration based on data from Maier, 2016a

They could choose between fully agree (+2) and fully reject (-2). The strongest motives are to find a fast financing solution (+1.3), a flexible financing solution including no need of a collateral and a charge-free early repayment prior to maturity (+1.0), and to find a cheaper financing solution (+0.5). The motives in the mid field are dissatisfaction with their banks (+0.4), financing diversification (+0.1), and difficulties to receive funds elsewhere (-0.1). The weakest motives are interested in fintechs (-0.3), other reasons (-1.0), and the avoidance of a record in the credit investigation company known as Schufa (-1.5).

Furthermore, the participants evaluated pre-defined factors between not important (1) and very important (5) and evaluated whether the bank or the crowdlending platform is at an advantage. The advantage could be evaluated with -2 (bank is at advantage) and +2 (crowdlending platform is at an advantage). The most important factors are reliability (4.55), trust (4.42), speed (4.32), simple process (4.32), flexibility (4.18), and simple legal procedure (3.94). Less important than the factors mentioned are collateral (3.89), interest rate (3.88), accessibility (3.78), fee (3.74), innovativeness (3.27), personal relation (2.89), and publicity effects (2.25). Reliability, trust, speed, flexibility, and simplicity were evaluated as more important than the economic factors such as collateral, interest rate, and fees. The least important factor is publicity effects. For all factors except personal relation, the crowdlending platform is at an advantage. The figures are summarised in table 7.

Table 7: Factors evaluation and comparison banks versus crowdlending based on Maier, 2016a

Factors	Level of importance	Service of bank or crowdlending platform at advantage	
n = 103	1 = not important, 5 = very important	-2 = bank, +2 crowdlending at advantage	
Reliability	4.55		+0.38
Trust	4.42		+0.07
Speed	4.32		+1.48
Simple process	4.32		+1.49
Flexibility	4.18		+1.19
Simple legal procedure	3.94		+1.07
Collateral	3.89		+1.19
Interest rate	3.88		+0.22
Accessibility	3.78		+0.17
Fee	3.74		+0.17
Innovativeness	3.27		+1.12
Personal relation	2.89		-0.53
Publicity effects	2.25		+0.45

Source: Own illustration based on data from Maier, 2016a

Although 73% of the participants mentioned an urgent need for funds, only 36% applied and 64% did not apply for a bank loan. The reasons why only 36% applied for a bank loan are not clear. The reasons might be the obstacles for traditional bank financing, the advantages of crowdlending relative to traditional banks, or the possible probability that the bank will reject the request. For 54% of the participants that both received and did not receive funds, the bank is the primary counterpart. Crowdlending is the primary counterpart for 39% that received funds and for 12% that did not receive funds. Finally, the author argues that the most participants consider their relationship bank as first point of contact and consider crowdlending more as an opportunity to diversify their financing (Maier, 2016a).

Based on the survey to SMEs mentioned above and a regression analysis, Maier also analysed the switching behaviour from traditional banking to crowdlending platforms (2016b). The switching intention, which was measured by the likelihood to switch, to recommend crowdlending, and to re-loan, is the dependent variable. Economic and functional factors, the image of crowdlending, and the SMEs' openness to innovation are the independent variables. The economic factor consists of the fee, interest rate, and required collateral. The functional factor means how the financing process is conducted. This factor includes convenience and transparency. The latter means process clarity while the former means reliability, speed, and simplicity. The functional factor also includes the personal relation to connect, understand, and to help the customers. The image factor means the customers' satisfaction based on the image of crowdlending. The author found that borrowers'

switching to crowdlending platforms is positively influenced by their convenience and process transparency perception. In contrast, it is not positively influenced by a positive image of crowdlending. Furthermore, the assumption of the positive influence of the SMEs' openness to innovation on the switching could not be fully supported. Additionally, the author found that borrowers' switching to crowdlending platforms is more driven by functional relative to economic factors. This could be an indication that the economic offer of crowdlending platforms is perceived as on par with the SMEs' banks, and could imply that convenience might be a key differentiator between different financing alternatives for SMEs.

In contrast to the study of Blohm et al. (2015), the study of Maier (2016a, 2016b) includes the perspective of SMEs, which means that the results can be discussed along the results of this research. However, the survey of Maier is to SMEs and not LMEs and consists of pre-defined categories, which limits the option to receive new insights. Furthermore, due to the quantitative approach, the study does not include a deep insight of the reasons for the evaluation.

Dorfleitner, Kapitz, and Wimmer analysed data of SMEs that succeeded funding through crowdinvesting and discussed whether or not crowdinvesting is a substitute for traditional financing for SMEs (2014). The research included 85 company and funding data sets of Seedmatch, Companisto, Innovestments, and Bankless24. The first three platforms mentioned focus on companies in the seed and start-up phase, while the latter focuses on SMEs. The average funding volume was 143 k€, the median funding volume was 100 k€, the minimum was 41 k€, and the maximum 1,000 k€. Considering solely Bankless24 the average funding volume was 72 k€ in average, 69 k€ in median, 51 k€ in minimum, and 100 k€ in maximum. The company's turnover was 220 k€ in average, 82 k€ in median, 0 € in minimum, and 1,200 k€ in maximum. The company's balance sheet volume was 113 k€ in average, 63 k€ in median, 2.5 k€ in minimum, and 605 k€ in maximum. The duration of the financing was 5 years in average, 4 years in median, 2 years in minimum, and 12 years in maximum. The company's age was 3 years in average, 2.5 years in median, 0.5 years in minimum, and 12.5 in maximum. 46 companies (54%) used silent partnerships, 35 (41%) subordinated profit-participating loans, and 4 (5%) participation rights as financing instrument. 75% of the companies were in the IT, software, internet, or e-commerce industry.

Due to the relatively low turnover and balance sheet values of the companies and the relatively low funding volumes, Dorfleitner, Kapitz, and Wimmer argue that crowdinvesting is more interesting for small companies (2014). Additionally, the authors argue that crowdinvesting is more interesting for companies in technology innovative industries. However, they also argue that the number of established SMEs and SMEs that are not from the technology innovative industry is increasing. As

De Crescenzo (2016) indicates that SMEs that request for crowdfunding are positioned in the innovative and traditional industry, and Maier (2016b) that the company's innovation is a limited driver in switching to crowdlending platforms. Dorfleitner, Kapitz, and Wimmer argue that crowdfunding platforms can be a substitute for business angels and venture capital funds, but relative to traditional banks, they have a minor role (2014). Loans to young companies are typically too risky from a bank's perspective due to missing collaterals and an uncertain future. Additionally, the authors argue that the costs are relatively high. The fee charged from the platform to the borrower varies between 5% and 10%. Furthermore, the authors argue that the protection of the intellectual property right is difficult due to the publication of the funding, and the evaluation of the company value is difficult especially for young companies.

The study of Dorfleitner, Kapitz, and Wimmer (2014) consider crowdfunding platforms that provide services to SMEs and start-ups in Germany, which means that the results can be discussed along the results of this research. However, they do not consider all aspects of a two-sided marketplace business model and do not consider the perspectives of LMEs – the argumentation that crowdfunding cannot be a substitute is based on the characteristics of the fundings on four crowdfunding platforms while three of them focus on start-ups instead of SMEs.

3.2.4 Strategic impact on traditional banks and traditional banks' reactions

Navaretti et al. assume that fintechs will not replace traditional banks in most of their key functions (2018). They claim there are strong complementarities between traditional banks and fintechs. Since fintechs have unbundled services, their scope is limited. For example, for financing fintechs, it will be difficult to offer diversified investment opportunities without taking the risk on their balance sheets. As fintechs expand their range of activities, the scope for regulatory arbitrage will decline. Due to the declining regulatory arbitrage and the adverse selection and moral hazard related problems, the authors argue that it is unlikely that financing fintechs will displace traditional banks in the long-term. Additionally, financing fintechs have a fee-based revenue model which requires a high scale of fundings, and thus a high scale of both borrowers and investors. Furthermore, a short-term technology advantage of financing fintechs will be displaced in the long-term as the technologies of traditional banks and fintechs converge. The authors assume that the business models of financing fintechs and traditional banks will co-exist, or the business model of financing fintechs will gradually converge towards that of traditional banks. According to the authors, the latter can be seen on Zopa, which is a crowdlending platform in the UK, that announced the opening of its own bank. However, since smaller banks may have difficulties to cope with the issues, fintechs may cause a new wave of acquisitions in the banking industry. Additionally, in

competitive segments, larger banks can acquire fintechs or can internally develop their own fintech activities. Furthermore, according to Belleflamme and Lambert, there will be a concentration within the fintech market due to the network effects and the economies of scale effects in terms of decreasing screening and creditworthiness evaluation related costs (2014). This implies that large platforms become larger, whereas small platforms face downward spirals. The study of Navaretti et al. (2018) includes aspects that can be used to discuss the results of this research. However, the study is based on theoretical aspects without empirical data that supports the argumentation.

The Basel Committee on Banking Supervision defined five scenarios to describe the possible impact of fintechs on traditional banks (2017). The scenarios are summarised by figure 22. The first scenario, defined as better bank, means that traditional banks digitise and modernise their business models to retain the customer relationship and core banking services. Based on their market knowledge and investment capacity, traditional banks become better in providing services by adopting new technologies or improving existing ones.

Figure 22: Strategic scenarios of traditional banks according to Basel Committee

Source: Own illustration based on Basel Committee on Banking Supervision 2017, p. 16

The second scenario, defined as new bank, means the replacement of traditional banks by new providers. This scenario implies that traditional banks cannot survive the wave of technology. The new providers obtain a banking licence under the existing regulatory regime and capture the customers of traditional banks by providing banking services in a more cost-effective and innovative way. The new providers can be neo banks, fintechs, or bigtechs.

The third scenario, defined as distributed bank, means the financial services become more modularised, but traditional banks can carve out enough of a niche to survive. The financial services are provided by both traditional banks and new providers. New businesses emerge to provide specialised niches. Traditional banks and new providers compete to own the customer relationship and to provide core banking services. In this scenario, traditional banks and new providers operate as joint ventures, partners, or other structures where the delivery of services is shared across parties. Lending platforms cooperate with traditional banks in marketing of credit products, approval processes, funding, and in compliance management. It might be that the platforms acquire their own licence. Customers may consume multiple financial services from different providers instead of remaining a single partner of one provider.

The fourth scenario, defined as relegated bank, means traditional banks become commoditised and cede the direct customer relationship to the new providers. The new providers use front-end customer platforms to offer the services. They use traditional banks for their banking licence to provide core services like lending, deposit taking, and other banking services. Depending on the contract, the balance sheet risk may or may not be kept by the relegated bank. This scenario means lending platforms become the public face to the customer. Their service may extend the range of lending to all types of banking services. The platforms meet the customers' needs, and traditional banks would exist to provide the operational and funding mechanism.

The fifth scenario, defined as disintermediated bank, means that banks become irrelevant as customers directly interact with the new providers. Since there is no need for balance sheet intermediation or trusted third parties, traditional banks are no longer significant providers. They are displaced from financial transactions by platforms and mechanisms like crowdlending. The authors mentioned that these scenarios are extremes and are not mutually exclusive. Therefore, the future evolution may likely be a combination of the different scenarios.

This study of the Basel Committee on Banking Supervision provides theoretical scenarios of the impact of fintechs on traditional banks (2017). However, it does not consider specifically financing fintechs that provide services to SMEs in Germany, does not include the disruptive innovation theory, and is not based on empirical data. Nevertheless, the results of this research can also be discussed along the defined scenarios.

In order to analyse the reactions of traditional banks to the emergence of fintechs, Brandl and Hornuf conducted a network analysis on contractual link data between banks and fintechs and among fintechs themselves (2017). The data was collected between January 2010 and June 2017

from the web-presence paymentandbanking.com, which continually maps the connection of fintechs with other companies, and from press releases, annual reports, web-presences, and magazines. The result is that banks mainly do not integrate fintechs directly to gain access to the technology but rather seek strategic partnerships. Of the total contractual links, 19% are actual investments, 74% strategic partnerships, and 7% are spin-offs. The contractual links can be between banks and fintechs or among fintechs themselves. Banks include fintechs that acquired a banking licence. Investment means the full integration of another company or the purchase of the shares (Brandl & Hornuf, 2017). The investments of banks in fintechs can also be through venture capital funds (European Banking Authority, 2018). According to Brandl and Hornuf, investment implies exclusive access to the technology (2017). Strategic partnership is a contractually fixed relationship which implies that one company uses the software of another by typically paying a transaction-based fee. Therefore, there is no exclusive access to the technology, but there is also not the risk as in full integration. Spin-off means an established fintech or traditional bank founded a separate legal entity.

According to the authors, fintechs play an active role in reshaping the industry. Some fintechs started as a regular start-up, and finally, received a banking licence or founded a bank as spin-off (e.g., fintech AG – biw Bank für Investments und Wertpapiere). There are also fintechs that directly integrated other fintechs. The reaction of traditional banks in Germany is different. While some banks acquired fintechs, others are more cautious about investing in fintechs. For the future, the authors assume a further consolidation of the fintech market in Germany. However, the dominance of strategic partnerships will not vanish due to structural reasons in the technology itself. The authors applied the theory of Teece that analysed the calculation of companies aiming to obtain access to a desired technology (1986). A tight regime of appropriability means the technology is relatively easy to protect from imitation, whereas a weak appropriability means the technology is almost impossible to protect from imitation. A weak regime of appropriability increases transaction costs because of the monitoring costs required. Therefore, especially for large companies it is an incentive to integrate the company of interest due to economies of scale effects. In contrast, a tight regime of appropriability has low transactions costs. In this context, the authors argue that the software innovations are tight as the source codes are often kept secret or protected by trade secrets, and the software often has to be adjusted to a specific company or context. Additionally, strategic partnerships will not vanish due to the characteristics of traditional banks' IT infrastructures. The digital requirements defined decades ago and the lack of coordination among banks led to siloed data storages maintained by individual participants. According to the authors, the most experts assume that the financial industry must reconcile the current system in the near future. Therefore, traditional banks hesitate to fully integrate fintechs and limit their participation

in the new wave of digitisation through strategic partnerships. The authors argue that although fintechs challenge traditional banks by their digital optimised cost structure and their affinity to new technology, they are not a self-sustaining alternative to the banking system. Almost all active fintechs rely on banks, mostly because they do not have a banking licence which is required to conduct core banking operations. The authors' opinion is that in future, fintechs with a banking licence will become more relevant (Brandl & Hornuf, 2017).

On the behalf of the Ministry of Finance of the German Government, Dorfleitner et al. analysed the fintech market in Germany to examine the actual and estimated future market volume (2016). In this context, the authors also sent a questionnaire to 9 traditional banks and 33 smaller, innovative banks in order to request their fintech related activities (2016). In total, 16 banks responded to the questionnaire, among which 3 of the 5 largest banks in Germany. The result is that the most traditional banks consider fintech activities as relevant topic, but their reactions are different. Out of 16 banks that responded, 3 have shares in fintechs and 13 cooperate with a fintech. The cooperation can be based on a contract or a financial or advisory support. Furthermore, the most banks do not consider fintechs as a threat but rather as a supplement and as a chance to drive innovation and digitisation. Regarding regulatory obstacles, the banks criticised the large number of different requirements and their related effort to implement and fulfil these requirements. They mentioned that they consider the regulatory requirements as a market entry barrier for fintechs. As already mentioned, the reaction of traditional banks is different. While banks like Santander and Commerzbank acquired fintechs, other traditional banks like HypoVereinsbank and Deutsche Bank are more cautious about investing in fintechs (Brandl & Hornuf, 2017). Commerzbank, one of the largest private banks, offered crowdlending services. The crowdlending platform from Commerzbank (Main Funders) went online mid of 2016 and offered loans to SMEs (Blohm et al., 2015). However, in April 2019 the crowdlending platform Creditshelf announced to acquire Main Funders (Creditshelf AG, 2018). Fidor Bank cooperates with different crowdfunding platforms. Customers of the bank can directly invest in crowdfunding projects via their online banking portal. Berliner Volksbank, one of the largest cooperative banks in Germany, invested in Bergfürst (Blohm et al., 2015).

The study of Brandl and Hornuf (2017) provides how traditional banks and fintechs are contractually linked to each other. The result that the strategic partnership is the most established form might be an indication that traditional banks do not consider fintechs as disruptive innovation. This is also supported by the survey of Dorfleitner et al. (2016). These results can be relevant to evaluate the disruptive innovation threat since the incumbents do not consider the entrants as treat. However,

these studies do not consider specifically financing fintechs that provide services to SMEs, and they do not consider the disruptive innovation theory.

3.2.5 Forecast of financing fintech market volume

Again, Dorfleitner et al. analysed the fintech market in Germany in order to examine the actual and estimated future market volume (2016). The authors sent a questionnaire to all active fintechs in Germany with a response rate of 25%. Based on the data received from the survey, a statistical approach, and a comparison with other technologies like online banking, they forecasted the future market volume for 2020, 2025, and 2035 with three different scenarios. The scenarios of the first segment are summarised by figure 23. The forecast of crowdlending and loans of the segment loans and factoring are merged by the authors because both categories service individuals and SMEs with a fixed interest payment. According to the authors, the volume of crowdlending to business and consumers was 189 mn€ in 2015. Relative to the already shown figures of Zhang, Ziegler et al. (2016) and Ziegler et al. (2019), there is a difference of 4 mn€. The volume of loans of the segment loans and factoring was 140 mn€ in 2015. The base scenario of the volume of crowdlending and loans consists of an increase to 5,000 mn€ in 2020, 7,000 mn€ in 2025, and 11,000 mn€ in 2035. One major assumption is that the demand of SMEs for crowdlending increases especially due to the Basel banking requirements.

Figure 23: Forecast crowdlending and loans volume in Germany by Dorfleitner et al.

Source: Own illustration based on Dorfleitner et al. 2016

The optimistic scenario consists of an increase to 38,000 mn€ in 2020, 63,000 mn€ in 2025, and 90,000 mn€ in 2035. This scenario includes higher growth rates especially for crowdlending to business than in the base scenario because the real estate volume increases, and loans are not provided to companies by traditional banks due to their risks. Additionally, fintechs have lower costs relative to traditional banks because they have automated processes and no branches, and

thus they offer better conditions. Additionally, due to big data and machine learning, fintechs have better credit risk management systems than traditional banks. The pessimistic scenario consists of a decrease to 257 mn€ in 2020 and then an increase to 420 mn€ in 2025 and to 602 mn€ in 2035. One major assumption is that the credit risk management systems are created in an interest low environment, and thus are not prepared for an increase in interest rate. In case of an interest rate increase, the interests for investors are not adequately increasing which results in less attractiveness. Furthermore, higher regulatory requirements leading to higher costs (Dorfleitner et al., 2016). The research conducted by Blohm et al., which consisted of a Delphi-study with expert interviews as already described, indicates that the market volume of crowdlending will be 162 mn€ in 2020 in Germany (2015).

According to the authors, the crowdfunding volume in Germany was 47 mn€ in 2015. Relative to the already shown figures of Zhang, Ziegler et al. (2016) and Ziegler et al. (2019), there is a difference of 2 mn€ (2016). The scenarios are summarised by figure 24. The base scenario consists of an increase to 69 mn€ in 2020, 113 mn€ in 2025, and 160 mn€ in 2035. One major assumption is a change in the business model including more automation in contract related issues.

Figure 24: Forecast crowdfunding volume in Germany by Dorfleitner et al.

Source: Own representation based on Dorfleitner et al. 2016

The optimistic scenario consists of an increase to 413 mn€ in 2020, 675 mn€ in 2025, and 959 mn€ in 2035. One assumption is an increase in volume due to an effective selection of the fundings. As a result, there are less insolvencies and liquidations and more follow-up financings. The risk-return-ratio improves and the attractiveness for investors increases. Furthermore, the assumption is that the requirements to transfer equity shares of German limited companies (GmbH) ease. Therefore, investors could gain equity shares instead of mezzanine like in the UK, which would make the investments more attractive. The pessimistic scenario consists of a decrease to 23 mn€ in 2020 and

then an increase to 38 mn€ in 2025 and to 53 mn€ in 2035. The assumption of the authors is that more insolvencies and liquidations occur which leads to lower or negative returns for the investors. Furthermore, investors that have a positive attitude towards crowdfunding, shift their funds to crowdlending. The mentioned research of Blohm et al. indicates that the market volume of crowdfunding will be 110 mn€ in 2020 in Germany (2015).

According to the authors, the factoring volume of fintechs was 500 mn€ in 2015. The scenarios are summarised by figure 25. The base scenario consists of an increase to 13,000 mn€ in 2020, 22,000 mn€ in 2025, and 32,000 mn€ in 2035. The assumption for the increase is based on the historical growth rates of factoring and a focus on a niche segment. The latter implies to focus on SMEs without requiring a minimum turnover. The factoring growth rate from 2013 to 2015 was about 10% (Deutscher Factoring Verband, 2015). The optimistic scenario consists of an increase to 60,000 mn€ in 2020, 101,000 mn€ in 2025, and 147,000 mn€ in 2035. The assumption is an increase in volume by serving not solely SMEs but also larger companies especially because of the platforms' user-friendliness.

Figure 25: Forecast German fintech factoring volume by Dorfleitner et al.

Source: Own representation based on Dorfleitner et al. 2016

The pessimistic scenario consists of an increase to 620 mn€ in 2020, 1,000 mn€ in 2025, and 2,000 mn€ in 2035. There is no additional customer value proposition, while traditional factoring providers focus on smaller companies and creating efficient processes to decrease the costs, and thus offer services to companies without requiring a minimum turnover. To a certain extent, factoring platforms are forced out by traditional factoring providers.

The three forecast scenarios of Dorfleitner et al. (2016) are strongly divergent in volume. Comparing the CAGR of the three scenarios between 2015 and 2035, there are differences up to 29%-points. The segment crowdlending and loans increases from 329 in 2015 to 602 mn€ in the pessimistic scenario and to 90,000 mn€ in the optimistic scenario in 2035. This means the CAGR varies between 3% and 32%. In crowdfunding the CAGR varies between 1% and 16% and in factoring between 7% and 33%. Therefore, the forecast provides no clear direction of the future market volume development. However, some assumptions mentioned in the scenarios can be discussed along the results of this research.

3.3 Summary and conclusion

The purpose of this chapter was to present the studies that are related to financing fintechs to provide an overview of the existing literature and to show the research gap. For this purpose, the narrative literature review is thematically structured into five subchapters.

The objective of the first subchapter was to describe the market volume development to show the actual relevance of financing fintechs. The results show that the financing fintech market in Europe is relatively small in comparison to volumes in the US or China. In Germany, the second largest market in Europe after the UK, the actual market share of financing fintechs is low relative to the total potential market. The factoring volume has the highest share of the total financing fintech market, while the crowdlending volume to business has the highest growth rate. As mentioned in chapter two, a high growth rate can be an indication of a disruptive innovation even though the actual market share is low (Christensen et al., 2004).

The objective of the second subchapter was to show the different definitions of financing fintechs, i.e. crowdlending, crowdfunding, and factoring platforms, and their business model characteristics. The results show that crowdfunding platforms are two-sided marketplace business models that provide an electronic matching to facilitate interactions between the distinct customer groups. In Germany, crowdlending is debt-based crowdfunding in form of a loan agreement with a fixed interest rate, while crowdfunding is mezzanine-based crowdfunding which can include a participation in profit, revenue, or increase of the company value. In Germany, for the provision of the loan in crowdlending, a banking licence or a cooperation with a bank is required. In crowdfunding a banking licence is not necessarily required. On factoring platforms companies can sell their accounts receivable mainly through automatic processes and less requirements than traditional factoring.

The objective of the third subchapter was to show studies that relate to the question whether or not the service of financing fintechs is a substitute for traditional banking services for companies in Germany. There are different studies. Based on a Delphi-study with expert interviews from academic disciplines, banks, consultancy companies, and from crowdfunding platforms, Blohm et al. argue that at least until 2020 crowdfunding can be considered more as a complementary than a substitutional service for SMEs in Germany (2015). The authors are not sure whether crowdfunding can become a mass product in the long term, which could lead to a substitution for traditional banking. Dorfleitner et al. argue that crowdfunding platforms can be a substitute for business angels and venture capital funds but less for traditional banks (2014). Bank loans to young companies are often too risky due to missing collaterals and an uncertain future. Additionally, the authors argue that the relatively high costs for crowdfunding, the risk that the business idea is reproduced, and the difficulties of the company value evaluation might be an obstacle. Based on the results of Maier, it can be derived that the process of SMEs' switching to crowdfunding platforms is more strongly driven by functional relative to economic factors (2016b). The factors reliability, trust, speed, simple process, flexibility, and simple legal procedure are evaluated as more important than collateral, interest rate, and fee. The literature indicates that SMEs on these platforms are small companies. The turnover and the funding volumes are small relative to the SME definitions described in chapter two.

The objective of the fourth subchapter was to show studies that relate to the strategic impact of fintechs on traditional banks and the reactions of traditional banks. There are also different studies. According to Navaretti et al., due to the declining regulatory arbitrage, the adverse selection and moral hazard related problems, the fee-based revenue model of financing fintechs, which requires a high scale, and the convergence of new technologies of traditional banks and fintechs, the authors argue that it is unlikely that financing fintech will displace traditional banks in the future (2018). The Basel Committee on Banking Supervision defined five strategic scenarios for the impact of fintechs on traditional banks, which range from replacement of traditional banks to replacement of fintechs (2017). These scenarios are extreme scenarios and are not mutually exclusive. According to Brandl and Hornuf, the most contractual link between banks and fintechs or fintechs themselves is the strategic partnership and not the integration (2017). The authors argue that the strategic partnership will not vanish due to structural reasons in the technology itself. The results of Dorfleitner et al. are that the most banks do not consider fintechs as a threat but rather as a supplement and as a chance to drive innovation and digitisation (2016). German traditional banks react differently. Some invest in fintechs, while others are more cautious.

The objective of the fifth subchapter was to present a forecast of the financing fintech market volume to illustrate the potential market volume for the future. However, since the three scenarios of Dorfleitner et al. (2016) are strongly divergent in volume, the forecast provides no clear direction of the future market volume development.

The objective of the narrative literature review is also to show the research gap. The research gap is specifically related to the research questions. Since countries adapt their regulatory framework to the local markets which results in different rules and therefore, in different business models (European Commission, 2016), the research gap is specifically related to empirical studies from Germany. Additionally, it includes official legal requirements from German regulators.

The relevant studies that are related to the research question one are summarised in table 8. Although they provide some aspects which are relevant for the definition of the deductively defined categories of the documentary research, they do not include all relevant aspects of a two-sided marketplace business model to understand in-depth the business model of financing fintechs. Based on these existing studies, the expert interviews with executives of LMEs in Germany could not be conducted since there would be no holistic picture and no in-depth understanding of the financing fintechs' business models.

Table 8: Research gap – studies related to research question one

Year	Author	Title	Methodology/ method	Major findings
2017a	BaFin.	Crowdinvesting.	Qualitative description in legal terms.	Legal requirements of crowdinvesting in Germany – no banking licence required, but others licences might be required, prospectus obligations and exceptions.
2017b	BaFin.	Crowdlending.	Qualitative description in legal terms.	Legal requirements of crowdlending in Germany – banking licence required for origination of loan, prospectus obligations and exceptions.
2017	Beck.	Crowdinvesting. Die Investition der Vielen.	Qualitative description based on empirical data.	Identification and description of five phases – from application to repayment, and some further aspects.
2016	Hagedorn & Pinkwart.	The financing process of equity-based crowd-funding: an empirical analysis.	Qualitative description based on empirical data.	Identification and description of seven phases – from application to repayment, and some further aspects.

Source: Own illustration

The relevant studies that are related to the research question two are summarised in table 9 – these studies are already explained in chapter 3.2.3. Although they provide some aspects which are relevant for the definition of the deductively defined categories of the documentary research and expert interviews, they do not provide an in-depth understanding of whether the services of financing fintechs can be a substitute for traditional banking services for LMEs in Germany. There is no study that considers the views of executives of LMEs. Additionally, the study of Maier consists of a survey with pre-defined aspects, which should be a disadvantage in relatively unexplored topics since there could be relevant aspects which are not considered in the survey. Based on these existing studies, it could not be evaluated to which extent the service of financing fintechs is a substitute for traditional banking services to LMEs in Germany.

Table 9: Research gap – studies related to research question two

Year	Author	Title	Methodology/ method	Major findings
2016a	Maier.	Mittelstandskredite in Zeiten des digitalen Wandels – Crowdlending in Deutschland.	Quantitative description of empirical data – survey to SMEs that applied for a loan at a crowdlending platform in Germany.	Functional factors are more important than economic factors in the decision to choose crowdlending. Publicity effect is the least important factor.
2016b	Maier.	Supply and demand on crowdlending platforms: connecting small and medium-sized enterprise borrowers and consumer investors.	Quantitative (regression analysis) analysis based on empirical data – same data as above.	SMEs intention to switch from traditional banking to crowdlending platforms is more driven by functional including convenience than economic components.
2015	Blohm et al.	Crowdfunding 2020.	Delphi-study based on expert interviews with 2 rounds to collect qualitative and quantitative data.	No common view whether in Germany in 2020 crowdfunding will be an important financial source for SMEs. For start-ups experts assume it can be important, while for large companies it likely not important. In the long-term authors are not sure whether in can be as substitute.
2014	Dorleitner, Kapitz, & Wimmer.	Crowdfunding as financing alternative for SMEs.	Quantitative description of empirical data – data of 4 crowdfunding platforms in Germany.	Due to the low turnover and low funding volumes, crowdfunding is more interesting for small companies, which are too risky for traditional banks – it be an alternative to business angels and venture capital.

Source: Own illustration

As previously shown, there is no study which includes an in-depth appraisal of the business models of financing fintechs that provide services to SMEs in Germany and no study that includes an in-depth understanding of whether the services of financing fintechs can be a substitute for traditional banking services. Therefore, there is no study that includes an evaluation of the disruptive innovation threat of financing fintechs that provide services to SMEs in Germany to traditional banks based on respective empirical data. However, some studies are identified which are related to the strategic impact of fintechs on traditional banks, which are illustrated in table 10.

Table 10: Research gap – studies related to research question three

Year	Author	Title	Methodology/ method	Major findings
2018	Navaretti et al.	Fintech and Banking. Friends or Foes?	Qualitative description – theoretical without empirical data.	Mainly due to the adverse selection, moral hazard, and the fee-based revenue model, it is unlikely that financing fintechs will displace traditional banks in the long-term.
2017	Basel Committee on Banking Supervision.	Bank of International Settlement.	Qualitative description – theoretical without empirical data.	Definition of five strategic scenarios for the impact of fintechs on traditional banks – from diminishing of traditional banks to diminishing of fintechs.
2017	Brandl & Hornuf.	Where did FinTechs come from, and where do they go?	Quantitative and qualitative analysis – based on empirical data.	Banks prefer a strategic partnership with fintechs instead of an integration due to structural reasons in technology.
2016	Dorfleitner et al.	FinTech-Markt in Deutschland.	Quantitative and qualitative analysis – based on empirical data.	The most banks do not consider fintechs as a threat but rather as a supplement and as a chance to drive innovation and digitisation.

Source: Own illustration

In conclusion, there are three different research questions, whereas in each topic, there is a research gap. This is illustrated by figure 26 (RQ = research question). Based on the literature review process described in appendix A and a track and trace approach, no study could be found that fulfil these gaps. This research is a contribution to close the research gaps while it is a consecutive process: first, the results of the business model analysis are required to explore and evaluate to which extent the service of financing fintechs is a substitute for traditional banking services to SMEs in Germany. Then, based on the results of both, the disruptive innovation threat of financing fintechs that provide service to SMEs in Germany to traditional banks can be evaluated.

Figure 26: Illustration of research gap related to research questions

Source: Own illustration

3.4 Limitations

Narrative literature reviews focus on broader topics instead of specific hypotheses (Onwuegbuzie & Frels, 2016). Therefore, bias is often associated with the conduction of narrative literature reviews which should be reduced as much as possible (Green et al., 2006). The research process including the selection criteria, terms used, logical connections, and databases is defined and documented. However, the databases might induce bias because they are selected by the author of this research. Other databases might provide a higher representative value of the current state of research. Additionally, the quality of the selected literature is evaluated by the author of this research which could induce bias as well.

4 Research philosophy and methodology and methods applied

The purpose of this chapter is to present the research methodology and methods applied in this research to achieve the research aim and objectives and to answer the research questions. Additionally, as recommended for qualitative research (Merriam & Tisdell, 2016), it shortly describes the research philosophy, which consists of how the researcher views the world. This includes metaphysical aspects such as ontology and epistemology. Since this research consists of a multi-method approach, it describes the methodology and methods applied for two different topics – the business model analysis based on a documentary research and the expert interviews with executives of LMEs. Methodology implies the decisions whether a qualitative or quantitative approach is more appropriate, and the decision which method within the respective approach is most appropriate. Method implies the procedures to obtain and analyse the data.

4.1 Research philosophy and methodology

Research method relates to techniques and procedures used to obtain and analyse data, while methodology relates to the theory of how research should be undertaken (Saunders et al., 2009). “Research methodology is a way to systematically solve the research problem” (Kumar, 2008, p. 5). Methodology relates to the logic behind the methods used in the context of the research. This includes the explanation of why particular methods are used or not (Kumar, 2008). However, according to Guba and Lincoln, the questions of method are secondary to the questions of research philosophy, not only in choices of method but in ontologically and epistemologically fundamental ways (Guba & Lincoln 1994). Ontology is related to the researcher’s view of the nature of reality or being, while epistemology is related to the researcher’s view regarding what constitutes acceptable knowledge (Guba & Lincoln, 1994; Saunders et al., 2009). Research philosophy entails assumptions about the way in which the researcher views the world – especially in qualitative research, it is common that this view is described in the study. These assumptions underpin the research methodology and methods (Merriam & Tisdell, 2016).

The philosophical position adopted in this research is that of realism (Saunders et al., 2009). Ontologically, this implies “that objects have an existence independent of the human mind” (Saunders et al., 2009, p. 114). However, realism can be further split into direct and critical realism. The former implies that what we experience via our senses represents the world accurately. Epistemologically, this means that the observed data is credible, while insufficient data implies inaccuracies in sensations. The latter is adopted in this research and means that we not solely see and sense objects, but also process what we see. This includes two steps to experience the world. First, there is the object itself and the sensations it conveys. Second, after the sensation meets our sense, there is a mental processing. Epistemologically, this implies that a phenomenon can be only

understand if its context is taken into account. While the philosophical position of interpretivism primarily results in qualitative methods and of positivism in quantitative methods, the method of the critical realism position is defined based on the research objective (Saunders et al., 2009).

The first objective is to qualitatively appraise in depth the business model of financing fintechs, i.e. crowdlending, crowdinvesting, and factoring platforms that provide services to SMEs in Germany. Quantitative research implies the numerical analysis of a high quantity of data that can be obtained through methods like surveys, documents, and experiments to test pre-defined hypotheses, while qualitative research implies the non-numeric analysis of a lower quantity of data that can be obtained through methods like interviews, observations, and documents to develop theories (Bruesemeister, 2008; Creswell, 2014; Robins, 2018). Qualitative research is preferred for problems that are more unexplored and for a deeper understanding of the problem under study (Brosius, Haas, & Koschel, 2012). It tries to gain a holistic picture of the problem (Creswell, 2014).

Financing fintech is a relatively unexplored topic. Although there are few studies that include some aspects of the business model of financing fintechs, which is illustrated in chapter three, they do not provide an in-depth understanding of the business models of financing fintechs. A quantitative approach would provide numerical results, while a qualitative approach provides an in-depth understanding of the business models. Therefore, to appraise in depth the business model of financing fintechs, a qualitative approach is more appropriate than a quantitative approach.

Financing fintechs exclusively provide their services online on the World Wide Web (Dorfleitner et al., 2017; Rossi & Vismara, 2017). In contrast to traditional banks with branches, the interface to the customers is on their platforms. The platform consists of the web-presence which can be open with an internet browser, the respective domain, and an access to the World Wide Web. Therefore, the major relevant information is on the financing fintechs' web-presences. Documents are often used as an umbrella term which includes written, visual, digital, and physical material (Merriam & Tisdell, 2016). A documentary research implies the analysis of natural data which means the data is not created for the research and without the researcher's involvement. The data can come from public or private sources (Salheiser, 2014). For the analysis of the business models, the data is on the web-presences of the relevant financing fintechs. Therefore, a documentary research is more appropriate and objective than interviews with executives of financing fintechs while an observation is not possible to appraise the business models. In order to analyse the data in a structured way and based on the results of the secondary research, a qualitative content analysis is applied.

According to Glaeser and Laudel, there are four different methods to analyse text material (2010). First, the free interpretation which means the researcher reads and interprets the material and finally summarises the most relevant results to answer the research question. This method does not include further rules. Due to its leeway, the inter-subjectivity is reduced. Second, sequent analytics methods which include the narrative analysis and the objective hermeneutic. The former can be applied for the analysis of narratives, while the latter is a method which firstly creates all possible interpretations of the text and then validates them with the text. All inadequate interpretations are sequentially excluded. Due to its high effort, it is not widely used. Third, the coding method which is primarily founded by the grounded theory. Passages that are relevant for the research question are labelled by codes. The codes can be defined in a hierarchal or network structure. Finally, the codes represent the content of the material which can be used for the analysis. Fourth, there is the qualitative content analysis. Based on a systematic approach, the text can be analysed to find relevant information. The relevant information can be extracted and can be processed independently from the initial text. "In qualitative studies, a form of content analysis is most often used to analyse documents" (Merriam & Tisdell, 2016, p. 179). A "content analysis is a systematic method of categorising and analysing the content of texts" (Steenkamp & Northcott, 2008, p. 12). In contrast to the other text analytical approaches like the grounded theory and the objective hermeneutics, the qualitative content analysis is more ruled-based which includes the category-based approach. The categories represent the key aspects that are briefly summarised. The category system is the major instrument in the analysis and summarises all categories and sub-categories. The categories and sub-categories can have a hierarchal structure. The category approach is similar to the coding in the grounded theory. However, the coding in the grounded theory is more open, while the category approach in the qualitative content analysis is more ruled-based. This includes the definition of the unit of analysis and a precise definition of the categories (Mayring, 2010a; Mayring & Fenzl, 2014).

The content analysis can be split into quantitative and qualitative content analysis (Krippendorff, 2013; Kromrey, 2014). Quantitative content analysis implies a correlation between the importance of a subject and the frequency of appearance within the text (Krippendorff, 2004). In contrast, the qualitative content analysis focuses on the complexity of the content of the material. The data is reduced, and the focus shifted from an individual level to a macro level (Schreier, 2012). The quantitative content analysis can also be considered as form orientated or objective analysis which involves counting of words or concrete references. In contrast, the qualitative content analysis can be considered as meaning orientated or subjective analysis which focuses on the analysis of the underlying themes in the text under investigation (Smith & Taffler, 2000). In this research a qualitative content analysis is applied because financing fintechs are a new phenomenon and an in-

depth understanding of the business model of financing fintechs is more relevant than the frequency of certain words.

The second objective is to critically explore and evaluate to which extent the service of financing fintechs is a substitute for traditional banking services to LMEs in Germany. Again, qualitative research is preferred for problems that are more unexplored and for a deeper understanding of the problem under study (Brosius, Haas, & Koschel, 2012). Since financing fintechs are a new phenomenon and a deep understanding of the attitude of executives of LMEs towards financing fintechs relative to traditional banking is more relevant than quantitative aspects for the evaluation of the disruptive innovation threat, a qualitative approach is applied. In order to evaluate the disruptive innovation threat, it is relevant to understand the customers (Christensen et al., 2015, 2004). A survey of executives of LMEs with pre-defined aspects would not provide such a deep understanding – a quantitative approach with pre-defined aspects implies a limitation for new aspects and does not provide an in-depth understanding of the attitude of the respondents.

As mentioned in chapter two, since traditional banks' major focus is not on smaller SMEs which are the least profitable customers, and large companies have a need for more complex financing solutions, switch more often between different banks and instruments with direct capital market access (Fouché et al., 2016; Renker, 2005), LMEs can be considered as mainstream customers. Large companies might be high-end customers as they have higher loan volumes, which imply lower costs per unit. Therefore, they should be the most attractive customers. Additionally, the need for more complex financial solutions could be understood as a requirement for a higher performance. Again, according to the disruptive innovation theory, incumbents often fail competing disruptive innovation because they do not consider it as disruption. This implies that the incumbents listen to their mainstream or high-end customers, give them the service or product performance they are looking for, and finally, they are threatened by the disruptive innovation their customers led them to ignore (Christensen & Raynor, 2003). However, whether or not the service is or has the potential to become a substitute is an essential aspect to evaluate the potential disruptive threat. Therefore, interviews with executive managers of LMEs in Germany are necessary, while the results have to be critically evaluated. This also implies that in case the executive managers reject the financing fintechs' services due to the limited performance, it can be an indication of disruptive innovation. Therefore, to critically evaluate the understanding of the issue, a holistic view is more relevant than analysing a high quantity of data. The different subjective perspectives of the persons under study are the central point in qualitative research (Flick, 2007). "Qualitative researchers are interested in understanding how people interpret their experience, how they construct their worlds, and what meaning they attribute to their experience" (Merriam & Tisdell, 2016, p. 6). The major objective of

interviews is to obtain special information. In case thoughts or behaviour cannot be observed because the situations preclude the presence of an observer or the situations took place at previous points in time, asking the people is an adequate method. Based on interviews, the researcher is allowed to enter the other person's perspective (Patton, 2015). The questions are asked depending on the disciplinary theoretical framework of the study. "The overall interpretation will be the researcher's understanding of the participants' understanding of the phenomenon of interest" (Merriam & Tisdell, 2016, p. 25).

Interviews can be split into structured, semi-structured, and unstructured (Glaeser & Laudel, 2010; Merriam & Tisdell, 2016). The structured interview, also known as standardised, is an oral form of a written survey, while the unstructured interview, also known as informal, completely consists of open-ended questions and is applied if the researcher does not know enough about the phenomenon to ask relevant questions. The semi-structured interview includes a mix of more or less structured questions, while the questions are flexibly used. The semi-structured interview is guided by a list of questions or issues that the researcher wants to explore (Merriam & Tisdell, 2016). In order to flexibly handle the questions to obtain a holistic picture, in this research semi-structured interviews are conducted. Additionally, this method is applied because there is already knowledge that is based on the results of the secondary and documentary research.

The interviewees are experts. An expert interview is one of the most applied methods in empirical social science and is mostly related to semi-structured questions (Meuser & Nagel, 2009; Trinczek, 2002). An expert is a person who has an edge in knowledge in a certain field. The knowledge is not necessarily exclusive for the person. However, it is not accessible for everyone. Additionally, a person can be considered an expert if they have the responsibility to develop, implement, and control a problem solution, and thus has access to privileged information. For example, over decision making processes (Meuser & Nagel, 2009). In case a person has a specific knowledge due to their role, they can be considered an expert (Helfferich, 2014). Managers can be considered an expert (Meuser & Nagel, 2009). Therefore, executive managers of LMEs are experts. This research focuses on executive managers who have an authority in financing decisions. This is primarily the role of the chief financial officer (CFO); however, it also depends on the kind of legal entity and the organisational structure of the company, therefore, it could be also another role – this is further described in section 4.3.3.

The reasons why this research focuses on executive managers are as follows: first, they represent the LMEs in terms of financing issues. In case other experts in financing issues within the LME are interviewed, there is the risk that they do not provide the opinion of the executive, and therefore,

they would not represent the LME. Second, they should know best how they want to finance their companies' assets and operations. Third, due to their authority in financing issues, they should explain best what factors are the most relevant in their decisions. However, the experts are also mainstream customers of traditional banks. Therefore, the results have to be critically evaluated due to the disruptive innovation theory's axiom that listening to its mainstream or high-end customers leads to the failure of the incumbent.

The advantage of semi-structured interviews is that the risk to focus on irrelevant issues is reduced by the guideline. Additionally, based on the guideline, the interviewer can be prevented from being incompetent due to a deep preparation and the structure of the guideline (Meuser & Nagel, 2002). The latter is especially relevant for interviews with managers (Trinczek, 2002). Furthermore, based on the guideline, the different interviews are better comparable (Helfferich, 2014).

As previously mentioned, there are different methods of text material analysis. Since the qualitative content analysis is more ruled-based including the category-based approach, it is applied for the analysis of the text material of the interviews. Due to the interview guideline of the semi-structured interviews that is created by the results of the literature review and the documentary research, there are already aspects that should be considered in the analysis. Additionally, for the analysis of a holistic view of the extent to which the service of financing fintechs is a substitute for traditional banking services to LMEs in Germany, the underlying themes and content are more relevant than the frequency of certain words. However, in a qualitative content analysis that is systematically conducted, quantitative aspects like frequency can be integrated. This can support the qualitative interpretation (Mayring, 2001). "How often a category occurs may give added weight to its meaning and importance as well" (Mayring, 2014, p. 41). Software that supports the procedure of qualitative content analyses is often used to integrate some quantitative aspects (Mayring, 2001).

Since both are qualitative studies, it is a multi-method approach (Saunders, Lewis, & Thornhill, 2009). Based on the results of the documentary research, the expert interviews can be conducted. For the interviews, a precise understanding of the business models of financing fintechs that provide services to SMEs in Germany is required. Therefore, it is not an application of a triangulation approach. Triangulation means that the results of the same subject are checked by different methods to compensate for the limitations of each method (Flick, 2007). Furthermore, a mixed-method approach is not applied because for both objectives a qualitative approach is more appropriate. A mixed method consists of an integrative quantitative and qualitative research (Creswell, 2014).

4.2 Primary research method – business model analysis based on documentary research

4.2.1 Research steps

The objective of the documentary research is to qualitatively appraise in depth the business model of financing fintechs, i.e. crowdlending, crowdinvesting, and factoring platforms that provide services to SMEs in Germany. The steps for the research were as follows.

After the definition of the research objective and the method, the sample and units of analysis were defined. The theoretical background was already shown in chapters two and three. The next step was the definition of the category system. This was necessary because the data was analysed by a qualitative content analysis. A content analysis that is based on online data generally relates to the same techniques as a classical content analysis (Welker & Wuensch, 2010).

The procedure of a qualitative content analysis comprises different variants (Dunger, 2013; Schreier, 2014). The qualitative content analysis of Mayring is a commonly used method in Germany (Schnell & Kolbe, 2013). The principles of a qualitative content analysis were founded in the 1920s and 1930s in the United States by Harold Lasswell and Paul Lazarsfeld. In Germany, the method was further developed by Juergen Ritsert. Based on these results, Mayring further developed the method (Mayring, 2000; Ramsenthaler, 2013). According to Mayring, a qualitative content analysis consists of the following three forms that can also be applied in combination: The summary, explication, and structuring content analysis. The summary content analysis means the material is reduced to the essential content to create a comprehensive overview through abstraction. This includes the inductive definition of categories. The explication content analysis means providing additional material on individual text components to increase the understanding and interpretation. The structuring content analysis means the filtering of particular aspects by assigning those aspects to categories that are deductively defined (Mayring, 2010a, 2014).

In order to answer the research question, a combination of the summary and structuring content analysis was applied primarily according to the principles of Mayring. This means the text was reduced to the essential content and assigned to categories to qualitatively appraise in depth the business model of crowdlending, crowdinvesting, and factoring platforms that provide services to SMEs in Germany. Mayring defined different procedures to conduct a qualitative content analysis. The two key approaches are the inductive and deductive definition of the categories (Mayring, 2000). According to Schreier, the different variants of a qualitative content analysis can also be combined (2014). The approach should be defined depending on the research questions and material used. According to Mayring, the inductive categories should be finalised after 10% to 50%

of the material was processed (2014). According to Steigleder, there is also the approach that the categories can be continually modified until the material was completely processed (2008). Therefore, for the approach of Steigleder, a previous test run of the category system is not needed. In case there is a new aspect that is related to the business model that is relevant although the material was already processed by more than 50%, this aspect should be considered. Therefore, in this research the approach of Mayring was adjusted by the suggestions mentioned by Steigleder.

For each segment, i.e. crowdlending, crowdfunding, and factoring platforms one category system was defined. The category system was defined based on both the deductive and inductive approach. Deductive means the definition of the categories is derived from the theory or the conceptual framework of the researcher, and inductive means the definition is derived from the content. Due to the assignment of the material to categories, individual points can be abstracted. The categories are a central instrument in the qualitative content analysis (Mayring, 2014). Based on the category system, a complex topic can be narrowed and structured into partial aspects (Meyen, Loeblich, Pfaff-Ruediger, & Riesmeyer, 2011). Based on the category system, the business model of financing fintechs can be qualitatively appraised. Since financing fintechs have a two-sided marketplace business model, the categories were assigned to the platform, borrowers, and investors. The results of each segment were discussed along the four components of a business model: The CVP, key processes, key resources, and profit formula, that are defined by Johnson et al. (2008) as illustrated in chapter two.

Figure 27: Steps of business model analysis based on documentary research

Source: Own illustration based on Mayring 2010b, p. 229; Mayring and Fenzl 2014, p. 550

The next steps were the data collection and analysis, followed by the description of the results. The last step was the discussion and conclusion. The steps mentioned are illustrated by figure 27. As shown by the figure, there are three back couplings. There is a back coupling from the collection of the data to the definition of the category system in case of category modifications based on the content. Additionally, there is a back coupling from the discussion and conclusion to the research objective in order to check whether the research objective is achieved and to the reflection of the theoretical background in the meaning that the current state of research is extended by this research. Since there is one common approach, this procedure was applied for all three segments, i.e. crowdlending, crowdinvesting, and factoring.

4.2.2 Definition of sample

First, the research population, and second, the sample size and strategy have to be defined. For the research population a set of inclusion or exclusion criteria or a combination of both have to be specified (Robinson, 2014). In order to consider solely trustworthy platforms and platforms that are in the scope of this research, inclusion and exclusion criteria were defined. All platforms that fulfil the criteria were relevant in this research. This implies a total population sampling. Since the fintech market is in the infant stages, there can be diverse business models with different characteristics that can be relevant in this research.

The criteria (C) and the related rationale (R) are described in the following:

- C1: Financing fintechs that provide crowdlending, crowdinvesting, or factoring services in Germany. Regarding factoring: Solely factoring platforms that include a financing function as defined by the BaFin (BaFin, 2009). Additionally, no consideration of reverse factoring. R1: As mentioned, these financing fintechs are in the scope of this research. Factoring platforms that provide solely dunning or enforceable services are not comparable with the financing services of traditional banks. Additionally, since reverse factoring is initiated by the company's customer (Nicoletti, 2018), it is not relevant in this research.
- C2: Financing fintechs that provide services to SMEs. This means the service can be exclusive for SMEs or for others as well. However, no platforms that exclusively provide their services to start-ups, consumers or others. Since the platforms are not obliged to apply to a common SME definition, it is valid if the platform mentioned SMEs as target group. R2: SMEs are in the scope of this research.

- C3: No financing fintechs that exclusively provide real estate or sustainability fundings. R3: The general financing of SMEs' assets and operations are in the scope of this research, while niches like real estate or sustainability fundings are not.
- C4: The web-presence of the financing fintech has a legal disclosure in German language (Impressum) with information about the legal entity, management, address, listings in the trade or regulatory registers as required in Germany according to section 5 of the Telemedia Act (TMG) and section 2 of the Service Information Regulation (DL-InfoV). R4: This is a German legal requirement. In case these requirements are not fulfilled, the provider cannot be considered as serious.
- C5: The web-presence is available in German language. R5: For providing services to SMEs in Germany, it can be assumed that the customers require communication in German.
- C6: On the web-presence German terms and conditions are available. R6: For providing services to SMEs in Germany, it can be assumed that the customers require German terms and conditions to understand the legal aspects. Additionally, it can be assumed that a serious financing fintech wants to provide the terms and conditions on its web-presence to work efficiently.
- C7: For the services, no physical meeting between the parties involved is required and no additional software except an internet browser is needed by the customer. R7: Financing fintechs provide their services exclusively online. In case a physical meeting is required, the service would be similar to the services of traditional banks with branches. Additionally, it can be assumed that the customers require a simple process without an additional software.

In total, 53 platforms were evaluated of which 21 were identified as relevant. The 21 relevant platforms were split into five crowdlending, seven crowdinvesting, and nine factoring platforms. The evaluation of the identified financing fintechs along the criteria defined is illustrated in table 11, where + means the criterion was fulfilled, x it was not fulfilled, and - it was not checked because one criterion was already not fulfilled.

Table 11: Overview of evaluation of sample for documentary research

Platform (starting domain) + = fulfilled; x = not fulfilled; - = not checked since one criterion already not fulfilled	Criteria						
	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7
advanon.de	+	+	+	+	+	x	-
auxmoney.com	-	x	-	-	-	-	-
bankless24.de (merged in Conda)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
bezahlt.de	+	+	+	+	+	+	+

Platform (starting domain)	Criteria						
+ = fulfilled; x = not fulfilled; - = not checked since one criterion already not fulfilled	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7
bilendo.de	X	-	-	-	-	-	-
billie.io	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
cashcape.com	X	-	-	-	-	-	-
cashpress.com	X	-	-	X	-	-	-
collect.ai	X	-	-	-	-	-	-
companista.com	-	X	-	-	-	-	-
compeon.de	X	-	-	-	-	-	-
conda.de	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
creditshef.com	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
crosslend.com	X	-	-	-	-	-	-
crxmarkets.com	X	-	-	-	-	-	-
debitos.com	X	-	-	-	-	-	-
decimo.de	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
deutsche-mikroinvest.de	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
entrafin.de	X	-	-	-	-	-	-
factoringbörse.de	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
ferratumbank.de	X	-	-	-	-	-	-
finnest.com	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
fintura.de	X	-	-	-	-	-	-
flexpayment.de	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
fundflow.de	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
fundingcircle.com	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
fundsters.de	-	X	-	-	-	-	-
giromatch.com	X	-	-	-	-	-	-
gosepp.com	X	-	-	-	-	-	-
interfin.de	X	-	-	-	-	-	-
kapilendo.de	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
katrim.de	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
kredittech.com	X	-	-	-	-	-	-
lendico.de	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Lionrocket.de	+	+	+	+	+	+	X
mainfunders.com	+	+	+	+	+	+	X
monefellows.com	X	-	-	-	-	-	-
pagido.de	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
pairfinance.com	X	-	-	-	-	-	-
prestacap.com	+	+	+	-	+	-	+
rechnung48.de	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
seedmatch.de	+	X	-	-	-	-	-
smava.de	-	X	-	-	-	-	-
spotcap.com	X	-	-	-	-	-	-
swisspeers.ch	X	-	-	-	-	-	-
trade.com	X	-	-	-	-	-	-
tradi.co	X	-	-	-	-	-	-
transvendo.de	+	+	+	+	+	+	+

Platform (starting domain)	Criteria						
+ = fulfilled; x = not fulfilled; - = not checked since one criterion already not fulfilled	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7
traxpay.com	x	-	-	-	-	-	-
trustbills.de	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
unternehmerich.de	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
valendo.de	x	-	-	-	-	-	-
vexcash.com	-	x	-	-	-	-	-

Source: Own source

In order to identify the relevant financing fintechs, a systematic approach was applied. First, by a search on fintech information portals. The fintech information portals crowdfunding.de, fintech-hub.eu, and paymentandbanking.com were used. Second, as recommended for online searches, an online search platform was used (Welker et al., 2015). The online search platform google.de was used with the key terms crowdlending, crowdinvesting, or factoring and “Mittelstand”. The search was conducted between 5 November and 8 November 2017.

4.2.3 Data collection and analysis

In order to qualitatively analyse data, different QDA-software can be used (Kuckartz, 2009; Mayring, 2001). MAXQDA is a software that supports the procedure. The software does not automatically conduct analysis but rather facilitates the organisation, categorisation, and coding (Mayring & Brunner, 2009). The software used for the data collection, coding, and the analysis was MAXQDA, Mozilla Firefox, and Microsoft PowerPoint. The web-presences of the platforms were opened with Mozilla Firefox as the internet browser. The procedure consisted of the following three steps.

First, categories and sub-categories were deductively defined. Second, the content of the web-presences was systematically read, inserted to MAXQDA, and coded. According to the literature, there are different views related to the reasonability of the storage of data in electronic form from online searches due to storage capacity reasons, transformation issues, and transformation restrictions especially for hyperlinks (Welker et al., 2015). However, in case of no data storage in electronic form, the reliability is limited due to the dynamic and transitory content on web-presences (Welker & Wuensch, 2010). Especially the fintech market is infant and dynamic. There are different options to archive the material of content analysis that is based on online data. The usage of automatic storage programs can cause issues in the illustration of the content. The manual storage can be considered as feasible alternative method (Ruediger & Welker, 2015). The options include the creation of screenshots or the download of total web-presences from online- to offline-modus (Roessler, Hautzer, & Luenich, 2014). In order to increase the reliability and to reduce the

issues that can be caused by the usage of an automatic storage program, the data in this research was stored from an online- to an offline-modus by a manual procedure with Mozilla Firefox as internet browser. The data of each relevant website of the respective web-presence was separately stored as text file and inserted to MAXQDA. The total population sampling consists of financing fintechs that provide services in Germany. Therefore, the material including the terms and conditions of the platforms is in German language. Due to potential losses in translation especially in a legal context in terms of contractual agreements, the material was coded in German in MAXQDA. The third step was that in case there was new meaning, a new category or sub-category was defined, and again the material was coded.

The procedure mentioned was conducted for all segments, i.e. crowdlending, crowdinvesting, and factoring. The three different category systems are in appendix B, C, and D. These category systems include the definition and coding rules of the categories and sub-categories and examples as recommended by Mayring and Fenzl (2014). Additionally, they include the information whether the category or sub-category was deductively or inductively defined. Deductively defined implies that the respective theoretical background is illustrated in the theoretical and conceptual frameworks or the narrative literature review. The categories were split into categories that are related to the platform, borrowers, and investors, and one category was defined for overall topics. Each category and sub-category have a number. The crowdlending category system consists of 26 categories and 56 sub-categories. The crowdinvesting category system consists of 26 categories and 62 sub-categories. The category system of factoring platforms consists of 15 categories and 36 sub-categories.

The data of the crowdlending platforms was collected between 11 and 15 November 2017. The data was collected of the web-presence

- fundingcircle.com on 11 November,
- kapilendo.de on 12 November,
- lendico.de on 13 November,
- unternehmerich.de on 14 November,
- creditshelf.com on 15 November 2017.

The data of the crowdinvesting platforms was collected between 16 and 22 November 2017. The data was collected of the web-presence

- unternehmerich.com on 16 November,

- kapilendo.de on 17 November,
- transvendo.de on 18 November,
- katrim.de on 19 November,
- finnest.com on 20 November,
- conda.de on 21 November,
- deutsche-mikroinvest.de on 22 November 2017.

The data of factoring platforms was collected between 23 November and 1 December 2017. The data was collected of the web-presence

- flexpayment.de on 23 November,
- rechnung48.de on 24 November,
- decimo.de on 25 November,
- billie.io on 26 November,
- pagido.de on 27 November,
- bezahlt.de on 28 November,
- fundflow.de on 29 November,
- trustbills.de on 30 November,
- factoringbörse.de on 1 December 2017.

To increase the inter-subjectivity, the units of analysis should be defined. The text of a qualitative content analysis is not interpreted as whole. The text can be divided into segments. The segmentation rules are defined as units of analysis. The units of analysis consist of the following three units. The coding unit means the smallest component of the text that can be assessed and assigned to one category. The context unit means what information of the whole material can be considered for the category assignment. The recording unit means which material is confronted with one category system (Mayring, 2014; Mayring & Fenzl, 2014).

The definition of the units of analysis in a qualitative content analysis that is based on online data is more difficult due to the hyper-textuality of the data (Welker et al., 2015). The hyper-textuality, also defined as non-linear structure, of the data on websites is caused by the different hyperlinks from one text to the next (Welker & Wuensch, 2010). It can be differentiated between website and web-presence. Website means the accumulation of heterogeneous objects like texts, pictures, and videos on one website without hyperlinks. Web-presence means a system of linked websites that

can be opened via hyperlinks (Luzar, 2004). In order to have clear distinctions of the relevant material, it is recommended to define whether it is only the starting page domain, the starting page domain including further defined hyperlinks, or the starting page domain including all hyperlinks (Welker et al., 2015). The latter means the web-presence.

For all categories except C2 (founding date) and C3 (banking or other financing related licence) the recording unit was the respective web-presence of the platform. This means the material that could be accessed by the starting page domain including all hyperlinks of the relevant financing fintech was considered to assign the text to a category. This can also include the registration as individual investor on the platform to receive financing contracts. In order to find the founding date of the legal entity, the search function on online-handelsregister.de was used. This is an online service for the German trade registry. In order to find whether or not the platform has a banking or other financing related licence, the search function on portal.mvp.bafin.de of the BaFin was used. There are financing fintechs that provide more than one segment. In this case, the financing fintech was identified as sample in each of the respective segment. As mentioned, for each segment, i.e. crowdlending, crowdinvesting, and factoring one category system was defined. Therefore, the recording unit consisted of all financing fintechs' web-presences within the specific segment. The context unit consisted of the financing fintechs' web-presences and the categories deductively defined. The coding unit consisted of several words or phrases with a meaning context.

The description of the results in chapter five is based on the category-based summary approach, which implies that the results were chronologically sorted by the categories. This approach reduced the redundancy in terms of number of words and supported the cross-case analysis. The meaning of the material that was related to a category or sub-category was summarised, paraphrased to a common wording, and translated from German to English. In case of illustrations, i.e. the examples of the contractual agreements and fund flows, PowerPoint was used. According to Kuckartz, in qualitative research the different content can be summarised and analysed based on a profile matrix (2016). The structure of the profile matrix of the documentary reach is illustrated by figure 28.

Figure 28: Profile matrix of documentary research

Source: Own illustration based on Kuckartz 2016, p. 38

The category-based perspective is illustrated by the rows, while the case-based perspective is illustrated by the columns. The former means the results are summarised by the categories defined, which represent the issue under study, while the latter means the results are summarised by the different cases like the persons who were interviewed. In this documentary research, the cases are the different financing fintechs. A coherence between two or more categories can be analysed by examining the content of the different categories that are allocated in different rows but within one column. For a cross-case analysis, different cases can be examined, which are allocated in different columns but within one row. The description of the results was summarised and inserted into the profile matrix. In case the information was not available for a category, zero was assigned. In total, three profile matrices were created respective for each segment, i.e. crowdlending, crowdinvesting, and factoring platforms. Due to the total population sampling strategy, the results are generalisable for crowdlending, crowdinvesting, and factoring platforms that provide services to SMEs in Germany.

4.2.4 Quality criteria

In contrast to quantitative research, qualitative research has no commonly accepted approach for quality criteria. Depending on the area of research and methods, there are different discussions about the quality criteria (Flick, 2014). A “content analysis is a research technique for making replicable and valid inferences from texts (or other meaningful matter) to the contexts of their use” (Krippendorff, 2013, p. 24). Additionally, the approach of the content analysis should be inter-

subjective (Brosius et al., 2012). For qualitative content analyses reliability, validity, and inter-subjectivity should be defined as quality criteria (Mayring & Brunner, 2009). The strategies to satisfy the quality criteria in this research are illustrated in table 12.

Table 12: Quality criteria for qualitative content analysis – business model of fintechs

Criteria	Strategies to satisfy quality criteria
Reliability	The data of the web-presences was stored as text files. The total material was coded a second time by the researcher independent of the first coding to increase the intra-coding reliability. Additionally, parts of the text were coded by another person to increase the inter-coding reliability.
Validity	For the definition of the categories, the deductive and inductive approach was applied. The categories were defined according to the mutually exclusive and collectively exhaustive principle. The deductive categories were defined based on a theoretical and conceptual framework and a narrative literature review.
Inter-subjectivity	The whole research procedure is documented. The units of analysis were defined, and the categories have definitions and coding rules. Additionally, it is documented whether the category is deductively or inductively defined.

Source: Own illustration

Reliability also includes the inter-coding reliability (Ramsenthaler, 2013). This means that at least a part of the text should be coded from another person. The other person should be introduced into the category systems. In case of deviations, the topics should be discussed. Additionally, there is the intra-coding reliability. This means that after the first coding, the researcher should code the total material or at least parts of the material again without considering the first coding (Mayring, 2010). In order to increase the validity, it is recommended to apply a combination of the deductive and inductive approach. Furthermore, the categories should have clear definitions in order to increase the inter-subjectivity. Additionally, the categories should be mutually exclusive and collectively exhaustive in order to increase the validity and reliability. Collectively exhaustive means that all relevant aspects or characteristics should be defined in the category system in order to answer the research question, and mutually exclusive means that each defined category should be distinctive from each other. The characteristics within a category should be exclusively related to the category defined (Brosius et al., 2012). Furthermore, the definition of the units of analysis is relevant in order to increase the inter-subjectivity (Mayring, 2014).

4.2.5 Limitations

Although the quality criteria of this research are reliability, validity, and inter-subjectivity, a common problem with qualitative content analyses is subjectivity (Mayring, 2010). This problem means that another researcher who wants to answer the same research question may come to other results even if the same data are used (Smith & Taffler, 2000). Krippendorff mentioned that

qualitative content analysis means the “data are made, not found, and researchers are obligated to say how they made their data” (Krippendorff, 2013, p. 81). This means the results of this qualitative content analysis are subjectively influenced. This includes the definition of the sample or more precisely the identification of the relevant financing fintechs, the definition of the deductive and inductive categories to qualitatively appraise the business model, and the analysis of the data. Another problem with a documentary research is authenticity (Merriam & Tisdell, 2016). This means that some information presented on the web-presences might not be correct. Additionally, the results are based on a point in time analysis. This means the business model of a financing fintech identified or more precisely its web-presence could change anytime. There can be quick changes and developments within the information technology (Gomber et al., 2017). Therefore, changes are likely. Additionally, new financing fintechs can be founded and existing ones can be abolished. Furthermore, the content of the fintech information portals and the algorithm of the online search platform can be changed. The motivation of financing fintechs is to make profit, and their services are provided online. Therefore, it can be assumed that they can be founded in the World Wide Web without obstacles. This means that all relevant financing fintechs should be identified. However, there is the risk that more relevant financing fintechs exist that are not presented in the fintech information portals and the online search platform used.

4.3 Primary research method – expert interviews with executives of LMEs

4.3.1 Research steps

In order to critically explore and evaluate to which extent the service of financing fintechs is a substitute for traditional banking services to LMEs in Germany, semi-structured expert interviews with executive managers were conducted. For the conduction of interviews with managers, there is no unique concept that has to be used, instead the common qualitative research instruments can be applied (Trinczek, 2002). Nevertheless, there are some aspects that should be considered in interviews with managers, which are described further below. The steps for the research were as follows.

After the definition of the research objective and method, the sample was defined. The theoretical background is already shown in chapter two and three, and the results of the documentary research are shown in chapter five. Based on these results, the interview guideline was created. It is recommended to use one guideline for all interviews in order to increase the comparability (Helfferich, 2014). Additionally, the units of analysis were defined. The next step was the data collection and analysis. The data was analysed based on a qualitative content analysis. The last two

steps were the description of the results and the discussion and conclusion. The steps are illustrated by figure 29.

Figure 29: Steps of expert interviews

Source: Own illustration based on techniques from Mayring 2010, p. 229

As seen by figure 29, there are two back couplings. There is a back coupling from the discussion and conclusion to the research objective in order to check whether the research objective was achieved and to the reflection of the theoretical background in the meaning that the current state of research is extended by this research.

4.3.2 Definition of sample

Different techniques can be applied for the sample definition. There are probability and non-probability techniques. The former is more relevant for quantitative research, while the latter is more relevant for qualitative research (Akremi, 2014).

According to Robinson, a four-step approach can be applied for sampling in interview-based qualitative research (2014). First, the research population has to be specified. Based on inclusion and exclusion criteria, the population can be defined. The results of the narrative literature review and documentary research indicate that financing fintechs currently serve smaller SMEs with a lower creditworthiness. To qualitatively evaluate the disruptive innovation threat, data of larger SMEs with a high creditworthiness is necessary. They are more attractive for traditional banks. Therefore, the focus of this research is on LMEs in Germany that have a relatively high

creditworthiness. The company's annual turnover should be between 50 and 500 mn€. Again, the definition of Grunow and Figgenger of large mid-sized companies includes an annual turnover between 50 and 500 mn€ (2006). The German state-owned development banking group, KfW, defines a company as SME if the annual turnover is not higher than 500 mn€ (Zimmermann, 2017). The equity ratio was considered for the representation of the creditworthiness. The higher the equity ratio, the more stable the company, the more independent from other financial sources, and the better the company's creditworthiness (Woehe et al., 2013). Equity ratios below 30% can be critical for the company (Preißler, 2008). Therefore, companies with a lower equity ratio than 35% were not relevant. It is difficult to exactly define the population in terms of numbers. 99.95% of the total number of companies are SMEs with less than 500 mn€ in annual turnover (Zimmermann, 2017). In total, 3,647 k companies existed in Germany in 2014. According to the quantitative definition of the IfM Bonn, thereof, 3,249 k (89.0%) micro, 307 k (8.4%) small, and 76 k (2.2%) middle companies existed. This implies that approximately 0.35% (12.8 k) of the total number of companies are companies with an annual turnover between 50 and 500 mn€. However, this number would need to be reduced by the companies with an equity ratio lower than 35%.

According to Robinson, the second step is the definition of the sample size (2014). In contrast to surveys in which the number of samples is a major consideration, in qualitative interviews the crucial factor is not the number of respondents but the potential of each person to contribute to the development of insight and understanding of the phenomenon under study (Merriam & Tisdell, 2016). Theoretical and practical aspects have to be considered for the definition of the sample size. The number of interviews has to be practical in terms of time and financial resources. Ideal is the theoretical saturation where no new insight is generated by further interviews (Robinson, 2014).

The third step is the definition of the sample strategy. The non-probability sampling can be split into convenience and purposive sampling strategy. Convenience sampling is a kind of random selection procedure, while purposive sampling is based on the researcher's judgment. The latter can ensure that particular aspects are represented in the sample. In this research the purposive sampling was applied or more precisely the quota sampling which relates to the purposive sampling strategy. The quota sampling implies that a set of categories is defined, and a minimum number of cases is required for the sampling (Robinson, 2014). This sampling strategy was defined in order to represent different industries, which intends a heterogeneous sample. The narrative literature review shows that not only technology innovative SMEs are interested in fundings through financing fintechs. Therefore, there was no focus on one specific industry. The definition of the minimum cases was based on the industry distribution of SMEs that is illustrated in chapter two. The minimum cases are illustrated in table 13.

Table 13: Minimum cases for sample definition

Industry	Share of total SMEs	Minimum required cases
Services to businesses	30.50%	3
Services to consumers	16.60%	2
Financial services	4.10%	0
Trade	17.40%	2
Construction	10.30%	1
Manufacturing	7.30%	1
Transportation and communication	4.90%	1
Catering	3.10%	0
Other industries	5.90%	0

Source: Own illustration; industry distribution based on KfW Banking Group, 2015, p.1

Since the share of financial services and catering is low, with rounding less than 5%, for these no minimum cases were defined. Regarding other industries, there is no concrete industry, and thus no minimum case was defined. In Germany, there are 16 federal states. The company size structure is similar among these federal states (Schwartz & Gerstenberger, 2018). Due to the similarity in the size structure, the relatively high number of federal states, and the already existing variation in industry, there was no variation in federal states. Due to practical and homogeneity reasons, solely companies in Bavaria were selected. In terms of number of employees of SMEs, Bavaria is the second largest federal state after North Rhine-Westphalia (Guentenberg, 2012; Schwartz & Gerstenberger, 2018).

Again, the company is represented by its executive managers. In order to interview the persons who represent the company, have an authority in financing decisions, have the best knowledge of how to finance their companies' assets and operations, and should best explain the reasons for their financing decisions, this research focuses on executives. Larger companies often have more executive managers with different responsibilities; however, it also depends on the kind of legal entity and the organisational structure of the company. This research focuses on executives with an authority in financing issues. The roles of the executives and the number of board members is explained in the next section.

The last step was the sourcing of the participants. In this research, companies were searched on following platforms: the searching platform www.google.de (searching terms: "Mittelstand Firmen Bayern", which means mid-sized companies Bavaria), the free encyclopaedia website www.wikipedia.de (search for companies based on the different communities in Bavaria), the job searching portal www.yourfirm.de (selection to companies in Bavaria), and

www.mittelstandspreis.com (selection to companies in Bavaria), which is a website that listed companies that were nominated for a SME reward.

In total, 129 companies were contacted between 30 July and 4 September 2018. These companies were selected based on the turnover, equity ratio, and industry. Some companies did not publish their turnover and equity ratio. For the turnover search, in addition to the company's web-presence, the searching platform google.de was used to find turnover related press releases. Based on these sampling criteria and the definition of the sourcing websites including the definition of the selection or searching terms, the sampling bias is reduced.

The recruitment of specific participants that work within an organisation can be contacted via a gatekeeper (Robinson, 2014). Depending on the shown contact data on the company's website, either the executive manager was directly or a gatekeeper (for example a media spokesperson) was contacted. All persons were contacted with a research information sheet that includes the requirements for the company.

4.3.3 Data collection and analysis

In total, 10 interviews were conducted and analysed. Since the theoretical saturation was achieved, no further interviews were conducted. Of the 10 interviews, six were conducted face-to-face on site (F-to-F) and four via call. The reason for the latter is that the executives preferred calls. Since the focus of the interviews was on the themes and content, there was no difference for this research. Nine interviews were conducted with an executive manager. The role of these executive managers included the responsibility of financing issues. One interview (number 9) was conducted with the manager of the financing department. The interview was planned with both the executive manager and the manager of the financing department. Prior to the interview, it was agreed that the executive manager attends on demand for certain questions that could not be answered by the manager of the financing department. This was not necessary. The manager of the financing department also had authority in financing issues, could answer all questions, and represented the executive manager. The managers of the company one, six, and ten were also owners of the company, while in case of the others the managers were not owners (they may have some shares as incentive but not a majority).

In table 14, the number of the interview, the role (CFO = Chief Financial Officer; MD = Managing Director; MF = manager of financing department), and gender (m = man; w = woman) of the interviewee, the information whether or not the executive manager is also the owner, the date, the

channel (F-to-F or call), the company industry (B-to-B = service to business; B-to-C = service to consumers), and the legal entity of the company are illustrated.

Table 14: Conducted expert interviews

No	Role	Gender	Manager also owner	Date	Channel	Industry	Legal entity	Board members
#1	MD	m	yes	14.08.18	F-to-F	Manufacturing	KG	1
#2	CFO	m	no	20.08.18	F-to-F	Trade & services B-to-C	AG	2
#3	CFO	m	no	22.08.18	F-to-F	Services B-to-B	AG	3
#4	CFO	m	no	29.08.18	Call	Services B-to-B	GmbH	4
#5	CFO	m	no	05.09.18	F-to-F	Manufacturing & trade	AG	3
#6	MD	w	yes	12.09.18	Call	Manufacturing & B-to-B	GmbH & Co KG	5
#7	CFO	m	no	10.10.18	F-to-F	Services B-to-B	GmbH	1
#8	CFO	m	no	31.10.18	Call	Manufacturing	GmbH	3
#9	MF	w	no	05.11.18	F-to-F	Services B-to-C and B-to-B	GmbH	2
#10	MD	m	yes	06.11.18	Call	Transport and construction	GmbH	2

Source: Own illustration

Since some companies have different business units, they are allocated to more than one industry. Additionally, there is a variety in the kind of legal entity. KG means it is a private company with a fully liable owner or more specific a fully liable complementary. In this case, the complementary is the sole managing director of the company. AG signifies a capital company based on stocks (not necessarily public), while GmbH signifies a capital company without stocks (Beck, 2014). In capital companies there are separated roles for ownership and management while the management can also be the owner of the company. The GmbH is represented by its managing directors (Geschäftsführer) according to the German Limited Company Act (GmbH Gesetz), while the AG is represented by its executives (Vorstand) according to the Stock Corporation Act. However, depending on the organisation of the company, the terminology of the management's role can include additional information, which depends on the functions within the organisation, e.g. Chief Financial Officer. Furthermore, the number of executives can vary. GmbH & Co KG signifies a private company, while the fully liable complementary is a GmbH. The roles shown in table 14 are taken from the respective company's website and were validated in the interviews. In case the LME have had more than one executive or managing director, the one with an authority decision in financing issues was selected. In order to have a common terminology, in this research the managers above are defined as executive managers. Due to the diversity in legal entity and number of board members, the definition of LME in this research is not limited to one legal entity or one board structure. The name of the interviewees and companies are not mentioned because anonymity of the data was agreed on.

The interviews were conducted based on a semi-structured guideline. The interview guideline is a list of questions the researcher intends to ask in the interview. In structured interviews, the guideline includes very specific questions listed in a particular order, while in unstructured interviews, the guideline includes few topical areas without a particular order. In semi-structured interviews, it is in between those two. The semi-structured interview guideline can include some specific questions, some more open-ended questions, and perhaps a list of some topical areas. The order of the questions depends on the study's objective, the time available, the person that is interviewed, and the sensitivity of some questions (Merriam & Tisdell, 2016). The guideline should be open and clear and designed to increase the flow of information without interruptions or changes of subjects. In an expert interview, the guideline can be more structured, and the questions can be more concretely and precisely defined because the focus is on the thematic and content (Helfferich, 2014). The questions can be flexibly handled, and the way in which questions are defined is a crucial consideration in extracting the information desired. In order to improve the quality of the data obtained by the interview, the questions and words used should be defined in a familiar language that makes sense to the respondent (Merriam & Tisdell, 2016). Especially at the beginning of the interviews with managers, managers have a dominant question-answer expectation. While the interview follows its own process, this expectation decreases. Additionally, since managers have mostly less time available, the guideline helps the interviewer conducting the interview in an appropriate way (Trinczek, 2002).

According to Strauss, Schatzman, Bucher, Ehrlich, and Sabshin, there are four different types of questions (1981). First, hypothetical questions in which the interviewer asks what the respondent might do, or what a particular situation might entail. Typically, these questions begin with what if or suppose. The response is usually a description of the person's actual experience. Second, the devil's advocate questions follow in which the respondent is challenged to consider an opposing view or explanation to a situation. These questions are used when the topic is controversial, and the researcher is interested in the respondent's opinion and feeling. Third, the ideal position questions in which the respondent is asked to describe an ideal situation. These questions elicit information and opinion and reveal positives and negatives. Finally, the interpretative questions provide a check on the researcher's understanding and offer an opportunity for more information, opinion, and feelings. Additionally, the interview can include probes by questions that follow up on something that was already asked. Probes can be in the form of asking for more details, clarifications, or examples. There are different types of questions which should be avoided. Multiple questions should be avoided, which means one question is actually a multiple question, or a series of single questions that do not allow the respondent to answer one by one. Additionally, leading questions should be avoided. These questions include a bias or an assumption of the researcher

which may not be held by the respondent. There is the risk that the respondent accepts the researcher's point of view. Finally, yes-or-no questions should be avoided. They give less information and can shut down or slow the flow of information. Why questions can uncover insights that might be speculative, but they might also suggest a new line of questioning. In asking why questions, the risk of dead-end responses has to be considered (Patton, 2015).

In order to create the guideline of this research, the four-step model of Helfferich was applied (2014). First, by brainstorming without well-phrased sentences all kinds of questions were collected. Second, the collected questions were critically evaluated and selected in terms of relevance for the research question and creation of new knowledge. Third, the remaining questions were sorted by chronological order and substantial affiliation. Finally, for specific questions different key aspects were subsumed under them in order to increase the information flow and to ensure that all relevant aspects are considered. In case the respondent does not provide enough information, the interviewer can fall back on these key terms. Prior to undertaking the interviews, the guideline was reviewed and refined through an iterative process with another postdoctoral student and the supervisory team, and a pilot was undertaken. The outcome of the review of the postdoctoral student was that the starting question needed to be modified in order to have a smoother introduction and of the supervisory team that the closing questions needed to be more open but context related. The pilot was useful to test the guideline and to gain some practice in interviewing. The outcome of the pilot was that the guideline was adequately designed. The interview questions (IQ) were categorised by the following five topics: IQ1) general information about the company and role, IQ2) financing preferences and bank relationships which can be directly asked (Mac an Bhaird, 2010), IQ3) substitute for traditional financing instruments by crowdlending and crowdinvesting, IQ4) substitute for traditional financing instruments by factoring platforms, and IQ5) closing questions. The guideline of this research including the rationale of the questions is in appendix F. The questions and key terms of the guideline are linked to the research question two of this research.

There are different ways to record interview data. Interviews can be audio or video recorded. The former is less intrusive than the latter, which includes the non-verbal behaviour. Additionally, the interviewer can take notes during or after the interview (Merriam & Tisdell, 2016). In this research the interviews were audio recorded. This ensured that everything what was said is preserved for the analysis. The non-verbal behaviour is not a crucial factor in this research because the main interest is the thematic and content. Based on a consent form, which was sent in advance, the interviewees were informed that the data will be recorded. To have a backup if one fails, the interviews were recorded with two devices. The duration of the interviews varied between 27 and

79 minutes. In total, the recording time of all interviews is 485 minutes. Furthermore, the recordings should be transcribed by certain rules (Mayring, 2014). For the transcription of the interviews, the following rules of Dresing and Pehl were applied (2018):

- The interview was transcribed word-by-word.
- Dialects and abbreviations were translated into standard German.
- Unfinished words were transformed into whole words.
- Stutters were removed, and if words were doubled, the word was transcribed once.
- Punctuations were inserted to ensure readability.
- Phrases like um, uh, etc. were removed.
- With change of speaker, an empty line was inserted which causes paragraphs.
- At the end of each paragraph a time code was inserted.

Since the interviewees were executive managers of companies in Germany, they were conducted in German. First, the recorded material was transcribed in German and then translated into English. The software f4transkript was used for the transcription procedure. The software supports the procedure by playing the audio recording slower and automatically including time codes. Since all executive managers were promised anonymity, the company related data was removed or replaced by X and Y. The transcripts were sent to the executive managers with the request to give feedback in case of any changes desired. No changes were needed.

In interviews the rights and interests of the interviewees need to be respected. The contact with other people can have an influence on these individuals or their environment in a direct or indirect way. Therefore, ethical aspects such as privacy, voluntary nature of participation and the right to withdraw, and the effects on participants of the way in which the data is used, analysed, and reported have to be considered (Saunders et al., 2009). “The avoidance of harm (non-maleficence) can be seen as the cornerstone of the ethical issues that confront those who undertake research” (Saunders et al., 2009, p. 186). The ethical aspects that have to be considered are also addressed in the guideline for ethical research that is published by the University Ethics Committee of the UWS. Under these ethical aspects, the conduction of the expert interviews is not critical. There is no physical or mental risk. All interviewees were adults. They were asked to take part as experts, and no sensitive personal information were involved. There was no pressure to participate and no payment for participation was offered. Additionally, confidentiality of data and anonymisation of the experts are assured.

The data was analysed by a qualitative content analysis. The material of the documentary research consisted of the web-presences of the financing fintechs, while the material of this qualitative content analysis consisted of the transcripts of the expert interviews. Therefore, the approach was slightly different. "Content analysis is not a standardized instrument that always remains the same; it must be fitted to suit the particular object or material in question and constructed especially for the issue at hand" (Mayring, 2014, p. 39). The software used was also MAXQDA, which supports the procedure. For the analysis of the transcripts, a combination of the summary and structuring content analysis was applied. As in the documentary research, the categories were both deductively and inductively defined. As already mentioned, in a qualitative content analysis that is systematically conducted, quantitative aspects like frequency can be integrated (Mayring, 2001).

Based on the steps recommended by Mayring (2014), the procedure of the qualitative content analysis consisted of the following steps. First, based on the theoretical background and the interview guideline, the categories including sub-categories were deductively defined. Second, the transcripts were uploaded to MAXQDA and the text was read and coded with these categories. The coding unit consists of several words or phrases with a meaning context. The context unit consists of the interview transcript, the theoretical and conceptual frameworks, the content of the narrative literature review, and the results of the documentary research, while the recording unit consists of all interview transcripts. A coding unit was solely assigned to one category or sub-category. The text that supports no or only little content to answer the research question was not coded. Third, in case of new relevant aspects coming from the material, a new category or sub-category was inductively defined. As in the documentary research, the categories could be continually modified until the material was completely processed. A list of the categories and sub-categories including their definitions and coding rules and examples was developed. In total, 17 categories and 72 sub-categories were defined. The category system is in appendix E. This includes also the information on whether the category or sub-category was deductively or inductively defined. The last step was that the results of the qualitative content analysis were described and discussed to answer the research question. As illustrated in the documentary research, a category-based and case-based summary approach is possible. The structure of the profile matrix of the expert interviews is illustrated by figure 30.

Figure 30: Profile matrix of expert interviews

Source: Own illustration based on Kuckartz 2016, p. 38

The profile matrix is different relative to the documentary research because the material of the expert interviews is more comprehensive and the meaning can be more divergent. To provide an overview of the results, the content of the profile matrix consists of 1, which means the statement is true, and 0, which means it is not true. The structure is the same as in the documentary research. The profile matrix of the expert interviews is in appendix G. Of the total text material, 58% was coded. Due to the limited extent of this research, the description of the results consists of the coded material which is most relevant to answer the research questions. The description of the results in chapter six is based on the category-based summary approach which implies that the results were chronologically sorted by the categories. This approach reduced the redundancy in terms of the number of words and supported the cross-case analysis.

The discussion of the results included the identification and evaluation of qualitative indicators that enable or disable the substitution of traditional banking services by the services of financing fintechs for LMEs in Germany. Since both the services of financing fintechs and traditional banks can be separately consumed, the indicators were discussed and evaluated as disabling the substitution, enabling the substitution, or as neutral if it is both disabling and enabling due to opposed rationales or neither disabling nor enabling. The indicators were evaluated for the status quo, and if there are any potential changes for the future, they were also evaluated.

Since qualitative interviews are mostly single case analyses, it is difficult to generalise the results (Mayring, 2001). In contrast to quantitative research, qualitative research focuses on the detailed analysis of single cases (Kuckartz, 2010). However, there are different methods to transfer the results of single cases to similar cases. One method is to describe and analyse the context of a single case, and then to generalise it to cases with a similar context. Another method is to increase the number of comparable cases (Mayring, 2001). The empirical typification is a combination of both the consideration of particularities of single cases and regularities to other cases (Kuckartz, 2010). Therefore, the empirical typification can be conducted by a cross-case analysis (Kuckartz, 2016). The comparison of commonalities and differences are necessary to create valid results (Kelle & Kluge, 2010). The empirical typification implies that objects with similar characteristics are summarised into one type. The objects of the same type should have a high homogeneity, while the different types within a typology should have a high heterogeneity. The total of types that are formed for a given phenomenon is termed typology (Kluge, 2000; Kuckartz, 2010). The empirical typification is not a separate method, instead the results of a qualitative content analysis can be used to define different types within a typology (Schreier, 2014).

4.3.4 Quality criteria

Especially for qualitative interviews there are different quality criteria (Flick, 2014; Helfferich, 2014; Steinke, 2007). Objectivity, as defined in quantitative research, cannot be a quality criterion for interviews due to the subjectivity of the method. Additionally, since the context is relevant for the data creation in interviews, reliability cannot be a quality criterion (Helfferich, 2014). Validity is the criterion that is not excluded (Steinke, 2007). Steinke defined four quality criteria which can be applied for expert interviews (2007). The criteria that are applied in this research with their description and the strategies to satisfy them are illustrated in table 15.

Table 15: Quality criteria for expert interviews

Criteria	Description	Strategies to satisfy quality criteria
Indication of method	It has to be checked whether the method is appropriate for the subject under study.	As described in the methodology chapter, semi-structured interviews with experts is an appropriate method to answer the research question.
Empirical evidence	It has to be assured that the results of the study are based on empirical data.	The recordings of the interviews were transcribed and analysed with a qualitative content analysis which includes definitions and coding rules and examples.
Generalisability	It has to be checked whether the results are representative and if yes, to show the limits.	It is not a quantitative research that is representative for a total population. However, by the number of conducted interviews, the theoretical saturation was achieved and indicators

Criteria	Description	Strategies to satisfy quality criteria
		were identified and evaluated which can be generalised to cases with a similar context.
Inter-subjectivity	It has to be assured that a third party can reconstruct the study.	The method, the definition of the sample, the data collection including the interview guideline, and the coding are documented. The interviews were audio recorded and transcribed.

Source: Own illustration based on Steinke 2007, p. 181

The qualitative content analysis that was applied to analyse the material of the expert interviews included the same quality criteria as the qualitative content analysis of the documentary research. To increase the intra-coding reliability, the total material was coded a second time by the researcher independent of the first coding. Additionally, parts of the text were coded by another person to increase the inter-coding reliability. To increase the validity, the categories were deductively and inductively defined. Since there are more inter-relations between the categories, for example, disadvantages in crowdlending may interrelate with advantages in relationship banking, the quality criterion that the categories should be mutually exclusive and collectively exhaustive is not as strictly applied as in the qualitative content analysis of the documentary research. Nevertheless, the material is only assigned to one category or sub-category. To increase the inter-subjectivity, the whole research procedure is documented. The units of analysis were defined, and the categories have definitions and coding rules. Additionally, it is documented whether the category is deductively or inductively defined.

4.3.5 Limitations

Although there are strategies to satisfy the quality criteria, there are limitations. “The key to getting good data from interviewing is to ask good questions; asking good questions takes practice” (Merriam & Tisdell, 2016, p. 117). The guideline was created based on the results of the secondary and documentary research. However, the researcher’s gained experience is limited. Therefore, this might be a limitation. Furthermore, due to the subjectivity of the method, the results are influenced by the researcher. Additionally, the possibility to generalise the results is limited because it is a qualitative research. The sample definition does not include a probability approach as in quantitative research that is representative for a total population. Furthermore, in purposive sampling there is the problem that the sample is influenced by the researcher’s own background, location, and connection (Robinson, 2014). However, the defined criteria for the sample selection such as industry, turnover, and equity ratio and the definition of the sourcing websites including the selection or searching terms reduce the sample bias.

4.4 Summary and conclusion

In order to achieve the research aim and objectives and to answer the research questions, this research consists of a qualitative multi-method approach. First, a business model analysis was conducted based on a documentary research, and second, expert interviews with executive managers of LMEs were conducted.

The objective of the documentary research is to qualitatively appraise in depth the business model of financing fintechs, i.e. crowdlending, crowdfunding, and factoring platforms that provide services to SMEs in Germany. This includes the first qualitative evaluation of the disruptive innovation threat of financing fintechs to traditional banks. A documentary research that consists of the material of the financing fintechs' web-presences and the application of a qualitative content analysis was selected as the suitable method based upon methodological considerations. Based on a total population sampling strategy, the material of the financing fintechs' web-presences was stored as text files and inserted to MAXQDA. Afterwards, the material was coded by deductively and inductively defined categories. The results are described from a category-based perspective. Additionally, the results are summarised in three profile matrices.

Based on the results of the business model analysis, the expert interviews with executive managers of LMEs in Germany could be conducted to critically explore and evaluate to which extent the service of financing fintechs is a substitute for traditional banking services. This includes the second qualitative evaluation of the disruptive innovation threat of financing fintechs to traditional banks. The method of expert interviews with executives of LMEs was selected as the suitable method based upon methodological considerations. Even though a quantitative approach includes a statistical representation, it would be less appropriate to understand in depth to which extent the service is a substitute. Based on a quota sampling strategy, 10 expert interviews were conducted to achieve the theoretical saturation. The interviews were recorded and transcribed. Afterwards, the transcripts were inserted to MAXQDA and coded by deductively and inductively defined categories. The results are described from a category-based perspective. Additionally, the results are summarised in one profile matrix.

The definition and documentation of the research steps including the sample definition and the data collection and analysis ensure that the research aim and objectives are achieved and the research questions are answered. Additionally, it increases the reliability, validity, and inter-subjectivity.

5 Results of primary research – business model analysis based on documentary research

The purpose of this chapter is to describe and discuss the research results of the documentary research to qualitatively appraise in depth the business model of financing fintechs, i.e. crowdlending, crowdinvesting, and factoring platforms that provide service to SMEs in Germany. Additionally, it includes a first evaluation of the disruptive innovation threat of financing fintechs that provide services to SMEs in Germany to traditional banks. For each financing fintech segment, i.e. crowdlending, crowdinvesting, and factoring platforms the results are separately described and discussed.

5.1 Business model of crowdlending platforms that provide services to SMEs

5.1.1 Description of results

In total, 21 financing fintechs were analysed, of which, five crowdlending platforms. Each platform was characterised with a number (#). As described in chapter four, the source of the content was the web-presence of the respective platform, while only for the founding date online-handelsregister.de was used, which is an online trade registry service; for checking of whether or not the platform has a banking licence, the search function on portal.mvp.bafin.de of the BaFin was used. Since crowdlending platforms are two-sided marketplace business models, the categories were split into three groups: Category one (C1) to C12 is related to the platform, C13 to C20 to the borrower, and C21 to C25 to the investor. C26 is related to overall topics without a specific defined content.

The results are summarised in one profile matrix which is illustrated in table 16. If certain information is not described in the following for a platform, then the information was not available. Whether or not the information was available, is also shown in the profile matrix – it is labelled with zero and not available in case of a category and with not available in case of a sub-category. C1 relates to formal aspects which describe the name of the platform's legal entity and starting domain:

- #01 Funding Circle Deutschland GmbH with the starting domain fundingcircle.com.
- #02 Kapilendo AG with the starting domain kapilendo.de.
- #03 Lendico Deutschland GmbH with the starting domain lendico.de.
- #04 UNIC AG with the starting domain unternehmerich.de.
- #05 Creditshelf GmbH with the starting domain creditshelf.com.

Due to simplification reasons, in the following the platforms are termed with the starting domain but without the top-level domain. C2 describes the legal entity's founding date, which varies between 2013 and 2015 – see details of each platform in profile matrix.

Again, the platform either needs an own banking licence or has to cooperate with a bank. Sub-category one of C3 (C3S1) describes that the platform has a banking licence on its own, while C3S2 describes it has no banking licence and cooperates with a bank. The latter also includes the information, whether the resale of the loan claim from the bank to the investors is direct or indirect. No platform has a banking licence on its own. Fundingcircle cooperates with Wirecard AG and Kapilendo with Fidor Bank AG. All platforms, except Unternehmerich, apply the indirect resale mechanism.

C4 describes the contractual agreements and fund flows between the parties involved. Both the indirect and direct resale mechanisms are already explained in chapter three. However, in order to illustrate the contractual agreements and fund flows, the mechanisms of Kapilendo and Unternehmerich are explained in the following. Kapilendo consists of two legal entities: Kapilendo AG and Kapilendo Funding GmbH. The borrower and each investor have a user contract with Kapilendo AG in order to use the platform. This contract can be agreed via registration on the platform. After the platform positively selected and published the funding, the investors can screen the funding and in case they want to invest, they have to click a button to offer. This click procedure is legally an *invitatio ad offerendum* meaning a request to receive an offer. Afterwards, the investors receive a contract with Kapilendo Funding GmbH via e-mail for the resale of the partial loan claim against the borrower. After the receipt of the e-mail, the investors can click a button on the platform to agree to the contract without a further written agreement. The agreement of the partial loan claim contract includes an agreement of an investment arrangement contract between Kapilendo AG and the investor. The investors transfer the funds to Kapilendo Funding GmbH. Instead of providing the loan, the platform arranges the loan between the partner bank (Fidor Bank AG) and the borrower. Therefore, there is a loan arrangement contract between Kapilendo AG and the borrower. Additionally, there is a loan agreement between Fidor Bank AG and the borrower which is only valid if the funding threshold is reached. Furthermore, there is a resale claim contract between Fidor Bank AG and Kapilendo Funding GmbH. Kapilendo Funding GmbH provides the funds to the bank, and the bank provides the funds to the borrower. The repayments of the loan and the interest payments that are transferred from the borrower to the investors are organised by the platform via Fidor Bank AG. The mechanism of Kapilendo is illustrated by figure 31. This mechanism of the indirect resale is also applied on Fundingcircle, Lendico, and Creditshelf.

Figure 31: Kapilendo – indirect mechanism of resale of loan claims to investors

Source: Own illustration

The direct resale mechanism of Unternehmerich is illustrated by figure 32. In contrast to the mechanism shown above, the investors have to transfer the funds to an escrow account of the bank. Furthermore, the bank directly resells the loan claim in partial claims to the investors. Therefore, there are no investment arrangement contracts, but contracts for the partial claim resale between the bank and the investors. The repayment and interest payments are transferred from the borrower to the bank and from the bank to the investors.

Figure 32: Unternehmerich – direct mechanism of resale of loan claims to investors

Source: Own illustration

C5 describes the countries in which the platform provides its services. Fundingcircle provides its services in Germany, the UK, the US, and the Netherlands. Lendico provides its services in Germany, Austria, Switzerland, the Netherlands, and Brazil, while the others provide their services solely in Germany.

C6 describes the kind of loan that is available through the platform. C6S1 means an annuity, while C6S2 means a bullet loan. Fundingcircle and Lendico provide annuity loans, Creditshelf bullet loans, and Unternehmerich and Kapilendo both, while on Kapilendo the bullet loans are only applicable in case of operating loans, which are limited to 100 k€. All categories and sub-categories previously mentioned were deductively defined.

Again, as illustrated in chapter three, there are different matching mechanisms to bring investors and borrowers together, which is described in C7. All sub-categories, except C7S5, were deductively defined. C7S1 means the funding is published on the platform with a fixed interest rate and maturity that is defined by the borrower; then, the investors can invest. This mechanism is not applied. C7S2 means that the funding is published on the platform with a fixed maturity that is defined by the borrower and a fixed interest rate that is defined by the platform; then, the investors can invest. This mechanism is defined as pre-defined interest rate mechanism. Kapilendo and Unternehmerich apply this mechanism. The duration of the publication is 30 days on Kapilendo and 120 days on Unternehmerich. Typically, on Kapilendo the payment to the borrower is between 45 and 60 days after the request for funding. C7S3 means that the funding is published on the platform with a fixed maturity that is defined by the borrower, while the interest rate is defined by a closed auction. This mechanism is defined as auction-based mechanism, which is applied by Creditshelf. Creditshelf defines interest rate ranges for the auction, which are based on the results of the creditworthiness evaluation and a maximum interest rate that is defined by the borrower. The duration of the publication is 2.5 weeks. The offers with the lowest interest rates win, while the remaining offers are not considered. The investors' offers are not published to each other. C7S4 means that the investors provide funds to the platform based on certain risk preferences, and the platform itself allocates the funds to the borrowers. This mechanism, also known as auto-bid, is not applied. C7S5 means that the decision of the loan offer with a fixed interest rate and maturity is by the platform itself based on an agreement with professional investors. First, the funding is published to the public with a fixed interest rate and maturity. Second, if not enough funds could be collected from the public, agreed funds from professional investors can be taken. This is defined as pre-agreed financing mechanism, which is applied by Fundingcircle and Lendico. The decision by the platforms is within two days. In case of a positive decision, the funding is published on the platforms for five days, and the fund transfer to the borrower is typically after seven days. For all mechanisms the

information of the funding including the identification of the company and economic data like the rating class or ranges defined, the loan volume, the purpose of the loan, and financial figures of the company are published to registered investors. However, on Creditshef anonymous publishing and publishing without showing financial figures are also possible. On Lendico anonymously publishing is also possible, while the platform mentioned that the more information is provided, the quicker the process to find investors.

Again, there are two funding principles: C8S1 means that the platform applies the all-or-nothing, while C8S2 means the keep-it-all principle is applied. All platforms apply the all-or-nothing principle. However, for the pre-agreed financing matching mechanism, the decision is in any case in advance by the platform.

C9 describes whether or not the platform selects the funding in advance before it is published. This selection includes the identification of the company and the person who represents the company, the eligibility of a funding according to the platforms' requirements, and the evaluation of the creditworthiness. C9S1 means the platform selects the funding, while C9S2 means it does not. All platforms select the funding in advance.

C10 describes which party conducts the creditworthiness evaluation. C10S1 means the platform itself, also based on input from a third party, and C10S2 means directly by a third party like a credit investigation company. Fundingcircle, Kapilendo, Lendico, and Creditshef evaluate the creditworthiness by themselves, also based on input from a third party. On Fundingcircle and Lendico the creditworthiness is automatically evaluated but in specific cases there can be individual evaluations by their credit risk experts. The evaluation on Creditshef consists of a combination of a traditional approach and a new approach that is based on big data analytics. This approach was not further specified. On Unternehmerich the creditworthiness is directly evaluated by a credit investigation company.

C11 describes the rating classes and the respective interest rates. Fundingcircle defined six rating classes from A+ to E with interest rate ranges from 3.79% to 16.61%. Kapilendo defined five rating classes from AA to D with interest rate ranges from 2.49% to 11.99%. Lendico defined five rating classes from A to E with interest rate ranges from 3.00% to 14.40%. The details are illustrated in the profile matrix. Again, on Creditshef the final results depend on the auction.

C12 describes the volume already financed and number of fundings on the platform. C12S1 means the volume, while C12S2 means the number of fundings. The volume already financed of the total fundings on Fundingcircle is 4,700 mn€ (international) and on Kapilendo 19 mn€. The number of the total fundings succeeded is 70,000 (international) on Fundingcircle and 78 on Kapilendo.

C13 describes the target borrower of the platform. There is no explicit definition required. In case the platform mentioned a certain target group, the sub-category was applied. However, some specifications of the borrower are described in C14. C13S1 means SME, C13S2 means freelancer, C13S3 means start-up, and C13S4 means large company as the target borrower. All platforms focus on SMEs as borrowers, whereas Unternehmerich also focuses on start-ups. The other groups were not mentioned. All previously mentioned categories and sub-categories were deductively defined. C14 and C15 and their sub-categories were inductively defined.

C14 describes the major requirements that have to be fulfilled by the borrower. C14S1 means the company must be a capital or private company as legal entity. Fundingcircle and Lendico require a capital or private company as legal entity, while Kapilendo requires a capital company. C14S2 means the company must fulfil a certain level of age in years. Fundingcircle and Lendico require at least two years, and Kapilendo and Creditshelf require three years. C14S3 means the company must have a certain annual turnover (in k€). Fundingcircle and Lendico require at least 50 k€, Kapilendo requires at least 300 k€ or 1,000 k€ depending on the kind of loan, and Creditshelf requires at least 2,500 k€. C14S4 describes the procedure of the bank for the borrower's authentication. On Fundingcircle the borrower can be requested to verify its identification through video or Post identification. On Lendico and Unternehmerich the verification is typically through Post identification. Video identification is a two-factor authentication procedure based on a web-based video stream in which a person shows their identity card to another. The ownership of the identity card and the biometric element of the person's picture can be verified through the video stream (Bender & Kuegler, 2016). Based on this procedure, there is no need to go to a branch (Dorfleitner & Hornuf, 2018). Video identification was first legally allowed by the circular 1/2014 of the BaFin related to section 12 of the anti-money laundering act (Geldwäschegesetz). Post identification is a two-factor authentication procedure in which staff of the Deutsche Post verifies the person based on a walk to a retail branch or by the delivery staff. Afterwards the data is electronically transferred to the party which requested the verification (Terboven, 2011). C14S5 means any further requirements. Fundingcircle requires that the equity ratio is at least between 5% and 10%. Kapilendo requires that the current profit must be at least 25 or 100 k€ depending on the kind of loan, and the profits must be positive for the last two years. Unternehmerich requires a viable business model without further specifications.

C15 describes the documents that are required from the borrower. C15S1 means the borrower must provide annual reports. Fundingcircle and Lendico require annual reports for the last two years, and Kapilendo and Creditshelf for the last three years. C15S2 means the borrower must provide a financial analysis of the current year, which is required on Fundingcircle, Kapilendo, Lendico, and Creditshelf. C15S3 means the borrower must provide current bank account statements, which is required on Fundingcircle, Lendico, and Creditshelf. C15S4 means the borrower must provide a cash flow forecast. Creditshelf requires a cash flow forecast for 12 months.

The categories C16 to C22 and their sub-categories were deductively defined. C16 describes whether or not a collateral or guarantee is required. C16S1 means a collateral, C16S2 a personal guarantee, and C16S3 no collateral or guarantee is required. Fundingcircle, Kapilendo, and Lendico require a personal guarantee of the executive manager or owner of the company. On Fundingcircle typically the owner who has more than 50% in shares provides the personal guarantee. In case there is no owner who has more than 50%, it should be a joint personal guarantee. Creditshelf typically requires no collateral, but in certain cases it can be demanded.

C17 describes the minimum and maximum loan volume. C17S1 means the minimum, while C17S2 the maximum loan volume (in k€) that is available through the platform. The minimum varies between 5 and 100 k€, while the maximum varies between 250 and 2,500 k€. The details are illustrated in the profile matrix. On Fundingcircle two loans can be parallelly financed in maximum, while the request for the second one has to be six months after the first one.

C18 describes the minimum and maximum loan maturity. C18S1 means the minimum, while C18S2 the maximum maturity in months. The minimum varies between 1 and 12 months, while the maximum varies between 12 and 60 months. The details are illustrated in the profile matrix.

C19 describes whether or not an early repayment of the loan is possible. C19S1 means the loan can be repaid prior to maturity without an additional fee, C19S2 means with an additional fee, and C19S3 means it is not possible. An early repayment without an additional fee is possible on Fundingcircle, Kapilendo, and Lendico. For the others the information was not available.

C20 describes the fee that has to be paid from the borrower to the platform (in % of volume or €). C20S1 means a one-off fee is charged independently whether or not the funding succeeded. Unternehmerich charges 1% for the creditworthiness evaluation. C20S2 means a one-off fee is charged if the funding succeeded. Fundingcircle, Kapilendo, Lendico, and Unternehmerich apply this kind of fee. On Fundingcircle it depends on the rating and maturity and ranges between 2% and

5%. On Kapilendo it depends on the maturity and ranges between 1.9% and 4.9%. On Lendico it also depends on the maturity and ranges between 2% and 4.5%. Unternehmerich charges a one-off fee of 0.5% for the funding set-up and 0.3% for the transaction and escrow service. C20S3 means an annual fee is charged. Unternehmerich charges 0.1%, and Creditshef charges between 1% and 5% which depends on the rating and maturity but at least 2.5 k€. The details are illustrated in the profile matrix.

C21 describes the kind of investors who can invest in the fundings. C21S1 means individual, while C21S2 professional investors. The latter includes institutional investors. On Fundingcircle, Kapilendo, Lendico, and Unternehmerich both can invest, while on Creditshef only professional investors are allowed to invest. On the latter the investors are typically family offices, high-net-worth-individuals, funds, and private banks.

C22 describes the volume that can be invested. C22S1 means the minimum loan volume that an investor has to invest, while C22S2 means the maximum volume that an investor can invest in one funding. For individual investors the minimum varies between 100 and 250 €, while the maximum varies between 5 and 10 k€. For the maximum volume of 10 k€, individual investors have to fulfil certain requirements which are already explained in chapter three. For professional investors there are minimums that vary between 10 and 50 k€, while the maximum is unlimited. The details are illustrated in the profile matrix.

C23 describes the fees that have to be paid from the investors to the platform (in % of volume or €). Five sub-categories were defined. C23S3 was inductively defined, while the others were deductively defined. C23S1 means a one-off fee is charged independently whether or not the funding succeeded. C23S2 means a one-off fee is charged if the funding succeeded. These two fee models are not applied. C23S3 means a one-off fee is charged if the repayment and interests are repaid by the borrower, which is applied on Unternehmerich. In this case Unternehmerich charges the investor with 0.25%. C23S4 means an annual fee is charged. Fundingcircle and Creditshef charge 1%. C23S5 means no fee is charged. Kapilendo does not charge the investors.

The last categories were deductively defined. C24 describes reporting covenants. C24S1 means that the platform explicitly obliges the borrower to publish certain information to inform the investors on a regular basis, while C24S2 means that the platform explicitly mentioned that there is no obligation. Kapilendo references to section 23 subsection 2 of the VermAnlG. This section implies that borrowers who are not obliged to publish an annual report according to the German Commercial Act (HGB) and who are issued investment products are obliged to publish an annual

report in the electronic trade registry or provide it on request to the investors six months after the business year. According to section 2a in relation to 23 of the VermAnlG, a detailed management report and statutory auditor are excepted.

C25 describes whether or not there is a secondary market. C25S1 means there is a secondary market for the investors to sell or buy the investments, while C25S2 means there is no market. Kapilendo explicitly mentioned that there is no regulated secondary market. Since the information was not available on the other platforms, it can be assumed that no secondary markets exist.

C26 describes any other information that can be relevant. Fundingcircle acquired Zencap in Germany in 2015.

Table 16: Profile matrix of crowdlending

	Platform number	#01	#02	#03	#04	#05
C1	Legal entity and domain	- Funding Circle Deutschland GmbH - funding-circle.com	- Kapilendo AG - kapilendo.de	- Lendico Deutschland GmbH - lendico.de	- UNIC AG - unternehmer-ich.de	- Creditsshelf GmbH - credit-shelf.com
C2	Founding date of legal entity	2013	2015	2013	2014	2014
C3	Banking licence	S2 = No banking licence, cooperation with partner bank (Wirecard AG and indirect resale mechanism)	S2 = No banking licence, cooperation with partner bank (Fidor Bank AG and indirect resale mechanism)	S2 = No banking licence, cooperation with partner bank (indirect resale mechanism)	S2 = No banking licence, cooperation with partner bank (direct resale mechanism)	S2 = No banking licence, cooperation with partner bank (indirect resale mechanism)
C4	Contractual agreements and fund flows	See illustration above	See illustration above	See illustration above	See illustration above	See illustration above
C5	Countries	- Germany - UK - US - Netherlands	Germany	- Germany - Netherlands - Austria - Switzerland - Brazil	Germany	Germany
C6	Kind of loan	S1 = Annuity	S1 = Annuity S2 = Bullet (for operating loan)	S1 = Annuity	S1 = Annuity S2 = Bullet	S2 = Bullet
C7	Matching	S5 = Pre-agreed financing mechanism	S2 = Pre-defined interest rate mechanism	S5 = Pre-agreed financing mechanism	S2 = Pre-defined interest rate mechanism	S3 = Auction-based mechanism
C8	Funding principle	S1 = All-or-nothing	S1 = All-or-nothing	S1 = All-or-nothing	S1 = All-or-nothing	S1 = All-or-nothing
C9	Selection of funding	S1 = Yes	S1 = Yes	S1 = Yes	S1 = Yes	S1 = Yes
C10	Party conducting credit-	S1 = Evaluation by platform	S1 = Evaluation by platform	S1 = Evaluation by platform	S2 = Evaluation directly by a third party	S1 = Evaluation by platform (also input of

Platform number		#01	#02	#03	#04	#05
	worthiness evaluation	(also input of third parties)	(also input of third parties)	(also input of third parties)		third parties; including traditional approach and new approach based on big data analytics – no further specification)
C11	Rating classes and interest rates	A+: 3.79-7.16% A: 4.32-8.58% B: 5.36-10.15% C: 6.92-11.78% D: 8.85-14.01% E: 11.97-16.61%	AA: 2.49-3.65% A: 3.55-4.79% B: 4.65-6.49% C: 6.29-8.29% D: 7.99-11.99%	A: 3.00-3.40% B: 4.30-5.40% C: 6.30-7.40% D: 9.30-10.40% E: 13.30-14.40%	0 = Not available	Interest rate ranges defined; final results depend on auction
C12	Financed volume and number of fundings	S1 = 4,700 mn€ in volume (international) S2 = 70,000 in number (international)	S1 = Crowdlending and crowdinvesting 19 mn€ in volume S2 = 78 in number	0 = Not available	0 = Not available	0 = Not available
C13	Target borrower	S1 = SME	S1 = SME	S1 = SME	S1 = SME S3 = Start-up	S1 = SME
C14	Major requirements	S1 = Capital or private company as legal form S2 = Company minimum age (2 years) S3 = Minimum annual turnover (50 k€) S4 = For borrower's authentication: Video or Post identification S5 = Others (equity ratio should be at least between 5% and 10%)	S1 = Capital company as legal form S2 = Company minimum age (3 years) S3 = Minimum annual turnover (300 or 1,000 k€ depending on kind of loan) S4 = For borrower's authentication: Not available S5 = Others (depending on kind of loan additional requirements like minimum profit of 25 or 100 k€ and minimum duration with positive profit of last 2 years)	S1 = Capital or private company as legal form S2 = Company minimum age (2 years) S3 = Minimum annual turnover (50 k€ for last 2 years) S4 = For borrower's authentication: Post identification	S4 = For borrower's authentication: Post identification S5 = (Viable business model without further specifications)	S2 = Company minimum age (3 years) S3 = Minimum annual turnover (2,500 k€) S4 = For borrower's authentication: Not available
C15	Major required documents	S1 = Annual reports (for last 2 years) S2 = Financial analysis of current year S3 = Current bank account statements (for last 3 months)	S1 = Annual reports (for last 3 years) S2 = Financial analysis of current year	S1 = Annual reports (for last 2 years) S2 = Financial analysis of current year S3 = Current bank account statements (for last 3 months)	0 = Not available	S1 = Annual reports (for last 3 years) S2 = Financial analysis of current year S3 = Current bank account statements S4 = Forecast

	Platform number	#01	#02	#03	#04	#05
						cash flow (for 12 months)
C16	Collateral or guarantee	S2 = Personal guarantee	S2 = Personal guarantee	S2 = Personal guarantee	0 = Not available	S3 = Not needed (in certain cases, collateral can be demanded)
C17	Loan volume	S1 = Minimum 5 k€ S2 = Maximum 250 k€ (maximum two loans parallel)	S1 = Minimum 25 k€ S2 = Maximum 2,500 k€ (for operating loan 100 k€)	S1 = Minimum 10 k€ S2 = Maximum 250 k€	S1 = Minimum 50 k€ S2 = Not available	S1 = Minimum 100 k€ S2 = Maximum 2,500 k€
C18	Maturity	S1 = Minimum 6 months S2 = Maximum 60 months	S1 = Minimum 12 months S2 = Maximum 60 months (for operating loan 12 months)	S1 = Minimum 12 months S2 = Maximum 60 months	0 = Not available	S1 = Minimum 1 month S2 = Maximum 36 months
C19	Early repayment	S1 = Yes, no additional fee	S1 = Yes, no additional fee	S1 = Yes, no additional fee	0 = Not available	0 = Not available
C20	Fees to be paid by borrower (in % of volume or €)	S2 = One-off fee if success of funding: Depending on rating and maturity: - 6 to 12 months 2% for rating A+ and A and 3% for B to E - 12 to 60 months 4% for rating A+ and A and 5% for B to E	S2 = One-off fee if success of funding: Depending on maturity: 12: 1.9% 24: 2.9% 36: 3.9% 48: 4.9% 60: 4.9% 3 = Annual fee: 0.75% including marketing services	S2 = One-off fee if success of funding: Depending on maturity (months): 12: 2.0% 24: 3.0% 36: 4.0% 48: 4.5% 60: 4.5%	S1 = One-off fee independent of success of funding: 1% for creditworthiness evaluation S2 = One-off fee if success of funding: 0.5 for project set-up and 0.3% for transaction and escrow 3 = Annual fee: 0.1%	S3 = Annual fee: Between 1% and 5% depending on rating and maturity (minimum 2.5 k€)
C21	Target investor	S1 = Individual investor S2 = Professional investor	S1 = Individual investor S2 = Professional investor	S1 = Individual investor S2 = Professional investor	S1 = Individual investor S2 = Professional investor	S2 = Professional investor
C22	Investment volume	For individual investors: S1 = Minimum 100 € S2 = Maximum 5,000 €	For individual investors: S1 = Minimum 100 € S2 = Maximum 10,000 €	0 = Not available (business model is revised)	For individual investors: S1 = Minimum 250 € S2 = Maximum 10,000 € For professional investors: S1 = Minimum 50,000 € S2 = Maximum unlimited	S1 = Minimum 10,000 € S2 = Maximum unlimited
C23	Fees to be paid by investor (in % of volume or €)	S4 = Annual fee: 1%	S5 = No fee	0 = Not available	S3 = One-off fee if fully repayment and payment of interest: 0.25%	S4 = Annual fee: 1%
C24	Reporting covenants	0 = Not available	S1 = Yes (reference to section 23 subsection 2 of the VermaAnG)	0 = Not available	0 = Not available	0 = Not available

	Platform number	#01	#02	#03	#04	#05
C25	Secondary market	0 = Not available	S2 = No	0 = Not available	0 = Not available	0 = Not available
C26	Others	In 2015 Funding Circle acquired Zencap in Germany	-	Business model is revised	-	-

Source: Own source

5.1.2 Discussion and conclusion

The objective is to qualitatively appraise in depth the business model of crowdlending platforms that provide services to SMEs in Germany. Along the four interrelated components, key processes, customer value proposition (CVP), key resources, and profit formula, defined by Johnson et al. (2008), and towards the question to which extent crowdlending is a substitute for traditional banking services to SMEs, the business model of crowdlending platforms is discussed and appraised in the following. Additionally, it includes the first evaluation of the disruptive innovation threat of crowdlending platforms to traditional banks. Since it is a total population sampling, the results can be generalised, while crowdlending platform implies platforms that provide services to SMEs in Germany.

The key process of crowdlending to SMEs in Germany can be divided into four phases as illustrated by figure 33. In the first phase, application and selection, the SME makes a funding application, and the platform selects the funding including the check of the identification, the eligibility of a funding regarding the platforms' requirements, and the evaluation of the creditworthiness.

Figure 33: Key process of crowdlending business to SMEs in Germany

Source: Own illustration

After a positive selection, the second phase is the matching. Considering the criteria of Tauscher and Laudien described in chapter two, all crowdlending platforms are two-sided marketplace business models (2018). They match independent actors from a demand and supply side via a digital platform. The actors enter direct interactions with each other, and the platforms provide a frame

for transactions without a substantial produce or trade of the service or product. Although there is a bank in between, there can also be direct interactions for the exchange of information. The selection and creditworthiness evaluation by the platform and the origination of the loan by the bank might be considered as substantial produce. However, the funds are provided by the investors for specific fundings without on-balance sheet transactions of the platforms. Three different matching mechanisms bring investors and SMEs together:

- 1) Pre-agreed financing mechanism: The funding is first published with a defined interest rate to the public and in case not enough funds could be collected, agreed funds from professional investors can be taken.
- 2) Pre-defined interest rate mechanism: The interest rate is defined by the platform, and the funding is published to investors.
- 3) Auction-based mechanism: The funding is published, and the final interest rate is defined in an auction based on interest rate ranges.

The auto-bid mechanism and the matching in which the borrower defines the interest rate that are described in the literature are not applied. The latter might not be applied due the adverse selection. The pre-agreed financing matching was inductively defined and describes a new mechanism that is not described in the literature.

The third phase is the loan origination. In order to originate the loan, all platforms cooperate with a bank. According to Lambert et al., as financing fintechs leverage on technology, the information flow can be more efficient, and thus due diligence can be faster conducted than in traditional financing (2018). The duration between the application and selection phase and the loan origination depends on the matching mechanism. In case of the pre-agreed financing mechanism, the loan origination is seven days after a successful application. The matching duration of the other mechanisms varies between 20 and 120 days. Therefore, the duration of the former can be an advantage relative to traditional banking, while the duration of the others can be a disadvantage, which is related to the publishing duration rather than technology reasons.

In the last phase, repayment phase, the investors receive the interest payments and repayment of the loan. In contrast to the literature, there are also bullet repayment structures. The services of financing fintechs can have a higher simplicity than services of traditional banks (Braune & Landau, 2017; Dorfleitner et al., 2016; Lenz, 2015). Whether or not the online process in crowdlending is simpler than the process in traditional banking with physical meetings depends on the company's subjective perception.

The CVP of a business model helps customers performing a job that needs to be done. The results show that based on crowdlending platforms, SMEs can take loans that have similar and dissimilar characteristics to traditional bank loans.

The maximum loan volume in crowdlending varies between 250 and 2,500 k€, while the latter is the threshold for the obligation to publish a prospectus. It can be assumed that larger SMEs partly demand higher loan volumes. Relative to the different SME definitions illustrated in chapter two, the minimum turnover requirements in crowdlending are low. Either there are no requirements mentioned or in case they are mentioned, they vary between 50 and 2,500 k€. The definition of the IfM Bonn defines SMEs up to 50 mn€ in turnover, while other definitions like the KfW Banking Group include companies with a turnover up to 500 mn€. The maximum funding volume and the low turnover requirements indicate that crowdlending platforms focus on smaller SMEs, which is also indicated in the literature. Again, according to Maier, of 409 fundings on a crowdlending platform, the average turnover was 1.4 mn€, the average loan volume 73 k€, and the average company age 13 years (2016a). Although of Maier's results the company age is relatively high, crowdlending platforms have relatively low company age requirements which vary between two and three years. This implies that SMEs on crowdlending platforms can be relatively young, while traditional banks focus on older companies. Additionally, as described in chapter two, traditional banks focus more on larger companies because the unit costs of funding decrease with an increase in loan volume. In case of a low loan volume, banks often avoid high efforts to reduce the information asymmetry. Furthermore, as mentioned in the literature and confirmed by this research, the maximum maturity of crowdlending fundings is limited to 60 months. It might be that larger SMEs demand longer maturities for long-term investments. The limitation of the funding volume and maturity of crowdlending indicates that the performance in terms of functionality is lower for larger SMEs relative to traditional banks.

According to Reichling et al., the most long-term bank loans have a fixed interest rate in Germany (2005). Crowdlending platforms also have fixed interest rates. However, the rating classes that are published have relatively high interest rates; especially under the aspect of a negative 12-month EURIBOR (European Central Bank, 2020). Three platforms provided their rating classes with different ranges, which consist of totally 16 rating classes. Clustering the 16 rating classes, three have an interest below 5%, nine an interest above 5%, and of four it ranges from below 5% to above 5%. The clustering is illustrated in table 17.

Table 17: Clustering of rating classes of crowdlending platforms

Cluster	Fundingcircle	Kapilendo	Lendico	#	in %
Complete range below 5%	-	AA: 2.49-3.65% A: 3.55-4.79%	A: 3.00-3.40%	3	19%
Range below and above 5%	A+: 3.79-7.16% A: 4.32-8.58%	B: 4.65-6.49%	B: 4.30-5.40%	4	25%
Complete range above 5%	B: 5.36-10.15% C: 6.92-11.78% D: 8.85-14.01% E: 11.97-16.61%	C: 6.29-8.29% D: 7.99-11.99%	C: 6.30-7.40% D: 9.30-10.40% E: 13.30-14.40%	9	56%
Total				16	100%

Source: Own illustration

Additionally, the fees that are charged to the SMEs are relatively high. Typically, banks charge a fee for the arrangement, commitment, and administration service (Coyle, 2002). These fees can be split into one-off and annual fees. The former typically ranges between 0.5% and 1.0%, and the latter is about 0.3% of the volume (Grunow & Figgenger, 2006). As already mentioned, according to Blohm et al., crowdfunding platforms charge the borrower about 10% of the volume (2015). Considering the total cumulated fees including one-off and annual fees for a successful funding with a loan duration of 36 months without compounding, the fee of the best ratings varies between 2.10% and 4.15% of the volume, while it varies between 2.30% and 15.00% for the worst ratings.

Considering the fees and interests under a bullet structure assumption due to simplification reasons, the total cumulated cost of capital of a SME with the best rating for a three-year loan without compounding ranges between 11.00% and 15.37% of the volume, while it ranges between 43.12% and 54.83% for a SME with the worst rating. These high interest rates and fees indicate that crowdlending platforms focus on SMEs with lower creditworthiness. This is also supported by Scardovi who indicates that the borrower segmentation of financing fintechs includes borrowers with low creditworthiness, while traditional banks focus on borrowers from a mid to high creditworthiness (2016). Blohm et al. (2015) and Kaefer (2016) also indicate that for some borrowers, it can be a residual financing meaning the access to traditional banks is limited.

Based on the different fee models, it can be derived that partly the platforms subsidise the participation of investors. There is either no fee, an annual fee, or a fee if the SME fully repaid the loan. For investors the total cumulated fee for a successful funding with a loan duration of 36 months without compounding ranges between 0% and 3% of the investment volume. The fee can be an instrument of the platform to steer the matching between the borrowers and investors and to increase the network effects. Due to the two-sided marketplace business model, if the platform

aims to increase the number of successful fundings on the platform, then a proportional increase of the number of borrowers and investors is required.

Regarding collateral, Maier argues that the requirements of crowdlending platforms might be lower due to the lower loan volumes (2016a). Three platforms require a personal guarantee instead of a collateral. For larger amounts the personal guarantee might not be sufficient to cover losses in case of default. Additionally, the personal guarantee required might be a limitation for larger SMEs. It can be assumed that owners of larger SMEs want to limit their personal liability by founding a capital company and that the willingness of executive managers who are not simultaneously the owners of the company is limited to provide a personal guarantee. This can also be an indication of a lower performance of crowdlending platforms.

The services of financing fintechs can have a higher simplicity, velocity, and transparency than the services of traditional banks (Braune & Landau, 2017; Dorfleitner et al., 2016; Lenz, 2015). Again, whether or not the online process is simpler depends on the company's subjective perception. The different durations of the matching mechanisms were already discussed. Assuming that transparency means an open communication about the business model, the services provided, and the fees charged, it should not be higher than in traditional banking. Although the different rating classes may not be published by traditional banks, the high ranges dilute the information for both borrowers and investors.

As described in the literature, the repayment option prior to maturity without a fee can be a motive for SMEs to use crowdlending. This can be an advantage for the SMEs, while it can be a disadvantage for the investors because they have again transaction costs in finding new investments; besides, loan contracts with traditional banks can also include early repayments (Grunow & Figgenger, 2006).

In contrast to traditional banks, which provide a wide range of services as described in chapter three, crowdlending platforms solely focus on crowdfunding. Additionally, since the platforms have no banking licence, it can be considered as a non-integrated organisation, which could be an indication of a disruptive innovation.

As already described, Navaretti et al. assume that it is unlikely that financing fintechs will displace traditional banks in the long-term due to the adverse selection and moral hazard related problems (2018). Traditional banks decrease adverse selection and moral hazard, which occur due the principal-agent (P-A) relation including the information asymmetry as described in chapter two. The P-A relation of crowdlending is illustrated by figure 34. The professional and individual investors are

the principles, and the SMEs are the agents. Both the platform and the white-label bank support the P-A relation.

Figure 34: P-A relation in crowdlending

Source: Own illustration

Due to the two-sided marketplace business model, the reduction of adverse selection and moral hazard is also relevant for SMEs. Suboptimal equilibriums on platforms where only low-quality companies remain is not in the interest of both, at least in the long-term. Although the motivation of crowdfunding platforms to reduce these problems may not be as high as of traditional banks because they do not take the credit risk on their balance sheet, it is relevant for the platforms' success (Leboeuf & Schwienbacher, 2018; Navaretti et al., 2018). Additionally, according to Agrawal et al. (2014) and Vismara (2018), the investors may systematically underinvest in due diligence or free-ride on investment decisions of others because of the low investment volume and the fixed cost component of due diligence that makes it economically inefficient.

The platforms can reduce the information asymmetry by decreasing the costs of access to information. All crowdlending platforms select the funding in advance, evaluate the creditworthiness, and define the interest rate or interest rate range. This also solves the problem of duplicated screening meaning the platforms' results of the creditworthiness evaluation can be reused by the investors. Therefore, crowdlending platforms reduce adverse selection.

According to Lambert et al., being more informed and experienced, professional investors can send a signal that the fundings they invest in have a high quality (2018), and according to Agrawal et al. (2014), based on crowd due diligence, which means that many investors review a given funding, fraud can be detected. On all crowdlending platforms professional investors who could send quality

signals to individual investors are allowed to invest. However, as described in the literature, this causes the risk of irrational herding which implies passively imitating other investors (Agrawal, Catalani, & Goldfarb, 2010, 2014; Zhang & Liu, 2012). On four platforms individual investors whose due diligence can also be used to detect fraud are allowed to invest.

As mentioned by the European Banking Authority, in crowdfunding there is the risk that the borrower's creditworthiness evaluation is not conducted pursuant to generally applicable standards, and thus the borrower attracts less interest from potential investors because of an incorrect assessment (2015). The consequence should be adverse selection. The creditworthiness evaluation is conducted either by the platform itself, also from input of a third party, or directly by a third party such a credit investigation company. The involvement of a third party can be considered as a quality signal to reduce adverse selection (Agrawal et al., 2014). As described in chapter two and three, fintechs might evaluate the creditworthiness of borrowers based on both big data and machine learning, and thus might provide faster and more accurate decisions. Only one platform applies a combination of a traditional and new approach based on big data analytics which was not further specified. The others may not apply or mention it. Although financing fintechs might have a relative advantage in short-term because traditional banks spend the largest share of their technology budget in maintenance (Milne & Parboteeah, 2016), the motivation of fintech founders in Germany is more on the business process optimisation rather than the technology related development (Brandl & Hornuf, 2017). Of 120 fintechs in Germany, 22% apply big data analytics (Gimpel, Rau, & Roeglinger, 2016), while only a few apply it to evaluate the creditworthiness of borrowers, which might be also due to data protection issues (Dorfleitner & Hornuf, 2018). A new approach including big data analytics can include opportunities that decrease adverse selection by a more accurate evaluation. However, it can also include risks that increase adverse selection by a more inadequate creditworthiness evaluation due to less experience.

As described in chapter two, traditional banks reduce moral hazard by frequently monitoring the SMEs, defining covenants, and by requiring collaterals. On crowdfunding for individual investors, the monitoring is inefficient due to the small investment volumes (Vismara, 2018). Although three platforms require a personal guarantee which should reduce the moral hazard, it might be a limitation for larger SMEs. Platforms can also define regulations, perform monitoring roles, or facilitate information disclosures of companies after the funds are provided to decrease the moral hazard (Agrawal et al., 2014; Lambert et al., 2018). One platform mentioned the obligation to publish the annual report to the investors, while there are no further reporting covenants that reduce the moral hazard. Although this can be at first an advantage for the SMEs, it can be a disadvantage for the investors, and thus also a disadvantage for SMEs in the long-term.

There is also the risk of fraud or fake investments, which is the most extreme example of moral hazard, meaning the loan is intentionally not repaid by a wrong identification (Agrawal et al., 2014; European Banking Authority, 2015). For the borrower's authentication three platforms mentioned that the bank applies the video or Post identification procedure. For example, issues in the authentication procedure can be seen on the neo bank N26. It was formally requested by the BaFin in May 2019 to improve its processes including the customer authentication procedure and partly to re-authenticate its customers' identifications, which was negatively published in press (Manager magazin, 2019; N26 Bank GmbH, 2019). This might reduce the motivation of potential investors.

In crowdlending, there is no relationship between the different parties. Based on relationship lending, traditional banks reduce the information asymmetry by gaining soft information. In contrast, crowdlending is based on the transaction-based lending technology by considering hard information primarily from annual reports. This is also argued by Navaretti et al. who mentioned that traditional banks have soft information through relationships, while financing fintechs operate more on hard information (2018). Since SMEs are often informationally opaque, the transaction-based approach can be a disadvantage if new approaches like big data and machine learning do not replace relationship banking. This is further discussed in chapter six.

As described in chapter two, traditional banks reduce the transaction costs. Crowdlending platforms publish the fundings on their platforms, and the information of the funding background, maturity, and creditworthiness are provided on the platform for the investors. Therefore, crowdlending platforms reduce the ex-ante transaction costs. In case of the auction-based mechanism, the negotiation costs are reduced because interest rate ranges are defined. However, investors and SMEs have to find the crowdlending platform they want to use, and investors have to screen the fundings. Additionally, due to the fact that more parties are involved than in traditional banking, it might be a higher effort for SMEs to understand the contractual agreements and fund flows. Regarding the number of transactions, i.e. contractual agreements, crowdlending causes more transactions than markets without financial intermediaries due to the involvement of the platform and bank. Again, in case no financial intermediary like a traditional bank is in between, there are $n \times m$ contracts, while the number is $n + m$ with a financial intermediary, where n is the number of borrowers and m the number of investors.

For example, three investors want to lend their funds to three different borrowers. In case of crowdlending with the direct resale mechanism, there are 21 contracts under the following assumptions: Each investor and borrower have one user contract with the platform, and each

borrower has one loan arrangement contract with the platform. Since each investor wants to lend to each borrower, there are three resale partial claim contracts between each investor and the bank. Finally, the bank has one loan contract with each borrower. This example is illustrated by figure 35. In case of the indirect resale mechanism, there are further contracts due to the resale from the bank to the platform before they are sold to the investors and the investor arrangement contracts.

Figure 35: Number of transactions in crowdlending to SMEs in Germany

Source: Own illustration

This implies that the number of contracts in crowdlending is higher than in financial markets without financial intermediaries. However, the costs of each transaction can differ from each other. Under the direct resale mechanism and assuming that one borrower has one funding, both the borrowers and the investors use the platform for the first time without a previous user contract, and all investors invest in all fundings on the platform in order to take portfolio effects, then the number of contracts in crowdlending to SMEs is

$$c = (n \times m) + (n \times 3) + m.$$

Again, traditional banks provide lot size, maturity, and risk transformation. According to Kaefer, since in crowdfunding the investors directly lend money to borrowers, there is no maturity and risk transformation (2016). This is also applicable for crowdlending platforms that provide services to SMEs in Germany. According to Kaefer, there can be secondary markets to trade the investments prior to maturity (2016). However, the results of this research show that there are no secondary

markets. Therefore, the reduction of adverse selection and moral hazard is even more relevant. Since SMEs can take loan volumes of 2,500 k€ at maximum, while individual investors can invest 10 k€ at maximum, there is a lot size transformation. The principle of crowdfunding implies a lot size transformation.

The key resources of crowdlending platforms should be the network of both investors and SMEs (especially if they reach a critical mass), the platform as technical function, and specialised employees especially in marketing and technology related topics.

Regarding the profit formula, the question is what qualitative strategic advantages and disadvantages crowdlending platforms have relative to traditional banks. The profit formula advantages and disadvantages are summarised by figure 36.

Figure 36: Crowdlending – profit formula advantages and disadvantages

	Crowdlending platforms / investors		Traditional banks	
	Advantages	Disadvantages	Advantages	Disadvantages
Revenue structure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Potential increasing return to scale and more scalable without physical limitations ▪ Partly funding related fee income from investors 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Only fee income and partly totally depending on new fundings (for platform) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Fee and interest income over relationship life-cycle 	
Fixed costs structure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ No branch personnel and building related costs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Platform and bank involved that want to make profit 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Economies of scale and scope effects ▪ Positive experience curve effects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Regulatory related costs
Credit risk costs structure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ New approach creditworthiness evaluation (information asymmetry) 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Soft information (information asymmetry) ▪ Collateral and covenants (moral hazard) 	

Source: Own illustration

The logic primarily includes that one party's advantage is the other's disadvantage and vice versa which is not illustrated to reduce the redundancy. Since in crowdlending the investors take the credit risk and receive the interest income, they are added on the left side. However, it has to be considered that these aspects are only qualitative aspects without considering quantities.

Crowdlending platforms have only fee income, while traditional banks, especially commercial banks, have interest and fee income. According to Braune and Landau (2017) and Schlotmann (2017), the fee income structure of fintechs requires a high scale on both sides (borrowers and investors) because of the two-sided marketplace business model. Possible interest income for the period between the provision of the funds by the investors until the origination of the loan, and a possible monetisation of information are not taken into consideration. In crowdlending the investors have the interest income. Traditional banks should have a revenue structure advantage because they have both kind of revenues, and thus have less pressure to make new businesses since they have interest income until the loans are repaid. Crowdlending platforms have different fee models. Some have an annual fee, while others have only a one-off fee if the funding succeeded. Although the latter is attractive for SMEs, it implies that the platforms' revenues are only based on new fundings. This might be part of a growth strategy especially due to network effects. Nevertheless, the fees are relatively high. It might be that the platforms which have not published the volume and the number of fundings that were already financed on the platform have a lower volume and less fundings than the platforms which have published the figures. If one platform reaches a critical mass, it can take advantages of positive network effects which can cause an increasing return to scale, which again can lead to a winner-takes-it-all result. The number of successful fundings can be considered as output while the number of investors and borrowers can be considered as input. The effort to acquire new borrowers and investors should decrease after reaching a critical mass as the positive network effects make it more attractive to join the platform. The platform could lower the fees to strengthen its position and to further squeeze out the competitors from the market or could profit from a higher margin. However, there can also be negative one-sided and cross-sided network effects. Additionally, relative to traditional banks, the business of crowdlending is more scalable without physical limitations. Due to the two-sided marketplace business model, crowdlending platforms can also have a funding related fee income from the investors.

According to Navaretti et al., since fintechs focus on specific segments that relate to less regulation than traditional banks, they can have a cost structure advantage until the regulatory arbitrage is ruled out as fintechs provide similar activities like traditional banks (2018). Dorfleitner and Hornuf also indicate that fintechs have less regulations than banks (2019). Although crowdlending platforms have no banking licence, there should be no fixed cost structure advantage because in crowdlending the involvement of a bank is required, which has to be compensated. Regarding the fixed costs, traditional banks are larger and provide different services, and thus they should have economies of scale and scope advantages. Based on mergers, acquisitions, and expansion, financing fintechs could increase their economies of scale and network effects. In 2015, Fundingcircle

acquired Zencap in Germany. Furthermore, Fundingcircle and Lendico also provide their services abroad. Since traditional banks should be longer established in the market, they should have positive experience curve effects. According to Braune and Landau (2017) and Schlotmann (2017), the cost structure of financing fintechs can be lower because they are operating online without physical branches. Since crowdlending platforms have no branches, they should have a related fixed costs structure advantage in terms of personnel and building related costs. The number of branches of traditional banks has decreased which implies their returns were not sufficient. According to Schwartz et al., the total number of branches of all banks in Germany decreased by 27% from 38,082 in 2000 to 27,886 in 2015 (2017). Thereof, about 2,200 branches closed in 2014 and 2015. Considering the whole period, the CAGR is -2.1%, while for the last two years it is -3.7%. This cost structure disadvantage of traditional banks is also related to a cost and revenue structure advantage. Traditional banks can take advantage of soft information over time through a relationship to reduce credit risk costs and increase revenues during the relationship life-cycle. Additionally, since traditional banks often require a collateral that might be higher than the private assets of a manager or owner and often define covenants, there can be cost structure advantages in terms of credit risk caused by moral hazard. Regarding the credit risk costs caused by the information asymmetry, a new approach of the creditworthiness evaluation can decrease or increase the related costs for the investors. This depends on whether or not the new approach evaluates the creditworthiness more accurately.

In a first conclusion, there are indications that crowdlending to SMEs in Germany can be a disruptive innovation threat for traditional banks. The relatively low turnover and company age requirements, the limited loan volume and maturity, the relatively high interest rates and fees, and partly the requirement of a personal guarantee indicate that crowdlending platforms focus on smaller and younger SMEs with lower creditworthiness. Since this kind of customers are not mainly targeted by traditional banks, they can be considered as low-end or non-customers. As described, traditional banks focus on larger SMEs with a medium to high creditworthiness. Although the interest rates and fees are relatively high, they might not be high for low-end and non-customers. As illustrated in chapter three, Maier showed that SMEs which applied for crowdlending evaluated the interest rate of the platform at advantage relative to traditional banking and as one of the strongest motives to use crowdlending (2016a). Therefore, the services of financing fintechs could bring relative advantages to low-end and non-customers like lower prices which indicates a disruptive innovation (Christensen et al., 2004). Again, disruptive innovation is often based on a business model which consists of non-integrated organisation and a different revenue and cost structure model, and it is against all incumbents (Christensen & Raynor, 2003; Christensen et al., 2004). Crowdlending platforms fulfil these criteria which supports the indication of a disruptive innovation. Again, due

to its performance limitation, mainstream and high-end customers should reject the new service or product (Christensen et al., 2004). LMEs might reject the service of crowdlending or not consider it as a substitute due to the limit in volume and maturity, the transaction costs, the fee and interest rate level, and the partly required personal guarantee.

5.2 Business model of crowdfinancing platforms that provide services to SMEs

5.2.1 Description of results

Seven crowdfinancing platforms were analysed. Thereof, both unternehmerich.de and kapilendo.de also provide crowdlending. As described in chapter four, the source of the content was the web-presence of the respective platform, while only for the founding date online-handelsregister.de was used; for checking of whether or not the platform has a banking licence, the search function on portal.mvp.bafin.de of the BaFin was used. C1 to C12 is related to the platform, C13 to C18 to the borrower, C19 to C25 to the investor, and C26 is related to overall topics without a specific defined content.

The results are summarised in two profile matrices which are illustrated in table 18 and 19. C1 relates to formal aspects by describing the name of the platform's legal entity and starting domain:

- #01 UNIC AG with the starting domain unternehmerich.de.
- #02 Kapilendo AG with the starting domain kapilendo.de.
- #03 Transvendo GmbH & Co with the starting domain transvendo.de.
- #04 Mplus SELV AG with the starting domain katrim.de.
- #05 Finnest GmbH with the starting domain finnest.com.
- #06 Conda Deutschland Crowdfinancing GmbH with the starting domain conda.de.
- #07 DMI Deutsche Mikroinvest GmbH with the starting domain deutsche-mikroinvest.de.

C2 describes the founding date of the legal entity which varies between 2002 and 2016 – see the details of each platform in the profile matrix.

C3 describes whether or not the platform has a banking or financing related licence. C3S1 means that the platform has a banking licence in Germany, C3S2 means it has no banking licence but another financing related licence, and C3S3 it has neither a banking licence nor another financing related licence. No legal entity has a banking licence. Deutsche-mikroinvest has a licence as financial service provider including as investment broker according to section 1 subsection 1a of the German Banking Act (KWG).

C4 describes the countries in which the platform provides its service. Finnest provides its service in Germany, Austria, Switzerland, and Slovakia. Conda provides its services in Germany, Austria, Switzerland, Poland, Lichtenstein, Slovakia, and Slovenia, while all other platforms provide their services only in Germany.

C5 describes the kind of financing instrument which is provided on the platform, while some platforms provide more than one. C5S1 means subordinated loan, which is provided on Transvendo, Finnest, Conda, and Deutsche-mikroinvest. Transvendo provides subordinated loans with and without an additional exit interest. C5S2 means subordinated profit-participating loan, which is provided on Unternehmerich, Kapilendo, Transvendo, Conda, and Deutsche-mikroinvest. C5S3 means silent partnership, which is provided on Unternehmerich and Deutsche-mikroinvest. C5S4 means participation right, which is provided on Conda and Deutsche-mikroinvest. All categories and sub-categories previously mentioned were deductively defined.

Again, as illustrated in chapter three, there are different matching mechanisms to bring investors and borrowers together, which is described in C6. C6S1 and C6S2 were deductively and C6S3 was inductively defined. C6S1 means that after the funding is published on the platform for the public with defined economic conditions and a defined maturity (if the information was available about which party defines the economic conditions, it is also described), the investors can invest. This matching is defined as pre-defined economic conditions mechanism, which is applied on Unternehmerich, Kapilendo, Transvendo, Katrim, Conda, and Deutsche-mikroinvest. The publication is on Unternehmerich 120 days, on Kapilendo 30 days, on Transvendo between 90 and 180 days, and on Deutsche-mikroinvest 60 days. On the latter for larger volumes and on Katrim the duration is unlimited. On Transvendo and Deutsche-mikroinvest the borrower defines the economic conditions. Transvendo calculates the company value before publishing the funding, and Deutsche-mikroinvest defines how the company value has to be calculated for a later application. C6S2 means that the funding is published on the platform with a defined maturity, while the interest rate is defined by an auction. This matching is defined as an auction-based mechanism, which is applied on Finnest. The borrower defines interest rate ranges. The publication in which investors can provide offers is between 30 and 60 days. Then, the borrower defines the highest common interest rate that is necessary to achieve the funding volume. All investors receive the highest common interest rate. The borrower can reject individual offers. C6S3 means that the funding is published on the platform for a private placement with limited investors. This is defined as private placement mechanism, which is also applied on Finnest. There was no further specification.

C7 describes the contractual agreements and fund flows between the parties involved. Again, as described in chapter three, an additional payment service provider with a separate account (assigned for a funding) can be involved. Two sub-categories were deductively defined. C7S1 means an additional payment service provider with a separate account is involved, while C7S2 means there is no involved. On Unternehmerich, Kapilendo, Transvendo, and Conda an additional payment service provider with a separate account is involved, while on the other platforms there was no indication. In order to show the contractual agreements and the fund flows of this principle, the example of Unternehmerich is illustrated by figure 37. The contract of the financing instrument is directly between the borrower and investors. The borrower and each investor have a user contract with the platform, which can be agreed on via registration on the platform. For the fund flows a payment service provider is assigned. In this case, it is Secupay AG. After the investors completed their offers, they have to transfer the funds to the payment service provider, which has an escrow account for the funding. In case the funding threshold is reached, the mezzanine contracts between the borrower and investors are agreed on. The payment service provider transfers the funds to the borrower. The repayment and interest payments are transferred from the borrower via the payment service provider to the investors. In case the funding threshold is not reached, the already transferred funds are transferred back from the escrow account to the investors.

Figure 37: Contractual agreements and fund flows of Unternehmerich

Source: Own illustration

On Katrim, Finnest, and Deutsche-mikroinvest there was no indication of a payment service provider with a separate account. The example of Katrim is illustrated by figure 38. In contrast to the example shown above, the investors directly provide the funds to the borrower. The borrower

on Katrim has to log a loan register with data of the investors and economic data including the volume and return for the investors.

Figure 38: Contractual agreements and fund flows of Katrim

Source: Own illustration

C8 describes the funding principle that is applied. C8S1 means the all-or-nothing, while C8S2 means the keep-it-all principle is applied. On Katrim, Finnest, and Deutsche-mikroinvest the keep-it-all principle, while on the other platforms the all-or-nothing principle is applied.

C9 describes whether or not the platform selects the funding in advance. C9S1 means the platform selects the funding, while C9S2 means it does not. The selection includes the identification of the company and the person who represents the company and the eligibility of the funding according to the platforms' requirements. This partly includes the evaluation of the creditworthiness or the validation of the business model. All platforms select the funding in advance before they are published.

C10 describes whether or not there is a creditworthiness evaluation or business model validation, and if yes, which party conducts it. C10S1 means there is no creditworthiness evaluation or business model validation. All platforms evaluate the creditworthiness or validate the business model, but on Katrim the information was not available. C10S2 means there is a creditworthiness evaluation which is conducted by the platform, while input of a third party might be possible. This is applied on Kapilendo. C10S3 means there is a creditworthiness evaluation which is directly conducted by a third party like a credit investigation company. This is applied on Unternehmerich. C10S4 means the platform validates the business model. This is applied on Transvendo, Finnest, Conda, and Deutsche-mikroinvest.

C11 describes the economic conditions of the financing instrument. C11S1 means there is a fixed interest rate paid from the borrower to the investors. C11S2 means there is some kind of participation in turnover, C11S3 means in profit, and C11S4 in increase of the company value. The financing instruments can include a combination of the sub-categories mentioned. On Unternehmeric a fixed interest rate and the participation in the turnover and profit are possible. For example, there is a fixed interest rate of 2% and a planned interest of 5.6% which depends on the profit. The calculation of the latter is as follows: The investor's investment volume divided by the company's value times 20% times the EBIT. If the investment volume is 10 k€, the company's value is 3.6 mn€, and the EBIT is 1 mn€, then the additional interest payment is 556 €. On Kapilendo a fixed interest rate between 7% and 10% and a participation in the turnover are possible. The participation in the turnover is limited to 25% of the investment volume. For example, there is a fixed interest rate of 7.5% and an additional one-time interest that is paid at the end of the maturity. If the turnover of one financial year during the term exceeds 25 mn€, then the additional interest rate is 5%. If the turnover exceeds 30 mn€, then the additional interest rate is 10%, and if the turnover exceeds 35 mn€, then it is 15% of the volume. On Transvendo for subordinated loans, a fixed interest rate between 7% and 10% is possible. There is also the possibility of an additional exit interest. There was no further information available about the level or limits of the additional exit interest. On Transvendo for subordinated profit-participating loans, a fixed interest rate of 1% and a participation in the profit and increase of the company value are possible. On Katrim, Finnest, and Conda there is a fixed interest rate for subordinated loans. On Finnest there can be an additional interest payment that depends on the profit or more precisely on the EBITDA (earnings before interest, taxes, depreciation, and amortisation) margin. For example, if the EBITDA margin, which is the EBITDA divided by the total turnover, is above 10%, then the investor receives an additional interest payment of 2%.

On Conda for subordinated profit-participating loans, additional to a fixed interest rate, the participation in the profit and increase of the company value are possible. For example, assuming an investor provides 1 k€ of a total loan volume of 1 mn€, the fixed interest rate is 4.5%, the interest is calculated on a pro-rata basis with 360 days per year, and the effective days are 365, then the fixed minimum interest payment to the investor is 45.63 €. Additionally, there is a participation in the profit and increase of the company value. Generally, if new shareholders invest, the share capital increases but the percentage per investor decreases, which is also known as dilution. The subordinated profit-participating loan on Conda does not include a shareholding relationship. Therefore, the mezzanine contract includes a definition of the loan nominal per 100 € of the total loan volume, which represents the logic of the share capital of a company. Based on this nominal,

the share of the investor in participation in the profit and increase of the company value can be calculated. In this example the nominal is 0.28 € per 100 € loan volume and the initial share capital is 35 k€. The capital base of the company is the initial share capital plus the sum of the loan nominal of the investors, which is the product of the nominal 0.28 € and the total loan volume 1 mn€ per 100 € ($1 \text{ mn€} / 100 \text{ €} * 0.28 \text{ €}$). Thus, the capital base is 37.8 k€, and for the investor who provided 1 k€, the investment share is 0.00741% ($1 \text{ k€} / 100 \text{ €} * 0.28 \text{ €} / 37.8 \text{ k€}$). The profit participation equals the investment share times the profit minus the transaction costs. The latter is 15% of the volume between the fixed interest rate and the profit participation. If the company makes a profit of 1,244,428 €, the total interest payment including the profit participation is 85.22 € ($1,244,428 \text{ €} * 0.0000741 - 6.99 \text{ €}$).

The company value is calculated in two ways while the higher value is applied. It is calculated by an external auditor and by a turnover multiple, which is defined in the contract. The latter is multiplied with the company's turnover as reported in the last annual report. For both the equity value is calculated meaning the liabilities, except the liabilities of the mezzanine contract, are deducted. Additionally, all interest payments including the profit participation that were transferred to the investors during the term have to be added. The participation in an increase of the company value equals the company value times the investor's proportional share minus the invested volume minus the interest payments including the profit participation minus the transaction costs for the profit participation and the transactions costs for the participation in an increase of the company value. The latter is 15% of the value of the company increase before the deduction of the related transaction cost. For example, at maturity the investment share of the investor is 0.00627%, the turnover multiple company value is 94,877,114 €, the company value calculated by the external auditor is 60,000,000 €, the interest payments including the profit participation paid to the investors during the term are 1,716.36 €, and the related transactions costs are 263.18 €, so then the participation in the company value is 2,523.87 € ($94,877,114 \text{ €} * 0.0000627 - 1,000 \text{ €} - 1,716.36 \text{ €} - 263.18 \text{ €} - 445.39 \text{ €}$). Regarding the participation rights on Conda, the participation in the profit and increase of the company value are possible. On Deutsche-mikroinvest a fixed interest rate and the participation in the profit and increase of the company value are possible. The total interest rate is between 4% and 11%.

C12 describes the volume already financed and the number of fundings of the platform. C12S1 means the volume, while C12S2 means the number of fundings. The total volume already financed of all fundings on Finnest is 20 mn€, on Conda 21 mn€, and on Deutsche-mikroinvest 13 mn€. The number of the total fundings succeeded are 95 on Conda.

C13 describes the target borrower of the platform. There is no explicit definition required. In case the platform mentioned a certain target group, the sub-category was applied. However, certain specifications of the borrower are described in C14. C13S1 means SME, C13S2 means freelancer, C13S3 means start-up, and C13S4 means large company. Unternehmerich, Transvendo, Conda, and Deutsche-mikroinvest focus on SMEs and start-ups. Kapilendo, Katrim, and Finnest focus solely on SMEs. The categories C8 to C13 and their sub-categories were deductively defined.

C14 describes the major requirements that have to be fulfilled by the borrower to publish a funding. Four sub-categories were inductively defined. C14S1 means the company must be a capital or private company as legal entity. Kapilendo and Conda require a capital company, while Deutsche-mikroinvest requires a capital or private company. C14S2 means the company must fulfil a certain level of age (required years). Kapilendo requires at least three years and Katrim two years. Finnest requires several years, which was not further specified. C14S3 means the company must have a certain annual turnover (in k€). Kapilendo requires 300 k€. C14S4 means any further requirements. As with crowdlending, Unternehmerich requires a viable business model. Katrim requires that the company is owner or family managed. Finnest requires that the company has sufficient equity, a positive EBITDA, a stable ownership structure, and an adequate management. Deutsche-mikroinvest requires that the owner or management has no criminal record.

C15 describes the documents that are required from the borrower. Four sub-categories were inductively defined. C15S1 means the borrower must provide annual reports. Kapilendo requires the annual reports for the last three years, Conda of the current year and a forecast, and Finnest obliges the borrower to provide annual reports on demand to the investors. C15S2 means the borrower must provide a financial analysis of the current year, which is applied on Kapilendo. C15S3 means the borrower must provide a cash flow statement. Conda requires a cash flow statement of the current year and a cash flow forecast. C15S4 means the borrower must provide a business plan, which is applied on Conda and Deutsche-mikroinvest.

C16 describes the funding volume. C16S1 means the minimum, while C16S2 the maximum funding volume. The minimum varies between 30 and 100 k€, while the maximum is 2,500 k€. The details are illustrated in the profile matrix.

C17 describes the funding maturity. C17S1 means the minimum, while C17S2 the maximum maturity in months. The minimum is for subordinated loans on Kapilendo, Finnest, and Transvendo 36 and the maximum 60 months. The minimum is for subordinated profit-participating loans on Transvendo 60 and the maximum 84 months. The minimum is for short-term funding on Deutsche-

mikroinvest 6 and the maximum 36 months. Generally, it is between 60 and 96 months. The minimum is for subordinated loans and subordinated profit-participating loans on Conda generally 60 and the maximum 120 months. For participation rights it is generally 120 months. The minimum is on Katrim 24 and the maximum 144 months.

C18 describes the fees that have to be paid by the borrower to the platform (in % of volume or €). The fees on Unternehmerich are the same as in crowdlending. C18S1 means a one-off fee is charged independently whether or not the funding succeeded. Finnest charges one-off 2.75% but at least 9,500 € for the service and support. Conda charges 2,000 €, 2,500 €, or 3,500 € depending on the service package for the set-up of the funding. It provides three packages with different services. C18S2 means a one-off fee is charged if the funding succeeded. Kapilendo applies this kind of fee but mentioned no specifications. Transvendo charges 9.5% and Conda 7.5%, 9.5%, or 11.5% depending on the service package. Deutsche-mikroinvest charges between 6.25% and 10.00%. C18S3 means an annual fee is charged. Transvendo applies this kind of fee but mentioned no specifications. Finnest charges annually 950 € and Conda 1.5%.

C19 describes the kind of investors who can invest. C19S1 means individual, while C19S2 means professional investors. The latter includes institutional investors. Both can invest in fundings on Unternehmerich, Kapilendo, Transvendo, and Deutsche-mikroinvest, while on Finnest solely individual investors can invest. On Katrim and Conda individual investors can invest, while there was no information available about professional investors.

C20 describes the volume of the investors they can invest. C20S1 means the minimum volume that an investor has to invest, while C20S2 means the maximum volume that an investor can invest. The minimum for individual investors varies between 100 and 250 € and the maximum varies between 5,000 and 10,000 €, while for professional investors the maximum can be unlimited. The details are illustrated in the profile matrix.

C21 describes voting or participation rights for the investor. C21S1 means the financing instrument includes a voting or participation right for the investor, while C21S2 means it does not include such a right. On all platforms the financing instruments do not include such a right.

C22 describes control rights for the investor. C22S1 means the financing instrument includes a control right for the investor, while C22S2 means it does not include such a right. Control rights have less influence on the company than voting or participation rights but more than information rights. For example, a control right is the validation of the accuracy of the annual report by accessing

the business records. On Unternehmerich there is a control right for silent partnerships, which consists of the validation of the annual report. On Deutsche-mikroinvest a control right can be defined, which was not further specified. Kapilendo and Conda explicitly mentioned that there are no control rights.

C23 describes information rights for the investor. C23S1 means the financing instrument includes an information right for the investor, while C23S2 means it does not include such a right. On Unternehmerich there is an information right for subordinated profit-participating loans without further specification, while for silent partnerships the information was not available. On Kapilendo the information right is as follows: Twice a year the borrower has to publish the turnover figures and a description of the cash flow situation and the business development via the platform. On Transvendo the information right is as follows: After six months of the provision of the funds, the borrower has to provide evidence of the fund employment. Additionally, on a quarterly basis the borrower must provide a status reporting to the platform about the business development including liquidity and assets and changes in corporate relationships. Furthermore, once a year the borrower has to publish the annual report. On Finnest the information right is as follows: The borrower has to provide once a year information of the business development and the annual report. Additionally, Finnest references to the already described section 23 subsection 2 of the VermAnlG. On Conda there is an information right for subordinated profit-participating loans. This implies that the borrower has to provide information about the turnover, cash flow situation, and business development on a quarterly basis and once a year the annual report. On Deutsche-mikroinvest investors can request quarterly reports. The categories C16 to C23 and their sub-categories were deductively defined.

C24 describes the fees that have to be paid by the investor to the platform (in % of volume or €). All five sub-categories, except C24S3, were deductively defined. C24S1 means a one-off fee is charged independently whether or not the funding succeeded. No platform applies this kind of fee. C24S2 means a one-off fee is charged if the funding succeeded. Finnest charges 1% but at least 25 €. C24S3 means a one-off fee is charged if the repayment and interests are repaid by the borrower. As in crowdlending, in this case Unternehmerich charges 0.25%. C24S4 means an annual fee is charged. No platform applies this kind of fee. C24S5 means there is no fee for the investor. Kapilendo, Transvendo, Katrim, Conda, and Deutsche-mikroinvest do not charge the investors.

The last categories C25 and C26 were deductively defined. C25 describes whether or not there is a secondary market. C25S1 means there is a secondary market for the investors to sell or buy the investments, while C25S2 means there is no such market. Unternehmerich, Finnest, Conda, and

Deutsche-mikroinvest mentioned that no secondary market exists. Since there was no information available on the other platforms, it can be assumed that no secondary markets exist. C26 describes any other information that can be relevant. The platform Bankless24 merged with Conda and was integrated into the platform of Conda.

Table 18: Profile matrix crowdfunding (platform 1-4)

	Platform number	#01	#02	#03	#04
C1	Legal entity and domain	- UNIC AG - unternehmerich.de	- Kapilendo AG - kapilendo.de	- Transvendo GmbH & Co. KG - transvendo.de	- Mplus SELV AG - katrim.de
C2	Founding date of legal entity	2014	2015	2016	2008
C3	Licence	S3 = No licence	S3 = No licence	S3 = No licence	S3 = No licence
C4	Countries	Germany	Germany	Germany	Germany
C5	Kind of financing instrument	S2 = Subordinated profit-participating loan S3 = Silent partnership	S2 = Subordinated profit-participating loan	S1 = Subordinated loan (two variants: With and without additional exit interest) S2 = Subordinated profit-participating loan	S1 = Subordinated loan
C6	Matching	S1 = Pre-defined economic conditions mechanism	S1 = Pre-defined economic conditions mechanism	S1 = Pre-defined economic conditions mechanism	S1 = Pre-defined economic conditions mechanism
C7	Contractual agreements and fund flows	S1 = Payment service provider with separate account in between (see illustration above)	S1 = Payment service provider with separate account in between (see illustration above)	S1 = Payment service provider with separate account in between (see illustration above)	S2 = No payment service provider with separate account in between (see illustration above)
C8	Funding principle	S1 = All-or-nothing	S1 = All-or-nothing	S1 = All-or-nothing	S2 = Keep-it-all
C9	Selection of funding	S1 = Yes	S1 = Yes	S1 = Yes	S1 = Yes
C10	Party conducting creditworthiness evaluation or business model validation	S3 = Creditworthiness evaluation directly by a third party	S2 = Creditworthiness evaluation by platform	S4 = Validation of business model by platform	0 = Not available
C11	Economic conditions	S1 = Fixed interest rate S2 = Participation in turnover development S3 = Participation in profit development (Rating classes: A+, A, B, C, C-; in general interest between 2.99% and 9.99%; see example shown above)	S1 = Fixed interest rate (based on rating and maturity between 7% and 10%) S2 = Participation in turnover development (additional interest payment depending on turnover development, maximum 25% of volume; see example shown above)	For subordinated loans: S1 = Fixed interest rate (based on rating and maturity between 7% and 10%; additional exit interest not defined in case of subordinated loans with additional exit interest) For subordinated profit-participating loans: S1 = Fixed interest	S1 = Fixed interest rate

Platform number	#01	#02	#03	#04
			rate (1%) S3 = Participation in profit development S4 = Participation in increase in company value	
C12	Financed volume and number of fundings 0 = Not available	S1 = Crowdlending and crowdinvesting 19.2 mn€ in volume S2 = 78 in number	0 = Not available	0 = Not available
C13	Target borrower S1 = SME S3 = Start-up	S1 = SME	S1 = SME S3 = Start-up	S1 = SME
C14	Major requirements S4 = Others (Viable business model without further specifications)	S1 = Solely capital companies S2 = Company minimum age (3 years) S3 = Minimum annual turnover (300 k€)	0 = Not available	S2 = Company minimum age (2 years) S4 = Others (owner or family managed company)
C15	Major required documents 0 = Not available	S1 = Annual reports (for last 3 years) S2 = Financial analysis of current year	S4 = Business plan	0 = Not available
C16	Funding volume S1 = Minimum 50 k€ S2 = Maximum 2,500 k€	S1 = Minimum 100 k€ S2 = Maximum 2,500 k€	S1 = Not available S2 = Maximum 2,500 k€	S1 = Minimum 30 k€ S2 = Not available
C17	Funding Maturity 0 = Not available	S1 = Minimum 36 months S2 = Maximum 60 months	For subordinated loans: S1 = Minimum 36 months S2 = Maximum 60 months For subordinated profit-participating loans: S1 = Minimum 60 months S2 = Maximum 84 months	S1 = Minimum 24 months S2 = Maximum 144 months
C18	Fees to be paid by borrower (in % of volume or €) S1 = One-off fee independent of success of funding: 1% for creditworthiness evaluation S2 = One-off fee if success of funding: 0.5% for project set-up and 0.3% for transaction and escrow S3 = Annual fee: 0.1%	S2 = One-off fee if success of funding (exact amount not specified)	S2 = One-off fee if success of funding: 9.5% S3 = Annual fee: Not defined	0 = Not available
C19	Target investor S1 = Individual investor S2 = Professional investor	S1 = Individual investor S2 = Professional investor	S1 = Individual investor S2 = Professional investor	S1 = Individual investor (no information about professional investors)

Platform number		#01	#02	#03	#04
C20	Investment volume	For individual investors: S1 = Minimum 250 € S2 = Maximum 10,000 € For professional investors: S1 = Minimum 50,000 € S2 = Maximum unlimited	For individual investors: S1 = Minimum 100 € S2 = Maximum 10,000 €	For individual investors: S1 = Minimum 100 € S2 = Maximum 10,000 € For professional investors: Higher volumes possible	S1 = Minimum 250 € S2 = Not available
C21	Voting or participation rights	S2 = No (for subordinated profit-participating loan; for silent partnership it was not available)	S2 = No	S2 = No	S2 = No
C22	Control rights	S1 = Yes (for silent partnership)	S2 = No	0 = Not available	0 = Not available
C23	Information rights	S1 = Yes (for subordinated profit-participating loan; for silent partnership it was not available)	S1 = Yes	S1 = Yes	0 = Not available
C24	Fees to be paid by investor (in % of volume or €)	S3 = One-off fee if fully repayment and payment of interest: (0.25%)	S5 = No fee	S5 = No fee	S5 = No fee
C25	Secondary market	S2 = No	0 = Not available	0 = Not available	0 = Not available
C26	Others	Crowdlending and crowdinvesting	Crowdlending and crowdinvesting	-	-

Source: Own source

Table 19: Profile matrix crowdinvesting (platform 5-7)

Platform number		#05	#06	#07
C1	Legal entity and domain	- Finnest GmbH (Austria) - finnest.com	- CONDA Deutschland Crowdinvesting GmbH - conda.de	- DMI Deutsche Mikroinvest GmbH - deutsche-mikroinvest.de
C2	Founding date of legal entity	2015	2014	2012
C3	Licence	S3 = No licence	S3 = No licence	S2 = Yes, other licence (licence as financial service provider including as investment broker according to section 1 subsection 1a of KWG)
C4	Countries	- Germany - Austria - Switzerland - Slovakia	- Germany - Austria - Switzerland - Poland - Lichtenstein - Slovakia - Slovenia	Germany
C5	Kind of financing instrument	S1 = Subordinated loan	S1 = Subordinated loan S2 = Subordinated profit-	S1 = Subordinated loan S2 = Subordinated profit-

Platform number		#05	#06	#07
			participating loan S4 = Participation right	participating loan S3 = Silent partnership S4 = Participation right
C6	Matching	S2 = Auction-based mechanism S3 = Private placement mechanism	S1 = Pre-defined economic conditions mechanism	S1 = Pre-defined economic conditions mechanism
C7	Contractual agreements and fund flows	S2 = No payment service provider with separate account in between (see illustration above)	S1 = Payment service provider with separate account in between (see illustration above)	S2 = No payment service provider with separate account in between (see illustration above)
C8	Funding principle	S2 = Keep-it-all	S1 = All-or-nothing	S2 = Keep-it-all
C9	Selection of funding	S1 = Yes	S1 = Yes	S1 = Yes
C10	Party conducting creditworthiness evaluation or business model validation	S4 = Validation of business model by platform	S4 = Validation of business model by platform	S4 = Validation of business model by platform
C11	Economic conditions	S1 = Fixed interest rate (interest rate finally defined by borrower) S3 = Participation in profit development (EBITDA margin)	For subordinated loans: S1 = Fixed interest rate For subordinated profit-participating loan: S1 = Fixed interest rate S3 = Participation in profit development S4 = Participation in increase in company value For participation right: S3 = Participation in profit development S4 = Participation in increase in company value (see example shown above)	S1 = Fixed interest rate S3 = Participation in profit development S4 = Participation in increase in company value (in total in general between 4% and 11%)
C12	Financed volume and number of fundings	S1 = 20 mn€ in volume S2 = Not available	S1 = 21 mn€ in volume S2 = 95 in numbers	S1 = 13 mn€ in volume S2 = Not available
C13	Target borrower	S1 = SME	S1 = SME S3 = Start-up (both with local focus)	S1 = SME S3 = Start-up
C14	Major requirements	S2 = Company minimum age (several years with organic growth) S4 = Others (sufficient equity and sustainable EBITDA, stable ownership structure, and adequate management)	S1 = Capital company as legal form (solely capital company)	S1 = Capital or private company as legal form S4 = Others (no criminal record of owner or management)
C15	Major required documents	S1 = Annual report (on demand of investors)	S1 = Annual report (current year and forecast) S3 = Cash flow statement (forecast and current year) S4 = Business plan	0 = Not available
C16	Funding volume	S1 = Not available S2 = Maximum 2,500 k€	S1 = Minimum 50 k€ S2 = Not available	S1 = Minimum 100 k€ S2 = Maximum 2,500 k€

Platform number		#05	#06	#07
C17	Funding Maturity	S1 = Minimum 36 months S2 = Maximum 60 months	For subordinated loans and subordinated profit-participating loan generally: S1 = 60 months S2 = 120 Months For participation rights: Generally, about 120 months; cancellation of contract after 120 months or sale of investment to other investors)	S1 = Minimum 6 months S2 = Maximum 96 months (short-term between 6 and 36 months; generally, between 60 and 96 months)
C18	Fees to be paid by borrower (in % of volume or €)	S1 = One-off fee independent of success of funding: 2.75% or at least 9,500 € for service and support S3 = Annual fee: 950 €	S1 = One-off fee independent of success of funding: 2,000 €, 2,500 € or 3,500 € for set-up of funding, depending on service package S2 = One-off fee if success of funding: 7.5%, 9.5%, or 11.5% depending on service package S3 = Annual fee: 1.5%	S2 = One-off fee if success of funding: In general, between 6.25% and 10.00%
C19	Target investor	S1 = Individual investor	S1 = Individual investor (no information about professional investors)	S1 = Individual investor S2 = Professional investor
C20	Investment volume	S1 = Not available S2 = Maximum 10,000 €	S1 = Minimum 100 € S2 = Maximum 5,000 €	S1 = Minimum 250 € S2 = Maximum 10,000 € (for individual investors, for professional not available)
C21	Voting or participation rights	S2 = No	S2 = No	S2 = No
C22	Control rights	0 = Not available	S2 = No	S1 = Yes (certain control rights can be defined – no further specification)
C23	Information rights	S1 = Yes	S1 = Yes	S1 = Yes
C24	Fees to be paid by investor (in % of volume or €)	S2 = One-off fee if success of funding: The higher value of 1% or 25 €	S5 = No fee	S5 = No fee
C25	Secondary market	S2 = No	S2 = No	S2 = No
C26	Others	-	Merger with bankless24, further business under CONDA	-

Source: Own source

5.2.2 Discussion and conclusion

The objective is to qualitatively appraise in depth the business model of crowdinvesting platforms that provide services to SMEs in Germany. The business model is discussed and appraised along the four interrelated components of a business model and towards the question to which extent crowdinvesting is a substitute for traditional banking services to LMEs. Additionally, it includes the first evaluation of the disruptive innovation threat of crowdinvesting platforms to traditional banks.

Since it is a total population sampling, the results can be generalised, while crowdfunding platform implies platforms that provide services to SMEs in Germany.

The key process of crowdfunding to SMEs in Germany can be divided into five phases as illustrated by figure 39. In contrast to the process described by Beck (2017) and Hagedorn and Pinkwart (2016) as shown in chapter three, this process explicitly includes a matching phase, which should be an essential phase in two-sided marketplace business models.

Figure 39: Key process of crowdfunding business to SMEs in Germany

Source: Own illustration

In the first phase, application and selection phase, the SME makes a funding application to the platform, and the platform selects the funding including the checking of the identification and the eligibility of a funding along the platform's requirements. The selection can include the creditworthiness evaluation or business model validation.

The second phase, after a positive application, is the contracting phase in which the SME and platform define the kind of financing instrument and partly the economic conditions. This can include the calculation of the company value. The financing instruments are subordinated loans, subordinated profit-participating loans, participation rights, and silent partnerships.

The third phase is the matching. Considering the criteria of Taeuscher and Laudien described in chapter two, all crowdfunding platforms are two-sided marketplace business models (2018). The contracts are directly between the investors and SMEs while there are no on-balance sheet transactions of the platforms. Three different matching mechanisms bring investors and SMEs together:

- 1) Pre-defined economic conditions mechanism: The funding is published with defined economic conditions for the public.
- 2) Auction-based mechanism: The funding is published, and the interest rate is defined in an auction.

3) Private placement: There is a private placement with a limited number of investors.

If the matching is successfully completed, then the investors either directly or indirectly provide the funds to the SME. The fourth phase is the holding phase. The investors hold their claims, receive the financial return, and become informed on a regularly basis. The duration between the application and selection phase and the provision of the funds depends on the matching mechanism. It can vary between 30 and 120 days, but it can also be unlimited.

At the end there is the exit in which the SME repays the funds. Whether or not the online process in crowdfunding is simpler than the process in traditional banking with physical meetings depends on the company's subjective perception.

The CVP of a business model helps customers performing a job that needs to be done. Based on crowdfunding platforms, SMEs can issue mezzanine instruments that have similar and dissimilar characteristics to program mezzanine or traditional bank loans.

In crowdfunding the maximum funding volume is 2,500 k€, which can be considered as a lower performance. It can be assumed that larger SMEs partly demand higher funding volumes. The total volume of program mezzanine typically ranges between 175 and 600 mn€ while the average volume of each borrower is 5.9 mn€ (Nohtse, 2012). Relative to the different SME definitions illustrated in chapter two, the minimum turnover requirements of crowdfunding platforms are low. Either there are no requirements mentioned or it is 300 k€. Typically, banks require a minimum turnover in program mezzanine and a high creditworthiness. The minimum turnover is typically 50 mn€ (Grunow & Figgener, 2006). The results of an analysis of 555 company data sets show that the average turnover of companies in program mezzanine is 103 mn€ (Jetter, 2008). The maximum funding volume and the low turnover requirements indicate that crowdfunding platforms focus on smaller SMEs, which is also indicated in the literature. Again, according to Dorfleitner et al., of 85 crowdfunding fundings on four platforms, the average company turnover was 220 k€, the average funding volume was 143 k€, and the average age was three years (2014). However, it has to be considered that three of the four platforms that were analysed by Dorfleitner et al. focus on start-ups. The crowdfunding platforms of this research also have relatively low company age requirements which vary between two and three years. This implies that SMEs on crowdfunding platforms can be relatively young, while traditional banks focus on older companies. In program mezzanine the average company age is 42 years (Jetter, 2008).

The fixed interest rate paid to the investors ranges between 1% and 10%, which is comparable with program mezzanine. Typically, in program mezzanine the total cost of capital ranges between 8% and 16%, where the fixed component ranges between 5% and 10% (Halt et al., 2017; Nohtse, 2012; Staroßom, 2013). The duration is also comparable with program mezzanine. Usually, the standardised contracts of program mezzanine have a maturity of 84 months and a bullet repayment structure (Halt et al., 2017; Nohtse, 2012; Staroßom, 2013).

Regarding the velocity, the duration until the provision of the funds is not as high as in the pre-agreed financing mechanism of crowdlending. However, it might be higher than in program mezzanine. That the platforms have no banking licence, and thus less regulatory requirements which have to be fulfilled, can be negatively or positively perceived by the SMEs. Regarding transparency, certain information was not available on some platforms. The information provided should also be provided by traditional banks.

As described in chapter two, traditional banks can decrease the problems of adverse selection and moral hazard which occur due to the principal-agent (P-A) relation including the information asymmetry. According to Agrawal et al., since in crowdfunding the investors participate in the success of the company, the risk caused by the information asymmetry is higher than that of other forms of crowdfunding (2014). Additionally, the mezzanine instruments are subordinated to debt. Again, the reduction of adverse selection and moral hazard is also relevant for the SMEs. The P-A relation of crowdfunding is illustrated by figure 40. The professional and individual investors are the principals that delegate a decision authority to the SMEs, which are the agents. The platform and partly a separate payment service provider support the P-A relation.

Figure 40: P-A relation in crowdfunding

Source: Own illustration

Two platforms evaluate the creditworthiness and four validate the business model. In both cases the investors receive information to reduce the information asymmetry, while for the latter it should be less than for the former. Additionally, there is no duplicated screening, meaning the platforms' results of the creditworthiness evaluations or business model validations can be reused by all investors. This reduces the problem of systematic underinvestment in due diligence or free-ride behaviour on the investment decisions of others. Therefore, crowdinvesting platforms reduce adverse selection. However, there is the risk that the creditworthiness evaluation or business model validation is not conducted pursuant to generally applicable standards. There is no platform that explicitly mentioned the application of a new creditworthiness evaluation approach that is based on big data or machine learning. They may not apply or not mention it. Partly a third party is involved which might be a quality signal to the investors.

Since the information such as the funding background, maturity, economic conditions, and partly the creditworthiness or business model related information is provided on the platform, they reduce the ex-ante transaction cost. Due to the SPV in between, the number of transactions in program mezzanine should be lower for the borrower than in crowdinvesting. Also relative to traditional bank loans, the number of transactions in crowdinvesting is higher due to the direct contracts between the investors and the borrower. The problems related to moral hazard are reduced because the investors are frequently informed about the business development. However, program mezzanine often includes further covenants (Jetter, 2008). Therefore, the risk caused by moral hazard should be higher in crowdinvesting.

As is crowdlending, the key resources of crowdinvesting platforms should be the network of both the investors and SMEs (especially if they reach a critical mass), the platform as a technical function, and specialised employees especially in marketing and technology related topics.

Regarding the profit formula, the question is what qualitative strategic advantages and disadvantages crowdinvesting platforms have relative to traditional banks. The advantages and disadvantages of crowdlending relative to traditional bank loans are already discussed in previous chapter. In the following, the aspects are relative to program mezzanine. The profit formula advantages and disadvantages are summarised by figure 41. Since in both crowdinvesting and program mezzanine the investors take the credit risk, they are added to the crowdinvesting platforms and traditional banks. However, it has to be considered that these aspects are solely qualitative aspects without considering quantities.

Figure 41: Crowdinvesting – profit formula advantages and disadvantages

	Crowdinvesting platforms / investors		Traditional banks / Program investors	
	Advantages	Disadvantages	Advantages	Disadvantages
Revenue structure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Potential increasing return to scale and more scalable without physical limitations ▪ Partly annual fee income 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Larger volumes for fee base 	
Fixed costs structure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ No branch personnel and building related costs 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Economies of scale and scope effects ▪ Positive experience curve effects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Regulatory related costs
Credit risk costs structure			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Soft information (information asymmetry) ▪ Stricter covenants (moral hazard) 	

Source: Own illustration

The revenues are fee-based in both crowdinvesting and program mezzanine. The one-off fee in crowdinvesting ranges between 1.8% and 11.5%. In program mezzanine it typically ranges between 2% and 5% (Keuper & Sikora, 2011). Both depend on new businesses, while crowdinvesting platforms partly charge an annual fee that ranges between 0.1% and 1.5%. Since traditional banks solely advise and sell in program mezzanine while the administration of the SPV is conducted by a separate fund management, this can be an advantage for the crowdinvesting platforms if there is a

positive profit margin meaning the annual fee covers its related unit costs. In contrast, in program mezzanine the volumes are higher which finally means higher revenues. Based on the fee models of crowdfunding platforms, it can be derived that they subsidise the investor side. Four platforms do not charge the investors, while one charges a fee of 1% if the funding succeeded, and one charges 0.25% if the funds are fully repaid by the SME. The latter should increase the incentive of the platform to decrease the adverse selection and moral hazard related problems. A possible monetisation of information is not taken into consideration.

Since crowdfunding platforms do not have branches, they can have a fixed cost structure advantage in terms of personnel and building related costs. In contrast, traditional banks are larger and provide different services, and thus they should have economies of scale and scope advantages. For example, there is one prospectus for each program that includes more companies, which can reduce the costs of unit. Of seven platforms, two platforms also provide their services abroad. This means they can increase their economies of scale effects. Additionally, since traditional banks should be longer established in the market, they should have positive experience curve effects. If one platform reaches a critical mass, it can take advantages of positive network effects which can cause an increasing return to scale, which again can lead to a winner-takes-it-all result. The business of crowdfunding is more scalable without physical limitations. However, there can also be negative one-sided and cross-sided network effects. Traditional banks have a banking licence, and thus higher regulatory related costs. However, for one platform there might also be some regulatory related costs due to its licence as investment broker. Regarding credit risk costs, traditional banks can take advantage of soft information gained over time through a relationship. Furthermore, covenants in program mezzanine can reduce the costs caused by moral hazard.

In a first conclusion, there are indications that crowdfunding to SMEs in Germany can be a disruptive innovation threat for traditional banks. The relatively low turnover and company age requirements and the limited loan volume indicate that crowdfunding platforms focus on smaller and younger SMEs. Since this kind of customers are not mainly targeted by traditional banks as already described, they can be considered as low-end or non-customers. Although the interest rates and fees might be high relative to traditional bank loans, they might not be high for low-end and non-customers. Again, disruptive innovation is against all incumbents (Christensen & Raynor, 2003). It could be a disruption against both program mezzanine and traditional bank loans. Since crowdfunding is more similar to program mezzanine than to traditional bank loans, the disruptive threat might be higher regarding traditional bank loans because it is not considered as threat. Relative to traditional bank loans and program mezzanine, the limited volume and the higher transaction costs can be considered as a lower performance. Relative to traditional bank loans, the

usage of mezzanine instruments partly including the participation in the turnover, profit or in an increase of the company value can be considered as lower performance, which might be an obstacle for LMEs to substitute traditional bank loans by crowdfunding.

5.3 Business model of factoring platforms that provide services to SMEs

5.3.1 Description of results

Nine factoring platforms were analysed. As described in chapter four, the source of the content was the web-presence of the respective platform, while only for the founding date online-handelsregister.de was used; for checking of whether or not the platform has a financing related licence, the search function on portal.mvp.bafin.de of the BaFin was used. C1 to C8 is related to the platform, C9 to C12 to the borrower, C13 and C14 to the investor, and C15 is related to overall topics without a specific defined content.

The results are summarised in two profile matrices which are illustrated in table 20 and 21. C1 relates to formal aspects by describing the name of the platform's legal entity and starting domain:

- #01 Flex Financial Solutions GmbH with the starting domain flexpayment.de.
- #02 Elbe-Factoring GmbH with the starting domain rechnung48.de.
- #03 Decimo GmbH with the starting domain decimo.de.
- #04 Billie GmbH with the starting domain billie.io.
- #05 Pagido UG with the starting domain pagido.de.
- #06 Finiata GmbH with the starting domain bezahlt.de.
- #07 Fundflow GmbH with the starting domain fundflow.de.
- #08 TrustBills Marketplace GmbH with the starting domain trustbills.de.
- #09 Atevis AG with the starting domain factoringbörse.de.

C2 describes the founding date of the legal entity which varies between 1998 and 2017. The details are illustrated in the profile matrix.

C3 describes whether or not the platform has a licence. C3S1 means the platform has a factoring or other financing related licence in Germany, while C3S2 means it has no licence. Rechnung48, Decimo, and Billie have a factoring licence from the BaFin, while all other platforms do not have a licence.

C4 describes the countries in which the platform provides its services. Factoringbörse provides its services in Germany, Austria, and Switzerland and Trustbills mentioned international presence but not specified countries, while all others provide their services only in Germany. C1 to C4 and their sub-categories were deductively defined.

C5 describes the matching between the investors and borrowers or the financing mechanism. This includes the contractual agreements and fund flows between the parties involved. C5S1 was deductively defined and means that after the registration and uploading of an account receivable by the borrower, the investors can bid in an auction to buy the account receivable. Before the investors can invest, the platform checks the eligibility of the borrower and account receivable. This matching is defined as auction-based mechanism, which is applied on Trustbills and Factoringbörse. The characteristics of Trustbills are as follows: The minimum price is defined by the borrower; the auction is an open vickrey auction that means the investor with the highest offer wins but the price paid is the second-highest offer; the duration of the auction is one, three, or seven days; the investors bid in 50 € increments; the registration takes between 10 and 24 days. The contractual agreements and fund flows of Trustbills are illustrated by figure 42. Since Trustbills offers both notification and non-notification factoring, there are two variants. The borrower (company) has a purchase agreement with its customer. Furthermore, the borrower and the investors have a user contract with Trustbills, which can be agreed on via the registration on the platform. The upload of the account receivable to the platform can also be through an enterprise resource planning (ERP) interface. In case an auction is successfully finished, Trustbills arranges a factoring contract between the investor and borrower. Both need a bank account at a partner bank on which Trustbills has an authority to access. After the agreement of the factoring contract, Trustbills initiates the fund transfer from the investor to the borrower. In case of notification factoring, the borrower's customer transfers the funds of the account receivable to the investor.

Figure 42: Contractual agreements and fund flows of Trustbills (notification)

Source: Own illustration

In case of non-notification factoring, the borrower's customer transfers the funds of the account receivable to the borrower. Then, Trustbills arranges the transfer of the funds to the investors. The contractual agreements and fund flows are illustrated by figure 43.

Figure 43: Contractual agreements and fund flows of Trustbills (non-notification)

Source: Own illustration

Since Factoringbörse also provides notification and non-notification factoring, the contractual agreements and fund flows illustrated above are also applicable for Factoringbörse. However, there is no requirement to have a bank account at a partner bank on which the platform has access. Additionally, on Factoringbörse the investors provide offers, and the borrower finally decides which offer wins.

C5S2 was inductively defined and it means that for the financing of the account receivable there is no separate investor involved. After the registration and upload of the account receivable by the borrower, the platform provides a decision whether or not to finance the account receivable. After a positive decision, the advance payment is 100% or less than 100% reduced by the fee. This matching is defined as platform decision mechanism, which is applied on Flexpayment, Rechnung48, Decimo, Billie, and Bezahlt. On Rechnung48, Decimo, and Billie the advance payment is generally 100% reduced by the fee, while on Flexpayment and Bezahlt it is between 80% and 90% reduced by the fee. Since there are differences between the platforms especially due to notification and non-notification characteristics and the amount of the advance payments, the contractual agreements and fund flows are illustrated in the following. The contractual agreements and fund flows of Rechnung48 are illustrated by figure 44. The borrower has a purchase agreement with its customer. Furthermore, the borrower has a user contract with the platform, which can be agreed on via the registration on the platform. After the platform decided to finance the account receivable, the platform and the borrower agree a factoring contract. The platform transfers the funds of the advance payment, i.e. 100% of the volume reduced by the fee, to the borrower typically within one business day. Since it is notification factoring, the borrower's customer transfers the funds of the account receivable to the platform.

Figure 44: Contractual agreements and fund flows of Rechnung48

Source: Own illustration

The example of Rechnung48 is also applicable for Decimo. On Billie it is non-notification factoring that means that the borrower's customer transfers the funds of the account receivable to the borrower. Afterwards, the borrower transfers the funds to the platform. On Billie the upload of the account receivable is also possible through an application programming interface (API). Based on APIs, different programs from different devices like computers and mobile devices can

communicate to each other (Brown, Fishenden, & Thompson, 2014; Kumaresan, Liberona, & Gnanamurthy, 2017). The funds transfer of the advance payment from Billie to the borrower is typically within two business days. The example of Billie is illustrated by figure 45.

Figure 45: Contractual agreements and fund flows of Billie

Source: Own illustration

On Flexpayment and Bezahlt the advance payment is between 80% and 90% reduced by the fee. The residual volume is paid after the borrower's customer paid the account receivable. In order to show the contractual agreements and the fund flows, the example of Flexpayment is illustrated by figure 46. The difference to Rechnung48 is as follows: Since it is notification factoring, the borrower's customer transfers the funds of the account receivable to the platform. Finally, the platform transfers the residual payment to the borrower. On Flexpayment the advance payment is transferred 15 minutes after the decision. The residual volume is paid when the borrower's customer paid the account receivable and at latest 120 days after maturity.

Figure 46: Contractual agreements and fund flows of Flexpayment

Source: Own illustration

Since Bezahlt provides non-notification factoring via a clearing account on the borrower's name at a partner bank, the fund flows are different to Flexpayment. The difference is that the borrower's customer transfers the funds of the account receivable to a clearing account that is opened on the borrower's name at a partner bank of the platform. Then, from the clearing account the residual payments for the borrower and for the platform (volume of account receivable minus residual payment for borrower) are transferred. The fund transfer of the advance payment from the platform to the borrower is typically within one business day. The contractual agreements and fund flows of Bezahlt are illustrated by figure 47.

Figure 47: Contractual agreements and fund flows of Bezahlt

Source: Own illustration

C5S3 was inductively defined and means that the platform acts as intermediary between the borrower and a separate factoring provider. After the registration and upload of the account receivable by the borrower, the platform commissions a factoring contract with a factoring provider on the borrower's behalf. The advance payment is 100% reduced by the fee. This matching is defined as intermediary mechanism, which is applied on Pagido. In this case the factoring provider is Grenkefactoring GmbH. The contractual agreements and the fund flows of Pagido are illustrated by figure 48. The borrower has a purchase agreement with its customer. Furthermore, the borrower has a user contract with the platform that includes that the borrower commissions Pagido to conclude a factoring contract with the factoring provider on the borrower's behalf, which can be agreed on via the registration on the platform. Additionally, Pagido acts as a trade representative according to section 84 of the German commercial law (HGB) for the factoring provider. Thus, there is a respective contract between them. The factoring contract is between the borrower and the factoring provider. The factoring provider transfers the funds of the advance payment, i.e. 100% of

the volume reduced by the fee, to the borrower typically within two business days. Since it is notification factoring, finally the borrower's customer transfers the funds of the account receivable to the factoring provider. The technical communication with Pagido is also possible through an API.

Figure 48: Contractual agreements and fund flows of Pagido

Source: Own illustration

C5S4 was inductively defined and means that the platform provides the information whether or not to finance the account receivable based on an agreement with institutional investors that provide the funds. Additionally, there is bank involved. After a positive decision, the advance payment is 100% reduced by the fee. This matching is defined as pre-agreed financing mechanism, which is applied on Fundflow. The borrower has a user contract with the platform, which can be agreed on via the registration on the platform. Fundflow provides the information whether or not to finance the account receivable based on an agreement with institutional investors that provide the funds. The borrower agrees a factoring contract with Wirecard Bank AG to sell the account receivable. Fundflow agrees a factoring contract with Wirecard Bank AG to buy the account receivable. The investors agree factoring contracts with Fundflow to partially buy the account receivable. The investors transfer the advance payment (total volume of account receivable reduced by fee) to a separate account to Wirecard Bank AG. Wirecard Bank AG transfers the advance payment (total volume of account receivable reduced by fee) to the borrower typically within one business day. Since it is notification factoring, the borrower's customer transfers the funds of the account receivable to Wirecard Bank AG, which again transfers the funds to the investors. The contractual agreements and fund flows of Fundflow are illustrated by figure 49.

Figure 49: Contractual agreements and fund flows of Fundflow

Source: Own illustration

C6 describes the factoring characteristics. Seven sub-categories were defined. C6S1 means that individual accounts receivable, while C6S2 means that total portfolios of accounts receivable can be financed. On all platforms, individual accounts receivable can be financed, while on Trustbills and Factoringbörse also total portfolios. C6S3 means it is notification, while C6S4 means it is non-notification factoring. Flexpayment, Rechnung48, Decimo, Pagido, and Fundflow solely provide notification factoring, while Billie and Bezahlt only provide non-notification factoring. On Trustbills and Factoringbörse both are possible. C6S5 means it is recourse, while C6S6 means it is non-recourse factoring. Billie and Bezahlt solely provide recourse factoring, while Flexpayment, Rechnung48, Pagido, Fundflow, Trustbills, and Factoringbörse solely provide non-recourse factoring. Decimo generally provides non-recourse factoring, while recourse factoring is possible on demand. C6S7 means that the platform provides dunning services. Flexpayment, Rechnung48, Decimo, Pagido, and Trustbills provide dunning service.

C7 describes whether or not there is a creditworthiness evaluation, and if yes, which party conducts the evaluation. C7S1 means there is no creditworthiness evaluation. On Trustbills the investors can evaluate the risk. C7S2 means there is a creditworthiness evaluation which is conducted by the platform, while input of a third party like a credit investigation company might be possible. This approach is applied on Flexpayment, Billie, Bezahlt, and Fundflow. C7S3 means there is a creditworthiness evaluation which is conducted directly by a third party like a credit investigation company. This approach is applied on Rechnung48, Decimo, and Pagido.

C8 describes the volume already financed and the number of fundings on the platform. C8S1 means the volume, while C8S2 means the number of factoring fundings. On Rechnung48 the volume is about 150 mn€ and the number of fundings 70 k per annum.

C9 describes the target borrower of the platform. There is no explicit definition required. In case the platform mentioned a certain target group, the sub-category was applied. However, some characteristics are described in C10. C9S1 means SME, C9S2 means freelancer, C9S3 means start-up, and C9S4 means large company. Flexpayment, Rechnung48, Decimo, Billie, Pagido, Bezahlt, and Fundflow focus on SMEs and freelancer. Factoringbörse exclusively focuses on SMEs, while Trustbills focuses on SMEs and large companies. The categories C6 to C9 were deductively defined.

C10 describes the major requirements that have to be fulfilled by the borrower. The first two sub-categories were deductively, while the others were inductively defined. C10S1 means the company must have a minimum annual turnover. Billie and Pagido require at least 50 k€, and Factoringbörse requires 100 k€ with the respective customer. C10S2 means that the company must fulfil a certain level of age (required years). Billie requires one year and Flexpayment and Trustbills three years. C10S3 means there is a maximum period of days between the provision of the services to the borrower's customer and the request for factoring. Flexpayment, Rechnung48, and Billie require less than 30 and Decimo less than 45 days. C10S4 means the borrower's customer must not be a consumer, and thus only business-to-business accounts receivable are accepted. Flexpayment, Rechnung48, Billie, Pagido, Trustbills, and Factoringbörse apply this requirement. C10S5 describes the procedure of the borrower's authentication. Flexpayment and Decimo require at the beginning an access to the borrower's online bank account in order to authenticate the borrower. Companies with a factoring licence from the BaFin according to section 1 subsection 1a sentence 2 number 9 of the German Banking Act (KWG) are also under the scope of the anti-money laundering act according to section 2 subsection 1 number 2 which also implies the identification and verification of the borrower. The online bank account requires a previous authentication by the bank. Banks perform their know-your-customer (KYC) identification and verification requirements when a customer opens an account and provides the identity documents such as identity card and company registration (Arner et al., 2019). The borrower fills in their bank account access data which is communicated via a third party (in this case it is FinTecSystems GmbH). According to the platform, based on this transaction, the bank account is read out once, but the data is not saved by the platform or FinTecSystems GmbH. A later read out would need a new input of the borrower. Flexpayment regularly requests the access for frequent validations. Billie also requires an access to the borrower's online bank account. This access is also used as input to evaluate the creditworthiness. On Rechnung48 video identification or Post identification is used for the

authentication. On Pagido the access to the borrower's online bank account or Post identification is used. On Bezahlt and Fundflow video identification is used. Trustbills requires a bank account at a partner bank with an authority to access. C10S6 means any further requirements. Flexpayment requires that the borrower' customer respectively its company is older than three years.

C11 describes the funding volume. C11S1 means the minimum, while C11S2 means the maximum volume in k€. On Rechnung48 and Decimo there is no minimum threshold and no maximum limit for the volume of the account receivable. On Flexpayment the minimum volume is 0.05 k€ and the maximum 30 k€, but based on individual agreements, the volume can be higher. On Billie the minimum volume is 0.2 k€ and the maximum typically 50 k€, but based on individual agreements, it can be 250 k€. On Trustbills the minimum is 15 k€.

C12 describes the fees that have to be paid by the borrower to the platform (in % of volume or €). C12S1 means a one-off fee is charged independently whether or not the funding succeeded. Trustbills charges 500 € for the registration, 0.1% (minimum 100 €) for uploading the account receivable and usage of the platform, and 0.02% (minimum 20 €) in case the borrower's customer approves a declaratory acknowledgment of its liability. Based on a declaratory acknowledgment approval, the existing obligation is undisputable. It removes nullity and makes the contract effective (Staab & Staab, 2014). C12S2 means a one-off fee is charged if the funding succeeded. Except Trustbills all platforms charge a one-off fee in case of funding. Flexpayment charges 3.95% but minimum 25 €. In case of regular usage, the fee can be reduced by 50%. Rechnung48 charges 3.97%. On Decimo, Billie, Pagido, and Bezahlt the fee depends on the creditworthiness and terms of payment. On Decimo it is 0.5%, on Pagido it is 2.9%, and on Billie it is 0.7% at minimum (for the latter typically between 1% and 3%). On Bezahlt the fee is 2.49% for the first usage and afterwards 2.49% at minimum.

C13 describes the kind of investors who can invest in accounts receivable. C13S1 means individual investors, while C13S2 means professional investors. The latter can include institutional investors. This is only relevant for the auction-based matching mechanism. Trustbills focuses on professional investors or more precisely only on institutional investors like banks and other institutional investors. Factoringbörse focuses also only on professional investors or more precisely on institutional investors with a licence from the BaFin.

C14 describes the fees that have to be paid by the investor to the platform (in % of volume or €). This is only relevant for the auction-based matching mechanism. C14S1 means a one-off fee is charged independently of whether or not the funding succeeded. Trustbills charges 500 € for

registration. C14S2 means a one-off fee is charged only if the funding succeeded. Trustbills also requires a one-off fee only in case of funding that depends on the residual term. In case of a residual term between 11 and 30 days the fee is 0.05%, between 31 and 60 days the fee is 0.1%, and in case of more than 60 days the fee is 0.15%.

C15 describes any other relevant topic. The two major shareholders of Trustbills are DZ Bank AG and Deutsche Bank AG.

Table 20: Profile matrix factoring platforms (platform 1-5)

	Platform number	#01	#02	#03	#04	#05
C1	Legal entity and domain	- FLEX Financial Solutions GmbH - flexpayment.de	- Elbe-Factoring GmbH - rechnung48.de	- Decimo GmbH - decimo.de	- Billie GmbH - billie.io	- Pagido UG - pagido.de
C2	Founding date of legal entity	2011	1998	2012	2016	2014
C3	Licence	S2 = No licence	S1 = Yes (BaFin licence according to section 1 subsection 1a sentence 2 number 9 KWG (factoring))	S1 = Yes (BaFin licence according to section 1 subsection 1a sentence 2 number 9 KWG (factoring))	S1 = Yes (BaFin licence according to section 1 subsection 1a sentence 2 number 9 KWG (factoring))	S2 = No licence
C4	Countries	Germany	Germany	Germany	Germany	Germany
C5	Matching/ financing	S2 = Platform decision mechanism	S2 = Platform decision mechanism	S2 = Platform decision mechanism	S2 = Platform decision mechanism	S3 = Intermediary mechanism
C6	Factoring characteristics	S1 = Individual account receivable S3 = Notification S6 = Non-recourse S7 = Dunning service included	S1 = Individual account receivable S3 = Notification S6 = Non-recourse S7 = Dunning service included	S1 = Individual account receivable S3 = Notification S5 = Recourse (on demand in certain cases) S6 = Non-recourse S7 = Dunning service included	S1 = Individual account receivable S4 = Non-notification S5 = Recourse	S1 = Individual account receivable S3 = Notification S6 = Non-recourse S7 = Dunning service included
C7	Party conducting creditworthiness evaluation	S2 = Evaluation by platform (input of a third party might be possible)	S3 = Evaluation by a third party like credit investigation company	S3 = Evaluation by a third party like credit investigation company	S2 = Evaluation by platform (input of a third party might be possible)	S3 = Evaluation by a third party like credit investigation company
C8	Financed volume and number of fundings	0 = Not available	S1 = 150 mn€ in volume p.a. S2 = 70 k fundings p.a.	0 = Not available	0 = Not available	0 = Not available
C9	Target borrower	S1 = SME S2 = Freelancer	S1 = SME S2 = Freelancer	S1 = SME S2 = Freelancer	S1 = SME S2 = Freelancer	S1 = SME S2 = Freelancer

Platform number		#01	#02	#03	#04	#05
C10	Major requirements	S3 = Maximum period of days between provision of services and request for factoring (30 days) S4 = Customer of borrower is not a consumer S5 = For borrower's authentication: Once access to online banking S6 = Others (customer of borrower is older than 3 years)	S3 = Maximum period of days between provision of services and request for factoring (30 days) S4 = Customer of borrower is not a consumer S5 = For borrower's authentication: Post or video identification for authentication	S3 = Maximum period of days between provision of services and request for factoring (45 days) S5 = For borrower's authentication: Once access to online banking	S1 = Minimum annual turnover (50 k€) S2 = Company minimum age (1 year) S3 = Maximum period of days between provision of services and request for factoring (30 days) S4 = Customer of borrower is not a consumer S5 = For borrower's authentication: Once access to online banking	S1 = Minimum annual turnover (50 k€) S4 = Customer of borrower is not a consumer S5 = For borrower's authentication: Once access to online banking
C11	Funding volume	S1 = Minimum 0.05 k€ S2 = Maximum 30 k€ or more by individual agreement	S1 = Minimum no threshold S2 = Maximum unlimited	S1 = Minimum no threshold S2 = Maximum unlimited	S1 = Minimum 0.2 k€ S2 = Maximum 50 k€ (on agreement 250 k€)	0 = Not available
C12	Fees to be paid by borrower (in % of volume or €)	S2 = One-off fee if funding: Maximum 3.95%, minimum 25 €; in case of regular usage, 50% reduction	S2 = One-off fee if funding: 3.97%	S2 = One-off fee if funding: Depending on creditworthiness and terms of payment (minimum 0.5%)	S2 = One-off fee if funding: Depending on creditworthiness and terms of payment (minimum 0.7%; in general, between 1% and 3%)	S2 = One-off fee if funding: Depending on creditworthiness and terms of payment (minimum 2.9%)
C13	Target investor	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable
C14	Fees to be paid by investor (in % of volume or €)	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable
C15	Others	-	-	-	-	-

Source: Own source

Table 21: Profile matrix factoring platforms (platform 6-9)

Platform number		#06	#07	#08	#09
C1	Legal entity and domain	- Finiata GmbH - bezahlt.de	- Fundflow GmbH - fundflow.de	- TrustBills Marketplace GmbH - trustbills.de	- Atevis AG - factoringbörse.de
C2	Founding date of legal entity	2016	2016	2017	2000
C3	Licence	S2 = No licence	S2 = No licence	S2 = No licence	S2 = No licence
C4	Countries	Germany	Germany	- Germany - International (not further specified)	- Germany - Austria - Switzerland

	Platform number	#06	#07	#08	#09
C5	Matching/financing	S2 = Platform decision mechanism	S4 = Pre-agreed financing mechanism	S1 = Auction-based mechanism	S1 = Auction-based mechanism
C6	Factoring characteristics	S1 = Individual account receivable S4 = Non-notification (clearing bank account at partner bank on name of borrower) S5 = Recourse	S1 = Individual account receivable S3 = Notification S6 = Non-recourse	S1 = Individual account receivable S2 = Portfolio of accounts receivable S3 = Notification S4 = Non-notification S6 = Non-recourse S7 = Dunning service included	S1 = Individual account receivable S2 = Portfolio of accounts receivable S3 = Notification S4 = Non-notification S6 = Non-recourse
C7	Party conducting creditworthiness evaluation	S2 = Evaluation by platform (input of a third party might be possible)	S2 = Evaluation by platform (input of a third party might be possible)	S1 = No Evaluation (to be conducted by investors)	0 = Not available
C8	Financed volume and number of fundings	0 = Not available	0 = Not available	0 = Not available	0 = Not available
C9	Target borrower	S1 = SME S2 = Freelancer	S1 = SME S2 = Freelancer	S1 = SME S4 = Large company S2 = Company minimum age (3 years) S4 = Customer of borrower is not a consumer S5 = For borrower's authentication: Bank account at a partner bank with access	S1 = SME
C10	Major requirements	S5 = For borrower's authentication: Video identification	S5 = For borrower's authentication: Video identification	S5 = For borrower's authentication: Bank account at a partner bank with access	S1 = Minimum annual turnover (100 k€ with customer p.a.) S4 = Customer of borrower is not a consumer S5 = For borrower's authentication: Not available
C11	Funding volume	0 = Not available	0 = Not available	S1 = Minimum 15 k€ S2 = Not available	0 = Not available
C12	Fees to be paid by borrower (in % of volume or €)	S2 = One-off fee if funding: Depending on creditworthiness and terms of payment (first usage 2.49%; afterwards minimum 2.49%)	0 = Not available	S1 = One-off fee independent of success of funding: 500 € for registration S1 = One-off fee independent of success of funding: 0.1% (minimum 100 €) for uploading and usage of auction and 0.02% (minimum 20 €) in addition if the borrower's customer approves a declaratory acknowledgment of its liability	0 = Not available
C13	Target investor	Not applicable	Not applicable	S2 = Professional investor (only banks and other institutional investors)	S2 = Professional investor (investors are only banks or factoring companies with licence)

Platform number	#06	#07	#08	#09	
C14	Fees to be paid by investor (in % of volume or €)	Not applicable	Not applicable	S1 = One-off fee independent of success of funding: 500 € for registration S2 = One-off fee if funding: Depending on residual term: 11-30 days: 0.05%, 31-60 days: 0.1%, more than 60 days: 0.15%	0 = Not available
C15	Others	-	-	Two major shareholders are DZ Bank AG and Deutsche Bank AG	-

Source: Own source

5.3.2 Discussion and conclusion

The objective is to qualitatively appraise in depth the business model of factoring platforms that provide services to SMEs in Germany. The business model is discussed and appraised along the four interrelated components of a business model and towards the question to which extent factoring platforms are a substitute for traditional banking services to SMEs. Additionally, it includes the first evaluation of the disruptive innovation threat of factoring platforms to traditional banks. Since it is a total population sampling, the results can be generalised, while factoring platform implies platforms that provide services to SMEs in Germany.

The key process of factoring on platforms can be divided into four phases as illustrated by figure 50. In the first phase, application and selection, the SME makes an application to the platform and uploads its account receivable to the platform. The platform selects the requests and, except in the auction-based matching mechanism, evaluates the creditworthiness.

Figure 50: Key process of factoring on platforms for SMEs in Germany

Source: Own illustration

The second phase, after a positive selection, is the matching or financing. Considering the criteria of Tauscher and Laudien (2018) that are described in chapter two, only Trustbills and Factoringbörse are two-sided marketplace business models. On Flexpayment, Rechnung48, Decimo, Billie, and Bezahlt there is no matching with investors. On Pagido there is solely one investor who provides factoring services and there is no direct interaction. On Fundflow there is also no direct interaction. In contrast to the literature that shows that the price of the account receivable can be either defined by the platform or by an auction mechanism (Dorfleitner, Rad, & Weber, 2017), the results of this research show four matching or financing mechanisms:

- 1) Auction-based mechanism: The auction mechanism in which after the upload of the account receivable by the borrower, the investors can bid in an auction to buy the account receivable.
- 2) Platform decision mechanism: After the upload of the account receivable by the borrower, the platform provides a decision whether or not to finance the account receivable – there is no separate investor involved.
- 3) Intermediary mechanism: The platform acts as intermediary between the borrower and a separate factoring provider.
- 4) Pre-agreed financing mechanism: The platform provides the information whether or not to finance the account receivable based on an agreement with institutional investors.

The third phase is the advance payment. After a positive decision or positive auction, the advance payment is transferred to the borrower. It can be 100% or less than 100% reduced by the fee. The duration between a positive decision or starting of an auction until the advance payment varies between 15 minutes and 24 days depending on the matching or financing mechanism.

The fourth phase is the settlement, which means the SME's customer pays the account receivable. In case of notification factoring, the customer directly transfers the funds to the platform or investor, otherwise to the SME. Whether or not the online process in factoring is simpler than the process in traditional banking with physical meetings depends on the company's subjective perception.

The CVP of a business model helps customers performing a job that needs to be done. The results of the documentary research show that SMEs can finance their accounts receivable through factoring platforms that have similar and dissimilar characteristics to traditional factoring.

Relative to the different SME definitions illustrated in chapter two, the minimum turnover requirements on factoring platforms are low. Either there are no requirements mentioned or if they are mentioned, they vary between 50 k€ in total and 100 k€ with the customer. This confirms the literature result which indicates that factoring platforms have no or lower turnover requirements. In contrast, the most banks require a minimum annual turnover between 0.5 and 5 mn€ of the borrower because otherwise the fixed cost components like monitoring the creditworthiness and site visits would be too high relative to the turnover (Harms, 2010). Additionally, traditional factoring is suitable for companies with a high creditworthiness and a diversified customer portfolio (Harms, 2010; Schulz, 2010). The company minimum age requirements on factoring platforms vary between one and three years. This means the SMEs can be relatively young. Young companies usually have a less diversified customer portfolio. Additionally, traditional banks provide the sale of total portfolios of accounts receivable, while factoring platforms focus on individual accounts receivable – except in the auction-based mechanism. Larger SMEs have probably more accounts receivable to sell. From the perspective of larger SMEs, this could be considered as a lower performance relative to traditional banking even though it can be partly uploaded by an API or integration to an ERP system. In contrast, for smaller SMEs this might be a relative advantage in terms of flexibility and technical requirements. The former means that the SME can flexibly decide whether or not to finance an account receivable, and the latter means that except an internet browser no additional software is required. The aspects mentioned indicate that currently factoring platforms focus on smaller and younger SMEs. In Germany, traditional factoring is typically used by larger SMEs because small companies often do not meet the minimum turnover requirements and large companies often have better financing conditions (Reichling et al., 2005).

The one-off fee that is charged if the funding of the account receivable is succeeded is between 0.50% and 3.97%, which is comparable with traditional factoring. Typically, the total fee for factoring range between 1% and 5% of the volume (Schulz, 2010). The risk costs range typically between 0.2% and 1.5%, and the service fee depends on the kind of service and typically ranges between 0.5% and 2.5% of the volume (Reichling et al., 2005). Relative to the total costs of crowdlending or traditional bank loans, the fees are high. For example, a factoring fee of 3% for an account receivable that has a term of payment of 60 days is comparable with an annual interest rate of about 18%.

As described in chapter two, traditional factoring can provide three following functions: Financing, credit insurance, and service function. On factoring platforms there is a higher flexibility in terms of what kind of factoring the SME wants to take without a general contract that has to be agreed on. The SME can select between notification and non-notification, recourse and non-recourse

factoring, and whether it wants to include a dunning service. In contrast, according to Staroßom, the contract of traditional factoring typically includes an ongoing sale of accounts receivable to the bank that usually obliges the borrower to provide offers to the bank to buy the accounts receivable (2013). Furthermore, it can be a relative advantage that the advance payment is partly 100% reduced by the fee. As described in chapter two, traditional factoring mostly includes a lower advance payment.

Regarding velocity, some platforms transfer the funds of the advance payment to the borrower between 15 minutes and 24 hours after a positive decision. This can also be a relative advantage. The fact that six platforms have no banking licence and consequently less regulatory requirements can be negatively or positively perceived by the SMEs. Regarding transparency, certain information was not available on some platforms. The information provided should also be provided by traditional banks.

As described in chapter two, traditional banks reduce the transaction costs and adverse selection. Since traditional banks can have soft information through relationship banking, there might be a relative advantage in terms of reducing the information asymmetry, which is especially more relevant for non-recourse factoring. There is no platform that explicitly mentioned the application of a new creditworthiness evaluation approach that is based on big data or machine learning. They may not apply or not mention it. The transaction costs should be lower in traditional factoring because it consists of the financing of total portfolios of accounts receivable. The platforms which offer an auction-based matching mechanism also provide the financing of total portfolios of accounts receivable. However, the auctions should cause higher transaction costs than a general agreement with a traditional bank that is agreed on once.

The key resources of factoring platforms should be the network of both the investors (for the auction-based matching mechanism especially if they reach a critical mass) and the SMEs, the platform as technical function, and specialised employees especially in marketing and technology related topics.

Regarding the profit formula, the question is what qualitative strategic advantages and disadvantages factoring platforms have relative to traditional banks. The profit formula advantages and disadvantages are summarised by figure 51. Since on factoring platforms separate investors partly take the credit risk, they are added to the factoring platform. However, it has to be considered that these aspects are only qualitative aspects without considering quantities.

Figure 51: Factoring platforms – profit formula advantages and disadvantages

	Factoring platforms / investors		Traditional banks	
	Advantages	Disadvantages	Advantages	Disadvantages
Revenue structure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Partly potential increasing return to scale and more scalable without physical limitations Partly account receivable related fee income from investors 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Higher steady income due to obligation to sell account receivable 	
Fixed costs structure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No branch personnel and building related costs 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Economies of scale and scope effects Positive experience curve effects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regulatory related costs
Credit risk costs structure			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Soft information (information asymmetry) 	

Source: Own illustration

There should be no difference in the revenue structure because both charge a one-off fee. However, the contract of traditional factoring usually includes that the company is obliged to provide an offer to the bank to buy defined accounts receivable, which can increase a steady income. In contrast, in case of a two-sided marketplace business model, the factoring platform can have an account receivable related fee income from investors and, if one platform reaches a critical mass, it can take advantages in terms of an increasing return to scale, which can lead to a winner-takes-it-all result. However, there can also be negative one-sided and cross-sided network effects. The business of factoring platforms is more scalable without physical limitations. A possible monetisation of information is not taken into consideration.

Since factoring platforms do not have branches, they can have a cost structure advantage relative to traditional banks in terms of personal and building related costs. Additionally, traditional banks have higher regulatory related costs due to their licences. At least relative to the six platforms that have no licence from the BaFin. In contrast, traditional banks should have higher economies of scale and scope effects. For example, traditional factoring is based on the financing of total portfolios of accounts receivable, which decreases the costs per unit. Additionally, since traditional banks should be longer established in the market, they should have positive experience curve effects. Furthermore, traditional banks can have a credit risk cost structure advantage due to the reduction of the information asymmetry based on soft information.

In a first conclusion, there are indications that factoring platforms that provide services to SMEs in Germany can be a disruptive innovation threat for traditional banks. The relatively low turnover and company age requirements and the focus mainly on individual accounts receivable indicate that factoring platforms focus on smaller and younger SMEs. Since this kind of customers are not mainly targeted by traditional banks, they can be considered as low-end or non-customers.

5.4 Overall discussion and conclusion

The objective was to qualitatively appraise in depth the business model of financing fintechs, i.e. crowdlending, crowdinvesting, and factoring platforms that provide services to SMEs in Germany. This includes the first qualitative evaluation of the disruptive innovation threat of financing fintechs that provide services to SMEs in Germany to traditional banks. As shown by the research gap which is illustrated in chapter three, this is the first study which appraised in-depth the business model of financing fintechs that provide services to SMEs in Germany based on a holistic view, and which provide an evaluation of the disruptive innovation threat of financing fintechs to traditional banks.

Applying the disruptive innovation theory (Christensen & Raynor, 2003; Christensen et al., 2015), crowdlending, crowdinvesting, and factoring could be considered as a combination of a low-end and new-market disruption since the results of the narrative literature review and the documentary research show that financing fintechs currently focus on customers who are not attractive for traditional banks. Low-end customers are currently served by traditional banks, but they are not considered as attractive, while non-customers are not served because of their low turnover or creditworthiness. Additionally, the performance of the services of financing fintechs is lower than the services of traditional banks, which further supports the indication of a disruptive innovation (Christensen & Raynor, 2003; Christensen et al., 2015). Again, a disruptive innovation is critical if the entrant's service or product is a substitute for the incumbent's service or product (Christensen & Raynor, 2003; Rafii & Kampas, 2002). As mentioned in chapter two, the personal judgment is relevant whether a service or product is a substitute for another service or product (Evans, 2014, p. 15). To explore and evaluate to which extent the service of financing fintechs is a substitute for traditional banking services to SMEs in Germany, expert interviews with executive managers of SMEs are necessary. The final evaluation of the disruptive innovation threat is illustrated in chapter seven.

5.5 Limitations

The limitations of the method are already described in chapter four. First, the results of the qualitative content analysis are subjectively influenced as described in chapter 4.2.5. This might include bias. Second, it might be that some information presented on the web-presences is incorrect. Third, the results are based on a point in time analysis, which means the business models could be changed in the meantime, new platforms could be founded, or existing platforms could be disappeared. However, since the documentary research is based on a total population sampling, the results are representative for all platforms that provide crowdlending, crowdinvesting, and factoring services to SMEs in Germany.

6 Results of primary research – expert interviews with executives of LMEs

The purpose of this chapter is to describe and discuss the research results of the expert interviews with executives of LMEs to critically explore and evaluate to which extent the service of financing fintechs is a substitute for traditional banking services to LMEs in Germany. Additionally, it includes a second evaluation of the disruptive innovation threat of financing fintechs that provide services to SMEs in Germany to traditional banks. For each segment, i.e. crowdlending, crowdfunding, and factoring platforms the results are separately described and discussed. Furthermore, the results of overall topics related to the executives' knowledge of or experience with financing fintechs, the financing instruments in usage and financing preferences, and the advantages and disadvantages of traditional and relationship banking are described and discussed in this chapter. These topics are contextually relevant to answer the research question.

6.1 Executive managers' knowledge of or experience with financing fintechs

6.1.1 Description of results

Again, 10 interviews were conducted and analysed. In the following, the executive managers are defined as executives added with the interview number shown in chapter four. These executives with an authority in financing decisions represent their companies. The companies are defined as LMEs added with the interview number shown in chapter four. This implies, for example, both LME1 and executive1 refer to the transcript of interview one (I1). As mentioned, with change of speaker, an empty line was inserted into the transcript, which causes sequential paragraphs (pa.). The total transcripts are in appendix H.

The category one (C1) was deductively defined with four sub-categories. The sub-category one of category one (C1S1) means the executive has knowledge about or experience with crowdfunding. Executive3 is familiar with crowdfunding because the LME wants to acquire a target company which is funded by crowdfunding (pa. 16 and pa. 50). This target company has less than ten employees. Executive7 (pa. 58) and executive10 (pa. 52) know the topic from newspapers. Executive8 gained minor experience with crowdfunding in his previous job (pa. 39), and executive9 had a first contact with a platform (pa. 52). C1S2 means the executive has knowledge about or experience with crowdlending, while C1S3 is related to crowdfunding, and C1S4 to factoring. No executive mentioned such knowledge or experience.

6.1.2 Discussion and conclusion

The results indicate that the executives of LMEs are not familiar with financing fintechs, especially not with crowdlending, crowdinvesting, and factoring platforms. The cause might be that financing fintechs have recently entered the market with a focus on smaller SMEs. The overall topic crowdfunding is most known. The interviews can be considered as expert interviews because these executives have an expertise in financing issues and know best how to finance their LMEs. However, the results have to be critically evaluated. According to the disruptive innovation theory, incumbents often fail because they listen to their mainstream or high-end customers, give them the service or product performance they are looking for, and finally, they are threatened by the disruptive innovation their customers led them to ignore.

6.2 Financing instruments in usage and financing preferences

6.2.1 Description of results

C2 describes the financing instruments that are or were used. If certain instruments are not used, this category includes the reasons why they are not used. Four sub-categories were defined. C2S1 means that after the foundation of the LME external equity was issued. LME2 went public as an exit for a professional investor (pa. 33-36) and LME3 for growth reasons (pa. 15-16). LME8 was acquired by a private equity fund, and the plan is to go public (pa. 1). Since LME7 was founded with little equity as a spin-off due to regulatory reasons, a capital increase was conducted to rise the equity ratio in order to receive a bank loan (pa. 26 and 30). The capital of LME9 was also increased in 2017 and 2018 (pa. 8).

C2S2 means that a bank loan is or was used. Apart from LME6 a bank loan is or was used by all LMEs (I1, pa. 13-14; I2, pa. 14; I3, pa. 14; I4, pa. 10; I5, pa. 5-6; I7, pa. 18; I8, pa. 7; I9, pa. 30; I10, pa. 9-10). To avoid the bank's influence, LME6 has no bank loans, which is also communicated to the customers (pa. 3-4). LME1 typically uses banks loans for larger investments (pa. 13-14). LME2 uses credit lines, real estate loans, and other bank loans (pa. 14). The credit line is between 125 and 150 mn€ in volume (I2, pa. 68). LME4 has long-term loans for real estate, medium-term loans between three and five years without the provision of a collateral, and short-term loans between one and three months (pa. 10). LME5 has short-term loans of 50 to 60 mn€ for working capital reasons (pa. 6). However, currently the volume is lower because it has more cash available. The LME receives loan offers between 5 and 20 mn€ in volume with an interest rate of 0.5% (I5, pa. 20 and 42). LME8 has a credit line of 100 mn€ that is provided by a banking consortium with a fixed interest rate which can be variably called and repaid (pa. 7-9). LME8 (pa. 8) and LME9 (pa. 8-10) have also short-term and long-term loans. The long-term loans of the latter vary between 100 and 150 mn€ in

volume and are partly for real estate reasons. Due to specific characteristics and the resulting administrative effort, the properties are not provided as collateral. The loans are provided based on the cash flow, equity situation, and the company's business model (I9, pa. 18).

C2S3 means that a mezzanine instrument is or was used. Mezzanine instruments are or were not used by the LMEs. Executive1 mentioned that he has a conservative view, and he does not know the conditions in mezzanine (pa. 10). Executive2 (pa. 16) and executive5 (pa. 18) mentioned that there was never a need for it (pa. 16). Additionally, executive2 (pa. 16-17) argues that the follow-on financing is difficult in mezzanine, and for executive9 it is too expensive (pa. 24).

C2S4 means that factoring is or was used by the LME. Factoring is or was used by three LMEs. LME2 is in the trade business and uses factoring in case of a direct debit payment procedure in which the customer signs instead of entering the pin (pa. 20-28). These claims are automatically sold to a factoring provider which can initiate a second payment run. There are between 1,500 and 2,000 transactions per annum based on a general agreement. The major reasons are the administrative effort in case there is no payment including the finding of the address, the dunning, the involvement of a lawyer, and to hedge the default risk. LME4 is in the service industry and has about 350,000 accounts receivable per annum (I4, pa. 10-15). To increase the cash flow and to hedge the default risk, the LME sells selected accounts receivable that have a long payment term and a high volume to a factoring provider. The volume or number of accounts receivable can be flexibly handled, and the total costs including the credit risk insurance are between 1.2% and 1.5% on the EURIBOR. LME5 used factoring in the past to reduce the administrative effort (I5, pa. 12-16). Instead of improving the cash flow, the intention was to reduce the administrative effort. The other LMEs have not used factoring. Executive3 mentioned that the LME has never needed it for cash flow or other reasons (pa. 82). Executive7 argues that the company has a relatively small wholesale customer base and a well-established billing process (pa. 22). According to executive8, the LME's business runs well, and its customers' payment morale is high (pa. 13). However, it is an option the executive wants to think about in future. In table 22, the financing instruments that are or were used are summarised. 1 means the statement is true, while 0 means it is not.

Table 22: Usage of financing instruments by LMEs

Category 1	LME1	LME2	LME3	LME4	LME5	LME6	LME7	LME8	LME9	LME10	Σ
S1 External equity	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	5
S2 Bank loan	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	9
S3 Mezzanine	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
S4 Factoring	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	3

Source: Own source

C3 describes the financing preferences. C3S1 means that internal financing is preferred over all other kinds of instruments. This includes that other instruments are only used in case the internal financing is not sufficient. In this context, the executives considered internal financing as the company's turnover. All executives prefer internal financing over all other financing instruments (I1, pa. 2; I2, pa. 31-32; I3, pa. 12; I4, pa. 27-30; I5, pa. 19-22; I6 pa. 7-9; I7, pa. 19-20; I8, pa. 60; I9, pa. 29; I10, pa. 6). Executive1 said, "One always earns ideally from own resources first. If you have earned it, you can actually spend it again" (pa. 6). He thinks his view is little dynamic but solid. However, he wants to ease this view a little bit and aims at an equity ratio of 70% to 80% in the long-term (I1, pa. 12). Executive3 said, "Otherwise, you have to knock on the wood, we have no financing issues, especially on the liabilities side" (pa. 14). Executive5 said, "The main shareholder wants to be independent of banks. He does not want to limit his scope of action through external partners. That is why he does not want to go public. So, he would never go public because he does not want to give a quarterly statement and then explain to anyone else why he should do anything. This is a topic of perceived freedom" (pa. 4). Additionally, the executive mentioned that the LME has sufficient cash reserves, and for him it makes no sense to take a loan for which the company has to pay interests while paying negative interests for its bank deposits (I5, pa. 20). Executive6 mentioned that the LME is 100% self-financed. This includes its real estate financing (I6, pa. 7 and 20). Executive8 mentioned that the economy is in great shape with full employment and well-filled order books, and thus the internal financing is possible. However, for larger strategic decisions like merges and acquisitions, the internal sources are not sufficient (I8, pa. 19). Executive10 mentioned that they invested a significant part of the profits of the last 50 years in real estate projects to generate cash flows in future to be more independent of banks. Nevertheless, for the real estate projects, bank loans are required (I10, pa. 6 and 19).

C3S2 means that debt financing is preferred over mezzanine or external equity. Eight executives prefer debt over mezzanine or external equity (I1, pa. 10; I2, pa. 32; I4, pa. 29-30; I5, pa. 23-24; I6, pa. 10; I7, pa. 31-32; I8, pa. 15; I10, pa. 18). Executive1 is used to debt financing, and it is safe for him because it worked well so far (pa. 10). Executive2 mentioned that he has a conservative view, and financing by debt is the cheapest form. However, he also finances medium-term investments by overdrafts because it is cheaper and due to the company's high creditworthiness there is always the option to switch to medium-term financing. Depending on the bank, the LME has a rating of A to BBB+ (I2, pa. 18 and 38). Executive8 also prefers to finance long-term investments with short-term credit lines to reduce the covenants, and thus the bank's influence (pa. 15-16). This executive also considers the German market as traditional, which he explained by the following statement: "I think it is very traditional, according to the motto, either you finance yourself or you go to a bank. That was also drummed into our heads for decades. And then there was also the wave of the 90s

and 2000s according to the motto, with the stock market crash and the economic crisis, I prefer to stay with a bank” (I8, pa. 57). Executive5 said, “You can demand almost everything in the negotiations with the banks” (pa. 24). According to the executive, the conditions can be favourably negotiated due to the company’s high creditworthiness and the negative interest environment.

C3S3 means that mezzanine or external equity is preferred over debt financing. Two executives prefer external equity over debt financing. Executive3 preferred to go public because the LME is settled in the industry 4.0 environment. The executive said, “That is such a mega trend. Since that perfectly fits in the stock market story. That was actually one of the main motives why we took this way” (I3, pa. 18). Industry 4.0 can be considered as an increasing interconnection between physical and virtual industrial machines. It implies a computerisation of manufacturing (Nicoletti, 2017). An alternative plan that consisted of mezzanine instruments was already defined. Additionally, for future investments the executive would prefer mezzanine over debt if internal financing is not sufficient. The reason is that the executive already considered mezzanine and there is a higher flexibility in balance sheet structuring (I3, pa.22-24). The equity of LME9 was increased on a regularly basis (pa. 8). In table 23, the financing preferences per LME are summarised – 1 means the statement is true, while 0 means it is not.

Table 23: Financing preferences per LME

Category 2	LME1	LME2	LME3	LME4	LME5	LME6	LME7	LME8	LME9	LME10	Σ
S1 Internal financing is preferred over all others	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	10
S2 Debt is preferred over mezzanine or external equity	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	8
S3 Mezzanine or external equity is preferred over debt	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	2

Source: Own source

6.2.2 Discussion and conclusion

The objective is to find what financing instruments are used and preferred by executives of LMEs. This includes a discussion whether executives of LMEs follow the pecking order or static trade-off theory. This can be relevant to evaluate what kind of financing fintech is more or less disruptive.

In summary, five LMEs use or have used external equity as a financing instrument of which two LMEs went public and another one plans to, which is an indication that LMEs can access capital markets, while nine LMEs use or have used bank loans and three factoring. In contrast, mezzanine is or was not used, which might be an indication that it is not a widespread financing instrument for LMEs. Since in these cases all executives prefer internal financing over all other instruments, it can be an indication that executives of LMEs follow the pecking order hierarchy, which is derived from the information asymmetries between the management and investors. Again, the theory implies that investors force executives to take internal financing first, debt second, and to issue equity as last resort to avoid sending a negative signal of an overvalued equity or dismissing a positive present value of an investment opportunity (Myers, 1984; Myers & Majluf, 1984). However, the results of this research indicate that executives of LMEs have rationales other than the assumptions of the theory. First, the management wants to act independently of banks, which implies to avoid or reduce the bank's influence on operative and strategic decisions. Second, the management wants to reduce the company's financial risk by avoiding or reducing financial obligations to banks or other investors. Third, the current economic conditions which cause high turnovers and negative interest rates. The former means that the positive economic situation generates cash that can be used for internal financing. The latter implies that the fact of negative interest rates for bank deposits discourages the management to take debt if there is cash available on its asset side independent of the spread between bank deposits and bank loans. Although in these cases, three LMEs have no separated management from the ownership, and thus there cannot be information asymmetries, there are no differences in financing preferences and their related causes relative to the other LMEs. This preference can also be defined as a conservative financing policy, which implies a high equity ratio and the focus on internal financing, while avoiding or reducing external financing (Schraml, 2010).

Since in these cases eight executives prefer debt over mezzanine or external equity, it might be a further indication that executives of LMEs at least partly follow the pecking order hierarchy. Again, the theory's assumption is that by issuing debt rather than equity and by undertaking an investment opportunity with a positive present value, the company value can be increased with less dilution of the true value of the existing shareholders (Myers, 1984; Myers & Majluf, 1984). However, the

results of this research indicate that executives of LMEs have rationales other than the assumptions of the theory. First, executives can be customised to bank loans with a positively proven experience. The focus on bank loans can also be interpreted as a conservative financing policy (Schraml, 2010). However, there can also be a deviation from a conservative financing policy. Executives partly finance medium- or long-term investments with short-term instruments because it is cheaper or does not include covenants. The golden balance sheet rule implies that long-term assets should be financed by long-term instruments (Reichling et al., 2005). Second, the economic conditions strengthen the LMEs' negotiation positions with banks. Third, for LMEs bank loans can be the cheapest form of external financing. Although the latter could be related to the costs that are caused by the information asymmetry, in this context, it is the capital cost rate. In the course of tax advantages, this could also be related to the static trade-off theory.

Since in these cases two executives prefer external equity or mezzanine over debt, it might be an indication that executives of LMEs at least partly do not follow the pecking order hierarchy. There can be different causes. First, the management wants to have a higher flexibility in balance sheet structuring, which can be an indication of the following of the static trade-off theory because it implies a target debt-to-equity ratio. Second, there is a favourable equity story that encourages the management to go public. A favourable equity story can be interpreted as information asymmetries between the management and investors where the intrinsic value of the equity is less than the market value. Again, according to the pecking order theory, the investors would avoid buying equity unless the company has already exhausted its debt capacity (Myers, 1984; Myers & Majluf, 1984). In this case, the LME had no debt obligations. Therefore, it might be a herding behaviour of the investors by following a trend of industry 4.0 while the management takes advantage of it in the favour of the existing shareholders.

The results can be ambiguously interpreted. There are two types: First, executives of LMEs that follow the pecking order hierarchy rules but based on different rationales. Second, executives of LMEs that partly follow the static trade-off and pecking order theory because internal financing is preferred first, and second, equity or mezzanine over debt is preferred to have a higher flexibility in balance sheet structuring, which implies a target debt-to-equity ratio. There are empirical studies indicating that the management of SMEs follow the pecking order theory, while there are also empirical studies indicating that the management of SMEs follow the static trade-off theory (Renner, 2016; Seehausen, 2014). The argument of Seehausen that the application of these theories to SMEs is limited because the theories are for companies that have an unlimited access to capital markets and where the management is separated from ownership, is not applicable in these cases (2014). Of the three LMEs where the management is not separated from ownership, there are no

differences in financing preferences relative to the other five LMEs within type one. The two LMEs within type two are not managed by their owners. The results should be further considered especially for possible preferences of crowdlending versus crowdinvesting.

6.3 Advantages and disadvantages of traditional and relationship banking

6.3.1 Description of results

Four categories were defined. The first, C4, was deductively defined and describes whether or not the LME has a relationship bank, and if yes, then it includes characteristics of the relationship. All executives mentioned that the LME has a relationship bank (I1, pa. 14; I2, pa. 14; I3, pa. 28; I4, pa. 32; I5, pa. 28; I6, pa. 14; I7, pa. 40; I8, pa. 25; I9, pa. 32; I10, pa. 28). LME1 has two relationship banks. One for the standardised business, and one for financing issues and foreign trade (pa. 14). LME2 has four relationship banks. One is the relationship bank for about 70 years (pa. 40). LME3 has three relationship banks for regional and national business (pa. 28). Nevertheless, they deal more on the asset side, for example, reverse cash pooling to avoid negative interest rates. LME4 also has more relationship banks for a term of 12 to 24 years (pa. 32). LME5 has three relationship banks which can be split into regional and international banks while the banking activities depend on the topic (pa. 14 and 28). LME8 has two relationship banks. One for operational issues, and another as lead bank in an international banking consortium (pa. 25-27). With the latter the LME does business for two and half years, and the executive considers this as a long-term relationship. LME9 has five relationship banks. One for operational issues that does not include financing, one for smaller financing volumes, and four for larger financing volumes (pa. 32). LME10 has four relationship banks (pa. 44). Two in Germany, one in Austria, and one in France.

C5 describes positive effects of having a relationship bank or doing business with a traditional bank. C5S1 was deductively defined and describes that due to the relationship, there is a higher reliability. Executive1 said, "The advantage is surely that you can rely on each other and that you know each other. You know the business or more specific the person on the other side which can be a stability" (pa. 16). He also mentioned that the relationship becomes more intensive by doing more business together. Executive2 said, "What is crucial for me that is that I can have confidence. That I know the banks behave like in the past and yes that I am trying to anticipate that benefits" (I2, pa. 48). This executive mentioned that the reliability is on both sides, which implies that the executive does not negotiate the last tenth of a percentage in case the bank has difficult times (I2, pa. 38). Executive3 mentioned that regarding the negative interest rates, there is often a concession of the bank due to mutual trust (pa. 32). He would expect this trust also on the liability side. Executive4 said, "Even nowadays there is a certain amount of seriousness and trust in the business. And on

both sides. It goes to the point that I do not change the banks like the shirts only because someone offers two tenths cheaper” (pa. 32). He mentioned that the bank wants to have loyal customers and he wants to have a reliable bank. Executive6 said, “I understand [reliability] in the traditional sense. I have a contact person; I can judge that. I know the person will do what they tell me. Simply because the person is also interested in a long-term partnership” (pa. 22). Executive9 said, “There is an uncanny trust there” (pa. 38). She associates the trust also with a higher loan availability. Executive10 said, “The relationship becomes better every year, from year to year and decade to decade” (I10, pa. 46). For example, when the LME started its business in France, it opened an account at a French bank. The financing was through the German bank because the French bank did not provide it. Today, the French bank often offers financing because it knows the LME now.

C5S2 was deductively defined and means that advisors of traditional or relationship banks have specific knowledge in different fields and provide special or customised services. Executive1 mentioned that the bank’s advisors have the knowledge and experience in payment transactions and hedges, which is necessary for the LME’s business because it exports to 30 countries worldwide (pa. 18). Additionally, executive1 (pa. 26) mentioned that the bank provides special offers like loans for energy saving technologies with low interest rates, and executive10 (pa. 38) mentioned the bank provides customised services. Executive8 mentioned that larger traditional banks cover international business activities including the required software and regulatory requirements like laundering controls, and thus they also have a positive effect on compliance issues (pa. 3).

C5S3 was deductively defined and means that due to the relationship the procedure for different topics including loan financing is faster or easier. Executive2 mentioned that it “was already possible to receive a financing over a larger amount than 10 million within ten days” (pa. 42). Executive10 also mentioned that the LME received a seven-digit financing within eight to nine days from the request to the payment (pa. 46). Executive3 mentioned that things can be done faster and easier because the bank is within walking distance (pa. 30). In the context of regulatory topics, he said, “that even in times of online etc., with such a personal contact, certain things go quicker and easier than when I have to talk to an anonymous administration [...] that has its charm if the bank is really not an anonymous hotline” (I3, pa. 30). Executive4 mentioned that if there is any issue, he can call them and after two minutes he has the information (pa. 36). Executive5 said, “And today, I am just calling Mr. X, who is the head of the bank, and say, look at that, please” (pa. 60). Additionally, he mentioned that they have prepared a financing solution in advance for a potential audit risk of the LME. In case the issue occurs, there is a fast financing solution up to 80 mn€ (I5, pa. 40). Executive7 mentioned that the LME’s business model is so special, and the bank’s advisors know the business

model and can correctly assess the cases. In case of a new bank he had to explain the business model (pa. 42).

C5S4 was deductively defined and means that the interest rate is lower due to the relationship. Executive1 mentioned that the interest is generally better because the bank does not want to lose the relationship (pa. 19). Executive2 also thinks that the interest rate is better at a relationship bank (pa. 44). He said, "But I am one who says I do not care about the last tenth because there are good conditions. Because someone tries to come in, just to get a foot in the door" (I2, pa. 46). Executive3 does not exactly know the causes, but he has the opinion that the interest is better (pa. 33). Executive4 mentioned slight differences like a tenth of a percentage and if a new bank offers a better interest, it is temporary to get in that cannot be kept in the long-term (pa. 40). Executive5 said, "So, there are already highly competitive prices. So, if you finance the photo studio like now and you play that out, you actually get better conditions than at another bank" (pa. 30). Additionally, he mentioned that one bank became a relationship bank seven years ago because it provided very good conditions (I5, pa. 32).

C5S5 was deductively defined and means that the collateral requirements are lower due to the relationship. Executive4 mentioned that the collateral requirements are better and that he does not know how a new bank would react if he would like to have 10 mn€ without providing a collateral (pa. 44).

C5S6 was deductively defined and means that higher loan volumes are available due to the relationship. Executive9 favours the relationship bank because higher loan volumes are available (pa. 38).

C5S7 was deductively defined and means that traditional communication channels like appointments or personal contacts with relationship banks are an advantage for the LMEs. Executive3 mentioned that if there is any topic, the advisor or branch executive comes to the LME and they can discuss the topic (pa. 42). This positive effect is also related to the previously mentioned effect that the process is faster and easier. Executive5 annually makes a banker's day where he invites all banks to provide the multi-year plan for the next years to increase transparency and to provide the same information to all banks (pa. 28 and 46). Executive10 also invites the bank once a year to review the entire year and to answer questions (pa. 50). The executive thinks that transparency increases trust and makes it easier in difficult times. Executive6 mentioned that she considers the personal meetings as an opportunity to maintain the relationship (pa. 30). Executive9 regularly initiates rating meetings to be informed about any changes in the creditworthiness. She

said, “You get then at some institutions like a traffic light that you see the value has now deteriorated or has become better” (I9, pa. 48).

C5S8 was inductively defined and means that due to the relationship, the bank advisor knows the business model and can check the plausibility of the investments. Executive6 mentioned that the bank advisor can be considered as a sparring partner to give feedback whether or not the project is meaningful and profitable (pa. 24-26). Executive5 also mentioned that the bank can be used to validate investments (pa. 76).

C6 describes negative effects of having a relationship bank or doing business with a traditional bank. C6S1 was inductively defined and implies a negative dependency on relationship banks. Executive1 mentioned an example of a company that failed due to the corresponding actions of its banks (pa. 6). He thinks that the failure of the company was intended by the banks by rejecting loans. Executive5 said, “The very critical thing we have never experienced here is when you do not have a good credit rating anymore and you have to negotiate with the banks that they keep up your line of credit, then you realise relatively quick, how strong the house banks are” (pa. 34). Executive10 mentioned that back in the 2007 banking crisis, “Those who need the loans do not get any and those who do not need it would get one” (pa. 20). Therefore, they invested a significant part of the profits of the last 50 years in real estate projects “to ensure independence of the banks” (I10, pa. 20). Additionally, he said, “We work very cooperatively with our banks, but it should stay with a partnership and not an intense dependency” (I10, pa. 20).

C6S2 was deductively defined and means that the requirements of covenants of traditional banks are a disadvantage. This includes the influence of the bank on the company's business. Executive3 said, “I know it from an auditor's point of view of clients who have always complained very much about these covenants. That is often a vicious circle. When the numbers go down, interest rates go up. This then mutually reinforces each other” (pa. 38). LME6 advertises its brand with no bank liabilities to show that it can independently act of banks (I6, pa. 10). As already mentioned, executive8 prefers credit line financing to reduce the covenants, and thus the bank's influences (pa. 15). He said, “It is clear if you make long-term bank financing in the 100 million range that the banks first have a say in organisational or business changes in the company. Of course, you try to exclude this as a company as far as possible” (I8, pa. 15).

C6S3 was deductively defined and means that the collateral requirements of traditional banks are a disadvantage. Executive1 mentioned that providing collaterals like mortgages is a major handicap, while all other things are not relevant to him (I1, pa. 24).

C6S4 was inductively defined and means that the interest rate is higher at the relationship bank. Executive7 mentioned that for an interest rate swap, the long-standing relationship bank was not the cheapest and he does not see any positive effects in interest rates (pa. 48). They always invite different banks to make offers.

C6S5 was inductively defined and means that the traditional bank's services are limited and not independent. Executive1 mentioned that banks are biased, and the services are pre-defined (pa. 22).

C6S6 was deductively defined and means that the traditional communication channels like appointments or personal contacts are a disadvantage. No executive mentioned such disadvantage.

C6S7 was inductively defined and means it is a disadvantage to have one relationship bank for financing and operational issues because financing issues can influence the operational business. Executive8 mentioned that he had that before that one bank was responsible for financing and operational banking issues and “this has developed unfavourably because risk management on the financing side has paralysed operational development” (pa. 29). Therefore, he prefers to decouple these topics from each other by having different banks. He also considers it as trade-off because then the company may not be an interesting partner for the bank. Executive9 also mentioned that it is a disadvantage to have one bank that provides both long-term financing and lines of credit (pa. 46). In case of a high volume of long-term financing, the line of credit may be reduced, which could influence the operational business.

C6S8 was deductively defined and means that relationship banks or traditional banking does not have any negative effects. Executive2 (pa. 50), executive3 (pa. 36), executive4 (pa. 46), executive7 (pa. 50), and executive9 (pa. 46) mentioned at first that they do not see any disadvantages. However, executive3, executive7, and executive9 mentioned later some disadvantages.

C7 describes indifferent points of relationship and traditional banking. All sub-categories were inductively defined. C7S1 means that the covenants are neither an advantage nor a disadvantage. Executive2 mentioned that the reports have to be created anyway and the provision to the bank is not an issue (pa. 52-54). Additionally, he mentioned that the LME has financial covenants that are more pro forma because they were defined 15 years ago. Executive4 mentioned that the LME has financial covenants in some agreements to meet certain ratios, while the most agreements do not include covenants because of equal treatment (pa. 48). He explained that by “The others do not

have it, so you do not get it” (I4, pa. 48). Also, executive5 (pa. 44), executive7 (pa. 52), executive9 (pa. 22), and executive 10 (pa. 44) do not see any issues in covenants.

C7S2 means that in relationship banking the collateral requirements are neither lower nor higher. Executive1 (pa. 26) argued that the collateral requirements are the same due to the Basel requirements, and executive2 (pa. 54) mentioned that all banks are equally treated. Executive9 said, “Let us say that we do not provide a collateral. And that is known from the start and accepted that way. Otherwise we would not do it” (pa. 44).

C7S3 means that in relationship banking the interest rate is neither lower nor higher. Executive8 mentioned that in case of loan volumes about 100 mn€, there is no difference in the interest rate (pa. 31). Executive9 mentioned that due to the LME’s high creditworthiness, the probability of default is the same, and thus there is no difference in the interest rate (pa. 42).

6.3.2 Discussion and conclusion

The objective of the expert interviews is to critically explore and evaluate to which extent the service of financing fintechs is a substitute for traditional banking services to LMEs in Germany. Since all executives interviewed mentioned that they have at least one long-term relationship bank, substituting traditional banking implies to substitute the services of long-term relationship banks. However, long-term can be differently interpreted. It varies between 2.5 and 70 years in these cases. The activities of relationship banks can be related to asset management, financing issues, and payment transactions. Again, according to Navaretti et al., based on powerful computers, big data and machine learning that explore, learn, and identify patterns may complement or substitute relationship banking (2018). Nevertheless, the production of soft information requires an access to large scale of private and public data.

The categories previously illustrated contain indicators that enable or disable the substitution of traditional and relationship banking by financing fintechs. In the following the indicators are discussed and evaluated as disabling the substitution, enabling the substitution, or as neutral if it is both disabling and enabling due to opposed rationales or neither disabling nor enabling. The evaluation is for the status quo, however, if there are any potential changes for the future, it is also evaluated. In table 24, the results are summarised.

Table 24: Evaluation of financing fintechs as substitute for traditional and relationship banking

Indicator	Disabling	Neutral	Enabling
1 Reliability and dependency	s	-	-
2 Velocity and convenience	s	-	-
3 Customised services and expertise	s	-	-
4 Interest rates	-	s	-
5 Collateral requirements	-	s	-
6 Loan volumes	s	-	-
7 Investment review	s	-	-
8 Exclusive cross product relationship	-	s	-
9 Covenants	-	s	-

Source: Own source

- 1) *Reliability and dependency*: The results of this research show that executives of LMEs partly consider a higher reliability on both sides due to relationship banking. This implies that for LMEs the loan availability can be higher, also in times where the company's financing situation is difficult, and for banks in terms of a reduction of the LMEs' price elasticities. As shown in chapter three, based on data of a survey to SMEs, Maier found that reliability is more relevant than economic factors (2016b). The results of this research indicate that also for the executives of LMEs, reliability can be more relevant than to receive the maximum favourable economic conditions. Reliability is based on knowing each other and expecting each other's behaviour, and it becomes more intensive in case of doing more business together. This implies that a signalling equilibrium is approached of the executives to reduce the information asymmetry. Currently, one platform mentioned that the approach of the creditworthiness evaluation includes big data analytics, which was not further specified. If an approach of big data and machine learning would access the information required and would improve pattern recognition, then it could be a substitute. However, it can be assumed that a possible increase in reliability of financing fintechs with a two-sided marketplace business model is lower than the reliability in relationship banking. First, the information must be transmitted to the investors. Second, in contrast to relationship banks, individual and professional investors of fundings do not have cross-product synergies during the relationship life-cycle, and thus might have more short-term driven interests. Nevertheless, executives of LMEs can also critically reflect the dependency on relationship banks, which implies that the loan availability is not higher at times where the company's financing situation is difficult or in a financial crisis. Consequently, there is a risk for LMEs if executives expect a higher reliability while their relationship banks have an informational

monopoly. The disadvantage of an informational monopoly is also discussed by Norden, which means a relationship bank observes proprietary information that cannot be transferred to another bank, which can cause a lock-in effect if the company does not have alternative banks or if it faces high switching costs (2015). Since the risk does not enable substitution but instead enable diversification, and in relationship banking there is a possibility of a higher reliability, this indicator is evaluated as disabling under the status quo.

- 2) *Velocity and convenience*: The results show that executives of LMEs can have a higher velocity and convenience of financing issues including loan decisions and provisions due to relationship banking. Additionally, the results indicate that executives of LMEs favour physical appointments and personal contacts. A close physical distance and personal relationship can reduce the information asymmetry (Cole, Goldberg, & White, 2004; Schwartz et al., 2017). The actions of the executives like a banker's day in which all banks are invited can be considered as a bonding instrument to reduce the information asymmetry. It can be assumed that a possible increase in velocity and convenience due to a new approach based on big data and machine learning is lower than the velocity and convenience in relationship banking due to the higher transaction costs of the services of financing fintechs as shown in chapter five. Therefore, this indicator is evaluated as disabling under the status quo. The transaction costs can be partly reduced by a change in business model, which is discussed in the following chapters.
- 3) *Customised services and expertise*: The results show that executives of LMEs receive customised services and an expertise of the advisors of traditional and relationship banks. Nevertheless, the results show also a disadvantage that the executives can perceive the services as limited and biased without alternatives. Financing fintechs currently focus on niches with standardised services and without advisors. Although in future big data and machine learning could provide individual services based on identified patterns as described by Dorfleitner and Hornuf (2018), which should also not be unbiased, it can be assumed that customised services of financing fintechs with a two-sided marketplace business model cannot be as individual and complex as in traditional banking due to the dependency on the investors. Therefore, this indicator is evaluated as disabling under the status quo. Assuming the investors solely invest in fundings they comprehend, a focus on professional investors, which can also be split into groups with a certain expertise, could increase the customisation.

- 4) *Interest rates:* The results show that executives of LMEs partly perceive that they receive lower interest rates due to relationship banking. If another bank provides lower interests, it can be an intertemporal pricing strategy by offering lower interest at the beginning to acquire the customer, but then increasing the interest for subsequent business. This is also supported by the results of Norden who also found that for SMEs the soft information that is available is higher due to a long-term relationship, and thus the interest rate is lower (2015). If a new approach based on big data and machine learning could produce soft information that is equal to relationship banking, then the effects can be neutralised, while a production of soft information that is more accurate can enable the substitution. However, there are also executives who do not observe any interest advantages especially if the volumes are about 100 mn€. Therefore, this indicator is evaluated as neutral under the status quo.
- 5) *Collateral requirements:* The results show that executives of LMEs partly perceive that the collateral requirements are lower due to relationship banking. This is also supported by the results of Norden who found that due to a long-term relationship, the collateral requirements are lower for SMEs (2015). If a new approach based on big data and machine learning could produce soft information that is equal to relationship banking, then the effects can be neutralised, while a production of soft information that is more accurate can enable the substitution. However, there are also executives who do not observe any differences in collateral requirements due to the Basel III requirements and an equal treatment of all banks. Therefore, this indicator is evaluated as neutral under the status quo.
- 6) *Loan volumes:* The results show that executives of LMEs partly perceive that the loan volumes can be higher due to relationship banking. This is also supported by the results of Norden who found that for SMEs the loan volumes available are higher due to a long-term relationship (2015). Therefore, this indicator is evaluated as disabling under the status quo. If a new approach based on big data and machine learning could produce soft information that is equal to relationship banking, then the effects can be neutralised, while a production of soft information that is more accurate can enable the substitution.
- 7) *Investment review:* The results show that executives of LMEs can favour the ability of the advisors of traditional and relationship banks to check the plausibility of investments, who can support the investment decisions. This can also reduce the information asymmetry for a later stage of the relationship. Although professional investors might also provide

plausibility checks, this is not as private as in traditional and relationship banking. Therefore, this indicator is evaluated as disabling under the status quo.

- 8) *Exclusive cross product relationship*: The results show that if an LME has solely one exclusive cross product relationship bank that covers long-term financing for investments and short-term financing for operational issues, based on a cross product informational monopoly, the bank can constrain the operational financing due to long-term financing issues. Therefore, executives partly separate these financing sources. This is the inverse effect of the result of Norden and Weber which implies that account activities help predicting future borrower defaults (2009). However, since this disadvantage does not enable substitution but rather diversification, this indicator is evaluated as neutral under the status quo.
- 9) *Covenants*: The results show that covenants of traditional banks can be negatively perceived by executives of LMEs due to the bank's influence on the strategic and operative decisions. There are also loan agreements without covenants because of equal treatment of all banks or pro forma covenants that are not negatively perceived by executives. Since financing fintechs also partly define covenants, this indicator is evaluated as neutral under the status quo.

Possible advantages of a lower interest rate, lower collateral requirements, and a higher loan volume that could enable the substitution due to a new approach based on big data and machine learning should not enable the substitution in the future since the technologies of traditional banks and financing fintechs should converge. Traditional banks can develop their own or can acquire the technology. Again, Navaretti et al. also assume that in the long-term the technology will converge (2018).

There is a first indication that financing fintechs cannot substitute the services of traditional and relationship banks. In the following chapters, this will be explicitly evaluated for crowdlending, crowdinvesting, and factoring platforms.

6.4 Crowdlending as substitute for traditional banking

6.4.1 Description of results

Three categories were defined. The first, C8, describes advantages, and the second, C9, disadvantages of crowdlending relative to traditional banking especially to traditional bank loans. C8S1 means that the procedure of crowdlending is faster or simpler. Executive8 assumes it is faster

although he has no experience (pa. 47). The impression of executive9 is “that everything is really simple, fast” (pa. 82).

C8S2 means that the publication to the investors is a positive signalling effect to the market. Executive3 thinks in equity story, and he considers this as positive for the company (pa. 62). The message sent to the market would be that the company’s philosophy fits the spirit of time and evolution (I3, pa. 62). Regarding the possible issue that a negative signalling to the market could occur if a funding through a crowdlending platform failed, he said, “Well, that is how self-confident you are. [...] I have to make the decision in advance. If I knew in advance that this could turn out bad, then maybe I should rather refrain from it” (I3, pa. 64). Executive9 would consider it as opportunity to show also to others than locals what services are provided by the LME (pa. 66). Regarding the possible issue that a negative signalling to the market could occur if a funding through a crowdlending platform failed, she said, “I do not see the risk to get no financing at all and not in the next few years” (I9, pa. 68). Executive10 considers it as a positive signalling to possible employees and said, “I would say in the IT field, as I said we have our own IT company which develops the logistics products, I could imagine, [...] that could be of interest to the employees in terms of employer branding” (I10, pa. 70).

C8S3 means that it is an advantage that crowdlending platforms are less regulated than traditional banks. Executive1 can imagine that the procedure is faster with less obligations (pa. 34). Executive5 positively considers it because he thinks that the market is overregulated (pa. 64), and executive9 solely sees advantages for borrowers (pa. 70).

C8S4 means that crowdlending is more flexible or transparent. Without experience executive8 assumes that it is more flexible (pa. 47), and executive9 considers it as more transparent, which includes a comparison of different offers (pa. 78). All sub-categories were deductively defined.

C9 describes disadvantages of crowdlending relative to traditional banking. C9S1 to C9S8 were deductively, while C9S9 to C9S13 were inductively defined. C9S1 means that the procedure of crowdlending is slower or more inconvenient. Executive4 said, “For 2.5 million, I make a call and hold a five-minute conversation. Then I have 2.5 million. I do not need to publish a funding. I do not need anything. The issue is done. This is also a convenience factor” (pa. 66). He assumes that the effort is higher in providing the information online, i.e. by uploading the documents to the platform, than to have a conversation with his bank advisor (I4, pa. 52). Executive5 said, “I think it is not easier. If you have people who have accompanied you for 10, 20 years. [...] And I say, listen, I need 10 million euros because we are building three new flagship stores in the Belgian market. I would

not have to explain that to them” (pa. 76). Executive7 also thinks that the anonymity of crowdlending and the online communication are more difficult than to have a physical meeting with a bank advisor who knows the company for 10 to 15 years to discuss certain issues including the negotiation of interest rates (pa. 70).

C9S2 means that the publication of the funding to the investors is a negative signalling effect. Executive1 thinks that a funding on a crowdlending platform could send the message to the market that the company has financing issues and does not receive funds from the bank (pa. 58-59). Additionally, for him it is an issue to publish financial figures on the platform. That is the reason why his company is a private company as a legal entity in order to have no obligations to publish financial figures. He mentioned that there are five customers who make the market and if they know the figures, they would reduce the price in a good year (I1, pa. 52). In order to present the company, he prefers other ways (I1, pa. 58). Executive4 also wants to separate the presentation of the company from financing issues (pa. 60). He does not want to publish financing issues, and he thinks that for advertising different information is needed. Additionally, he is cautious about the control of the data meaning to whom the data is available on the internet (I4, pa. 54). Executive2 mentioned that the consequences of receiving no funds from the investors would be a significant damage (pa. 74 and 80). He thinks the business is then broken. Executive6 also thinks that a crowdlending funding would damage the LME’s core brand (pa. 36). She mentioned that the company successfully exists since XX (anonymity of data), and there are many competitors that exist today but not tomorrow. Executive8 thinks that it may be a negative signalling effect to the market if the annual report includes the information that the company is financed by crowdfunding and not by traditional investors (pa. 51-53). However, he thinks that depends on the size of the company and the industry – for larger companies and companies in traditional industries like engineering the negative effects might be higher.

C9S3 means it is a disadvantage that crowdlending platforms are less regulated than traditional banks. Executive1 thinks that regulations convey a certain security and assumes higher interest rates as consequence due to the higher risks for the investors (pa. 40). Executive4 considers it an issue because he does not exactly know how and where the data is used (pa. 55). Executive6 strictly manages compliance issues, and it would be a problem not to completely know the partners (pa. 38). Executive10 thinks in the long-term it needs a reasonable and manageable regulation so that nobody is betrayed especially individual investors that have less funds available (pa. 71).

C9S4 means that the executive considers it risky that the idea which is published to the investors can be reproduced. Executive6 considers it as risky because a product of the LME has already been copied (pa. 39).

C9S5 means it is a disadvantage or even an exclusion criterion that a personal guarantee is partly required. Executive1 is liable anyway because the legal entity is a private company (pa. 30). However, he mentioned that there must be a significant relation to the company to be liable for the loan. He thinks the shareholder should provide such guarantee, which should be difficult in case of more than one (I1, pa. 42). Executive2 mentioned that in case of a personal guarantee he would provide them more collateral than he provides to the banks and “that would completely mess up all the funding” (pa. 68). Additionally, he said, “There will never be a CEO in personal liability. Nobody does” (I2, pa. 66). Executive5 said, “I would say to our main shareholder, yes, like to give a security, but I am not part of it” (pa. 74). In this context executive7 said, “I would never do that. I would be stupid” (pa. 122).

C9S6 means it is a disadvantage or even an exclusion criterion that the volume per funding is limited to 2.5 mn€. Executive2 said, “For me it is definitely no financing strategy especially since the volume can actually only be a bycatch. Because companies in our scale not only have 2.5 million line of credit but have 125, 140, 150 million” (pa. 68). Executive4 thinks it would be probably too low because the last warehouse expansion was ten times higher (pa. 62). Executive6 said, “If you say the limit is 2.5 million per project, if I understand you correctly, you have to imagine as a large medium-sized company, I spent this in the morning for machines of the training workshop” (pa. 32). Executive7 said, “We need millions. We cannot get very far with 2.5 million” (pa. 120). Executive9 mentioned that the LME’s construction projects are much higher, and she does not consider these platforms for this kind of financing projects (pa. 76).

C9S7 means that the limited maturity is a disadvantage. Executive9 said, “I think you will not find anyone [investor] for a long-term financing. That would be more of a bridging loan” (pa. 58). The long-term loans of this company are between 10 and 15 years (I9, pa. 12).

C9S8 means that the interest rates or fees are a disadvantage or even an exclusion criterion. Executive1 said, “16.6% is of course completely ineligible. 2.5% good. But I would not do it today” (pa. 38). Executive2 thinks that the one-off fees are not acceptable (pa. 84). Executive7 assumes that it has to be more expensive because the platform and the white-label bank want to make profit (pa. 80).

C9S9 means that the topic is unknown, and thus it is a disadvantage. Executive1 is used to have bank loans, and crowdlending is a new topic, and thus he would need an advisor (pa. 32 and 40). Executive5 is also not used to crowdlending, and he wants to communicate with a person and not to a machine (pa. 62). Executive2 mentioned that if he would like to take funds through this way, he must convince the board of the advantages, and it would probably decline something unknown (pa. 86). Executive7 critically considers the contractual construction, which is difficult to understand, while at a bank there is only a one-to-one relation without further parties being involved (pa. 94).

C9S10 means that the investors' feedback of the service or product is a disadvantage because they do not have expertise. Executive5 critically considers the feedback because the most people do not know the business (pa. 78). He said, "Just as if you were a sports car manufacturer and anyone who can pay one million euros explains how the new sports car should look like because he has already bought it once before" (I5, pa. 77 and 80). Therefore, he would not value any feedback.

C9S11 means it is a disadvantage if the customers are simultaneously the investors because if the LME has difficult times and cannot repay the loan or interest, it can lose its customers. Executive2 said, "Because the fan base is, I say, the circle of customers and if you come to a bad situation and the best customers do not longer receive their money, then you lose these fans. Also, not good" (pa. 88).

C9S12 means that for a planned IPO (initial public offering) or sale of the company, crowdlending is inadequate. Executive8 said, "or at the end of the day, I want to sell my company in a timely manner, then one should rather, I can say, demonstrate more transparent and stable structures. That helps immensely in such a process" (pa. 49).

C9S13 means the risk that the platform cannot be established and disappears again. Executive6 said, "The house bank is normally available tomorrow. I do not know that from the platforms" (pa. 18). She thinks that fintechs are in a dynamic environment, and they come and go relatively quickly (I6, pa. 37).

C10 describes indifferent points to crowdlending relative to traditional banking. All sub-categories were inductively defined. C10S1 means that less regulation is neither an advantage nor a disadvantage. Executive2 said, "because our business model is that we buy and sell goods and not that we lend money" (pa. 86). Executive7 said, "I say as a borrower, I do not care. I receive money from someone, and it is his problem to receive it back" (pa. 94).

C10S2 means the personal guarantee that is partly required is neither an advantage nor a disadvantage. Executive1 of the private company as legal entity is fully liable in any case (pa. 30). Executive3 said, “My personal liability, that is my natural person, would not be an exclusion criterion. You can certainly split also on several persons. But then the question would be, it is a joint debtor. But that would not be an exclusion criterion for me now” (pa. 56).

C10S3 means that the executive does not see a risk of the reproduction of the idea that is published on the platform. Executive3 does not consider it as risky because when the LME approaches new projects, the knowledge is in the minds of the engineers or software developers (pa. 66). Executive4 also does not care as long as it is not required to publish the detailed technical plans (pa. 58). Executive5 said, “If I build a logistics centre for 90 million over there, as X did, everyone knows it. [Idea reproduction] is very difficult in our industry because you are under surveillance anyway” (pa. 70). Executive8 thinks that if the LME would be at any innovation fairs to place to the market, then the risk of followers is also there (pa. 59).

C10S4 means that the threshold of 2.5 mn€ is neither an advantage nor a disadvantage. For executive1 it is not sufficient for large investments, but he could consider it for complementary investments or for diversity reasons (pa. 50). For executive3 it is no disadvantage as long as he can create more fundings (pa. 80). Executive9 thinks that for projects like increasing energy efficiency the threshold is no disadvantage (pa. 76).

C11 describes under what circumstances the executive would request funding through crowdlending. Four sub-categories were deductively defined. C11S1 means that crowdlending would be used if no bank loans are available. For executive1 (pa. 70) and executive5 (pa. 58) crowdlending would be a possibility if there is no bank loan available. Executive1 assumes that if there is no bank loan available, the interest rate is higher in any case (pa. 70).

C11S2 means that crowdlending would be used in case the economic conditions are equal to bank loans. Assuming crowdlending has equal economic conditions, executive3 could imagine using crowdlending if the related administrative effort is not significantly higher than in traditional banking (pa. 52-54). The administrative effort is a decisive criterion. The reason why he would use it is that it fits the LME’s corporate philosophy of industry 4.0. Executive4 mentioned that in case of a homogeneous product, the hard facts as the economic conditions are up to 90% decisive (pa. 52). “That means interest rate and collateral should be the same, so none” (I4, pa. 52). The other 10% are soft facts such as administrative effort. He assumes a higher effort through crowdlending than in traditional banking. Additionally, he would like to have a flexible repayment structure.

Executive9 would try it for energy efficiency topics like replacing the lighting or heating system with a maturity between two and three years (pa. 62). Nevertheless, she mentioned that the administrative effort should not be significantly higher (I9, pa. 58). The main driver for her is diversification (I9, pa. 64). It protects the line of credit (I9, pa. 68). Furthermore, she mentioned that if the business model would not be so real estate-based and if the LME would have more assets like machines, she could consider it as a competition to traditional banks (I9, pa. 102).

C11S3 means that crowdlending would be used if the economic conditions are better than bank loans. Executive1 mentioned that fintechs involve more risk and uncertainty, and thus he would use it if the interest rate is lower for a half to one percentage point (pa. 40). Executive5 would also attempt crowdlending if the interest rate is significantly lower or the volume higher because he knows the relationship bank, and it has proven to be a reliable partner (I5, pa. 60). Executive7 first mentioned that crowdlending would not be a realistic option (pa. 62). He said, "So, the banks overrun us. They call me regularly and ask, if you need more money. That is why I have never dealt with it, and I cannot imagine that it really matters to us in the future" (I7, pa. 62). However, later in the interview he mentioned that he would only consider it if there is a significant economic benefit (I7, pa. 68). He would evaluate the trade-off between the savings and the additional administrative effort relative to the status quo (I7, pa. 72). He mentioned that the current banking process is established including the reporting requirements (I7, pa. 68). Executive10 first mentioned that he would not finance through crowdlending because he assumes that this kind of financing is only necessary if the growth rates are too high (pa. 60). Later in the interview he mentioned that he would evaluate the influence of the investors and the reliability in crowdlending (I10, pa. 74). Currently, the LME has loans for working capital reasons with an interest rate below 2%. He thinks that it might be interesting if the general interest rate level increases with some kind of distortion.

C11S4 means that crowdlending would not be used or solely if there is no other financing available. Executive2 assumes that there are always relationship banks, and he thinks this is the better way. He said, "You can also negotiate terms with two or three banks. And either it works then, or it does not. But I could never imagine doing that through crowdlending or crowdinvesting" (I2, pa. 72). He does not consider it as diversification. Executive6 would also not finance through crowdlending, and said, "Then everything else would have gone down the drain. Then our core strategy would have gone awry if I resorted to these means" (pa. 32).

6.4.2 Discussion and conclusion

The objective is to critically explore and evaluate to which extent the service of crowdlending platforms is a substitute for traditional banking services especially bank loans to LMEs in Germany. Again, the service of crowdlending and banks in terms of a banking licence are perfect complements because the process of crowdlending requires a banking licence. Currently, the platforms have no banking licence, and thus their service is a perfect complement to the service of the white-label banks.

The categories previously illustrated contain indicators that enable or disable the substitution of traditional and relationship banking by crowdlending platforms. The results are summarised in table 25.

Table 25: Evaluation of crowdlending as substitute for relationship and traditional banking

Indicator s = status quo; p = potential change for future if any	Disabling	Neutral	Enabling
1 Transaction costs including velocity and convenience	s	-	-
2 Signalling effect	s	-	-
3 Less regulation and data protection	s	p	-
4 Flexibility and transparency	-	s	-
5 Risk of idea reproduction	s	-	-
6 Collateral requirements	s	p	-
7 Limited funding volume	s	-	-
8 Limited maturity	s	p	-
9 Interest rate and fee	s	p	-
10 Unknown topic	s	p	-
11 Product or service feedback	-	s	-
12 Risk customers as investors	s	p	-
13 Financing structure for sale	s	-	-
14 Risk platform disappears	s	p	-

Source: Own source

- 1) *Transaction costs including velocity and convenience:* The results of this research show that executives of LMEs partly assume that crowdlending can be faster and simpler. As shown in chapter three, based on a survey to SMEs that applied for a crowdlending funding, Maier found that the platform was evaluated at advantage in speed and simple processes relative to traditional banking (2016a). However, executives of LMEs also demonstrated that a personal contact with the bank advisor is faster and more convenient. This includes loan provisions of 2.5 to over 10 mn€. Although a new approach based on big data and machine

learning might decrease the information asymmetry, the velocity and convenience of crowdlending should be lower than in traditional and relationship banking due to the higher transaction costs. Therefore, this indicator is evaluated as disabling under the status quo. The principle of crowdlending involves a crowd that consists of a large number of investors and a white-label bank, which causes more transactions – also for the company. This could be reduced by focusing on professional investors who invest larger volumes to reduce the number of transactions. However, this still requires more transactions than traditional banking, and thus it should not completely neutralise the disabling effects.

- 2) *Signalling effect*: The results show that executives of LMEs partly consider the publication of fundings as a positive signalling to the financial market in terms of being an innovative company, to possible customers in terms of presenting the company's service or product, or to possible employees especially within the IT industry in terms of being an interesting employer. In contrast, other executives of LMEs consider it as a negative signalling to the financial market because it shows that other financing is not available. This also includes the negative signal if a funding fails. Leboeuf and Schwienbacher argue that if a borrower fails to receive a funding, a second attempt to raise funds is difficult, while a failed attempt for a bank financing is restricted by the bank's confidentiality (2018). In case it is not confidentially managed by a traditional bank, it can have negative consequences for both. For example, in 2002 the then CEO of Deutsche Bank publicly stated that he would not provide equity or debt to the Kirch Group. It was a German media group that went bankrupt two months after the statement. After a long-term legal dispute, in 2014 they agreed on a settlement with a payment of 925 mn€ (Manager magazin, 2016). The executives who consider it as positive signalling to the financial market or customers argued that they would have an opinion in advance whether or not to receive funds, and they would not consider it if they are not confident. This implies it cannot be a substitute if the executive is not confident that the company will receive the funds. Therefore, and since there should be a distortion of the positive relative to the negative signalling effects meaning the negative financing consequences of failing a funding should be higher than the positive signalling effects, this indicator is evaluated as disabling under the status quo. Anonymously publishing, which is partly possible on crowdlending platforms, could be a signal that the executives are not confident or there is unfavourable information of the company, which could attract less investors. One platform mentioned the more information is provided, the quicker the process to find investors. A private placement with selected professional investors and non-disclosure agreements that include the obligation to keep the information secret, which is currently not provided by crowdlending platforms, could

reduce this problem, while this would be contrary to the principle of crowdfunding, and should not completely neutralise the disabling effects.

- 3) *Less regulation and data protection:* The results show that executives of LMEs partly consider it positive that crowdlending platforms are less regulated than traditional banking because they assume that the procedure can be faster. As shown in chapter three, based on a survey to SMEs that applied for a crowdlending platform, Maier found that the platform was evaluated at an advantage concerning the legal procedure relative to traditional banking (2016a). There are also executives who do not consider any effects for borrowers, while there is also the assumption that the interest rates can be higher due to higher risks for the investors. However, as previously shown the procedure should not be faster than in traditional banking due to the transactions required. Additionally, there is a critical consideration of the data protection, which is also discussed by Dorfleitner and Hornuf (2019), and background knowledge about the investors. Therefore, this indicator is evaluated as disabling under the status quo although there are also executives who are indifferent about this aspect. If authorities introduce further regulations, then the disabling effects could potentially be neutralised.

- 4) *Flexibility and transparency:* The results show that executives of LMEs can assume that crowdlending is more flexible and more transparent. As shown in chapter three, based on a survey to SMEs that applied for a crowdlending funding, Maier found that the platform was evaluated at an advantage in flexibility relative to traditional banking (2016a). The results show that also relationship banks can provide transparency by showing the creditworthiness evaluation on a regular basis. In chapter five, it is already mentioned that crowdlending platforms should not be more transparent than traditional banks, and LMEs can also flexibly repay traditional bank loans. A possible increase in flexibility of crowdlending should be limited due to the two-sided marketplace business model, which requires the flexibility of the investors. Therefore, this indicator is evaluated as neutral under the status quo.

- 5) *Risk of idea reproduction:* The results show that executives of LMEs partly do not consider the risk of idea reproduction because they would not publish the details, their business is transparent anyway, or they would publish the ideas anyway to place to the market. However, there is also a critical view because the product of one LME was already reproduced. Additionally, in case of a substitution there would be no traditional bank loans available, also not for sensitive topics related to research and development. Therefore, this

indicator is evaluated as disabling under the status quo. A private placement could reduce this problem but would not completely neutralise it.

- 6) *Collateral requirements*: The results show that the personal guarantee partly required is not inevitably an issue for executives who are not simultaneously the owner of the LME. However, the most executives would not provide a personal guarantee, also not because it is an issue in terms of equal treatment to other financing providers. If executives would be personally liable for the company's liabilities, then they should be participated equally in the opportunities, and thus the principle of the principal-agent relation in terms of the separation of the management from ownership would be reduced. Additionally, the private assets of executives are probably limited and might not cover the losses in case of a default. There is also a platform that does not require a personal guarantee or collateral. This might not be accepted by the investors in the long-term due to the higher risk especially under the moral hazard aspect. LMEs partly receive bank loans without providing a collateral while relationship banks have soft information. If a new approach based on big data and machine learning could produce soft information that is equal to relationship banking, then the effects can be neutralised. If the investors require a collateral, either the platform could include the service of evaluating and in case of a default liquidating the pledged asset and distributing the resulting funds to the investors, or it could assign it to another party. This could also neutralise the disabling effect.
- 7) *Limited funding volume*: The results show that the funding volume limit of 2.5 mn€ is not inevitably an issue as long as more fundings can simultaneously be created. However, the most executives critically consider the limit because they need financing volumes up to 150 mn€. Since a volume of 150 mn€ would require 60 crowdlending fundings, it would cause inadequate transaction costs. If the limit of the funding volume and the volume per investor would increase, the transactions costs could be reduced. A focus on professional investors could not completely neutralise the effects. Additionally, the latter is against the principles of crowdfunding that involves a crowd that consists of a large number of investors.
- 8) *Limited maturity*: The results show that LMEs partly have long-term fundings between 10 and 15 years. This implies that crowdlending, which has a maximum maturity of five years, cannot be a substitute under the status quo. It might be difficult to find investors for longer terms especially if there is no secondary market. In case of the establishment of a secondary market and a focus on professional investors this might be neutralised.

- 9) *Interest rate and fee*: The results show that the current interest rates and fees of the best ratings of crowdlending platforms should not be attractive for LMEs as demonstrated by the executives. Therefore, this indicator is evaluated as disabling under the status quo. In contrast, as shown in chapter three, based on a survey to SMEs that applied for a crowdlending funding, Maier found that the platform was slightly evaluated at an advantage in interest rate and fee relative to traditional banking (2016a). The profit formula advantages and disadvantages of crowdlending platforms relative to traditional banks, which should partly influence the interest rates and fees, are illustrated in chapter five. If a new approach based on big data and machine learning could produce soft information that is equal to or higher than in relationship banking, and the platforms have more economies of scale effects while their business is increasing and they are consolidating, then the disabling effects of higher interest rates and fees might be neutralised.
- 10) *Unknown topic*: The results show that it can be an issue for executives of LMEs that crowdlending is an unknown topic. This includes that the executive board has to be convinced and the contractual construction is more difficult to understand because more than two parties are involved. Therefore, this indicator is evaluated as disabling under the status quo, while it could be potentially neutralised in the future if crowdlending is more established. The latter might be supported by an introduction of further regulations.
- 11) *Product or service feedback*: The results show that executives of LMEs do not value the product or service feedback of the investors. As argued by Agrawal et al., if the investors are individual investors without a professional background, the additional value to the company such as industry knowledge, relationships, and status are limited (2014). Since feedback does not have to be realised by the executives, it is evaluated as neutral under the status quo.
- 12) *Risk customers as investors*: The results show that executives of LMEs can critically consider that the customers can be simultaneously the investors. This implies that if the company has difficult times and cannot repay the loan or interest, it can lose its customers. Therefore, this indicator is evaluated as disabling under the status quo. This could be neutralised by focusing solely on professional investors.

- 13) *Financing structure for sale*: The results show that executives of LMEs can critically consider the financing structure of crowdlending if the owner aims to sell the company including to go public, while a more transparent and stable structure would support the procedure. Although one LME currently aims to acquire a target company that is financed by crowdfunding, this indicator is evaluated as disabling under the status quo. This target company has less than ten employees, while for LMEs it might be different.
- 14) *Risk platform disappears*: The results show that executives can critically consider the risk that the platform cannot be established and disappears again. Therefore, this indicator is evaluated as disabling under the status quo, while in future it might be neutralised if crowdlending platforms are established and consolidated.

The results differ regarding the circumstances under which executives of LMEs would request a funding through crowdlending platforms. The results show that executives of LMEs partly reject crowdlending unless there is no traditional bank loan or other financing source available. There are also executives who would attempt crowdlending if the economic conditions are equal to bank loans and the administrative effort is not significantly higher, while there are also executives who would solely attempt crowdlending if the economic conditions are better. The rejection could be an indication of a disruptive innovation as illustrated in chapter two. However, the results of this evaluation indicate that crowdlending cannot substitute traditional and relationship banking, which disables a disruptive innovation.

6.5 Crowdfunding as substitute for traditional banking

6.5.1 Description of results

Three categories were defined. The first, C12, describes advantages and the second, C13, disadvantages of crowdfunding relative to traditional banking including traditional mezzanine instruments. Since crowdlending and crowdfunding have common characteristics and the executives interviewed had limited time available, certain aspects were not re-discussed. However, one aspect has been mentioned again by executive3. C12S1 was inductively defined and means that the publication to the investors is a positive signalling effect relative to traditional mezzanine. Executive3 said, "Bank financing is more likely to take place in the backyard. Here I am completely open and transparent. That might be a disadvantage, but I believe that the advantages outweigh. From my personal point of view that one just goes with the time" (pa. 76).

The three sub-categories of C13 were inductively defined. C13S1 means a possible influence on the company's business is negatively considered. Executive1 mentioned that due to the mezzanine instruments, it is more extensive in terms of influence (pa. 62). He is convinced that the LME is on the right path, and thus it is logical to him to keep out an external influence. "At least an external influence of persons, of institutions that have neither a clue of the own business, of the daily routine, nor an overview. And therefore, to keep the distance as far as possible" (I1, pa. 62).

C13S2 means that the economic conditions are a disadvantage or even an exclusion criterion. Executive2 mentioned that the LME's overdraft financing without the provision of a collateral is below 1% (pa. 64). He said, "and that is why I mean, there is every form of financing and with my credit rating, I do not have to resort to other markets where to which other risk structures are related" (I2, pa. 64).

C13S3 means that crowdinvesting is related to a higher administrative effort. In this context executive4 said, "It will be a high effort from the structuring. Because it is just a mixture of equity and debt capital" (pa. 68).

C14 describes under what circumstances the executive would request a funding through crowdinvesting platforms, and whether crowdlending or crowdinvesting is preferred. Four sub-categories were deductively defined. C14S1 means that financing through crowdinvesting is preferred over crowdlending. Executive3 prefers crowdinvesting over crowdlending since he prefers mezzanine instruments over bank loans (pa. 70). He thinks that he has more flexibility in terms of balance sheet structuring (I3, pa. 72). Executive5 would consider crowdinvesting only as last option if no other financing is available (see more in sub-category four). However, he would prefer crowdinvesting over crowdlending due to the entrepreneurial involvement but only one that is based on an adequate symmetry of opportunities and risks (I5, pa. 83-92). Executive8 thinks that larger companies generally have a problem to work with so many parties (pa. 43). He said, "Larger companies usually seek [...] two or three different strategic partners in the ownership structure. And then, in principle, they may have one or two funding partners who play an active or passive role at the end of the day" (I8, pa. 43). However, since crowdinvesting is more similar to the concept of private equity like the participation in an increase of the company value, he prefers crowdinvesting over crowdlending.

C14S2 means that financing through crowdinvesting is preferred over bank loans. Executive3 said, "It is at least an equivalent alternative, if not a bit preferred alternative" (pa. 74). As already mentioned, executive3 prefers mezzanine over bank loans. The reason is more flexibility in terms

of conditions and balance sheet structuring. However, the decisive criteria are the economic conditions, and the financing structure must fit the project (I3, pa. 68).

C14S3 means that financing through crowdlending is preferred over crowdinvesting. Executive7 assumes that crowdinvesting is more difficult to understand including the related risks and interests (pa. 98). Therefore, he would have to invest more effort to exactly understand the topic. He always applies the approach that he wants to understand the topic by himself before he does something like that. Executive10 prefers to keep the profits in the company as long as possible (pa. 80). He said, "We know what we can [...]. That is certainly selfish. But then you better take it yourself" (I10, pa. 80). Additionally, he assumes that it is purely a mathematical decision to pay only a fixed interest or participation in turnover or profit (I10, pa. 82).

C14S4 means crowdinvesting would not be used or only as last option in case no other financing is available. Executive1 said, "You only do that if there is no other way" (pa. 62). He wants to avoid some kind of turnover or profit participation and the external influence. For executive2, it is "definitely no" option (pa. 90). Executive4 said, "And for me it would be only a case if I would get no capital outside" (pa. 68). Executive5 would also consider crowdinvesting as the last option (pa. 82). He would prefer to find a wealthy person in the industry who has money, expertise, and contacts. For example, he mentioned someone who is known in the industry and has helpful contacts. He said, "Before I would go down with strangers on a bidding process or a platform, I would rather search for a person who has high liquid stocks, who has a certain personality" (I5, pa. 82). Executive6 thinks that crowdinvesting does not fit the company (pa. 46). Executive9 argues that the LME has already an equity ratio about 50%, and she said, "whether we have 50% or 50% plus x now does not matter. Therefore, this is not a possibility for us because it is too expensive, too small and too cumbersome. That does not pay off" (pa. 86).

6.5.2 Discussion and conclusion

The objective is to critically explore and evaluate to which extent the service of crowdinvesting platforms is a substitute for traditional banking services (primarily relative to traditional bank loans because the LMEs do not or did not use traditional mezzanine, which is also an indication that it is not a widespread financing instrument) to LMEs in Germany.

The categories previously illustrated contain indicators that enable or disable the substitution of traditional and relationship banking by crowdinvesting platforms. Since crowdlending and crowdinvesting have common characteristics, the indicators transaction costs including velocity

and convenience, less regulation, risk of idea reproduction, limited funding volume, unknown topic, product or service feedback, risk customers as investors, financing structure for sale, and risk that the platform disappears (that are previously evaluated in crowdlending) can be transmitted to crowdinvesting, especially under the aspect of substituting traditional bank loans. Additionally, there are further indicators that are discussed and evaluated in the following. The results are summarised in table 26.

Table 26: Evaluation of crowdinvesting as substitute for relationship and traditional banking

Indicator s = status quo; p = potential change for future if any	Disabling	Neutral	Enabling
1 Signalling effect	s	-	-
2 Economic conditions	s	-	-
3 Mezzanine instrument related transaction costs	s	-	-
Transmitted from crowdlending	-	-	-
4 Transaction costs including velocity and convenience	s	-	-
5 Less regulation and data protection	s	p	-
6 Risk of idea reproduction	s	-	-
7 Limited funding volume	s	-	-
8 Unknown topic	s	p	-
9 Product or service feedback	-	s	-
10 Risk customers as investors	s	p	-
11 Financing structure for sale	s	-	-
12 Risk platform disappears	s	p	-

Source: Own source

- 1) *Signalling effect*: As also shown in the previous chapter, executives of LMEs can consider the publication of the funding as a positive signalling effect to the financial market in terms of being an innovative company. However, as previously discussed, since executives also critically consider the publication and the negative financing consequences of not receiving a funding should be higher than the positive signalling effects, this indicator is evaluated as disabling the substitution of traditional bank loans and traditional mezzanine under the status quo. Due to the prospectus obligation, there might also be negative signalling effects in program mezzanine, but which cannot be related solely to one company if the funding fails.

- 2) *Economic conditions*: The results show that executives of LMEs can critically consider the economic conditions of crowdfinancing. As shown in chapter two, the capital cost rate of mezzanine is higher than of debt. Therefore, this indicator is evaluated as disabling the substitution of traditional bank loans under the status quo.

- 3) *Mezzanine instrument related transaction costs*: The results show that executives of LMEs can critically consider the administrative effort because of the usage of mezzanine instruments. Since mezzanine instruments have characteristics of both equity and debt and can include a participation in the turnover, profit, and increase in the company value, the ex-ante and ex-post transaction costs should be higher than of traditional bank loans. Therefore, this indicator is evaluated as disabling the substitution of traditional bank loans under the status quo.

The results show that executives of LMEs partly reject crowdfinancing unless there are no other financing sources available. The chapter that consists of a description of the financing instruments that are used by the LMEs includes rationales why executives of LMEs do not want to use mezzanine instruments. Additional rationales are avoiding the participation in the success of the company and conveying no advantages in terms of increasing the equity ratio because it is already on a high level. It could be expected that executives who prefer debt over mezzanine also prefer crowdlending over crowdfinancing, while executives who prefer mezzanine over debt prefer also crowdfinancing over crowdlending. However, the results show that executives can prefer debt over mezzanine while preferring crowdfinancing over crowdlending. Additionally, executives can prefer mezzanine over debt while preferring crowdlending over crowdfinancing. This supports the indication that the rationales of executives of LMEs differ from the assumptions of the static trade-off and pecking order theory. The rejection of crowdfinancing could be an indication of a disruptive innovation. However, the results of this evaluation indicate that crowdfinancing cannot substitute traditional and relationship banking, which disables a disruptive innovation.

6.6 Factoring platforms as substitute for traditional banking

6.6.1 Description of results

Three categories were defined. The first, C15, describes advantages and the second, C16, disadvantages of factoring platforms relative to traditional banking especially to traditional factoring. No advantages were mentioned.

C16S1 means that the procedure of factoring platforms is related to a higher administrative effort. Two executives who use factoring for their companies mentioned that the administrative effort would be too high. Executive2 said, “After all, I do not have time to see each time if I can sell a claim through a platform. This must be a well-rehearsed process. You set that up once and then it has to repeat itself permanently in the routine” (pa. 98). Executive4 said, “And now we really have a very simple system. We download the open items twice a week from our SAP system via a programmed export. I mean, they also get the individual items. That is also the case. But the platform is based on the fact that I pluck lots of individuals out of it” (pa. 76). The LME has about 10,000 invoices a month with an average volume between 40 and 50 € (I4, pa. 74).

C16S2 means that the publication of the usage of factoring causes a negative signalling. Executive1 said, “Ultimately, this is always a signal that the company is doing badly” (pa. 64). He aims for the opposite, to send a signal of a good financial situation (I1, pa. 65). In this context executive3 said, “That would be such an argument or a theoretical disadvantage for me. Whether that would be an exclusion criterion, I do not think so” (pa. 84).

C16S3 means that the economic conditions are a disadvantage. Executive2 argues that the fees of the factoring platforms are too high if they are projected for an annual basis (pa. 96-98). He thinks a fee of 0.9% of the account receivable might be acceptable. As already mentioned, LME4 is currently charged for its factoring including the hedging of the default risk between 1.2% and 1.5% per annum (pa. 14). The executive assumes that the factoring platforms cannot offer such conditions (I4, pa. 14-16).

C17 describes under what circumstances the executive would request a funding through a factoring platform. Four sub-categories were deductively defined. C17S1 means that factoring platforms would be used in case the conditions are equal to traditional factoring. Executive8 said, “I would not rule it out in principle, I have to say very clearly. [...] There are industries where factoring is not an issue at all. [...] If you go into the classic German mechanical engineering middle class today and you are doing factoring, then you have a bad market reputation. [...] If you go into the high technology today, factoring is normal” (pa. 69). He thinks it depends on the economic situation. If the default rate is low and the terms of conditions are good, then the need for factoring is lower. He would try it through a platform if he would like to use factoring (I8, pa. 73). Executive10 would also try it through a platform (pa. 86). However, he questions the sense of factoring. He argues that factoring is only needed if there is an extreme growth which cannot be covered by itself, and he does not prefer such growth (I10, pa. 94).

C17S2 means that factoring platforms would be only used in case the conditions are better than traditional factoring or bank loans. Executive2 said, “The factoring rate would have to be significantly below the borrowing rate which I pay to the bank” (pa. 96). He means that the rate on the factoring platform should be at 0.9% per annum.

C17S3 means that factoring platforms are preferred over traditional factoring. Executive3 would prefer factoring platforms over traditional factoring if he would like to use factoring (pa. 88). He assumes that the way through a platform is related to less administrative effort (I3, pa. 88).

C17S4 means that factoring is not used or only used if other instruments are not available. Executive1 said, “I would not do that. For the moment I completely exclude that” (pa. 64). Executive5 thinks that factoring could be used to save the costs of the internal department that handle the accounts receivable and to quickly receive the money if it would be important (pa. 94). However, he argues that the cost savings of the internal department could not be realised since he would need someone who handles the related procedure on the platform. Therefore, he would not do it through a platform. Regarding the general usage of factoring, executive6 said, “Then our liquidity cover would have to be so low that we worry about such things. Then we would have completely different problems” (pa. 50). However, if there is no other option available than the usage of factoring, then she would do it also through a platform. However, prior to that she would like to take a deeper look at the terms, confidentiality, and reliability on the platforms (I6, pa. 52-54).

C17S5 means that factoring would be individually used in case of accounts receivable that have a high volume or risk. Although executive5 first mentioned he would not use it, he later said, “Maybe with a high account receivable where we cannot get further. And in other cases, if we have a 30 million account receivable, I would not take the risk” (pa. 94).

6.6.2 Discussion and conclusion

The objective is to critically explore and evaluate to which extent the service of factoring platforms is a substitute for traditional banking services especially traditional factoring to LMEs in Germany. The categories previously illustrated contain indicators that enable or disable the substitution of traditional and relationship banking by factoring platforms. The results are summarised in table 27.

Table 27: Evaluation of factoring platforms as substitute for traditional factoring

Indicator s = status quo; p = potential change for future if any	Disabling	Neutral	Enabling
1 Signalling effect	-	s	-
2 Economic conditions	s	p	-
3 Transaction costs	s	p	-

Source: Own source

- 1) *Signalling effect*: The results show that executives of LMEs can critically consider the publication of the intention to use factoring. They assume that this implies a negative signal to the market that the company has financing difficulties. The signal can be sent to potential investors and to the customers. In case of the auction-based and pre-agreed financing mechanism, the information should be more published than in traditional factoring even though solely institutional investors are involved. However, on the other two matching and financing mechanisms, the information should be as private as in traditional factoring. Staroßom also argues that notification factoring can be a negative signal to the market (2013). However, on the platforms non-notification factoring is partly possible. Therefore, this indicator is evaluated as neutral under the status quo.

- 2) *Economic conditions*: The results show that the current economic conditions on factoring platforms should not be attractive for LMEs as demonstrated by the executives. Therefore, this indicator is evaluated as disabling under the status quo. If a new approach based on big data and machine learning could produce soft information that is equal to or higher than in relationship banking, and the platforms have more economies of scale effects while their business is increasing and they are consolidating, then the disabling effects of higher fees might be neutralised.

- 3) *Transaction costs*: The results show that executives of LMEs critically consider the administrative effort of financing individual accounts receivable. In these cases, the number of annual transactions varies between 1,500 and 350,000. Due to the higher transaction costs of financing individual accounts receivable or auctions of total portfolios which also should cause higher transactions costs than a general agreement, this indicator is evaluated as disabling under the status quo. If factoring platforms would provide general agreements, then it could potentially neutralise the disabling effects. The financing of individual accounts receivable might be interesting for accounts receivable that have high volumes and/or high risks, but it cannot substitute traditional factoring.

The results differ regarding to the circumstances under which executives of LMEs would request a funding through a factoring platform. Executives of LMEs partly reject factoring platforms unless there are no other financing sources available. There are also executives who would attempt factoring platforms only if the economic conditions are equal or better. The rejection could be an indication of a disruptive innovation as illustrated in chapter two. The results of this evaluation indicate that under the status quo factoring platforms cannot substitute traditional factoring, which disables a disruptive innovation. However, there are potential adjustments of the business model of factoring platforms that can neutralise the disabling effects.

6.7 Overall discussion and conclusion

The objective was to critically explore and evaluate to which extent the service of financing fintechs is a substitute for traditional banking services to LMEs in Germany. This is relevant in order to evaluate the disruptive innovation threat of financing fintechs that provide services to SMEs in Germany to traditional banks. Again, according to the disruptive innovation theory, incumbents often fail competing disruptive innovation because they do not consider it as disruption since the entrants firstly serve low-end or non-customers. However, as their performance increases, they finally serve mainstream customers and disrupt the incumbents (Christensen & Raynor, 2003). As described in chapter four, LMEs can be considered as mainstream customers of traditional banks. However, a disruptive innovation is solely critical if the entrant's service or product is a substitute for the incumbent's service or product (Christensen & Raynor, 2003; Rafii & Kampas, 2002).

As shown by the research gap which is illustrated in chapter three, this is the first study which explored and evaluated to which extent the service of financing fintechs is a substitute for traditional banking services to LMEs in Germany. Based on the results, indicators were identified and evaluated as disabling the substitution or as neutral. No indicator was evaluated as enabling the substitution. Therefore, the results show that in the status quo the services of crowdlending, crowdinvesting, and factoring platforms cannot be considered as a substitute for traditional banking services for LMEs in Germany. For crowdlending and crowdinvesting there are no potential adjustments which could substitute the traditional banking services in the future, while factoring platforms might have the potential to neutralise the disabling effects. However, neutralising the effects does not imply enabling the substitution. The final evaluation of the disruptive innovation threat is illustrated in the next chapter.

6.8 Limitations

The limitations of the method are already described in chapter four. First, the results of the interviews are influenced by the researcher due to the subjectivity of the method. This might include bias. Second, the sample definition by the researcher might include bias. Third, the experience of the researcher gained is limited which might have had an influence on the questions asked in the interviews. Fourth, the results of the qualitative content analysis are subjectively influenced as described in chapter 4.2.5. This might include bias. Fifth, although the theoretical saturation was achieved by the conduction of ten interviews, the possibility to generalise the results is limited. The sample definition does not include a probability approach as in quantitative research that is representative for a total population. Sixth, solely companies in Bavaria were selected. Although the results are not representative for Bavaria due to the application of a qualitative approach, it might be that in other federal states executives have different views. Seventh, the executives can be considered as experts regarding financing issues, but they have no or limited experience with financing fintechns. This might have an influence on the financing preferences. Eighth, it might be that the executives did not express the full truth especially in case of unfavourable information for the company, although anonymity of the data was agreed on.

7 Overall conclusions

The purpose of this chapter is to present the overall conclusion. This consists of the synthesis of the previous results to qualitatively evaluate the disruptive innovation threat of financing fintechs, i.e. crowdlending, crowdinvesting, and factoring platforms that provide services to SMEs in Germany to traditional banks. Additionally, it includes the restatement of the research aim and questions to ensure that the aim is achieved and the questions are answered, the illustration of the contribution to knowledge, the reflection of the used methods and limitations, and the outlook for future research.

7.1 Synthesis of findings – evaluation of the disruptive innovation threat

The overall aim of this research is to critically examine the potential disruptive innovation threat of financing fintechs, i.e. crowdlending, crowdinvesting, and factoring platforms that provide services to SMEs in Germany to traditional banks.

The disruption could occur if the following incremental stages are successfully completed. As explained in chapter two, for the ex-ante evaluation the stages of Rafii and Kampas (2002) are adjusted. First, financing fintechs enter a foothold market by serving non-customers or low-end customers. Second, traditional banks do not react. At this stage, the identification of whether or not the innovation is disruptive should be more difficult for traditional banks than at a later stage. The reaction costs of traditional banks can also be lower, while there is also the risk that they invest although it is not a disruptive innovation. The reaction costs consist of acquiring a financing fintech or establishing a financing fintech service by itself – either an integration into the existing organisation or the establishment of a separate company. Third, financing fintechs move up-market and enter the mainstream market by overcoming entry barriers. This includes adjustments of their business models. Fourth, traditional banks do not react. The identification of whether or not the innovation is disruptive should be more precise than at stage two, while the reaction costs should be higher especially due to the network effects. The risk that traditional banks invest although it is not a disruptive innovation should be lower. Fifth, mainstream customers switch if the service is a substitute for the service of traditional banks and if their switching costs are not substantial. Sixth, traditional banks do not react, and finally, they are displaced to some degree which can range from minor revenue losses to liquidation. This depends on whether or not traditional banks have a portfolio of different business models.

The results of the narrative literature review and the documentary research indicate that financing fintechs have already taken a market entry foothold by serving low-end and non-customers, while the reaction of traditional banks is different. Some banks acquired financing fintechs, others are

more cautious about investing in financing fintechs. However, the most banks do have solely a cooperation. The stage mainstream market entry might be partly reached because the results of the expert interviews show that executives of LMEs would attempt the services of financing fintechs under different circumstances. Potential adjustments of the business model of financing fintechs which could support reaching the market entry stage are discussed in the previous chapter. The reaction of traditional banks might not change. However, the results show also that under the status quo the service of financing fintechs cannot be considered as a substitute for traditional banking services, and thus financing fintechs likely do not reach the stage of mainstream customers switching. Therefore, it cannot be a critical disruptive threat. For crowdlending and crowdinvesting there are no potential adjustments which could substitute the traditional banking services in the future, while factoring platforms might have the potential to neutralise the disabling effects. However, neutralising the effects does not imply enabling the substitution. The evaluation is illustrated by figure 52.

Figure 52: Final evaluation of disruptive innovation threat based on six stages

Source: Own illustration based on adjusted input of Rafii and Kampas 2002

The results show that due to structural reasons in the business model of financing fintechs and the services required from executives of LMEs in Germany, the disruption is limited. There are competitive two-sided marketplace business models in non-financing markets as shown by the

market values of Booking Holdings and Airbnb. The business models of these platforms are more scalable than business models that have the assets on the company's balance sheet (traditional value chains – from left to right). However, two-sided marketplace business models in financing markets can be different. Higher transaction costs and higher information asymmetries disable the substitution. Additionally, traditional banking is more private, which is an advantage because there is no risk of sending negative signals. Financing decisions of executives can have a long-term impact on the success of the company, while decisions in other markets do not have that impact. Furthermore, due to the two-sided marketplace business model, the reduction of the adverse selection and moral hazard is also relevant for the borrowers. Although financing fintechs partly reduce the adverse selection and moral hazard, the reduction should be higher in traditional banking due to relationship banking and a higher motivation because of the risk transformation of traditional banks. The disabling effects can be partly reduced if financing fintechs acquire a banking licence. However, then financing fintechs become a bank. This implies a traditional value chain, which moves from left to right. For example, taking deposits of savers and providing loans to borrowers. This supports the assumption of Navaretti et al. that the business models of financing fintechs will gradually converge towards traditional banking (2018). A direct bank would partly reduce the problems, while it could not completely substitute traditional banking as executives of LMEs primarily prefer relationship banking and physical contacts.

The Basel Committee on Banking Supervision defined five strategic scenarios for the impact of fintechs on traditional banks as illustrated in chapter three (2017). The results of this research imply that the occurrence of the scenario three (financial services become more modularised and traditional banks and the new providers have both customer relations), four (traditional banks are solely in the background while the new providers have the customer relations), and five (there is no need for balance sheet intermediation while the new providers directly interact with customers) are specifically for financing fintechs unlikely due to structural reasons in the business model of financing fintechs and the services required from executives of LMEs. In case traditional banks implement possible technology advantages as big data and machine learning, the occurrence of scenario one (traditional banks are kept as major provider by adopting their business models) is increased. Although financing fintechs with a banking licence could not completely substitute traditional banking, traditional banks should observe the financing fintech market to avoid scenario two (traditional banks are replaced by new providers that acquire a banking licence).

Factoring platforms might have the most potential to be disruptive for traditional banks. Therefore, traditional banks should observe whether factoring platforms move up-market by serving LMEs. Due to the high scale required and the network effects, and thus a possible winner-takes-it-all

result, the number of platforms will decrease in future. The consolidations might also be cross-product, -country, and -customer group. If there is finally one platform that controls the market and obtains a banking licence, then this would increase the potential threat to traditional banks. Therefore, the observation of whether financing fintechs consolidate should not be neglected. Furthermore, the observation of whether bigtechs acquire financing fintechs or establish financing services as fintechs should not be neglected. Bigtechs might be more disruptive because they should have more customers and more customer data to enable network effects, should already apply approaches like big data and machine learning (that could produce soft information and might be an advantage for the future), and should have more capital available.

7.2 Restatement of aim and research questions

The overall aim of this research was to critically examine the potential disruptive innovation threat of financing fintechs, i.e. crowdlending, crowdinvesting, and factoring platforms that provide services to SMEs in Germany to traditional banks. Based on the aim, the following three questions were defined:

- 1) What defines the business model of financing fintechs, i.e. crowdlending, crowdinvesting, and factoring platforms that provide services to SMEs in Germany?
- 2) In a critically exploratory and evaluative way, to which extent is the service of financing fintechs a substitute for traditional banking services to SMEs in Germany?
- 3) To what extent are financing fintechs that provide services to SMEs in Germany a disruptive innovation threat to traditional banks?

The research question one was approached by the conduction of a documentary research that consisted of the material of 21 different web-presences of financing fintechs and the application of a qualitative content analysis. The results are shown in chapter five. The research question two was primarily approached by the conduction of ten semi-structured expert interviews with executive managers of SMEs and the application of a qualitative content analysis. The results are shown in chapter six. The research question three was approached by the synthesis of the results of the previous questions and a qualitative evaluation of the disruptive innovation threat. The results are shown in chapter five to seven.

7.3 Contribution to knowledge and application areas

Based on the results of the narrative literature review, a research gap was identified that is illustrated in chapter three. The research gap was one motivation of the researcher to conduct this research, and thus to contribute to knowledge, as the contribution to knowledge closes the research gap. This research contributes to knowledge in three different ways, which is summarised on a high-level by figure 53.

Figure 53: Illustration of contribution to knowledge

Source: Own illustration

The first contribution is an in-depth understanding of the business models of financing fintechs, i.e. crowdlending, crowdinvesting, and factoring platforms that provide specifically services to SMEs in Germany. As mentioned, the business model is essential for the evaluation of the disruptive innovation of entrants (Christensen & Raynor, 2003; Johnson, Christensen, & Kagermann, 2008). The study of Hagedorn and Pinkwart split the general process of crowdinvesting in Germany into seven phases (2016), while Beck defined five similar phases (2017). However, these studies do not include all relevant aspects of a two-sided marketplace business model, and for the other two segments, there are no similar studies. The legal information for crowdlending and crowdinvesting in Germany from the BaFin also does not provide an in-depth understanding of the platforms' business models (2017a, 2017b). In contrast, the results of this study include a profile matrix for each segment with categories that were deductively and inductively defined, and the categories were split into the different parties – borrower, investors, and platform – of a two-sided marketplace business model. The deductively defined categories contribute to knowledge in terms of novel content in this context, while the categories that were inductively defined contribute to knowledge in terms of novel aspects that were not previously considered. Furthermore, the

business model of each segment was evaluated along the four interrelated components of a business model, i.e. customer value proposition (CVP), key resources, key processes, and profit formula, and along their disruptive innovation threat to traditional banks.

The contribution can be further split into academic and practical contribution while the former consists of several aspects: First, the results can be used for further studies – for example, for a survey to LMEs in Germany to test the outcome of this study that the services of financing fintechs cannot be a substitute for traditional banking services. For the conduction of a survey, the pre-requirement is an in-depth understanding of the business model of financing fintechs. Second, the results are from a point in time analysis, therefore, the same method can be applied to analyse whether the business models have been changed. Third, the same method can be applied to analyse the business model of financing fintechs in other countries. Regarding the practical contribution, traditional banks and consultancy companies can use the results to evaluate the potential disruptive innovation threat of financing fintechs to traditional banks.

The second contribution is an in-depth understanding that for executives of LMEs the service of financing fintechs, i.e. crowdlending, crowdinvesting, and factoring platforms cannot be a substitute for traditional banking services. Based on the results of the expert interviews with executive managers and the application of a qualitative content analysis, qualitative indicators were identified and evaluated as disabling the substitution or as neutral. Regarding the Delphi-Study of Blohm et al., the authors argue that crowdfunding is no substitute for traditional banking services in the status quo, while for the future they are not sure whether it becomes a mass product which substitutes traditional banking services (2015). In contrast, the results of this study show it cannot be a substitute. The survey of Maier shows that SMEs evaluated crowdlending at advantage, especially the factors speed, simple process, and flexibility (2016a, b). In contrast, the results of this study show more disadvantages for crowdlending platforms including the factors speed and convenience. Regarding the data collection and analysis of four crowdinvesting platforms by Dorfleitner et al., the authors argue that due to the low turnover and low funding volumes, crowdinvesting is more interesting for small companies, which are too risky for traditional banks (2014). This is similar to the results of this study that crowdinvesting cannot be a substitute for traditional banking services.

The academic contribution is that the results can be used for further studies – for the mentioned survey to LMEs in Germany, the results of this study can be used to define hypotheses which can be tested in the survey. The practical contribution is that traditional banks can have a deeper understanding of the attitude of executives of LMEs towards financing fintechs relative to

traditional banking. Again, incumbents often quantify the size of the market rather than understand the customer (Christensen et al., 2015, 2004). This could help traditional banks to better understand their customers.

The third contribution to knowledge consists of a synthesis of the results of the primary research. Due to structural reasons in the business model of financing fintechs and the services required from executives of LMEs, they cannot be a substitute for traditional banking, and thus the disruptive innovation threat is limited. The establishment of two-sided marketplace business models in financing markets especially for LMEs in Germany is limited. This outcome is similar to the study of Navaretti et al. without empirical data that mainly due to the adverse selection, moral hazard, and the fee-based revenue model, it is unlikely that financing fintechs will displace traditional banks in the long-term (2018). However, this study consists of empirical data and the application of the disruptive innovation theory. Based on a network analysis on contractual link data between banks and fintechs, Brandl and Hornuf found that banks prefer a strategic partnership with fintechs instead of an integration (2017), and Dorfleitner et al. found that the most banks do not consider fintechs as a threat but rather as a supplement and as a chance to drive innovation and digitisation (2016). However, these studies did not consider the disruptive innovation theory, which implies that the incumbents do not consider the entrants as threat, which finally can lead to the disruption.

The academic contribution is as follows: first, the results can be used for further studies in the field of strategic management related to fintechs. Second, the methodology and methods can be used to examine the potential disruptive innovation threat of other companies – for example, for the evaluation of the disruptive innovation threat of bigtechs to traditional banks. Since fintechs have a multi-disciplinary nature, which means it can include topics from finance, information technology, law, entrepreneurship, business and management, economics, and strategic management, the results can be used also in other academic fields.

The practical contribution consists of several aspects: First, the results show that the actions of traditional banks can be limited because there is no critical disruptive innovation threat. Nevertheless, banks should observe the market. Second, financing fintechs can include the results to define their strategy. In order to move up-market to serve mainstream customers, a two-sided marketplace business model is difficult in financing markets. Third, for consultants who strategically advise traditional banks or financing fintechs, the results can be used. Fourth, it can help the regulatory authorities to define certain steering mechanisms to reduce the risk of certain parties or to support market participation. As the Financial Stability Board argues that “technology-enabled innovation in financial services (FinTech) is developing rapidly. With its emergence, there will be

both opportunities and risks to financial stability that policymakers, regulators, supervisors and overseers should consider” (2017, p. 1). Therefore, “authorities should consider developing their own capacity to access existing and new sources of information” (Financial Stability Board, 2017, p. 2). The addressed macro financial risk of the Financial Stability Board that the funding flows on financing fintechs become too large and unstable (2017), can be reduced based on the results of this study. In contrast to the other mentioned studies, the results of this study show that financing fintechs currently serve small companies with lower volumes while the up-market movement to larger companies is limited. Therefore, although there are high growth rates in the market, the market with larger companies, which should have a higher economic impact in terms of market size, is limited. However, this also supports the arguments from the European Commission (2016), that financing fintechs could increase the access to financial sources for SMEs that have difficulties to access traditional financial sources, which could increase the overall efficiency in the economy. However, due to the two-sided marketplace business model of financing fintechs, this also increases the risk that investors who invest their funds on platforms make losses due to an inadequate risk evaluation, which should decrease the efficiency of the economy. Therefore, for the regulatory authorities, it is essential to observe the market and to increase the investor protection, especially for individual investors with little financial background, if necessary.

During the research work, the research project and the results of the business model analysis were presented at different conferences. The first poster was presented at the MAXQDA international conference in Berlin (Germany) in February 2019 and the second at the UWS conference in Scotland in June 2019. Furthermore, the results of the business model analysis were shown in a presentation at the CARF (Controlling, Accounting, Risk, Finance) conference in Luzern (Switzerland) in September 2019 and a paper was published in the conference proceedings. In addition, future publications of the results of this research are intended in two different journals. Subject to the successful completion of the review process, it is planned to publish the results of the business model analysis and expert interviews of crowdlending and factoring platforms.

7.4 Reflection of used methods and limitations

A qualitative multi-method approach was selected as the suitable approach based upon methodological considerations to achieve the overall research aim. Since it is a strategic topic and financing fintechs are a new phenomenon, an in-depth understanding of the theme under study is more appropriate than an approach that tests pre-defined hypotheses.

A narrative literature review was selected as the suitable method based upon methodological considerations to provide a wide overview of financing fintech related topics. The wide overview could be used as a basis for the primary research. In contrast, the focus of a systematic literature review is solely on one specific subject, which would be less appropriate to answer the research questions.

A documentary research that consisted of the material of the financing fintechs' web-presences and the application of a qualitative content analysis was selected as the suitable method based upon methodological considerations to appraise the business model. In contrast, a quantitative approach would not provide an in-depth understanding of the business models.

The conduction of expert interviews was selected as the suitable method based upon methodological considerations to explore and evaluate to which extent the service of financing fintechs is a substitute for traditional banking services to LMEs in Germany. Even though a quantitative approach includes a statistical representation, it would be less appropriate to understand in depth to which extent the service is a substitute.

Another limitation that is not already mentioned is that this research concerns only the traditional financing services of traditional banks to SMEs and LMEs and not to other customers such as consumers or institutional customers. This implies that it concerns only a part of the corporate banking services and no other business models of traditional banks such as retail banking. Furthermore, there is no differentiation of traditional banks. There can be differences between large and small traditional banks and between private, cooperative, and public saving banks especially under the aspect of the production of soft information due to different hierarchical organisational structures. Furthermore, as already mentioned, since the countries have their own regulatory requirements, the results are only valid for Germany.

As already mentioned, the disruptive innovation theory can be considered as a more radical approach in comparison to other strategic theories. There are also criticisms about the theory. Practitioners can have issues in identifying a disruptive innovation threat ex ante to be able to formulate and implement a timely strategy (Huesig, Hipp, & Dowling, 2005; Keller & Huesig, 2009). King and Baatartogtokh assume that the theory provides warnings of what may happen, but they criticise that the theory is not widely quantitatively tested in academic research (2015). Additionally, there might be further approaches to evaluate the disruptive innovation threat of financing fintechs to traditional banks. However, independent of the disruptive innovation theory, this research provided an in-depth understanding of the business models of financing fintechs that

provide services to SMEs in Germany, and the results of the expert interviews with executives of LMEs show that financing fintechs cannot be a substitute for traditional banking services. Due to structural reasons in the business model of financing fintechs and the services required from executives of LMEs, the strategic impact of financing fintechs on traditional banks is limited.

7.5 Outlook for further research

Recommendations for further research are as follows. First, as mentioned, the business model analysis of financing fintechs was a point in time analysis, which implies that the business models could be changed and financing fintechs could be diminished and founded in the meantime. Therefore, a documentary research, based on the same approach, could be conducted to evaluate the dynamic of the financing fintech market. Second, research could be conducted to find whether there is a trend of a winner-takes-it-all result of financing fintechs that provide services to SMEs in Germany. Third, a survey to executives of LMEs in Germany could be conducted to quantitatively test that financing fintechs cannot be a substitute for traditional banking. Finally, due to the two-sided marketplace business model, interviews with individual and professional investors could be conducted to evaluate their willingness to lend to LMEs in Germany.

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9 Appendix

The following appendices contains additional information and data which was used to conduct this research. The whole appendix contains eight sections:

- Appendix A: Initial narrative literature review - searching process and results per database
- Appendix B: Category system crowdlending
- Appendix C: Category system crowdfunding
- Appendix D: Category system factoring platforms
- Appendix E: Category system expert interviews
- Appendix F: Guideline expert interviews
- Appendix G: Profile matrix expert interviews
- Appendix H: Transcript 1 to 10

Appendix A: Initial narrative literature review - searching process and results per database

UWS One Search							
Search terms	Results	1 Limitation	1 Results	2 Limitation	2 Results	Number of findings	Date
FinTech	264	-	-	-	-	8	18.06.2017
Alternative finance	260,898	Instead of contains, equals	208	-	-	5	18.06.2017
Crowdfunding	3,026	AND SME	62	-	-	3	18.06.2017
Crowdlending	19	-	-	-	-	3	18.06.2017
Market place lending	46,772	Instead of contains, equals	2	-	-	0	19.06.2017
Marketplace lending	6,610	AND SME	186	-	-	3	19.06.2017
Peer-to-peer lending	806	AND SME	23	-	-	2	20.06.2017
P2P lending	47,855	AND SME	440	-	-	3	20.06.2017
Crowdinvesting	25	-	-	-	-	2	20.06.2017
Equity-based crowdfunding	96	-	-	-	-	2	20.06.2017
Online invoice trading	726	-	-	-	-	1	20.06.2017
Platform invoice trading	441	-	-	-	-	0	20.06.2017
Online factoring	15,324	Instead of contains, equals	0	-	-	0	21.06.2017
Platform factoring	3,905	Instead of contains, equals	1	-	-	0	21.06.2017
Factoring FinTech	3	-	-	-	-	0	21.06.2017

Google Scholar Search							
Search terms	Results	1 Limitation	1 Results	2 Limitation	2 Results	Number of findings	Date
FinTech	10,200	AND SME	518	-	-	14	22.06.2017
Alternative finance	2,760,000	Instead of contains, equals	3,320	AND SME	851	12	22.06.2017
Crowdfunding	36,300	AND SME	2,180	AND Germany	949	6	23.06.2017
Crowdlending	877	AND SME	135	-	-	3	23.06.2017
Marketplace lending	98,200	Instead of contains, equals	368	-	-	2	23.06.2017

Google Scholar Search							
Search terms	Results	1 Limitation	1 Results	2 Limitation	2 Results	Number of findings	Date
Peer-to-peer lending	28,600	Instead of contains, equals	4,820	AND SME	961	3	24.06.2017
P2P lending	17,900	Instead of contains, equals	2,500	AND SME	710	2	24.06.2017
Crowdfunding	1,300	and SME	185	-	-	4	24.06.2017
Equity-based crowdfunding	2,100	Instead of contains, equals	1,330	AND SME	365	4	25.06.2017
Online invoice trading	19,200	Instead of contains, equals	5	-	-	1	25.06.2017
Platform invoice trading	11,800	Instead of contains, equals	1	-	-	0	25.06.2017
Online factoring	96,400	Instead of contains, equals	40	-	-	2	25.06.2017
Platform factoring	39,600	Instead of contains, equals	6	-	-	0	25.06.2017
Factoring FinTech	205	-	-	-	-	2	25.06.2017

EBSCO Search							
Search terms	Results	1 Limitation	1 Results	2 Limitation	2 Results	Number of findings	Date
FinTech	224	-	-	-	-	8	28.06.2017
Alternative finance	211	-	-	-	-	4	28.06.2017
Crowdfunding	1,302	AND SME	22	-	-	1	28.06.2017
Crowdlending	1	-	-	-	-	0	28.06.2017
Marketplace lending	36	-	-	-	-	0	28.06.2017
Peer-to-peer lending	172	-	-	-	-	2	28.06.2017
P2P lending	310	-	-	-	-	3	28.06.2017
Crowdfunding	3	-	-	-	-	0	28.06.2017
Equity-based crowdfunding	6	-	-	-	-	0	28.06.2017
Online invoice trading	55	-	-	-	-	0	28.06.2017
Platform invoice trading	12	-	-	-	-	0	28.06.2017
Online factoring	1	-	-	-	-	0	28.06.2017
Platform factoring	2	-	-	-	-	0	28.06.2017
Factoring FinTech	0	-	-	-	-	0	28.06.2017

GVK plus (German union catalogue via HAW) Search

Search terms	Results	1 Limitation	1 Results	2 Limitation	2 Results	Number of findings	Date
FinTech	147	-	-	-	-	5	28.06.2017
Alternative finance	2,922	AND SME	57	-	-	2	28.06.2017
Crowdfunding	1,386	AND SME	27	-	-	1	28.06.2017
Crowdlending	28	-	-	-	-	2	30.06.2017
Marketplace lending	39	-	-	-	-	1	30.06.2017
Peer-to-peer lending	136	-	-	-	-	2	30.06.2017
P2P lending	55	-	-	-	-	1	30.06.2017
Crowdinvesting	111	-	-	-	-	2	30.06.2017
Equity-based crowdfunding	16	-	-	-	-	0	30.06.2017
Online invoice trading	2	-	-	-	-	0	30.06.2017
Platform invoice trading	0	-	-	-	-	0	30.06.2017
Online factoring	1,010	Instead of contains, equals	22	-	-	0	30.06.2017
Platform factoring	19	-	-	-	-	0	30.06.2017
Factoring FinTech	1	-	-	-	-	0	30.06.2017

Appendix B: Category system crowdlending

Category		Sub-category		Definition and coding rules	Example (translated from German to English)	Deductive (d) or inductive (i)
No	Name	No	Name			
C1	Legal entity and domain	-	-	Name of legal entity and name of starting domain.	- Kapilendo AG - www.kapilendo.de (web-presence Kapilendo).	d
C2	Founding date	-	-	Founding date by year of legal entity. In order to find the founding date of the legal entity, the search function on online-handelsregister.de should be used. This is an online service for the German trade registry.	"The company Kapilendo AG [...]. The company was founded on 12.03.2015" (web-presence online-handelsregister.de).	d
C3	Banking licence	S1	Yes, banking licence	The platform has a banking licence by its own. In order to find whether the platform has a banking licence or not, the search function on portal.mvp.bafin.de of the German Federal Financial Supervisory Authority should be used.	No example since no platform has a banking licence.	d
		S2	No banking licence	Cooperation with partner bank. If available, including of name of partner bank.	"The loans are provided by our partner Bank named Fidor Bank" (web-presence Kapilendo).	d
C4	Contractual agreements and fund flows	-	-	Contractual agreements and fund flows between parties: Platform, SMEs, investors, and third parties.	Illustration with Microsoft PowerPoint - see separate file.	d
C5	Countries	-	-	Countries in which the platform provides its services. Solely the web-presence is considered, not other related legal entities with other web-presences.	Possibility to select following countries: - Germany - The Netherlands - United Kingdom - United Sates (web-presence Fundingcircle).	d
C6	Kind of loan	S1	Annuity	The loan which is provided has an annuity repayment structure.	"We offer classical loans with an annuity repayment structure" (web-presence Kapilendo).	d
		S2	Bullet	The loan which is provided has a bullet repayment structure.	"We offer operational loans with a bullet repayment structure" (web-presence Kapilendo).	d

C7	Matching	S1	Funding is published with fixed interest rate defined by borrower	The matching to bring investors and borrowers together is that the funding is published on the platform with a fixed interest rate and maturity defined by borrower. The investors can then invest in the funding. In addition, description of the information which is published to the investors.	No example since no platform applies this mechanism.	d
		S2	Pre-defined interest rate mechanism	The matching to bring investors and borrowers together is that the funding is published on the platform with fixed maturity defined by the borrower and a fixed interest rate defined by the platform. The investors can then invest. In addition, description of the information which is published to the investors.	"You define the maturity by yourself. [...] We define your creditworthiness. [...] The projects are published on the platform for 30 days. In this period investors can invest (web-presence Kapilendo).	d
		S3	Auction-based mechanism	The matching to bring investors and borrowers together is that the funding is published on the platform with a fixed maturity defined by the borrower while the interest rates are defined by a closed auction. In addition, description of the information which is published to the investors.	"On Creditsshelf loan projects are arranged via an auction. In general, the maturity of the auction is 2 weeks. In advance Creditsshelf defines interest rate ranges in which the investors can bid (web-presence Creditsshelf).	d
		S4	Auto-bid	The matching to bring investors and borrowers together is that the investors provide funds to the platform based on certain preferences like risk level and interest rate and the platform itself allocates funds to the borrowers. In addition, description of the information which is published to the investors.	No example since no platform applies this mechanism.	d

		S5	Pre-agreed financing mechanism	The matching to bring investors and borrowers together is that the decision of the loan offer with a fixed interest rate and maturity is by the platform itself based on an agreement with professional investors. First, the funding is published to the public with a fixed interest rate and maturity. Second, if not enough funds could be collected from the public, funds from the agreed professional investors are taken. In addition, description of the information which is published to the investors.	"After the online request is completed and we received all required documents, the request is evaluated by our experts within 48 hours. [...] The decision and a defined interest rate are provided to the borrower by a specialised advisor. In case the borrower takes the offer, the funding is published to the public for 5 days and afterwards the loan is provided. [...] In case the funding goal is not reached after this period, the remaining amount is paid by our contracted professional investors. This means the loan is anyway provided" (web-presence Fundingcircle).	i
C8	Funding principle	S1	All-or-nothing	The all-or-nothing principle is applied.	"In order to provide the loan, the funding volume must be achieved by 100%" (web-presence Kapilendo).	d
		S2	Keep-it-all	The keep-it-all principle is applied.	No example since no platform applies this principle.	d
C9	Selection of funding	S1	Yes	The platform selects the funding in advance before they can be uploaded to the platform. This includes the identification, eligibility of borrower according to platforms' requirements, and evaluation of creditworthiness.	"Only selected companies!" (web-presence Kapilendo).	d
		S2	No	The platform selects not the funding in advance before they can be uploaded to the platform.	No example since all platforms select funding.	d

C10	Party conducting creditworthiness evaluation	S1	Evaluation by platform (input of third parties might be possible)	The evaluation of the creditworthiness is conducted by the platform. Input of third parties might be possible.	"Fundingcircle has six different rating classes, from A+ to E. In which rating class your company is depends on the probability of default of the loan. The probability of default is defined by our credit risk experts based on input of third parties like the Creditreform and the annual reports" (web-presence Fundingcircle).	d
		S2	Evaluation by third parties like credit investigation company	The evaluation of the creditworthiness is conducted by third parties like a credit investigation company.	"The nominal interest rate is defined based on the creditworthiness which is calculated by Schufa, Creditreform, or another rating agency" (web-presence Unternehmerich).	d
C11	Rating classes and interest rates	-	-	Represents what rating classes are applied and the respective interest rate.	"Our rating classes and related interests: A: 3.00-3.40% B: 4.30-5.40% C: 6.30-7.40% D: 9.30-10.40% E: 13.30-14.40%" (web-presence Lendico).	d
C12	Financed volume and number of total funding	S1	Volume in mn €	Represents the volume already financed by platform.	"Since our start in summer 2015 in total the investors invested 19 mn € in SMEs" (web-presence Kapilendo).	d
		S2	Number of funding	Represents the number of funding already financed by platform.	"78 financed projects (web-presence Kapilendo).	d
C13	Target borrower	S1	SME	SMEs can apply on platform.	"Lendico provides a flexible financing solution for SMEs" (web-presence Lendico).	d
		S2	Freelancer	Freelancers can apply on platform.	No example since no platform mentioned freelancer as target group.	d
		S3	Start-Up	Start-Ups can apply on platform.	"On Unternehmerich SMEs, start-ups, and real estate projects can apply for a loan" (web-presence Unternehmerich).	d
		S4	Large company	Large companies can apply on platform.	No example since no platform mentioned large companies as target group.	d

C14	Major requirements	S1	Capital or private company as legal form	The company must be a capital or private company as legal form.	"We provide loans to capital companies that are at least 3 years old" (web-presence Kapilendo).	i
		S2	Company minimum age	The company must fulfil a certain level of age (required years).	"We provide loans to capital companies that are at least 3 years old" (web-presence Kapilendo).	i
		S3	Minimum annual turnover	The company must have a certain annual turnover (in k €).	"The minimum average turnover was 50 k € per annum for the last two years" (web-presence Lendico).	i
		S4	Procedure for borrower's authentication	The procedure to authenticate the borrower, for example via online banking access, Videoident, or PostIdent.	You can be offered to bring a verification of the identity of the person who represents the loan agreement (generally via PostIdent) (web-presence Lendico).	i
		S5	Others	Any further requirements.	"Specific requirements. Classical loans: - positive profit for last 2 years - profit higher than 100 k € (web-presence Kapilendo).	i
C15	Major required documents	S1	Annual reports	For the application, the borrower must provide annual reports.	"What do we need from you? [...] The annual reports for the last two years" (web-presence Lendico).	i
		S2	Financial analysis of current year	For the application, the borrower must provide a financial analysis of current year.	"What do we need from you? [...] Financial analysis of the current year" (web-presence Lendico).	i
		S3	Current bank account statements	For the application, the borrower must provide current bank account statements.	"What do we need from you? [...] Bank accounts of the main bank account for last three months" (web-presence Lendico).	i
		S4	Forecast cash flow	For the application, the borrower must provide a cash flow forecast.	"What documents do you have to provide? [...] Cash flow statement for the next 12 months (web-presence Creditsheff).	i
C16	Collateral or guarantee	S1	Collateral needed	For the loan, the borrower must provide a collateral.	No example since no platform requires a collateral.	d
		S2	Personal guarantee	For the loan, the borrower must provide a personal guarantee.	"In general, Fundingcircle requires a personal guarantee" (web-presence Fundingcircle).	d

		S3	Not needed	For the loan, no collateral is needed.	"The loan projects are generally unsecured" (web-presence Creditsshelf).	d
C17	Loan volume	S1	Minimum	Represents the minimum loan volume in k €.	"You can get a financing between 25 k € and 2,5 mn €" (web-presence Kapilendo).	d
		S2	Maximum	Represents the maximum loan volume in k €.	"You can get a financing between 25 k € and 2,5 mn €" (web-presence Kapilendo)".	d
C18	Loan maturity	S1	Minimum	Represents the minimum loan maturity in months.	"Maturity is from 1 to 5 years" (web-presence Lendico).	d
		S2	Maximum	Represents the maximum loan maturity in months.	"Maturity is from 1 to 5 years" (web-presence Lendico).	d
C19	Early repayment	S1	Yes, no additional fee	The loan can be repaid prior to maturity without additional fee.	"No, we do not charge you by a prepayment" (web-presence Fundingcircle).	d
		S2	Yes, additional fee	The loan can be repaid prior to maturity with additional fee.	No example since no platform applies this.	d
		S3	No	The loan cannot be repaid prior to maturity.	No example since no platform applies this.	d
C20	Fees to be paid by borrower	S1	One-off fee independent of success of funding	The fee to be paid by the borrower consists of a one-off fee independent whether or not the funding succeeded (in% or €).	"Administration fees are charged independent of the success of the company" (web-presence Unternehmerich).	d
		S2	One-off fee solely if success of funding	The fee to be paid by the borrower consists of a one-off fee if the funding succeeded (in% or €).	"After a successful arrangement of a loan between investors and a borrower, we charge a fee for the arrangement. This fee is between 1.9% and 4.9% of the volume" (web-presence Kapilendo).	d
		S3	Annual fee	The fee to be paid by the borrower consists of an annual fee (in% or €).	"We charge a marketing and administration fee [...]. This fee is 0.75% of the volume per annum" (web-presence Kapilendo).	d
C21	Target investor	S1	Individual investor	Individual investors can invest in funding.	"As market place for financing of companies, Unternehmerich brings together companies with a financing need with private and professional investors. (web-presence Unternehmerich).	d

		S2	Professional investor	Professional investors can invest in funding.	"As market place for financing of companies, Unternehmerich brings together companies with a financing need with private and professional investors! (web-presence Unternehmerich).	d
C22	Investment volume	S1	Minimum	Represents the minimum loan volume that an investor has to invest in € or k€.	"Starting with the volume of 250 € investors can invest in selected companies" (web-presence Unternehmerich).	d
		S2	Maximum	Represents the maximum loan volume that an investor can invest in in € or k€.	"The maximum volume for private investors is 10 k€ according to the Small Investor Protection Act" (web-presence Unternehmerich).	d
C23	Fees to be paid by investor	S1	One-off fee independent of success of funding	The fee to be paid by the investor consists of a one-off fee independent whether or not the funding succeeded (in% or €).	No example since no platform has this kind of fee.	d
		S2	One-off fee solely if success of funding	The fee to be paid by the investor consists of a one-off fee if the funding succeeded (in% or €).	No example since no platform has this kind of fee.	d
		S3	One-off fee if fully repayment and payment of interest	The fee to be paid by the investor consists of a one-off fee if the repayment and interests are repaid by the borrower (in% or €).	"Each investor is only obliged to pay a success fee to Unternehmerich in case the investor fully received all claims from the investment (e.g. repayment, interests, dividends etc.). Only in this case there is a one-off fee of 0.25% of the volume" (web-presence Unternehmerich).	i
		S4	Annual fee	The fee to be paid by the investor consists of an annual fee (in% or €).	"Overview fees for the investors: [...] The Creditsheff service fee is 1% of the volume (web-presence Creditsheff).	d
		S5	No fee	There is no fee for the investor.	"The registration and investing are free of charge" (web-presence Kapilendo).	d
C24	Reporting covenants	S1	Yes	It is explicitly mentioned that the borrower is obliged to publish certain information to inform the investors on a regular basis	No example since no platform explicitly mentioned it.	d

				about its business during the term of the loan.		
		S2	No	It is explicitly mentioned that the borrower is not obliged to inform the investors on a regular basis about its business during the term of the loan.	No example since no platform explicitly mentioned it.	d
C25	Secondary market	S1	Yes	There is a secondary market for the investors to sell or buy the investments.	No example since no platform mentioned that there is a secondary market.	d
		S2	No	There is no secondary market for the investors to sell or buy the investments.	No example since no platform mentioned that there is no secondary market.	d
C26	Overall topics	-	-	Any other relevant topics.	"Fundingcircle acquired Zencap" (web-presence Fundingcircle).	D

Appendix C: Category system crowdfinvesting

Category		Sub-category		Definition and coding rules	Example (translated from German to English)	Deductive (d) or inductive (i)
No	Name	No	Name			
C1	Legal entity and domain	-	-	Name of legal entity and name of starting domain.	- Kapilendo AG - www.kapilendo.de (web-presence Kapilendo).	d
C2	Founding date	-	-	Founding date by year of legal entity (might be different from activation of platform). In order to find the founding date of the legal entity, the search function on online-handelsregister.de should be used. This is an online service for the German trade registry.	"The company Kapilendo AG [...]. The company was founded on 12.03.2015" (web-presence online-handelsregister.de).	d
C3	Licence	S1	Yes, banking licence	The platform has a banking licence by its own. In order to find whether the platform has a banking licence or not, the search function on portal.mvp.bafin.de of the German Federal Financial Supervisory Authority should be used.	No example since no platform has a banking licence.	d
		S2	Yes, other financing related licence	The platform has no banking licence but another financing related licence.	The company has a licence as financial service provider including as investment broker according to section 1 subsection 1a of KWG (web-presence portal.mvp.bafin.de).	d
		S3	No licence	The platform has neither a banking licence nor another financing related licence.	No example since the platforms did not mention that they do not have a licence.	d
C4	Countries	-	-	Countries in which the platform provides their services. Solely the web-presence is considered, not other related legal entities with other web-presences.	"More than 20 mn € for real champions in four countries: Germany, Austria, Switzerland, Slovakia" (web-presence Finnest).	d
C5	Kind of financing instrument which is provided on platform	S1	Subordinated loans	The financing instrument is a subordinated loan.	"Companies can issue mezzanine instruments via our platform". This include subordinated loans (web-presence Deutsche-mikroinvest).	d
		S2	Subordinated profit-participating loans	The financing instrument is a subordinated profit-participating loan.	"Companies can issue mezzanine instruments via our platform". This include subordinated profit-participating loans (web-presence Deutsche-mikroinvest).	d

		S3	Silent partnerships	The financing instrument is a silent partnership.	"Companies can issue mezzanine instruments via our platform". This include silent partnerships (web-presence Deutsche-mikroinvest).	d
		S4	Participation right	The financing instrument is a participation right.	"Companies can issue mezzanine instruments via our platform". This include participation rights (web-presence Deutsche-mikroinvest).	d
C6	Matching	S1	Pre-defined economic conditions mechanism	The matching to bring investors and borrowers together is that the funding is published on the platform for public with defined economic conditions and maturity (if available specification who defines economic conditions). The investors can then invest in the funding.	"You define the maturity by yourself. [...] We define your creditworthiness. [...] The projects are published on the platform for 30 days. In this period investors can invest (web-presence Kapilendo).	d
		S2	Auction-based mechanism	The matching to bring investors and borrowers together is that the funding is published on the platform with a defined maturity while the interest rate is defined by an auction.	"Invest to your desired interest rate. In case you would like to invest in a funding, then you can provide an offer. You define the volume you want to invest (e.g. 5 k €) and to which interest rate (e.g. 5%). After all investors provided their offer, a common interest rate [the highest] is defined. This is the interest to which the company takes the offer. For example, a company needs 800 k €. The offers of the investors are in total 750 k € with 3%, 4%, and 5%. In case 750 k € are enough for the company, all investors receive an interest rate of 5%. Investors who required a higher interest rate are not considered (web-presence Finnest).	d
		S3	Private placement	The matching to bring investors and borrowers together is that the funding is published on the platform for private placement. The investors can then invest in the funding.	"A company may also conduct a private placement on Finnest. At the same time the circle of invited investors is limited" (web-presence Finnest).	i

C7	Contractual agreements and fund flows	S1	Payment service provider with separate account in between	Between the investors and the borrower is an additional payment service provider with a separate account. In addition, illustration of example to show the contractual construction and the fund flows between the involved parties.	"After the offer, the investor has to transfer the funds to the respective escrow account of the payment service provider or partner bank". [...] The repayment and interest payments are allocated from the payment service provider or partner bank to the investors" (web-presence Unternehmerich). See example of contractual construction and fund flows in PowerPoint file.	i
		S2	No payment service provider with separate account in between	Between the investors and the borrower is no additional payment service provider with a separate account. This means direct transfer of funds between the involved parties. In addition, illustration of example to show the contractual construction and the fund flows between the involved parties.	"The borrower is obliged to log a loan register which has to be up to date. This include data of the investors (name, address, account data) and the loan volume, date of the provision of the funds, interest rate and interest payments. [...] The provision of the funds is taken place by a one-off transaction to the account of the borrower (web-presence Katrim). See example of contractual construction and fund flows in PowerPoint file.	i
C8	Funding principle	S1	All-or-nothing	The all-or-nothing principle is applied.	"In order to provide the loan, the funding volume must be achieved by 100%" (web-presence Kapilendo).	d
		S2	Keep-it-all	The keep-it-all principle is applied.	No example since no platform applies this principle.	d
C9	Selection of funding	S1	Yes	The platform selects the funding in advance before they can be uploaded to the platform. This includes the identification, eligibility of borrower according to platforms' requirements. Additionally, this can include the evaluation of creditworthiness or validation of business model.	"Only selected companies!" (web-presence Kapilendo).	d

		S2	No	The platform selects not the funding in advance before they can be uploaded to the platform.	No example since all platforms select the funding.	d
C10	Party conducting creditworthiness evaluation or business model validation	S1	No check or validation	There is no evaluation of the creditworthiness or a validation of the business model.	There are different steps: Application for funding upload. After selection, preparation for upload. Upload of funding. Finishing funding. No mentioning that the selection is based on a creditworthiness check or a validation of the business model (web-presence Conda).	d
		S2	Evaluation by platform (input of third parties might be possible)	The evaluation of the creditworthiness is conducted by the platform. Input of third parties might be possible.	"Our credit experts define your individual interest rate" (web-presence Kapilendo).	d
		S3	Evaluation by third parties like credit investigation company	The evaluation of the creditworthiness is conducted by third parties like a credit investigation company.	"The nominal interest rate is defined based on the creditworthiness which is calculated by Schufa, Creditreform, or another rating agency" (web-presence Unternehmerich).	d
		S4	Validation of business model by platform	The platform validates the business model.	"In general, Transvendo checks and validates the documents in order to get a picture of the project and to evaluate whether the project is suitable. The business model, business plan and financial plan are in the focus" (web-presence Transvendo).	d
C11	Economic conditions	S1	Fixed interest rate	There is a fixed interest rates paid from the borrower to the investors. If available, specification of value in %.	"The investors receive an annual interest (in general between 7% and 8%) for their investments (web-presence Transvendo).	d
		S2	Participation in turnover development	There is any kind of participation in the turnover development. If available, specification of value in %.	"Furthermore, some companies pay an additional payment to the crowd that is based on the turnover" (web-presence Kapilendo).	d
		S3	Participation in profit development	There is any kind of participation in the profit development. If available, specification of value in %.	The investors receive a fixed interest rate of 1% and they are participating in the profit and increase of company value (web-presence Transvendo).	d

		S4	Participation in increase in company's value	There is any kind of participation in increase in company's value. If available, specification of value in %.	The investors receive a fixed interest rate of 1% and they are participating in the profit and increase of company value (web-presence Transvendo).	d
C12	Financed volume and number of funding	S1	Volume in mn €	Represents the volume already financed by platform.	"Since our start in summer 2015 in total the investors invested 19 mn € in SMEs" (web-presence Kapilendo).	d
		S2	Number of funding	Represents the number of funding already financed by platform.	"78 financed projects (web-presence Kapilendo).	d
C13	Target borrower	S1	SME	SMEs can apply on platform.	"By these investments you support the German SME market" (web-presence Kapilendo).	d
		S2	Freelancer	Freelancers can apply on platform.	No example since no platform mentioned freelancer as target group.	d
		S3	Start-Up	Start-Ups can apply on platform.	"On Unternehmerich SMEs, start-ups, and real estate projects can apply for a loan" (web-presence Unternehmerich).	d
		S4	Large company	Large companies can apply on platform.	No example since no platform mentioned large companies as target group.	d
C14	Major requirements	S1	Capital or private company as legal form	The company must be a capital or private company as legal form.	"We provide loans to capital companies that are at least 3 years old" (web-presence Kapilendo).	i
		S2	Company minimum age	The company must fulfil a certain level of age (required years).	"We provide loans to capital companies that are at least 3 years old" (web-presence Kapilendo).	i
		S3	Minimum annual turnover	The company must have a certain annual turnover (in k €).	"The minimum average turnover was 50 k € per annum for the last two years" (web-presence Lendico).	i
		S4	Others	Any further requirements.	"Specific requirements. Classical loans: - positive profit for last 2 years - profit higher than 100 k € (web-presence Kapilendo).	i
C15	Major required documents	S1	Annual reports	For the application, the borrower must provide annual reports.	"Annual report of last three years" (web-presence Kapilendo).	i
		S2	Financial analysis of current year	For the application, the borrower must provide a financial analysis of current year.	"Financial analysis of current year" (web-presence Kapilendo)."	i

		S3	Forecast cash flow	For the application, the borrower must provide a cash flow forecast.	The platform needs a cash-flow statement (web-presence Conda).	i
		S4	Business plan	For the application, the borrower must provide a business plan.	"A detailed description of the business model" (web-presence Conda).	i
C16	Funding volume	S1	Minimum	Represents the minimum funding volume in k €.	"You can get a financing between 25 k € and 2,5 mn €" (web-presence Kapilendo).	d
		S2	Maximum	Represents the maximum funding volume in k €.	"You can get a financing between 25 k € and 2,5 mn €" (web-presence Kapilendo)".	d
C17	Funding maturity	S1	Minimum	Represents the minimum funding maturity in months.	"The maturities are between 1 and 5 years" (web-presence Kapilendo)".	d
		S2	Maximum	Represents the maximum funding maturity in months.	"The maturities are between 1 and 5 years" (web-presence Kapilendo)".	d
C18	Fees to be paid by borrower	S1	One-off fee independent of success of funding	The fee to be paid by the borrower consists of a one-off fee independent whether or not the funding succeeded (in% or €).	"Administration fees are charged independent of the success of the company" (web-presence Unternehmerich).	d
		S2	One-off fee if success of funding	The fee to be paid by the borrower consists of a one-off fee if the funding succeeded (in% or €).	"After a successful arrangement of a loan between investors and a borrower, we charge a fee for the arrangement. This fee is between 1.9% and 4.9% of the volume" (web-presence Kapilendo).	d
		S3	Annual fee	The fee to be paid by the borrower consists of an annual fee (in% or €).	"We charge a marketing and administration fee [...]. This fee is 0.75% of the volume per annum" (web-presence Kapilendo).	d
C19	Target investor	S1	Individual investor	Individual investors can invest in funding.	"As market place for financing of companies, Unternehmerich brings together companies with a financing need with private and professional investors. (web-presence Unternehmerich).	d
		S2	Professional investor	Professional investors can invest in funding.	"As market place for financing of companies, Unternehmerich brings together companies with a financing need with private and professional investors! (web-presence Unternehmerich).	d

C20	Investment volume	S1	Minimum	Represents the minimum loan volume that an investor has to invest in €.	"Starting with the volume of 250 € investors can invest in selected companies" (web-presence Unternehmerich).	d
		S2	Maximum	Represents the maximum loan volume that an investor can invest in €.	"The maximum volume for private investors is 10 k € according to the Small Investor Protection Act" (web-presence Unternehmerich).	d
C21	Voting or participation rights	S1	Yes	The financing instrument includes a voting right or other participation rights for the investor.	No example since no provided financing instrument has a voting or participating right.	d
		S2	No	The financing instrument includes no voting right or participating for the investor.	"The subordinated loan contract includes a right for interest payments which does not include rights of membership especially participation and voting rights" (web-presence Unternehmerich).	d
C22	Control rights	S1	Yes	The financing instrument includes a control right for the investor. Control rights have less influence on company than voting or participation right but more than information right. For example, control right is the validation of the accuracy of the annual report by accessing the business records.	Investors of silent partnerships are always allowed to validate the annual report (web-presence Unternehmerich).	d
		S2	No	The financing instrument includes no control right for the investor.	"Regarding to the company the crowd investor has no [...] control right" (web-presence Kapilendo).	d
C23	Information rights	S1	Yes	It is explicitly mentioned that the borrower is obliged to inform the investors on a regular basis about certain information like the business development and financial figures during the term of the loan.	"In case the funding is successfully financed according to number 2.2 of this contract, the company has to provide twice a year a report on the platform of the development of the company. The development report consists of the turnover in numbers for the last half year and a description of the cash flow situation and business development in text form without figures" (web-presence Kapilendo).	d

		S2	No	It is explicitly mentioned that the borrower is not obliged to inform the investors on a regular basis about certain information.	No example since no platform has this kind of fee.	d
C24	Fees to be paid by investor	S1	One-off fee independent of success of funding	The fee to be paid by the investor consists of a one-off fee independent whether or not the funding succeeded (in% or €).	No example since no platform has this kind of fee.	d
		S2	One-off fee if success of funding	The fee to be paid by the investor consists of a one-off fee if the funding succeeded (in% or €).	"Investors: In case of successful financing - only in this case - the investors are charged with 1% of the volume but in minimum 25 €" (web-presence Finnest).	d
		S3	One-off fee if full repayment and payment of interest	The fee to be paid by the investor consists of a one-off fee if the repayment and interests are repaid by the borrower (in% or €).	"Each investor is only obliged to pay a success fee to Unternehmerich in case the investor fully received all claims from the investment (e.g. repayment, interests, dividends etc.). Only in this case there is a one-off fee of 0.25% of the volume" (web-presence Unternehmerich).	i
		S4	Annual fee	The fee to be paid by the investor consists of an annual fee (in% or €).	No example since no platform has this kind of fee.	d
		S5	No fee	There is no fee for the investor.	"The registration and investing are free of charge" (web-presence Kapilendo).	d
C25	Secondary market	S1	Yes	There is a secondary market for the investors to sell or buy the investments.	No example since no platform mentioned that there is a secondary market.	d
		S2	No	There is no secondary market for the investors to sell or buy the investments.	There is no regulated secondary market (web-presence Finnest).	D
C26	Overall topics	-	-	Any other relevant topics.	Bankless24 merged with Conda (web-presence Bankless24).	d

Appendix D: Category system factoring platforms

Category		Sub-category		Definition and coding rules	Example (translated from German to English)	Deductive (d) or inductive (i)
No	Name	No	Name			
C1	Legal entity and domain	-	-	Name of legal entity and name of starting domain.	- FLEX Financial Solutions GmbH - flexpayment.de (web-presence Flexpayment).	d
C2	Founding date	-	-	Founding date by year of legal entity (might be different from activation of platform). In order to find the founding date of the legal entity, the search function on online-handelsregister.de should be used. This is an online service for the German trade registry.	The company 4Factoring CASA Kapital GmbH was founded on 07.03.2011 and renamed to FLEX Financial Solutions GmbH on 11.11.2013 (web-presence online-handelsregister.de).	d
C3	Licence	S1	Yes, factoring or other financing licence	The platform has a factoring or other financing related licence. In order to find whether the platform has a licence or not, the search function on portal.mvp.bafin.de of the German Federal Financial Supervisory Authority should be used.	Decimo has a factoring licence according to section 1 subsection 1a sentence 2 number 9 KWG (web-presence portal.mvp.bafin.de).	d
		S2	No financing related licence	The platform has no financing related licence.	No example since the platforms did not mention that they do not have a licence.	d
C4	Countries	-	-	Countries in which the platform provides its services. Solely the web-presence is considered, not other related legal entities with other web-presences.	"The Atevis AG is a platform for factoring and alternative financing in German speaking countries: Germany, Austria, Switzerland (web-presence Factoringbörse).	d
C5	Matching/ financing including contractual agreements and fund flows	S1	Auction-based mechanism	The matching to bring investors and borrowers together is that after the registration and upload of account receivable by the borrower, investors can bid in an auction to buy the account receivable. During the registration and upload procedure, the platform checks the eligibility of the borrower and its account receivable. In addition, contractual agreements and fund flows between the involved parties have to be illustrated.	"Here registration. [...] What is Trustbills? Trustbills is an auction platform on which suppliers can sell their accounts receivable with balance sheet effects. Based on a bid mechanism, an auction, the account receivable can be sold to institutional investors. [...] Account receivable can be uploaded manually or automatically" (web-presence Trustbills). See example of	d

					contractual agreements and fund flows in PowerPoint file.	
		S2	Platform decision mechanism	For the financing of the account receivable there is no separate investor involved. After the registration and upload of the account receivable by the borrower, the platform provides a decision whether or not to finance the account receivable. After a positive decision, the advance payment can be 100% or less than 100% reduced by the fee. In addition, contractual agreements and fund flows between the involved parties have to be illustrated.	"You can register here. [...] You upload your account receivable to the platform. We evaluate it and give you feedback. [...] We pay 100% of the account receivable reduced by the fee (web-presence Rechnung48). See example of contractual agreements and fund flows in PowerPoint file.	i
		S3	Intermediary mechanism	The platform acts as intermediary between the borrower and a separate factoring provider. After the registration and upload of the account receivable by the borrower, the platform commissions a factoring contract with the factoring provider on the borrower's behalf. After a positive decision, the advance payment is 100% reduced by the fee. In addition, contractual agreements and fund flows between the involved parties have to be illustrated.	"Pagido commissions for the borrower factoring contracts on the behalf of the borrower" (web-presence Pagido). See example of contractual agreements and fund flows in PowerPoint file.	i
		S4	Pre-agreed financing mechanism	The platform provides the information whether or not to finance the account receivable based on an agreement with institutional investors that provide the funds. Additionally, there is bank involved. After a positive decision, the advance payment is 100% reduced by the fee.	"You can finance your unpaid accounts receivable within one business day. For this our partner bank Wirecard Bank AG buys your account receivable". [...] "As the resell to us". [...] "In order to invest, investors agree factoring contracts with Fundflow" (web-presence Fundflow).	i
C6	Factoring characteristics	S1	Individual account receivable	Individual account receivable can be sold on the platform.	"You upload your account receivable to the platform" (web-presence Rechnung48).	d
		S2	Portfolio of accounts receivable	Individual account receivable can be sold on the platform.	"The sale of national and international accounts receivable, also individual accounts (web-presence Trustbills).	d

		S3	Notification	The borrower's customer is informed about the factoring. In case the bank account data like IBAN is changed and communicated to the borrower's customer, it is defined as notified factoring.	"For you customer, there is no change except the bank account to which the customer will transfer the amount. [...] Q&A: "The customer paid the amount to our bank account and not to yours. What can I do? In this case please transfer the amount to our bank account" (web-presence Bankless24).	d
		S4	Non-notification	The borrower's customer is not informed about the factoring.	"Discreet: The financing of your account receivable will be not communicated to your customer" (web-presence Innolend).	d
		S5	Recourse	It is recourse factoring meaning the credit risk is kept by the borrower.	"What happens in case of default? Innolend does not take the credit risk of the account receivable. In case your customer does not pay the account receivable, you have to pay back the money" (web-presence Innolend).	d
		S6	Non-recourse	It is non-recourse factoring meaning the platform or investor takes the credit risk of the borrower's customer.	"We take the full credit risk in case of default (non-recourse factoring)" (web-presence Rechnung48).	d
		S7	Dunning service included	The platform provides additional dunning services.	"Does Rechnung48 provide a dunning service? Yes, in case your customer is not paying the account receivable within the term of credit, we take over the dunning service via phone and writing" (web-presence Rechnung48).	d
C7	Party conducting creditworthiness check	S1	No check	There is no check of the creditworthiness.	"Like Ebay Trustbills uses the principle of an internet-based auction mechanism (web-presence Trustbills). There is no mentioning of any creditworthiness check by the platform.	d
		S2	Check by platform (input of third parties might be possible)	The check of the creditworthiness is conducted by the platform. Input of third parties might be possible.	"In order to reduce the service as far as possible, we have to check different data, your creditworthiness	d

					as well" (web-presence Bezahlt).	
		S3	Check by third parties like credit investigation company	The check of the creditworthiness is conducted by third parties like a credit investigation company.	"In order to provide you an individual offer, we need information about the creditworthiness of you and your customer which we receive from external credit investigation companies like the Creditreform" (web-presence Innolend).	d
C8	Financed volume and number of funding	S1	Volume in mn €	Represents the volume already financed by platform.	"Financing of accounts receivable since 1998: [...] 70 k transactions" (web-presence Rechnung48).	d
		S2	Number of funding	Represents the number of funding already financed by platform.	"Financing of accounts receivable since 1998: [...] 150 mn € in financing volume" (web-presence Rechnung48).	d
C9	Target borrower	S1	SME	SMEs can apply on platform.	"Innolend provides SMEs to finance their accounts receivable" (web-presence Innolend).	d
		S2	Freelancer	Freelancers can apply on platform.	"We focusing on freelancer and small SMEs" (web-presence Rechnung48).	d
		S3	Start-Up	Start-Ups can apply on platform.	"Participants are national and international companies [...] Consumer and sole proprietor cannot participate" (web-presence Trustbills).	d
		S4	Large company	Large companies can apply on platform.	"Participants are national and international companies [...] Consumer and sole proprietor cannot participate" (web-presence Trustbills).	d
C10	Major requirements	S1	Minimum annual turnover	The company must have a certain annual turnover (in k €).	For companies with an annual turnover of 50 k € (web-presence Pagido).	d
		S2	Company minimum age	The company must fulfil a certain level of age (required years).	"The participants have to be listed in the trade registry or to have an operating business for at least 3 years" (web-presence Trustbills).	d
		S3	Maximum period in days between provision of	There is a maximum period in days between the provision of the services from the company to the	"Minimum requirements: The date of the provision of the service is not	i

			services and request for factoring	customer and the request for factoring (days).	older than 4 weeks" (web-presence Flexpayment).	
		S4	Customer of borrower is not a consumer	The borrower's customer is no consumer. This means solely business-to-business.	"We focusing on freelancer and small SMEs with accounts receivable to commercial customers" (web-presence Rechnung48).	i
		S5	Procedure for borrower's authentication	The procedure to authenticate the borrower, for example via online banking access, video or Post identification.	"Because of the anti-money laundering act, you can use Flexpayment after the identification of your person. This procedure can be conducted by the access to your online banking account" (web-presence Flexpayment).	i
		S6	Others	Any further requirements.	"Possible reason why Flexpayment does not accept your account receivable: [...] Your customer's company is younger than 3 years" (web-presence Flexpayment).	i
C11	Funding volume	S1	Minimum	Represents the minimum funding volume in k €.	"A financing request can be conducted for accounts receivable between 5 k € and 250 k €" (web-presence Innolend).	d
		S2	Maximum	Represents the maximum funding volume in k €.	"A financing request can be conducted for accounts receivable between 5 k € and 250 k €" (web-presence Innolend).	d
C12	Fees to be paid by borrower	S1	One-off fee independent of success of funding	The fee to be paid by the borrower consists of a one-off fee independent whether or not the funding succeeded (in% or €).	For the one-time registration a fee of 500 € is charged. For the uploading of the account receivable and usage of the auction 0.1% of volume (minimum 100 €) is charged (web-presence Trustbills).	d
		S2	One-off fee if success of funding	The fee to be paid by the borrower consists of a one-off fee if the funding succeeded (in% or €).	"The service fee is 3.97% per account receivable. There are no additional fees. This all-in fee includes creditworthiness check, payment on the next day, dunning service, and credit risk" (web-presence Rechnung48).	d

C13	Target investor	S1	Individual investor	Individual investors can invest in funding.	"Advanon is an online platform on which customers can receive cash from external investors for their account receivable. [...]. Register here as investor. We evaluate the data and give you feedback. [...] As German citizen you need a residence in Germany" (web-presence Advanon).	d
		S2	Professional investor	Professional investors can invest in funding.	Institutional investors, banks, and companies can invest (web-presence Trustbills).	d
C14	Fees to be paid by investor	S1	One-off fee independent of success of funding	The fee to be paid by the investor consists of a one-off fee independent whether or not the funding succeeded (in% or €).	For the one-time registration a fee of 500 € is charged (web-presence Trustbills).	d
		S2	One-off fee if success of funding	The fee to be paid by the investor consists of a one-off fee if the funding succeeded (in% or €).	"The buyer of accounts receivable pays a closing fee depending on the residual term of the account receivable meaning from the day the auction starts to the maturity of the account receivable: 11-30 days: 0.05%, 31-60 days: 0.1%, more than 60 days: 0.15% of volume" (web-presence Trustbills).	d
C15	Overall topics	-	-	Any other relevant topics.	"In Germany, Advanon is working together with Wirecard AG" (web-presence Advanon).	d

Appendix E: Category system expert interviews

Category		Sub-category		Definition and coding rules	Example	Deductive (d) or inductive (i)
No	Name	No	Name			
C1	Executives' knowledge of or experience with financing FinTechs	S1	Knowledge about or experience with crowdfunding	The interviewee has knowledge about or experience with crowdfunding.	"So only indirectly because one of our targets has been funded by crowdfunding" (I3, pa. 46).	d
		S2	Knowledge about or experience with crowdlending	The interviewee has knowledge about or experience with crowdlending.	No example since no executive mentioned such experience.	d
		S3	Knowledge about or experience with crowdinvesting	The interviewee has knowledge about or experience with crowdinvesting.	"So, it was something spontaneous. That was a financing. It would have been called a public bond in the direction, maybe for marketing reasons" (I9, pa. 52).	d
		S4	Knowledge about or experience with factoring	The interviewee has knowledge about or experience with factoring platforms.	No example since no executive mentioned such experience.	d
C2	Financing instruments in usage	S1	External equity	External equity is or was used after the foundation of the LME or planned as financing instrument. This means either the LME went public (IPO) or a capital increase conducted. In addition, some characteristics can be explained. If it is not used, this also includes arguments why it is not used.	"What we have is equity financing, which we have already used. We are a public company. We already carried out a capital increase (I2, pa. 14).	d
		S2	Bank loan	A bank loan is or was used as financing instrument. This means the LME uses or used a bank loan. This include subsidised loans. In addition, some characteristics can be explained. If it is not used, this also includes arguments why it is not used.	"If, in the special case, they were not sufficient for larger investments, then the classic bank financing through loans" (I1, pa. 2).	d
		S3	Mezzanine	Mezzanine is or was used as financing instrument. This means the LME uses or used mezzanine. In addition, some characteristics can be explained. If it is not used, this also includes arguments why it is not used.	No example since no company mentioned mezzanine.	d

		S4	Factoring	Mentioning that factoring is or was used as financing instrument. This means the LME uses or used factoring. In addition, some characteristics can be explained. If it is not used, this also includes arguments why it is not used.	"Factoring is also an issue for us. We do factoring for two reasons. Once liquidity and secondly also hedge" (I4, pa. 10).	d
		S5	Others	Mentioning of all other financing instruments. In addition, some characteristics can be explained. If it is not used, this also includes arguments why it is not used.	"Classic fleet financing based on purchase and buy-back, leasing for the fleet and car sector" (I10, pa. 10).	d
C3	Financing instrument preferences	S1	Internal financing is preferred over all other	Internal financing is preferred for investments. Other instruments are solely used in case internal financing is not sufficient.	"But you can find that in so-called family-owned companies that one always earns ideally from own resources first. If you have earned it, you can actually spend it again" (I1, pa. 6).	d
		S2	Debt financing is preferred over mezzanine or external equity	Debt financing is preferred over mezzanine or external equity for investments.	"Because financing through the banks is always the cheapest form for me. Besides, I am maybe conservative too" (I2, pa. 38).	d
		S3	Mezzanine or external equity is preferred over debt financing	Mezzanine or external equity is preferred over debt financing for investments.	"Interviewer: Have you had considered alternatives like borrowed capital, over loans or also towards mezzanine capital? Interviewee3: I agree. Both, more likely even towards the mezzanine. And not so much in the direction of classic loans" (I3, pa. 19-20).	d
C4	Characteristics of relationship banking	-	-	The LME has a relationship bank. Description of characteristics of relationship banking.	"Yes, we have one relationship bank with which we process more or less the standardised business. In addition, there is another bank which was involved once for a financing issue and which is especially processing our foreign trade" (I1, pa. 14).	d
C5	Positive effects of relationship traditional banks	S1	Higher reliability	Due to the relationship there is a higher reliability. This includes that loans are more available, also in times where the financing position	"The advantage is surely that you can rely on each other and that you know each other" (I1, pa. 16).	d

			of the company is not so good or higher loan volumes. In addition, this includes that there is a better knowledge of each other meaning the company and industry and vice versa.		
S2	Specific knowledge and special or customized offers	Advisors of traditional or relationship banks have specific knowledge in different fields and provide special or customized services.	The points are the conditions and what they are offer. For example, an energy loan, a specialised loan with low interests in the course of energy saving technologies. This was very interesting because it fitted to us. If another bank does not provide such offer, either the bank does not have it or not thinking about to offer it, then the offer is different (I1, pa. 26).	d	
S3	Higher velocity or easier	Due to the relationship the procedure for different topics including loan financing is faster or easier.	"And today, I am just call Mr. X, who is the head of the bank, and say, look at that, please. But it could suddenly become more complicated, at least for me" (I5, pa. 60).	d	
S4	Lower interest	Due to the relationship the interests are lower.	"Interviewer Did you receive better conditions from the bank with which you have a longer relationship than with the new one? Interviewee1: In general, yes. The risk to lose the relationship was always too unpleasant for the bank" (I1, pa. 19-20).	d	
S5	Lower collateral requirements	Due to the relationship the collateral requirements are lower.	"Of course. I do not know now how others would react when I say that I would like to have 10 million € from you without collateral" (I4, pa. 44).	d	
S6	Higher loan volumes available	Due to a relationship, higher loan volumes are available.	"Because it is not always the case with us that it is said to be a small volume but it gets higher. And that is where we need efficient banks that can invest in larger amounts. So that is the advantage" (I9, pa. 38).	d	

		S7	Communication channel as advantage	The appointments or the personal contact with relationship banks are an advantage to strengthen the relationship and to exchange knowledge.	"Another advantage is that you have a corporate key account manager at the bank's side, with whom you can often discuss meticulous topics which you can develop further" (18, pa. 29).	d
		S8	Plausibility of investment	Since the relationship bank advisor knows the company and the business it can check the plausibility of the investment idea, so as double check or reviewer.	"which also speaks for me as a house bank as sparring partner. That when I present a project, the partner bindingly says we are going with you or not and gives feedback that this is a meaningful project (16, pa. 24).	i
C6	Negative effects of relationship and traditional banks	S1	Dependency on loan availability	It implies a negatively dependency on relationships bank.	"but a very solid way of financing. Because you are free of all bank influence. If you, e.g. I do not know if you know that. But company X. Person Y set up X in the 1970s / 1980s which has failed through the corresponding actions of the banks. In which for one day the loans have been rejected (11, pa. 6).	i
		S2	Covenants as disadvantage	Covenants of traditional banks are a disadvantage. This includes the influence of the bank on the company's business.	"I know it from an auditor's point of view of clients who have always complained very much about these covenants. That is often a vicious circle. When the numbers go down, interest rates go up" (13, pa. 38).	d
		S3	Collateral as disadvantage	Collateral requirements of traditional banks are a disadvantage.	"If you have to provide certain collaterals like mortgages for larger investments, then it is a major handicap" (11, pa. 24).	d
		S4	Higher interest rate	The interest rate is higher at the relationship bank.	"I think there was our long-standing bank, the Bayern LB, was not the cheapest" (17, pa. 48).	i
		S5	No independent services	The traditional bank's services are limited and not independently.	"Well, like every bank that mainly products of the bank, the service ability of the bank or branch with which you make business are defined and alternatives like FinTechs are not provided since the bank is biased" (11, pa. 22).	i
		S6	Communication channel as disadvantage	The traditional communication like appointments or personal contacts are seen as disadvantage.	No example since no company mentioned such disadvantage.	d

		S7	Financing and operations from one hand	Having one relationship bank for financing and operational issues is a disadvantage since the financing issues can influence the operational businesses.	"That is always the problem, from my point of view, I had that before, that a house bank was also the financing partner. In my view, this has developed unfavourably because risk management on the financing side has paralysed operational development in the first place" (18, pa. 29).	i
		S8	No negative effects	Relationship and traditional banks do not have disadvantages.	"I see by the way we do the business no disadvantages. Only benefits" (12, pa. 50).	d
C7	Indifferent points to relationship and traditional banks	S1	Indifference of covenants	Covenants are neither an advantage nor a disadvantage.	"So now we have only one financial covenant in our loan agreement which is not a problem" (17, pa. 52).	i
		S2	Indifference of collateral	Due to relationship banking the collateral requirements are neither lower nor higher.	"Let us say that we do not provide a collateral. And that is known from the start and accepted that way. Otherwise we would not do it. I cannot treat the others more unfavourable" (19, pa. 44).	i
		S3	Indifference of interest rate	Due to relationship banking the interest rate is neither lower nor higher.	Our rating is indeed in the investment grade. So that is why the difference is not that big anymore. Even if the evaluations come then, the PD (Probability Default). It is relatively the same. That means there is not much room left. They are about the same (19, pa. 42).	i
C8	Advantages of crowdlending	S1	Higher velocity or easier as advantage	The procedure of crowdlending is faster or easier, and thus it is an advantage in relation to traditional banking. This includes that the procedure is completely online without physical meetings.	"Supposedly, it is the way it is sold, absolutely easy" (19, pa. 78).	d
		S2	Positive signalling effect	The publication to the investors is a positive signalling effect to the market.	"Because such a thing can certainly also be part of our approach, we always have to think in equity story. Which messages do you give out? What is positive for the company? And that is certainly positive for the company. Because it simply corresponds to the spirit of times a bit. The evolution" (13, pa. 62).	d

		S3	Less regulation as advantage	It is an advantage that crowdlending platforms are less regulated than traditional banking.	"That can go faster or can run without obligations, I can imagine" (I1, pa. 34).	d
		S4	Higher flexibility or transparency	Crowdlending is more flexible or transparent in relation to traditional banking.	"I think it is certainly more flexible" (I8, pa. 47).	d
C9	Disadvantages of crowdlending	S1	Slower or more inconvenient	The procedure of crowdlending is slower or more inconvenient, and thus it is a disadvantage.	"For 2.5 million, I make a call and hold a five-minute conversation. Then I have 2.5 million. I do not need a published funding. I do not need anything. The issue is done. This is also a convenience factor" (I4, pa. 66).	d
		S2	Negative signalling effect	The publication of the funding to the investors is a negative signalling effect.	"I would damage the core content of our brand" (I6, pa. 34).	d
		S3	Less regulation as disadvantage	It is a disadvantage that crowdlending platforms are less regulated than traditional banking.	"And, also these regulations convey a certain security" (I1, pa. 40).	d
		S4	Idea reproduction as disadvantage	The executive considers it risky that the idea, which is published to the investors, can be reproduced.	"In the field of innovations this is a very close market for us. And we have already been copied, of course" (I6, pa. 40).	d
		S5	Personal guarantee as disadvantage	It is a disadvantage or even an exclusion criterion that a personal guarantee is required.	"Once you are in the legal form of a limited liability company or a stock company and you do not get one hundred percent of the shares anywhere, this will never be the case. There will never be a CEO in personal liability. Nobody does" (I2, pa. 66).	d
		S6	Threshold 2.5 mn € as disadvantage	It is a disadvantage or even an exclusion criterion that the volume per funding is limited to 2.5 mn €.	"Another serious criterion would be the amount of the funding" (I4, pa. 66).	d
		S7	Maturity as disadvantage	The limited maturity is a disadvantage.	"And I think you will not find anyone for a long-term financing. That would be more of a bridging loan" (I9, pa. 58).	d
		S8	Interest or fee as disadvantage	The interest rates or fees are a disadvantage or even an exclusion criterion.	"16.6% is of course completely ineligible. 2.5% good. But I would not do it today" (I1, pa. 38).	d

		S9	Unknown topic	The topic is unknown, and thus it is a disadvantage.	"Borrowing money somewhere along the way would mean that I would have to convince my board of the benefits of this FinTech. And then I think, if someone does not deal with the topics, that if you do not quite understand that, you would also decline" (I2, pa. 86).	i
		S10	Investors' feedback as disadvantage	Investors' feedback of product or service is a disadvantage because the investors do not have an expertise.	"Just as if you are a sports car manufacturer and anyone who can pay one million euros explains how the new sports car should look like because he has already bought it once before. So that is why I do not value the expertise from the outside so much and have no meaning for me anymore" (I5, pa. 80).	i
		S11	Customers as investors as disadvantage	It is a disadvantage if the customers are simultaneously the investors because if the company has difficult times and cannot repay the loan or interest it can lose its customers.	"Because the fan base is, I say, the circle of customers and if you come to a bad situation and the best customers do not longer get their money, then you lose these fans. Also, not good" (I2, pa. 88).	i
		S12	Inadequate for IPO or sale of company	For a planned IPO or sale of the company, crowdlending is not suitable but rather a more stable and transparent financing.	"And if I am already in a more mature stage and I say, as a mid-sized company I am planning to go IPO to take the next big step. Or at the end of the day, I want to sell my company in a timely manner, then one should rather, I can say, demonstrate more transparent and stable structures. That helps immensely in such a process" (I8, pa. 49).	i
		S13	Risk of disappearance	The risk that the platform cannot establish and disappears again is considered as disadvantage.	"And the house bank is normally available tomorrow. I do not know that from the platforms" (I6, pa. 18).	i
C10	Indifferent points to crowdlending	S1	Indifference of less regulations	Less regulation is neither an advantage nor a disadvantage.	"Yeah, well, what would scare me off is when I lend money. This does not happen in our business model anyway because our business model is that we buy and sell goods again and not that we lend money" (I2, pa. 86).	i

		S2	Indifference of personal guarantee	The required personal guarantee is neither an advantage nor a disadvantage.	"In my individual case, if you are familiar with the legal entity form of a KG and you consider my role as complementary, this is the case anyway, since I am fully liable" (I1, pa. 30).	i
		S3	Indifference of risk of idea reproducing	The executive does not see any risk of reproducing the idea that is published in the funding.	"Actually, not so much because the ideas are only the knowledge, when we approach new projects, that is in our heads in the minds of engineers or software developers" (I3, pa. 66).	i
		S4	Indifference of threshold of 2.5 mn €	The threshold is neither an advantage nor a disadvantage.	"Not mandatory. There are already projects that exceed this amount which far exceed 2.5 million" (Interviewee1, pa. 50).	i
C11	Circumstances for using crowdlending	S1	No bank loan available	Crowdlending would be used in case no bank loans are available.	"Only if the house bank could not keep up. Pure from today's point of view" (I5, pa. 58).	d
		S2	Equal economic conditions	Crowdlending would be used in case the conditions are the same as a bank loan.	"Interviewer: But let us say the terms are the same. Would you like to try it? Interviewee3: Yes, I could imagine. Because it just fits a bit to our corporate philosophy. It also has the touch of Industry 4.0 or this digital approach. In that sense, I can already imagine that" (I3, pa. 53-54).	d
		S3	Better economic conditions	Crowdlending would be used in case the conditions are better than a bank loan.	"FinTechs involves more risks, more uncertainty and that would be the case in the beginning, then the interest rates would have to be correspondingly cheaper" (I1, pa. 40).	d
		S4	No or last option	Crowdlending would not be used not or solely if there is no other financing available. Text is only allocated to this category if the executive does not mention during the interview that he would use it if the conditions would be better than traditional financing.	"Interviewer: Let us say the internal financing is not enough and you would need additional funds. Under what circumstances would you apply for a loan lending platform? Interviewee6: If you want to get an insight into large medium-sized companies, family-run companies, then the answer is, then everything else would have gone down the drain. Then our core strategy would have gone away if I resorted to these means" (I6, pa. 31-32).	d

C12	Advantages of crowdinvesting	S1	Positive signalling effect	The publication to the investors is a positive signalling effect.	"Bank financing is more likely to take place in the backyard. Here I am completely open and transparent. That might be a disadvantage, but I believe that the advantages outweigh. From my personal point of view that one just goes with the time that it suits the company, the way of financing" (I3, pa. 76).	i
C13	Disadvantages of crowdinvesting	S1	Possible influence as disadvantage	A possible influence on the company's business is considered as negative.	"With a mezzanine share, it is a step more extensive, more extensive in terms of influences" (I1, pa. 62).	i
		S2	Economic conditions as disadvantage	The economic conditions are a disadvantage or even an exclusion criterion.	"At 10%? You know, I am currently in the overdraft below 1%. Without having to hand over collateral somewhere. And that is why I mean, there is every form of financing and with my credit rating, I do not have to resort to other markets where to which other risk structures are related " (I2, pa. 64).	i
		S3	Higher administrative effort	Crowdinvesting is related to a higher administrative effort.	"And, of course, it will be a high effort from the structuring. Because it is just a mixture of equity and debt capital" (I4, pa. 68).	i
C14	Circumstances for using crowdinvesting and preferences	S1	Crowdinvesting is preferred over crowdlending	Financing through crowdinvesting is preferred over crowdlending.	"But today, I would prefer crowdinvesting to crowdlending a bit" (I3, pa. 70).	d
		S2	Crowdinvesting is preferred over bank loan	Financing through crowdinvesting is preferred over a bank loan.	"It is at least an equivalent alternative, if not a bit preferred alternative" (I3, pa. 74).	d
		S3	Crowdlending is preferred over crowdinvesting	Financing through crowdlending is preferred over crowdinvesting.	"Interviewer: Ok. And would you rather tend to crowdlending or crowdinvesting? The second would be with the mezzanine instruments. Interviewee10: Crowdlending" (I10, pa. 75).	d
		S4	No or last option	Crowdinvesting would not be used or solely as last option in case no other financing is available.	"You only do that if there is no other way" (I1, pa. 62).	d
C15	Advantages of factoring platforms	-	-	Any advantages related to factoring platforms.	No example since no executive mentioned such advantage.	d

C16	Disadvantages of factoring platforms	S1	High administrative effort	The procedure of factoring platforms is more administrative, and thus it is a disadvantage.	"That does not work for us. Because of the small business. I have a customer because every single screw box is calculated individually. Because it is just an automated process. I have about 10,000 invoices a month. And there is maybe an average of 40-50 euros each" (I4, pa. 74).	d
		S2	Negative signalling effect	The publication of the usage of factoring causes a negative signal to the market.	"Ultimately, this is always a signal that the company is doing badly. He is in this situation. This is not just a cherry on the cake, with which I start my company on other legs but there are already considerable problems there" (I1, pa. 64).	d
		S3	Economic conditions as disadvantage	The economic conditions are a disadvantage.	"That should make it easier for me to put up a cash for, I do not know, 0.9% percent and not let me discuss 4% off my demands. Does not make sense" (I2, pa. 96).	d
C17	Circumstances for factoring platforms	S1	Equal economic conditions	Factoring platforms would be used in case the conditions are the same as traditional factoring.	"Interviewer: I mean you do not use factoring now, but maybe you would want to use factoring, could you imagine that? Interviewee10: I can basically imagine it" (I10, pa. 85-86).	d
		S2	Better economic conditions	Factoring platforms would be solely used in case the conditions are better than traditional factoring or bank loans.	"So, the factoring rate would have to be significantly below the borrowing rate which I pay to the bank" (I2, pa. 96).	d
		S3	Factoring platform is preferred over traditional factoring	Factoring platforms are preferred over traditional factoring.	"In that sense, I would perhaps prefer this from" (I3, pa. 88).	d
		S4	No or last option	Factoring is not used or solely used in case other instruments are not available.	"I would not do that. For the moment I completely exclude that" (I1, pa. 64).	d
		S5	High volume or risk	Factoring is individually used in case of accounts receivable that have a high volume or risk.	"Maybe with a high account receivable where we cannot get further. And in other cases, if we have a 30 million account receivable, I would not take the risk because the risk is too high for me" (I5, pa. 94).	i

Appendix F: Guideline expert interviews

1 Information of company and role

1.1 Please, could you provide some information about your company?

Key terms: founding year, turnover, employees, industry.

1.2 And about your role?

Key terms: decision-making authority.

2 Financing preferences and relationship banking

2.1 What financing instruments do you use for your company?

Key terms: bank loan, mezzanine, factoring.

2.2 What type of financing do you prefer for investments?

Key terms: external debt, external equity, internal financing.

2.3 Do you have one or more long-term bank relationships?

2.4 In your opinion, what are the major advantages of a bank relationship? And major disadvantages?

Key terms: trust, availability, maturity, interest, fee, collateral, appointments.

3 Substitute for traditional financing by crowdlending and crowdinvesting

3.1 Do you know crowdlending and crowdinvesting? Do you have already experience with it? May I tell you about it?

3.2 Assuming you want to finance an investment opportunity, under what circumstances would you request for a crowdlending loan?

Key terms: no bank loan available, lower or equal economic conditions (interest and fee) as a bank loan, diversification, preference to bank.

3.3 In your opinion, what are the major advantages of crowdlending relative to a traditional bank loan? And disadvantages?

Key terms: collateral, velocity, simplicity e.g. no branch visit, repayment prior to maturity without fee, threshold 2.5 mn€, risk to less regulation, risk of reproduce idea.

3.4 Assuming you want to finance an investment opportunity, under what circumstances would you request for funds through a crowdinvesting platform?

Key terms: no bank loan available, no crowdlending available, too low equity ratio.

3.5 In what way do you consider crowdinvesting as alternative to a traditional bank loan?

3.6 In your opinion, what are the major advantages of crowdinvesting relative to traditional banking? And disadvantages?

Key terms: velocity, simplicity e.g. no branch visit, threshold 2.5 mn€, risk to less regulation, risk of reproduce idea.

4 Substitute for traditional financing instruments by factoring platforms

4.1 Do you know factoring platforms? Do you have already experience with it? May I tell you about it?

4.2 Assuming you want to refinance an account receivable, under what circumstances would you request for funds through a factoring platform?

Key terms: no other instruments available, lower or equal fees.

4.3 In your opinion, what are the major advantages of factoring platforms relative to traditional factoring? And disadvantages?

Key terms: fee, velocity, simplicity, flexibility, no minimum turnover requirement.

5 Further questions

5.1 In this context, is there anything I did not ask but you expected to be asked?

5.2 Referring to the interview context, is there anything else you consider as important?

The interview questions (IQ) were categorised by the following five topics: IQ1) general information about company and role, IQ2) financing preferences and bank relationships, IQ3) substitute for traditional financing instruments by crowdlending and crowdinvesting, IQ4) substitute for traditional financing instruments by factoring platforms, and IQ5) closing questions.

- IQ1.1: Please, could you provide some information about your company? IQ1.2: And about your role? R1.1 and R.1.2: Both questions could bring additional information to the information collected in advance. Additionally, it is a topic to smoothly start the interview.
- IQ2.1: What financing instruments do you use for your company? R2.1: This question provides an understanding of the current financing situation which is also relevant for further questions to be asked in the interview. IQ2.2: What type of financing do you prefer for investments? R2.2: This question is based on the static trade-off and pecking theory. This is relevant since crowdlending is debt-based, crowdinvesting mezzanine-based, and factoring internal financing. IQ2.3: Do you have one or more long-term bank relationships? R2.3: This question provides the information whether or not the company has long-term bank relationships and is the starting point for the next question. IQ2.4: In your opinion, what are the major advantages of a bank relationship? And disadvantages? R2.4: These questions provide first indications to which extent the service of financing FinTechs is a substitute for traditional banking services.
- IQ3.1: Do you know crowdlending and crowdinvesting? Do you have experience with it? May I tell you about it? R3.1: These questions provide the interviewee's knowledge base and experience gained. Additionally, it offers for the interviewer the opportunity to provide more information about the business model. IQ3.2: Assuming you want to finance an investment opportunity, under what circumstances would you request for a crowdlending loan? R3.2: This is a hypothetical question and should provide indications to which extent the service of crowdlending is a substitute for traditional banking services. IQ3.3: In your opinion, what are the major advantages of crowdlending relative to a traditional bank loan? And disadvantages? R3.3: These questions provide factors that influence the evaluation of to which extent the service of crowdlending is a substitute for traditional banking services. Therefore, it provides a deeper insight. IQ3.4: Assuming you want to finance an investment opportunity, under what circumstances would you request for funds through a crowdinvesting platform? R3.4: This is a hypothetical question and should provide indications to which extent the service of crowdinvesting is a substitute for traditional banking services. IQ3.5: In what way do you consider crowdinvesting as alternative to a traditional bank loan? R3.5: This question provides indications to which extent the service

of crowdinvesting is a substitute for traditional bank loans. IQ3.6: In your opinion, what are the major advantages of crowdinvesting relative to traditional banking? And disadvantages? R3.6: These questions provide factors that influence the evaluation of to which extent the service of crowdinvesting is a substitute for traditional financing instruments. Therefore, it provides a deeper insight.

- IQ4.1: Do you know factoring platforms? Do you have experience with it? May I tell you about it? R4.1: These questions provide the interviewee's knowledgebase and experience gained. Additionally, it offers for the interviewer the opportunity to provide more information about the business model. IQ4.2: Assuming you want to refinance an account receivable, under what circumstances would you request for funds through a factoring platform? R4.2: This is a hypothetical question and should provide indications to which extent the service of factoring platforms is a substitute for traditional banking services. R4.3: In your opinion, what are the major advantages of factoring platforms relative to traditional factoring? And disadvantages? R4.3: These questions provide factors that influence the evaluation to which extent the service of factoring platforms is a substitute for traditional banking services. Therefore, it provides a deeper insight.
- IQ5.1: In this context, is there anything I did not ask but you expected to be asked? R5.1: This question checks whether there is a further major point that was not asked. Additionally, it provides the information whether the executive manager's expectation was different from actual interview. This can be helpful for the further interviews. IQ5.2: Referring to the interview context, is there anything else you consider as important? R5.2: This question offers the opportunity to provide any further information and is a smooth end for the interview.

Appendix G: Profile matrix expert interviews

Category	Sub-category	LME										Total			
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10				
C1	Executives' knowledge of or experience with financing FinTechs	S1	Knowledge of or experience with crowdfunding	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	7	
		S2	Knowledge of or experience with crowdlending	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		S3	Knowledge of or experience with crowdinvesting	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		S4	Knowledge of or experience with factoring	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
C2	Financing instruments in usage	S1	External equity	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	5	
		S2	Bank loan	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	10	
		S3	Mezzanine	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	8	
		S4	Factoring	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	10	
		S5	Others	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	5	
C3	Financing instrument preferences	S1	Internal financing is preferred over all other	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	10	
		S2	Debt financing is preferred over mezzanine or external equity	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	8	
		S3	Mezzanine or external equity is preferred over debt financing	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	2	
C4	Characteristics of relationship banking	-	-	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	10	
C5	Positive effects of relationship traditional banks	S1	Higher reliability	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	9	
		S2	Specific knowledge and special or customized offers	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	4	
		S3	Higher velocity or easier	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	8	
		S4	Lower interest	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	5	
		S5	Lower collateral requirements	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	
		S6	Higher loan volumes available	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	
		S7	Communication channel as advantage	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	6	
		S8	Plausibility of investment	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	2	
C6	Negative effects of relationship and traditional banks	S1	Dependency on loan availability	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	3	
		S2	Covenants as disadvantage	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	3	
		S3	Collateral as disadvantage	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	
		S4	Higher interest rate	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	
		S5	No independent services	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	

Category	Sub-category	LME										Total			
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10				
	S6	Communication channel as disadvantage	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
	S7	Financing and operations from one hand	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	2		
	S8	No negative effects	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	5		
C7	Indifferent points to relationship and traditional banks	S1	Indifference of covenants	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	6	
		S2	Indifference of collateral	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	4	
		S3	Indifference of interest rate	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	2
C8	Advantages of crowdlending	S1	Higher velocity or easier as advantage	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	2
		S2	Positive signalling effect	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	4
		S3	Less regulation as advantage	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	5
		S4	Higher flexibility or transparency	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	2
C9	Disadvantages of crowdlending	S1	Slower or more inconvenient	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	3	
		S2	Negative signalling effect	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	5	
		S3	Less regulation as disadvantage	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	4	
		S4	Idea reproduction as disadvantage	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	
		S5	Personal guarantee as disadvantage	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	5	
		S6	Threshold 2.5 mn € as disadvantage	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	5	
		S7	Maturity as disadvantage	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	
		S8	Interest or fee as disadvantage	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	3	
		S9	Unknown topic	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	4	
		S10	Investors' feedback as disadvantage	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	
		S11	Customers as investors as disadvantage	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	
		S12	Inadequate for IPO or sale of company	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	
		S13	Risk of disappearance	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	
C10	Indifferent points to crowdlending	S1	Indifference of less regulations	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	2	
		S2	Indifference of personal guarantee	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	
		S3	Indifference of risk of idea reproducing	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	5	
		S4	Indifference of threshold of 2.5 mn €	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	3	
C11	S1	No bank loan available	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	2		

Category	Sub-category	LME										Total		
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10			
Circumstances for using crowdlending	S2	Equal economic conditions	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	3	
	S3	Better economic conditions	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	4	
	S4	No or last option	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	2	
C12	Advantages of crowdinvesting	S1	Positive signalling effect	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	
C13	Disadvantages of crowdinvesting	S1	Possible influence as disadvantage	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	2	
		S2	Economic conditions as disadvantage	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	
		S3	High administrative effort	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	
C14	Circumstances for using crowdinvesting and preferences	S1	Crowdinvesting is preferred over crowdlending	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	3	
		S2	Crowdinvesting is preferred over bank loan	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	
		S3	Crowdlending is preferred over crowdinvesting	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	2
		S4	No or last option	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	6
C15	Advantages of factoring platforms	-	-	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
C16	Disadvantages of factoring platforms	S1	High administrative effort	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	2	
		S2	Negative signalling effect	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	
		S3	Economic conditions as disadvantage	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	2	
C17	Circumstances for factoring platforms	S1	Equal economic conditions	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	2
		S2	Better economic conditions	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
		S3	Factoring platform is preferred over traditional factoring	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
		S4	No or last option	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	3
		S5	High volume or risk	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1

Appendix H: Transcript 1 to 10

Transcript: Interview 1

1	Interviewer: What kind of financing instruments do you currently use? #00:01:58-7#
2	Interviewee1: So, there were two main pillars from the past. Once the self-financing, i.e. the financing from own funds. If, in special case, they were not sufficient for larger investments, then the classic bank financing through loans. #00:02:17-0#
3	Interviewer: Ok, through traditional bank loans. Do you use overdrafts? #00:02:21-1#
4	Interviewee1: No, we do not need it generally. #00:02:27-4#
5	Interviewer: Did you gain experience with mezzanine instruments? #00:02:35-0#
6	Interviewee1: No, not at all. So, we are really very conservative so far. So, my father, who passed away in 2016, had a very special influence on that. And it was so important to him. But you can find that in so-called family-owned companies that one always earns ideally from own resources first. If you have earned it, you can actually spend it again. Of course, if you look at the German entrepreneurial landscape like that, it is very solid, only a little bit dynamic, but a very solid way of financing. Because you are free of all bank influence. If you, e.g. I do not know if you know that. Company X. Person Y set up X in the 1970s / 1980s which has failed through the corresponding actions of the banks. In which for one day the loans have been rejected. Where they say today that was most likely a put-up affair. As one is independent of banks in the context of such funding from own funds. #00:04:17-1#
7	Interviewer: I understood. Do I am right that you prefer internal financing for future investments? #00:04:22-6#
8	Interviewee1: For the future, I feel the need to relax my father's consistent perspective. We have something planned and you have to see that you are putting the necessary investments for machines and organisations in the right direction. So, that you can finance a certain need for action. Basically, I see also other possibilities. Even though, I admit it quite openly, we are still unfamiliar with the respective risks or the corresponding influence that can be expected. #00:05:15-8#
9	Interviewer: Do you prefer mezzanine instruments over bank loans? #00:05:21-1#
10	Interviewee1: The bank loan is something that I used to. It is safe. Because it often worked. Regarding mezzanine, I do not know the conditions right now. There is also a lack. I say in concrete terms the advise. What could be done if a suitable form of financing is lucrative, i.e. of interest and it would also fit well into the project. Then I say, if there is a professional who accompanies this for us or on our side, it would be an easier step for us in this way. When one says, with what risks one goes. Because that is always the way to weigh which risks are connected. What happens if you have to rebuild it? What happens if it works normally, if you shorten or if you want to extend? All of these topics, which have probably been extensively studied in large companies with appropriately developed business departments, are on our scale rather rare with our past. So, for us, now it is still unfamiliar. #00:06:59-7#
11	Interviewer: In what way do you have a fixed equity ratio, also regarding the future? Or do you say, you do not have a fixed equity ratio or it depends on the respective conditions and circumstances? #00:07:21-6#
12	Interviewee1: Of course, that is the question. How much debt relative to equity? Especially of really large companies, the saying is that ratios with 50% to 60% debt is

	completely okay. This is not my point of view according to our kind of company. I would define a limit of 10%. This means 10% debt relative to the liable equity, this is definitely the limit. However, in the long term this could be increased to 20% to 30%. But I only see the necessity when it is really there. #00:08:08-5#
13	Interviewer: You mentioned that you had some bank loans. Do you have one or more long-term bank relations? #00:08:19-9#
14	Interviewee1: Yes, we have one relationship bank with which we process more or less the standardised business. In addition, there is another bank which was involved once for a financing issue and which is especially processing our foreign trade. #00:08:40-7#
15	Interviewer: Do you see any advantages or disadvantages of relationship banks? #00:08:51-4#
16	Interviewee1: The advantage is surely that you can rely on each other and that you know each other. You know the business or more specific the person on the other side which can be a stability. This means if you need a certain financing solution for a certain foreign trade business, the question is whether the bank can provide this. Do they have a solution or do they make a mess? The question is what kind of service ability do they have. If you know this, the relationship becomes more intensive since you do more and more business together. #00:09:48-0#
17	Interviewer: You can rely more and more on the bank. In case you are in a situation in which it is a bit more difficult, you know the bank is on your side. The bank relationship already exists for a long term, there is long-term cooperation, and the bank is a reliable partner. #00:10:03-5#
18	Interviewee1: The bank is a reliable partner, yes. Especially regarding the operating business related to payment transactions and hedges of foreign trade business. There is an experience. In the meaning that they do this, the hedges and formalities which are needed. This is for us very important since we do not have such a department or structure which is build up for such foreign trade. There was not such business. We have many European countries. In total, we export to 30 countries. In case you have a country beyond the European countries with certain requirements in payment transactions or transportations that have to be fulfilled, you have to bring all this information together. Maybe you have a cooperation with a stirring partner on site who said, yes wonderful, the customer wants this and that product. Perfect, now it can start. Then you have to understand and collect the information in a relatively short term, how the business should be organised. How it should be processed. A letter of credit is from country to country different. #00:11:38-7#
19	Interviewer: You mentioned that you have a second bank for a financing issue. Did you receive better conditions from the bank with which you have a longer relationship than with the new one? #00:11:52-7#
20	Interviewee1: In general, yes. The risk to lose the relationship was always too unpleasant for the bank. #00:12:14-6#
21	Interviewer: And do you see any disadvantages? #00:12:14-6#
22	Interviewee1: Well, like every bank. That mainly the products and services of the bank or branch with which you make business are defined and alternatives like FinTechs are not provided since the bank is biased. This is less dynamic. When I think about the Bitcoin topic. As all banks exorbitantly cautioned. I say, sure, it has its reasonability to some extent. But you do not have to question the whole currency system only while there is some hype in the country. This is based on the banking system and

	safeguarding reasons. If you would be a banker, you probably do the same. #00:13:34-7#
23	Interviewer: How is it about the covenants? There are often covenants of banks which implies the regularly reporting of annual reports, the fulfilment of certain ratios, and fulfilment security measures to secure certain assets. Do you see any disadvantages? #00:14:04-1#
24	Interviewee1: Yes, of course. If you have to provide certain collaterals like mortgages for larger investments, then it is a major handicap. In case of a mortgage and a default event, like the mentioned company X, the bank has full access. If you do not like it, hands off. All other things are not that much important. #00:14:40-7#
25	Interviewer: Regarding the two bank relationships, the longer-term and shorter-term. You mentioned that the interest was better at the longer-term relationship bank. Did you have the opinion that the conditions were better as well, meaning including the covenants and collateral requirements. This means whether the longer-term relationship bank had less covenants and collateral requirements. #00:15:00-7#
26	Interviewee1: Regarding the collateral, this is about the same. You can identify that the processes are standardised due to the Basel requirements. In case the bank defines a certain loan volume, you have to provide this or that kind of information or collateral. This is similar to all banks. The points are the conditions and what they are offer. For example, an energy loan, a specialised loan with low interests in the course of energy saving technologies. This was very interesting because it fitted to us. If another bank does not provide such offer, either the bank does not have it or not thinking about to offer it, then the offer is different. #00:16:17-8#
27	Interviewer: Then, we are jumping to crowdlending and crowdinvesting. We shortly already talked about it. I told you some things about it and you indicated your opinion towards crowdlending and crowdinvesting. Assuming you want to invest, under which circumstances would you request a financing through crowdlending? Crowdlending, like a bank loan with a fixed interest rate. #00:16:53-5#
28	Interviewee1: To answer this question soundly, I would need more knowledge about it. How does the financing really work? Also, in the respect of collateral and accessibility to the collateral. Regarding this, I know too less to say under which circumstances I would finance through crowdlending. I can imagine I would do it without any obstacles if there is an advisor who advises us to find a solution which is fitted to us. However, you need an expert. A soundly expert who might be liable if something goes wrong. In this case, not only seller of souls who tell you something, instead you have the impression that the guy provides you with passion and has an obligation. #00:18:17-9#
29	Interviewer: Then, I can say some details. According to the most crowdlending platforms, the borrower has to provide a personal guarantee for the loan. There are no further collateral requirements. If you want to finance a machinery, you do not have to provide the machinery as collateral, solely the personal guarantee. Is this an exclusion criterion for you? #00:18:49-3#
30	Interviewee1: In my individual case, if you are familiar with the legal entity form of a KG and you consider my role as complementary, this is the case anyway, since I am fully liable. For other cases, I could imagine that there must be a strong personal relation to the company in order to be liable for the loan. #00:19:24-2#
31	Interviewer: Yes, as complementary you are fully liable anyway. Regarding crowdlending, you get a support from the platform, however, there is no such advisor

	like at a bank. At the bank you have an advisor who is searching for a financial solution. At the platform it is not the case. #00:19:49-1#
32	Interviewee1: I tell you, in the beginning until you know how it works you have to have input to be able to estimate that. When done once, twice or three times, there is a certain amount of certainty as with all the new procedures you have. Starting from the smartphone, God knows where. If one knows, what happened and has from more or less professionals the statements and can estimate what the structure is. I cannot do that either. #00:20:29-0#
33	Interviewer: FinTechs are less regulated than banks. At banks you know it. You already said so. There is Basel and that is just a regularity of many. Regarding FinTechs, it is true that in the case of crowdlending, the loan is finally distributed via a bank. So, the investors give the money to the platform. The platform to the bank. The bank provides the loan. But the bank then resells the partial claims directly to the investors. So, the whole loan claim as partial claims to the investors. And, so the bank is completely out. But otherwise there are not so many regulations. The FinTechs do not need a banking license. Would you consider that negatively? #00:21:18-0#
34	Interviewee1: I am just wondering what this may have a negative impact on me or on our company or on this form of financing? That can go faster or can run without obligations, I can imagine. The question is what components are involved which may cause problems in the long term. #00:21:49-0#
35	Interviewer: Of course, investors have more risk in that sense. Because investors give the money and you would take that as a borrower. Thus, there might be more risk on the investor side. #00:22:02-3#
36	Interviewee1 I would now expect interest rates to be higher. #00:22:03-4#
37	Interviewer: So, the interest rates are in crowdlending between 2.49%, so rounded up to 2.5% and 16.6% currently. I have looked at all crowdlending platforms that meet certain quality criteria, and there are different ratings that vary from platform to platform. That depends on the credit rating you have and the maturity. The interest rate varies between 2.5% and 16.6%. #00:22:45-2#
38	Interviewee1: All right, 16.6% is of course completely ineligible. 2.5% good. But I would not do it today. Yes, there is the context. Because there is less regulation, there is more risk. So, you pay more. #00:23:06-4#
39	Interviewer: Yes, but of course it can also be the opposite because the bank is no longer in between. So, the bank gets deposits from you, from me, from different people and then provides a loan. In between is a margin. Now, with investors and borrowers coming together and having a proper risk assessment, the margin is not in between, of course. That in theory, it could also be that the interest rate is higher for the investor and at the same time lower for the borrower. So, the question is already up to date and in my investigation. It is just that they focus on medium-sized companies that do not have the best credit rating. But it may also be just an initial stage that evolves later. I would not focus too much on interest rates. That might also fit to my next question. If the interest rate is the same, you do not know so much about crowdlending yet, but let us just say, I have just said a few things with the regulations and safety, the interest rate would be the same, would you or could you tell if you would try crowdlending? #00:24:29-8#
40	Interviewee1: From today's perspective, no. From today's perspective because I am just used to the classic bank loan. And also, these regulations convey a certain security.

That would be the first step there. If the alternative over the FinTechs involves more risks, more uncertainty and that would be the case in the beginning, then the interest rates would have to be correspondingly cheaper. If you say that, good grief, if that is half a percentage point or one percentage point. My dear man then you have to deal with it, if you save money. #00:25:15-9#

41 Interviewer: Ok. Then I understood that if the interest rate were lower, then you would test it if necessary. You would delve deeper into the subject in order to weigh the risks even more. But then it would be ... #00:25:33-6#

42 Interviewee1: Yes, it should be cheaper. One more question about personal liability. If I imagine even if you have a GmbH and the CEO is facing the situation that he needs funding. The manager will then not go into the commitment. Who will do that then? Normally this would have to be done by the shareholders. Either in the commonality. Then, again the question is how to organise it? If you have 5-6 shareholders in the GmbH, then each would have to take over a sixth. I think that is difficult. #00:26:12-8#

43 Interviewer: Yes, I agree. So, I see that as a point that could be a hurdle. I am also looking forward to my next interview. There it is more or less the case that the managing directors are not involved at the same time. And it will probably get more difficult. #00:26:32-2#

44 Interviewee1: That is the whole point. How does one want to organise it? If he does not have partners who are very close to the daily's business. If they are very close, then they might have a look and say, well, for the plant, for the packaging plant over x millions, so that we strengthen the efficiency. Maybe there is the willingness of the individual to participate. If in individual cases, perhaps the shareholder gets a profit share for it. There is the question of how to do that. To take the risk, he would have to get some bonus. That he would then, if the profits increase through these investments and he has mitigated the risk with, he would indeed get a higher share. So, I think of shareholders, if there are several shareholders for a very exciting topic, whether that is solvable? #00:27:47-6#

45 Interviewer: Yes. I also see that as a point. I just think about the future. It is not a point carved in stone. That could be even changed by FinTechs. If there is a need and that is the only point, I think that could be also solved by FinTech provider. #00:28:09-7#

46 Interviewee1: In this constellation, as you just put it, I consider this type of financing very suitable for sole proprietors or start-ups. Because they regularly have the problem to even find a bank that provides money for a fixed idea. And if you find people who you can explain that way. What is this TV soap called? The Dragons' Den. And you have a smart concept. Some sell their new porridge or whatever that means. And the banks say I do not spend any money on Porridge, but when people find out about this crowdfunding community, they say something because it is interesting. Because I like it a lot and it fits in well with the times. And that is even a bit higher in terms of interest rates. Because the question is something going on or do I have higher interest rates? And if that suits. Then of course that says, that is my baby, that is my kid, that is where I value it. So, I personally go into the risk. That could work much better. #00:29:28-6#

47 Interviewer: Yes, exactly. There are also many FinTechs who focus on start-ups. They are not in my focus right now. I just wanted to look at those who are not focused on start-ups because the banks, just like you said, are not lending to start-ups like that. And I am just interested to what extent the bank's business is at risk. #00:29:50-4#

48 Interviewee1: Yes, you could go there and say, exactly this shareholder problem, this personal liability is the whole very much in the way. #00:29:59-3#

49	Interviewer: There is one more point. They are all limited to 2.5 million volumes. But per funding. You could also promote or upload multiple fundings. Otherwise you would have to create a prospectus for investors and that is related to a high effort. That would not be profitable anymore. Do you see that as a disadvantage? #00:30:23-8#
50	Interviewee1: Not mandatory. There are already projects that exceed this amount which far exceed 2.5 million. Where, for example, building a hall which we have just finished. That goes far beyond. But complementary investments or similar are doing well with 2.5 million. So, as a stone in diversity. #00:31:04-7#
51	Interviewer: If you upload the funding, they will be visible to investors. To what extent would that be a disadvantage for you, that the idea behind it or a project, whatever it is, could be copied? #00:31:22-7#
52	Interviewee1: Yes, that is the topic of competitive behaviour or exposure to competitors. That is a very significant point. I would not want it now. Because an advantage of a KG with my personal liability is also that we are not subject to publicity. That you will not find any annual reports or something else in the Federal Gazette. That is in the current competitive situation in our product niche, one must clearly say, where there are nationwide four players already very helpful that one does not have to answer questions there. Also, towards the trade partners. We also have a very big and important food trade business. There are actually still five people as buyers who make the market today. And if they have the opportunity to look how our company financially looks like very concrete, then in the best case if we have a good year, they say I shorten something away. #00:32:44-6#
53	Interviewer: I understood that as a point. Of course, you would also have to, if you upload the funding or in the case of financing, to report to the investors on a regular basis. Quasi how it has developed etc. #00:33:05-3#
54	Interviewee1: If this is published for everyone, not just for the corresponding investors. #00:33:12-3#
55	Interviewer: These reports would only be for the investors. Initially in the funding, which would show what you want to do, you do not have to publish any numbers. You just have to publish the numbers to the platform. And if the conclusion takes place regularly towards the investors. But for potential investors, you just need the funding. You want to build a new warehouse, introduce the company. That would be enough for that. Another point: When you publish the funding and it becomes visible to the investors. This can also be a marketing effect, just to show presence. #00:35:45-2#
56	Interviewee1: Yes, of course. #00:35:45-2#
57	Interviewer: How would you see that as an advantage, and perhaps that would outweigh the risk that the idea might be copied by competitors? #00:35:45-2#
58	Interviewee1: If you only want to run a certain project or a specific image marketing, then the component that you need financing or in the context of a financing request to the outside is not required. There are plenty of opportunities to present what the company has in mind, etc., in order to build a certain image, if that is what you want. I think that is not absolutely necessary. Just because it is right now or how it goes on. The question is, how is such a form of financing judged by the public or the professional public? If so, as just indicated. Banks do not give money to certain companies but the FinTechs because of the lack of regulations. Then that would mean by the reverse assumption if one considers the professional public that they have problems with the financing. Then what you want to send, like a solid company which you continue to

	<p>build on. Would translate the solidity of the cooperation and make it questionable. Logically we are on the other track. Today we are on the road as a very solid, extremely solidly financed company. Which also allows us to negotiate with machinery companies if you need anything. To have a very good starting position and achieve very good results. #00:37:39-8#</p>
59	<p>Interviewer: I understood that negatively. Companies in the market which are trying to get funding there, get no credit elsewhere: This has a negative impact on the company. #00:37:56-3#</p>
60	<p>Interviewee1: Right, that is right. This is very important. #00:38:00-7#</p>
61	<p>Interviewer: The topic was crowdlending now. There is also crowdinvesting with mezzanine instruments, where investors are even more involved in profits or sales, or in company value participation. You have already said that you cannot say under what circumstances you would use crowdlending. I think it is the same here, or maybe you can say right there, these are financing instruments that you would not use. #00:38:39-3#</p>
62	<p>Interviewee1: With mezzanine share, it is a step more extensive, more extensive in terms of influences. You only do that if there is no other way. So again, this start-up idea. If one accepts that there is someone who has a participation in turnover. If there is one or whatever. If there is no other way. One leaves the external influence if one is convinced of it, as we for example, that one is on the right path, then one tries logically to keep out an external influence. At least an external influence of persons, of institutions that have neither a clue of the own business, of the daily routine, nor an overview. And therefore, to keep the distance as far as possible. #00:39:57-8#</p>
63	<p>Interviewer: So far you have not had any experience with factoring. Could you imagine, or under what circumstances would you refinance a claim on a factoring platform? #00:40:14-4#</p>
64	<p>Interviewee1: I would not do that. For the moment I completely exclude that. In some cases, we are faced with a factoring service in between. That means if we buy something, then you have to make payments to a bank or the buyer. Ultimately, this is always a signal that the company is doing badly. He is in this situation. This is not just a cherry on the cake with which I start my company on other legs, but there are already considerable problems there. #00:41:00-4#</p>
65	<p>Interviewer: You want to present the image to the outside, the sound financial situation and see this as a negative signal. #00:41:09-5#</p>
66	<p>Interviewee1: It is exactly like that. #00:41:09-5#</p>
67	<p>Interviewer: Then we come to the end. Is there still or did you expect another question in connection with this topic? #00:41:19-9#</p>
68	<p>Interviewee1: Good question. That would be very helpful in the aftermath or in the context of what you have briefly touched to get in written. That means the different crowdfunding, crowdlending. What does that mean? As a summary, a kind of wiki. What we talked about. Where can one hold on? Maybe also links, about with more information. That could be helpful. #00:42:20-8#</p>
69	<p>Interviewer: OK. So, in advance? #00:42:25-7#</p>
70	<p>Interviewee1: No, in advance or now. Now I do not want to say that I need an excess of information. If someone never heard about FinTechs or from the modern possibilities, then you probably will not be invited to the interview because that is another way of</p>

thinking. But anyone who is in the least bit concerned with it or even with the possibility of how we speak now then you can exchange views. It is probably often the case that the information is or may not be available to one. #00:43:12-6#

71 Interviewer: I can send you a few links and information afterwards. #00:43:23-9#

72 Interviewee1: Exactly. Because, if you are still investigating that, then maybe you could or maybe you will find providers where you say, even in this organisational structure. I think we can take with us in any case, that it depends on the legal entity form. As long as that is the case with personal liability. That fits or excludes and that you need development there and if someone offers, then that is information that could be helpful. #00:43:54-6#

Transcript: Interview 2

1	Interviewer: Thank you for taking the time. I have prepared questions. I would just go through it. #00:00:15-2#
2	Interviewee2: With pleasure #00:00:15-2#
3	Interviewer: First. Of course, I know your company and have looked at the annual report. I can also say briefly what I have read and you may also be able to amend or correct it. You make a turnover of approximately 170 million. #00:00:30-8#
4	Interviewee2: Gross turnover, yes. #00:00:32-8#
5	Interviewer: Gross turnover. Your company has an equity ratio of about 60% and you have about 800 employees. #00:00:39-7#
6	Interviewee2: Yes, exactly. Between 800 and 900, depending on the season. #00:00:45-6#
7	Interviewer: And you are the CFO responsible for financing, IT, and HR. #00:00:53-2#
8	Interviewee2: Yes, that is right. #00:00:54-7#
9	Interviewer: All right. There is nothing to add? #00:00:55-7#
10	Interviewee2: No. #00:00:57-1#
11	Interviewer: Then I would go straight to the questions. I have also seen in the annual report that you make a balance of funds between the companies and also have bank loans. #00:01:09-1#
12	Interviewee2: Yes. #00:01:09-8#
13	Interviewer: Now my question would be. Which financing instruments do you use? Maybe in addition? Maybe you can tell something about it? #00:01:18-5#
14	Interviewee2: So, of course, what we have is equity financing which we have already used. We are a public company. We already carried out a capital increase. That is one part. On the debt side, we actually work with three subtypes of loans. One is overdraft, in the private sector one would perhaps say dispo to it. Normal bank loans and then, however, also real estate loans because we suggest, yes that is now also 17 years ago, where we started to buy the property at place X. Of course, this has only gone through bank loans which are secured with the property. #00:02:08-3#
15	Interviewer: Ok. Regarding mezzanine capital, do you have experience? #00:02:10-6#
16	Interviewee2: No. First, we did not need it. Mezzanine financing was also very expensive back then. In relation to the bank loans. Depending on the bank, we have a rating of A to BBB + for the company. So, from this side extremely good conditions. So that mezzanine never stood for consideration. In addition, the subject of mezzanine has a huge disadvantage. You suddenly get the funds but how then the follow-up financing looks like, how the funds must be paid back then was also open. And then some companies get a problem in the last minute. Because they did not get a follow-up financing. #00:03:12-0#
17	Interviewer: Ok. I understand. So, you did not consider mezzanine because it was a) too expensive and b) because of the follow-up financing, there are also problems. #00:03:21-6#

18	Interviewee2: Yes. And then of course the different terms. I have always made sure that the maturities are never exactly finished straight to the point. That it is always floating in principle. In recent years, I have to say that we have refinanced almost exclusively on overdraft account. Even if it went into the medium-term range. This is not necessarily aligned to matching maturities, which is a golden rule, but since our credit rating is so strong, I have always been able to switch from short term to medium term. But short-term loans are just the cheapest thing available. #00:04:07-2#
19	Interviewer: And I think factoring was no topic for you? #00:04:13-1#
20	Interviewee2: Basically no. Factoring is only available on one page. We have the direct debit procedure too. And if the customers do not enter the PIN number but sign it, we have claims against the customers. That is already determined over 10 years ago that we sell these claims. And for the simple reason: Because we as a dealer if the customer has not paid, then always comes the whole administrative effort. We first have to get the address. The address procurement already costs money. Then we have to pursue the whole thing. Then you have to remind. Then you have to give the matter to the lawyer who in turn tried to recover that. That did not count anymore. So that if we sell the receivables, it is better for us. In this case, the buyer then can easily initiate a second payment run. This at the beginning of the month, when usually the salaries are in the bank account and you can make a move again. And we could not do this. #00:05:33-6#
21	Interviewer: Ok, then you have a framework contract with the provider and the claims are automatically directly ... #00:05:41-9#
22	Interviewee2: Exactly, immediately ceded and we get the money directly. #00:05:44-5#
23	Interviewer: Ok. #00:05:44-5#
24	Interviewee2: And then we have no more payment default. That is all on the side of the factor provider. #00:05:49-4#
25	Interviewer: Can you say something about the conditions for this? #00:05:49-4#
26	Interviewee2: Well, I would say it is really cheap. And that is because I know how much manpower we had to use there in the past to keep the whole topic somewhere up to date and to process the reminders. Doing the first, second, third reminders and giving that to a lawyer. To keep that up again. Every year 1,500 to 2,000 cases come to us somewhere because the customers did not pay or the account was not covered. And then as I said about the bureaucracy to keep somewhere up to date and then they try somehow to get something out which is clearly the better option. #00:06:38-0#
27	Interviewer: Ok. I understand. You weighed the administrative costs you have. #00:06:43-9#
28	Interviewee2: Administrative costs and default. Because there are customers who simply cannot pay more. And there, as I said, the situation came there, that we said that we can do this also by factoring. #00:06:57-1#
29	Interviewer: Ok. Then to the next question. If you are now making an investment, which form of financing would you currently prefer? #00:07:05-8#
30	Interviewee2: Overdraft credit on the one hand and a consideration might possibly be a medium-term financing. Because interest rates are not becoming lower at the moment. So, you can start to spread some risk. That would in principle be my preferred form of financing. #00:07:35-4#

31	Interviewer: Ok. Would you prefer the overdraft facility to internal financing? Or would you first say that you would try using own funds? #00:07:45-6#
32	Interviewee2: Own funds if you mean to optimize the Cashflow anywhere. We have been doing this for many years as a public company. Since it may still be possible to say afterwards: If I do everything perfectly well, I may be able to downsize the inventory another million or so. But with the interest we pay, this is lost life effort. All in all, we are doing quite well with our credit limits which we have and which we do not exploit by any means. If we do not overstrain the relationship with the banks, if we use funds there. #00:08:29-4#
33	Interviewer: Ok. You went public. Now I do not know when that was. Did you accompany this? #00:08:37-6#
34	Interviewee2: Yes, this was in 1998. 20 years ago. #00:08:44-8#
35	Interviewer: And then you had the fundings, that you have external equity ... #00:08:49-9#
36	Interviewee2: Not really. It was like that. I have to start differently. We have had a financial investor. X from Hamburg. And as always with financial investors they need their exit strategy. And their exit strategy which was chosen at that time was the IPO. We did that in 1998. I was already at the board at that time. I have been a member of the board for 20 years now. #00:09:28-7#
37	Interviewer: That means you would prefer the overdraft, perhaps first to medium term credit. Then mezzanine instruments. I also think for the future, so you would not look at it now for investment. #00:09:44-0#
38	Interviewee2: Definitely no. Because financing through the banks is always the cheapest form for me. Besides, I am maybe conservative too. For me, the topic of relationship matters quite a lot. And relationship has the advantage: At least that should hold even though the business is not so good. That business does not run so well, this is not only the case in companies. This is equal with banks. As part of a relationship for me is also when you see that a bank at the moment has to fight hard. Then I do not even haggle for the last tenth of a percent. That is when I like to leave it. In Bavaria they say, the church in the village. Conversely, I expect the same way and have never been disappointed. #00:10:40-1#
39	Interviewer: This is a perfect transition. You have already read my next question. That is exactly the topic of banking relationship. How many banking relationships do you have? #00:10:47-2#
40	Interviewee2: These are four banks. The DZ Bank, the HypoVereinsbank. The HypoVereinsbank is the house bank of our company. With whom we have been working together since the war. Then the Commerzbank and the Bayerische Landesbank. And then we still have the real estate financing. At that time, we did not do the first financing through the banks but through insurance. But now it will be replaced by banks. Just as the tranches expire. Because the financing of insurance is more expensive today than if I make it through the bank. Was different then. #00:11:41-2#
41	Interviewer: Then I understood. You definitely see advantages in a bank relationship. That when the times are e.g. are not so good that you can count on the bank providing you even if you are not doing well financially. #00:12:01-0#

42	Interviewee2: And, also the speed. So that was already possible to receive a financing over a larger amount than 10 million within ten days. This is only possible if you know each other. If the trust is there, on both sides. And of course, there is an invaluable advantage here, too, which is that we also have a lot of substance in that the property is worth somewhere today, I would say, a three-digit million worth of property that is owned today. That means the money the bank provides us is safe. #00:12:54-3#
43	Interviewer: And do you notice that also on the conditions? #00:12:54-3#
44	Interviewee2: Yes. #00:12:54-2#
45	Interviewer: That they are better than having a new bank? #00:13:00-2#
46	Interviewee2: Of course. I have to start differently. The entire Landesbanken which have reorganised and set up somewhere. I think that each Landesbank has presented itself to us. But I am one who says I do not care about the last tenth because there are good conditions. Because someone tries to come in, just to get a foot in the door. Basically, I am already interested in something like that in which I cultivate contacts. You never know where things are going in the banking landscape. So earlier, the Dresdner Bank was also a bank of us. Well, at some point Dresdner Bank merged with Commerzbank. And that does not mean that the volumes have doubled somewhere. So, you have to think with all possibilities somewhere and always have a backup position somewhere. We have them through the contacts we have. And otherwise, yes, it takes a very long time in any case until we make friends with the topic of a new banking relationship somewhere. It cannot be achieved from overnight; it rather takes a few years. You can see how it fits together and if there is the possibility you can start something to do together. But of course, you always have to see that this way is supported of the existing banking partners. #00:14:40-6#
47	Interviewer: I understood, also regarding the conditions. There are already banks trying to get a foothold. Maybe also with partially more favourable conditions. However, you are also sceptical about that because you know ... #00:14:58-7#
48	Interviewee2: This is not the decisive criterion. But what is crucial for me that is that I can have confidence. That I know how the banks behave like in the past and yes that I am trying to anticipate that benefits. As I continue this direction. And that has always been in favour of the existing banks. #00:15:25-2#
49	Interviewer: Do you also see certain disadvantages due to a banking relationship? #00:15:30-8#
50	Interviewee2: I see by the way we do the business no disadvantages. Only benefits. #00:15:41-0#
51	Interviewer: For example, if you have to meet certain requirements. Banks usually demand that you have to deliver certain reports. #00:15:50-4#
52	Interviewee2: That has to be done anyway. We are in the half-year report and still have to submit a quarterly report. As a listed company. We are standardised in that. So that does not matter. And quarterly, the banks are also informed by us. But always quarterly, sometimes even monthly because the data are there. Just as a shareholder or, let us say, a major shareholder has an increased need for information somewhere, so do the banks. I understand that. This is not a disadvantage for me. #00:16:33-6#
53	Interviewer: Then there are so called covenants, if the banks pretend that certain key figures have to be met. #00:16:41-4#

54	Interviewee2: We have that too. But the covenants I would say are pro forma covenants today. These are covenants that were defined 15 years ago. And we do it that every bank has the same covenants. So not that it is no longer comparable to each other. Banks make sure that nobody has more collateral. But that is not a problem for us because everyone is put somewhere equal. Because each fund that came in is just as valuable to me. Otherwise, we do not have to provide any special collateral with exceptions from real estate loans. What we have are all management loans. #00:17:38-7#
55	Interviewer: Then I would come to the next topic. On the subject of crowdlending and crowdinvesting. Do you already have experience with crowdfunding or have you ever been informed about this topic? #00:17:52-4#
56	Interviewee2: Well, the terms I know when it comes to underdeveloped countries like India, to provide certain projects by the population which would not normally have the opportunity to finance a way on the capital market. That they still get the funds to make something happen. Then I know another house in Austria. They supposedly did all the real estate financing via crowdlending. Should be a really great building. Fits, however, also to the philosophy of the company. That should be Green Earth. I do not know if you have heard of it before? #00:18:44-7#
57	Interviewer: Not, yet. #00:18:44-7#
58	Interviewee2: They make furniture from solid wood. Ecologically flawless etc. They have financed their building through crowdlending which I have heard from an ex-employee who has changed to the company. #00:19:06-4#
59	Interviewer: Then I would just say a few words about the two topics: Crowdlending and crowdinvesting. So, in principle it is so that this happens completely online without a visit, without physical appointments. You create a funding, upload the funding to a platform, and find investors who invest. Regarding crowdlending, it is like a bank loan. You have a fixed interest rate and a fixed term. This is possible with annuity loans or it will be repaid at the end of maturity. Crowdinvesting is the same principle but it is based on mezzanine instruments. So, they are subordinated loans, subordinated loans with profit participation or a silent participation or profit participation rights. #00:20:01-4#
60	Interviewee2: But related to a higher interest, or? #00:20:03-0#
61	Interviewer: Yes exactly. So, I looked at all German crowdlending and crowdinvesting platforms that offer financing to SMEs and the interest rate on crowdinvesting platforms was between 1% and 10%, the fixed rate plus participation on profit, turnover or increase of the company value. #00:20:31-6#
62	Interviewee2: It is just like that, if I demand 10% in advance on interest, I cannot demand so much in profit. Somewhere you have to rebel then and say it comes out somewhere over a longer period, a weighted interest, so 5% or 6%. #00:20:47-7#
63	Interviewer: Yes, exactly. It may be a bit higher. There are also mezzanine programs from traditional banks and interest rates are higher. Well, I say it, it depends, of course, but I think so at 10%, that is about ... #00:21:02-6#
64	Interviewee2: At 10%? You know, I am currently in the overdraft below 1%. Without having to hand over collateral somewhere. And that is why I mean, there is every form of financing and with my credit rating, I do not have to resort to other markets where to which other risk structures are related. #00:21:26-8#

65	Interviewer: Crowdlending has interest rates from 2.5% to 16% fixed. That it is without further participation. All have a maximum duration, of crowdlending of five years and limited to 2.5 million. In addition, there is still a point, of course, that in companies like yours, if you are a managing director or CFO, it is a public company and you are an employee, that can of course be a disadvantage. They demand a personal guarantee. #00:22:04-0#
66	Interviewee2: Well, I suppose this might be interesting to someone who has a one-time project and wants to finance it and does not want to finance it through the bank, and he is in an owner-managed company. Once you are in the legal form of a limited liability company or a stock company and you do not get one hundred percent of the shares anywhere, this will never be the case. There will never be a CEO in personal liability. Nobody does. #00:22:39-1#
67	Interviewer: And under what circumstances would you request funding through crowdlending? #00:22:47-5#
68	Interviewee2: If I build a house and the bank does not provide me with funds, even then you have to ask yourself, does that make any sense that I buy a house somewhere or build it by myself. So, for me it is definitely no financing strategy especially since the volume can actually only be a bycatch. Because companies in our scale not only have 2.5 million line of credit but have 125, 140, 150 million. And that I give the water glass with another colour, so to speak, for such a drop, definitely no. That would change the whole structure, and then, in fact, I would give these lenders more collateral than I give to the banks. So that would completely mess up all the funding and refinancing. This is definitely no instrument for the capital-managed company. #00:23:58-8#
69	Interviewer: The 2.5 million refer to the funding. You could create several fundings. #00:24:08-0#
70	Interviewee2: But not on the same topic. #00:24:09-1#
71	Interviewer: Yes, exactly. Not on the same topic. But then I understood that. So, the 2.5 million, that is for you a K.O. criterion. Then the personal guarantee would be a K.O. criterion. Assuming you do not have the personal guarantee and you would need if necessary, only the 2.5 million, would you then prefer it to a bank? #00:24:44-8#
72	Interviewee2: Everyone has a bank, even only for private business. There is always a bank relationship somewhere and personally as I said, I believe that the banking relationship is always the better way. Because you can get all the lenders. You can all compare more or less. You can also negotiate terms with two or three banks. And either it works then or it does not. But I could never imagine doing that through crowdlending or crowdinvesting. #00:25:33-9#
73	Interviewer: And if conditions were better for crowdlending? #00:25:37-9#
74	Interviewee2: It is not an alternative for me because I say. What is if the company is in a more difficult situation and then I cannot get any funding. That is a point. The second point is also a negative point: With banks you always have preliminary talks. Should it be the case that people are trying to set up a financing project via crowdlending. And you will not get it done. It is like having a stamp on the forehead. It does not work. Since you make your business broken. So, in my eyes, I see no advantage at all. #00:26:25-4#
75	Interviewer: I understood. So, if you upload the funding and then you would not get any money from the crowd, through the investors. This risk would be there for you and

	the negative consequence would be for you that you would have an image damage. #00:26:44-1#
76	Interviewee2: Not only a damage to the image, but it can lead to the fact that a Schufa entry is there and that you get elsewhere by that no money anymore. It does not work. Where I would imagine if I have somewhere, have a social commitment and try to do something good for cheap money. Since I could imagine that but then only if I do not have to deal with the issue and transfer amount x somewhere and have the guarantee that I get the money back. Then I do not have to get 10%, instead 1% or 2% or something would be enough. That has a very different purpose. That is no form of financing a business. #00:27:37-6#
77	Interviewer: Ok. I mean it could be a marketing effect. You can upload a funding. Many investors, individual and professional investors see it. Would you consider that as an advantage? #00:27:51-4#
78	Interviewee2: No, not at all. Then everyone knows what I want to do. #00:27:53-3#
79	Interviewer: Would you overweight the risk of idea copy to the marketing effect? #00:28:01-4#
80	Interviewee2: And as I said, there is always at least theoretically the probability that it is just not funded. And the reputational damage, that is huge. #00:28:18-6#
81	Interviewer: And would you take it as a risk that the FinTechs are not that regulated? So, it is like that on crowdlending: The loan would actually provide through a bank. It is so, the platform collects the money, the platform provides the funds to the bank, the bank provides the loan. Because in Germany only the bank can grant a loan with a banking license and then the bank resells partial claims to the investors, and thus the bank is outside again. But otherwise there is ... #00:28:51-1#
82	Interviewee2: But reporting is going on both to the bank because it is likely to keep some claims and ultimately takes place towards the investors. And as I said, a middleman is in between, so I actually pay double fees. #00:29:08-6#
83	Interviewer: Yes. So, you mean the transaction fee, so the fairy. The fee is one-off between 1.9% and 5%. #00:29:20-4#
84	Interviewee2: That is madness. #00:29:21-5#
85	Interviewer: And then there is still a partial annual fee of 0.1% to 5%. Ok, but then I understood. And regarding the regulations. Does that rather deter you from the fact that otherwise there are no regulations? #00:29:41-9#
86	Interviewee2: Well, what would scare me off is when I lend money. This does not happen in our business model anyway, because our business model is that we buy and sell goods and not that we lend money. Borrowing money somewhere along the way would mean that I would have to convince my board of the benefits of this FinTech. And then I think, if someone does not deal with the topics, that if you do not quite understand that, you would also decline. So, as I said I companies in our scale, there will be no percent which will finance something like that. To all times they already have a financing. That is not all are fully equity-financed, they all have financing in principle, and then you are back in the matter of equality very quickly. That then existing lenders would not allow someone else to do another get security. And then I am back on the subject, if you have to put something on the legs, as a small SME and it is otherwise not so easy to receive funds because for banks it is too risky, then it can be an alternative for such craft business. But the craft businesses usually also have a house bank that

	maps their entire business dealings which also know the company very well. Actually, there should be no problem to get the money and to get better terms there. #00:31:49-6#
87	Interviewer: So, you would not consider it as diversification? #00:31:51-7#
88	Interviewee2: No, for God's sake. Unless I say I have something against the banks and for political reasons, I prefer to get the money from my fan base. Then it can be something but that too has disadvantages. Because the fan base is, I say, the circle of customers and if you come to a bad situation and the best customers do not longer receive their money, then you lose these fans. Also, not good. #00:32:24-6#
89	Interviewer: Then I think about crowdfunding, that is even a bit sharper than crowdlending through the mezzanine instruments. A higher interest rate. For you also no alternative and the circumstances would be at least exactly as you just described, not an option. #00:32:49-1#
90	Interviewee2: Definitely no. I am really sorry now that I am for the topic of crowdfunding and crowdfunding as such a bad contact since I illuminate all this from the negative side somewhere. But good ... #00:33:06-3#
91	Interviewer: But you do not have to be sorry because I just want to investigate. Quite neutral because I want to find out how it is just with larger medium-sized companies and especially for really larger medium-sized companies, an alternative or not. #00:33:20-7#
92	Interviewee2: Well, now we are listed and maybe that is another obstacle on the way. That may be true. #00:33:34-4#
93	Interviewer: Now, of course, the situation is a bit different here. There are still factoring platforms too. You can upload an invoice, there are different mechanisms, it can be auctioned or the platform finances it directly. And when the feedback from the platform is positive, you get your money. Directly, also relatively fast. Of course, this is not so applicable to you now because you have a lot of small individual items with the direct debit system. #00:34:11-7#
94	Interviewee2: First that and second the company to whom we sell the receivables has a strategic advantage. Because they can trigger a payment run again. And no one else can do that. They can do a so-called repurchase run again. And the advantage, as I said, no one else can do it and therefore, this cannot be a point. That we seek refinancing somewhere else. #00:34:44-9#
95	Interviewer: Maybe short on the factoring platforms. The fees are between 0.5% and 4% of the volume of receivables. Assuming you would want to refinance a claim, under what circumstances would you try such a factoring platform? #00:35:11-0#
96	Interviewee2: So, the factoring rate would have to be significantly below the borrowing rate which I pay to the bank. That should make it easier for me to put up a cash for, I do not know, 0.9% percent and not let me discuss 4% off my accounts receivable. Does not make sense. #00:35:39-1#
97	Interviewer: Exactly, so the interest rate is relatively high, if you count on the year. #00:35:46-2#
98	Interviewee2: Exactly, that is one thing and the second. After all, I do not have time to see each time if I can sell a claim through a platform. This must be a well-rehearsed process. You set that up once and then it has to repeat itself permanently in the routine. This must be a scalable process behind it. It cannot be that each time you

	redefine the business process. And then watch what the claim is doing right now. What are the interest rates or offers that come in and that does not pay off? #00:36:29-6#
99	Interviewer: Ok, yes, I understood. Even with traditional factoring you actually sell entire portfolios and have a framework contract. This is of course flexible. There you upload the individual accounts. And that would be a disadvantage for you. #00:36:48-3#
100	Interviewee2: There you get administration effort without end. No, for God's sake. #00:36:55-4#
101	Interviewer: Ok. Then we come to the end. Is there anything else that I did not ask in the context but what you might have expected? #00:37:08-1#
102	Interviewee2: Related to Crowdfunding, crowdfunding no. Everything OK. #00:37:16-7#
103	Interviewer: Or maybe want to give me another topic from the context of the interview? #00:37:23-9#
104	Interviewee2: Well, what I could imagine that it might be more interesting for maybe one or the other private person, if you have a problem on one side or the other of a fundamental nature to work together with banks. That may always be true. If you say no, I prefer to move somewhere in the private sector. But then it is no longer economically based, but that is a question of attitude behind it. That could be something. But for companies in size of this, so in the middle class I say times of 50 - 200 million sales, I cannot imagine that definitely. #00:38:18-0#
105	Interviewer: Ok. #00:38:18-0#
106	Interviewee2: Because there is so much responsibility behind it, that cash inflows and refinancing runs like clockwork somewhere. Because there really is never a problem. Since no one would run the risk that he says, now I do something quite different because I think that sympathetic or something. Maybe pay more money. Everyone shakes their heads. For God's sake, that is not possible. #00:38:49-7#
107	Interviewer: Yes, because I conduct the interviews. And there is the model of Christensen, the disruptive innovation model that means. He says, so disruptive innovation, these are companies that are new to the market and serve first a segment that is not in the focus of established companies. As you have already said. These are now topics for small businesses, maybe a little craftsman. For consumers anyway. This theory states that such companies often establish themselves in this niche market which is not interesting for the established. The established companies then do not see the new as competition and then they continue to develop, rather quickly. They adapt their business model, such as, theoretically, you could abolish the guarantee, you could increase the volume. You could already ... #00:39:48-3#
108	Interviewee2: Yes, then it could be that they developed so far this business model, that it is interesting for the big ones and then they just buy the companies. #00:40:02-5#
109	Interviewer: So exactly. The Commerzbank has a crowdlending platform, main funders. But this was more present at first. Now they are down a bit again. It may be that the demand was not there, but there are some banks that are more active in the business. Either they found FinTechs or invest into FinTechs, while others are a little more restrained. My next step is to see how it would fit in with this model, that they work their way up into the market. And maybe even customers like you, serving a larger midsize company. #00:40:48-2#

110 Interviewee2: So maybe I am too conservative or too old, but I would settle the likelihood that this is going to be a big issue, which I would put under 10% somewhere. Unless in the banking world which can always be, there is again the next crisis and there will be no more funds. There has already been something like that. Even with a good credit rating, you had difficulties getting new funds. But as I said, I do not see the problem in companies of our size because we did also so well on the banking crisis. That refers to the German area because you can always switch to foreign banks. The possibilities always exist. And last but not least, one still has the topic also that one makes more self-financing over equity increase. But as I said we are at 60%. #00:41:50-2#

Transcript: Interview 3

1	Interviewer: I have prepared a questionnaire. I would just go through that. #00:00:18-2#
2	Interviewee3: Yes, please. #00:00:18-2#
3	Interviewer: We have talked briefly about the company. About a few numbers. Maybe a few more numbers that would be interesting for me. I have seen you have an equity ratio of 80%-85% which is reported in the nine months report. Now I just saw in the 6-month report that the ratio was at 50% or 55%. Now I am not sure if I miscalculated that. #00:00:48-0#
4	Interviewee3: No, that is in fact a bit related to the IPO. Until the IPO, we were still in the old world, if you like. In Q3. In Q1 of the calendar year, the IPO had taken place with the corresponding increase in equity. So, there is quite a gap between the number in the prospectus and now. Because in between was exactly the IPO. And that is why these different percentages can also be explained. #00:01:16-4#
5	Interviewer: Oh, that is good. Then that is about 85%. And number of employees, I think is at 260, have I seen. #00:01:24-5#
6	Interviewee3: Yes, it always depends on which date we turn it off. We also acquired another company in Y. We also communicated that. And if you count the acquisition into consideration, we are now over 300 now. So, the 260 were probably from another booklet, right? #00:01:52-5#
7	Interviewer: From the internet presence. #00:01:55-2#
8	Interviewee3: Exactly, that is a bit outdated insofar as we have already made two acquisitions in the year. Earlier this year in X. X there. And now just a month ago Y. And if I count both together, we have passed the 300 threshold. Whereby that is for Europe. Here at the location in Germany are about 180, 190 employees. And the remaining 100, 110 are spread across central and northern European countries. #00:02:39-8#
9	Interviewer: And regarding the offer. So, you offer A. Both A and B. #00:04:34-5#
10	Interviewee3: Yes exactly (more details from A and B). #00:05:14-0#
11	Interviewer: Well, I think have the essential information about the company. Then I would go directly into the technical questions. We also talked briefly about the fact that you went public. So, this was one financial instrument. Which financing instruments do you generally use or do you use others? #00:06:07-1#
12	Interviewee3: Yes. We had luck, especially when you look into the past that we were exclusively equity financed. Uli Höhnes always likes to talk about the fixed-term department and the credit department. We do always have the fixed-term department. Because if you look at the Q3 financial statements under the balance sheet, we have a relatively high level of liquid funds, so that we currently do not depend on the liabilities or on the financing side. But if we were to do larger activities in the future, we can imagine financing them with borrowed capital or equity. At least partially to pay the purchase price. But until that happens, we will have enough cash on the assets side to make further small or mid-sized acquisitions. #00:06:07-1#
13	Interviewer: So, you do not have any bank loan? #00:06:14-4#

14	Interviewee3: We had a smaller financing. But that was more like subsidised loans here for the premises. Otherwise, you have to knock on the wood, we have no financing issues, especially on the liabilities side. #00:06:32-3#
15	Interviewer: Then exactly to the preferences. You went public. In what ways did you think of other alternatives then? #00:06:41-8#
16	Interviewee3: Absolute. It was also important for us, driven by our main shareholder, to grow here. And if you could not have taken the necessary capital for growth through the stock market, which is a good thing if you look at the price developments, then we would be confident in liability financing via banks or other instruments. We are also working on targets, without naming names. I am not allowed to do that. These are e.g. today also financed by such crowdfunding. In that respect that is quite familiar to me. Also, alternative forms of financing which do not run over the classical banks. So that would have been an alternative for us at the time. #00:07:26-8#
17	Interviewer: But you then opted for the IPO, i.e. for external equity. #00:07:39-2#
18	Interviewee3: Yes. The main motivation was actually that we settle in this Industry 4.0 environment. That is such a megatrend. Since that perfectly fits in the stock market story. That was actually one of the main motives why we took this way. #00:08:01-4#
19	Interviewer: Have you had considered alternatives like borrowed capital, over loans or also towards mezzanine capital? #00:08:10-7#
20	Interviewee3: I agree. Both, more likely even towards mezzanine. And not so much in the direction of classic loans. So that would be back then. We had to check quickly. Before you have to look how is the stock market environment and in X, it was still relatively stable. Afterwards there were extreme fluctuations. In that sense, it also made the decision easier for us. Otherwise we would have gone quite fast towards alternative forms of financing. The plans were already on the table. #00:08:43-2#
21	Interviewer: Ok. Then you have mentioned it briefly. If funding is needed for further investment in the future, you will definitely have some upside on the asset side, but you would also consider other sources of funding. And that would be the first time you go towards a normal loan. So more of a normal loan or even more towards mezzanine? #00:09:09-7#
22	Interviewee3: Actually, the latter. The good thing is that the considerations were already there and then we would rather go in the direction of mezzanine. There are many different varieties. So, I also have a bit of bank background before my studies. At least that is what I did at a bank. #00:09:29-1#
23	Interviewer: Ok. #00:09:30-4#
24	Interviewee3: Yes exactly. At a bank that no longer exists today. Dresdner Bank. In that respect, that is quite familiar to me. Also, the whole topics. But then you have to look, when it becomes more concrete which form you use. I do not know if that also aims a bit in the direction. Of course, we already have leasing financing in part. Whereby the operative leases are for IT, for other office equipment topics. This is actually practiced practice with us, that we cover this through leasing and not through purchase. In this respect, we also have some financing at this site. Classic leasing. I do not know if you already know the new IFRS, with this new leasing standard. This will rattle the balance sheet. Since we are just thinking about what consequences that would have for us if we would someday change. Because today we still account according to HGB. #00:10:32-2#

25	Interviewer: Ok. #00:10:34-9#
26	Interviewee3: So, it fits well in the direction of investment financing. Even if that are rather replacement investments and no new investments. #00:10:45-6#
27	Interviewer: Ok, I understood that. But you currently have no credit. Do you still have a house bank relationship for other business? #00:10:58-2#
28	Interviewee3: Absolutely yes. And not just one. We have been working with three house banks for years. Exactly, which are also active here nationally and partly regionally. The company has grown historically. The company is now almost 40 years old. And, of course, we are more concerned with the investment side and not with the liability side which is not that trivial anymore in times of negative interest rates or threatened negative interest rates. We also had to look at how we transfer the funds from A to B within these three house banks, so that it does not come to negative rates. So, the reverse cash pooling. Cashpooling was used to avoid debit interest, today I want to avoid punitive interest. Paradox situation. #00:11:51-6#
29	Interviewer: And do you see advantages and disadvantages with a house bank relationship? #00:11:57-9#
30	Interviewee3: So, advantage is, just when I think of the local bank, that some things can be done more easily and quickly. Because it is really in walking distance. That even in times of online etc., with such a personal contact, certain things go quicker and easier than when I have to talk to an anonymous administration in Frankfurt or wherever the head office is. So that has its advantage that you have a common and solid relationship for years. Mr X appreciated that much more than me because he grew up together with them. But that has its charm if the bank is really not an anonymous hotline. You know the people. Then things go in spite of many regulations a lot more straightforward and faster. #00:12:59-3#
31	Interviewer: And do you also have the feeling that there is trust in terms of, right now you are in a very good situation financially, but if for example, a situation comes up, when you need liquid funds quickly, that the bank will be there faster? #00:13:16-9#
32	Interviewee3: Yes, I think so. So, you also see it on the negative or on the penalty interest side. There is often a concession because there is a mutual trust. And I would expect the same, or expect it to be possible. #00:13:35-5#
33	Interviewer: Because you just said there is a concession. Do you see that the house bank offers you better conditions than, for example, another bank? #00:13:47-5#
34	Interviewee3: Yes. So, if this is 1:1 related to it, I do not know. But I can clearly confirm the fact. And I think so, that is my personal opinion, that there is already a connection there. Give and take. Despite the whole regulation. Today, for banks it is not easy to earn any money at all, but I see that already, yes. #00:14:12-0#
35	Interviewer: Ok. Do you see also some disadvantages through a house bank relationship? #00:14:20-4#
36	Interviewee3: Would not come to me spontaneously, no. Sure, so having a house bank is a question of definition. But which I would most likely call our bank is more like a smaller bank. Maybe that does not have the European approach, as it would then have an HVB or Commerzbank. That might be a disadvantage, but now they are so far from the handling of the banking, so that I could now find no difference. No, so we are very happy with them. #00:14:56-8#

37	Interviewer: Maybe you have had a bank loan in the past, where you also get certain conditions, so-called covenants. I do not know now. But would you consider that a disadvantage? #00:15:08-5#
38	Interviewee3: I know it from an auditor's point of view of clients who have always complained very much about these covenants. That is often a vicious circle. When the numbers go down, interest rates go up. This then mutually reinforces each other. I know this situation. As we said, we had a loan, but that was because it was manageable and had no such covenants included. But I already know this situation as such. #00:15:47-3#
39	Interviewer: Oh ok. But you only had this one promotional loan so far and you have not had a single loan in history so far. #00:15:54-2#
40	Interviewee3: No, we are very proud of that. Maybe we had one at the beginning. But the last few years, the last 10 and also before my time here, there was never a debt issue. Rarely in the modern day. #00:16:11-2#
41	Interviewer: And I also think that you have appointments with banks. Because you personally thought some things are going faster. Would find that positive or rather negative? #00:16:22-4#
42	Interviewee3: Absolutely yes. So, if I have a topic, then comes the bank advisor or the branch manager to us in the house. And then really if it should be quick, if it should burn, if we have to transfer any purchase price and if foreign currency issues are to be discussed. How do you secure that? Then they are here. And that does not work if I have to go to Munich to the centre. That is a few kilometres, after all. Here it is only two minutes' walk. This is not to beat. #00:17:02-6#
43	Interviewer: Oh, two minutes' walk. #00:17:04-0#
44	Interviewee3: Yes, or two minutes by car. #00:17:08-0#
45	Interviewer: Yes, ok I understood that. Then I would come to the next topic. To crowdlending and crowdinvesting. Have you experience or points of contact? #00:17:14-8#
46	Interviewee3: So only indirectly because one of our targets has been funded by crowdfunding. Just a lot of people collect money, small sums of money, which in total then leads to a profitable amount. That is how they financed their start-up phase back then. In that sense I had indirect points of contact with it. #00:17:42-1#
47	Interviewer: Then maybe I can say a few more words. There is an umbrella term crowdfunding. That is a generic term. That means I collect money from many people or from investors and can then use that for any projects. There are two categories. Once with financial return and once without financial return for the investors. That without financial return is with donations or some other kind of compensation. And with financial return, we can differentiate between crowdlending and crowdinvesting. And crowdlending is simply a kind of bank loan. So, there is a fixed interest rate, a fixed term and then either an annuity or at the end of the term the loan is completely repaid. And regarding crowdinvesting, in contrast, mezzanine instruments are used. So, these are subordinated instruments. Subordinated loans with an interest rate that is partly participated in the turnover or in the profit or in the company value increase. Also, silent partnerships or participation rights. But in principle, both work that way. You create a funding, upload the funding to the platform, find investors and then you get the money. Everything is online and there are also different mechanisms of how investors and borrowers come together. At crowdlending, where it is some kind of

credit, there is the first variant. The funding is uploaded by the company. The platform itself does conduct a credit check, sets an interest rate and then investors can invest. The second variant is that it is an auction. That the interest rate is determined by an auction. And the third variant is that the platform itself finances the loan or at least agrees to the loan or rejects the loan because the platform itself has an agreement with professional investors. And then the platform checks, says yes or no. And if so, the funding will continue to be available for five days on the platform for additional investors. But in case of not enough funds, it is covered by the professional investors. That is an overview of the three matching variants for crowdlending. Everything for medium-sized companies. First of all, for a smaller target group. For me, it is interesting to find out how it is for larger medium-sized companies. Because there are a few more points that I will discuss again which are now interesting for larger companies. Because that can be hurdles again and that is what I would like to discuss. Interest rates on crowdlending currently stand at 2.49% - 16%, depending on credit quality and maturity. Of the ratings at least that I have found on the platforms. I looked at all the platforms that met certain quality criteria and analysed them. And not all platforms published interest rates that way. But those were the ones that published interest rates. So, the maturity of the loans is up to five years and there is also a fee that gets the platform. This is currently 1.9% - 5% once. And then there are some annual fees which are 0.1% - 5%. Then I would come directly to my next question. Assuming you want to make an investment, under what circumstances would you ask for funding through crowdlending platforms? #00:22:15-7#

- 48 Interviewee3: Above all, the formal aspect would be important to us. Since I am doing something difficult to estimate. Is the formal effort less or is it easier than doing it through a classic bank loan? Since you will consider advantages and disadvantages. When it comes to bank financing, one would especially have this covenant topic. And I think that, at least, I suspect, will not be so relevant in many crowdfunding topics. So, I think, you would just have to estimate the effort which variant would be just the better. But I know from this target that they were very happy with this process that they started then. And also surprised that the money what came in was a multiple of that what was originally planned. #00:23:18-8#
- 49 Interviewer: Ok. Regarding the target, can you possibly say a turnover or employee size? #00:23:25-2#
- 50 Interviewee3: That is relatively small. They are under ten people, so employees. And the turnover is just seven digits. If it comes at all. So, a classic start-up. This is a typical example of companies using such forms of financing. #00:23:45-6#
- 51 Interviewer: I am just looking at more platforms that focus more on established companies for small and mid-sized companies. There are also platforms that focus specifically on start-ups. But then I understood that. The administrative effort is definitely a decisive reason. #00:24:13-4#
- 52 Interviewee3: And of course, the terms and conditions. You could also, if we had such a situation, give conditions from the bank or from the banks and that compare with what theoretically could come on the novel form. For me these would be the two criteria. Conditions and administrative effort. #00:24:36-4#
- 53 Interviewer: And let us say, hypothetically, the administrative effort is limited. Maybe a bit more at the beginning. Because you have a relationship with the bank for a long time and you probably already have more effort. But let us say the terms are the same. Would you try it? #00:24:58-3#

54	Interviewee3: Yes, I could imagine. Because it just fits a bit to our corporate philosophy. It also has the touch of Industry 4.0 or this digital approach. In that sense, I can already imagine that. #00:25:12-0#
55	Interviewer: There is, as I said, still focus on smaller companies. You are already listed. You are the CFO, an employee of the company. Currently, crowdlending platforms demand personal liability. They have no covenants or other collateral requirements but they have personal liability. How would it play with you here? Would that be a direct knockout criterion or could you consider that? #00:26:04-9#
56	Interviewee3: My personal liability, that is my natural person, would not be an exclusion criterion. You can certainly split also on several persons. But then the question would be, it is a joint debtor. But that would not be an exclusion criterion for me now. #00:26:26-3#
57	Interviewer: Ok. The crowdlending platforms do not have a banking license. But the loan would be provided through a bank. So that works like that, that is the next step: If the platform got the money from the investors, the platform gives the money to the bank. If you want to provide a loan in Germany, you need a banking license. Therefore, the bank then provides the loan but then resells as partial claims the whole thing to investors, and thus the bank is out there again. So, the bank is more of a white label bank. But otherwise the whole thing is not so regulated. You mentioned the regulations, and banks already have a lot of regulations. Would you put off that? That this market is not so regulated? #00:27:22-0#
58	Interviewee3: No. So, for me, this regulation is also partly negative. So that would not scare me. #00:27:30-7#
59	Interviewer: You would rather see this as positive because one or the other unbureaucratic ... #00:27:37-8#
60	Interviewee3: No. Clearly a minimum standard must be respected but this excess. I have a very good comparison within Europe where we stand with Germany. There we are, I think somewhere in the middle. In countries like Poland which are even more bureaucratic than we are. This is always exciting to see or read for me. Holland completely liberal and unbureaucratic. Poland the other extreme. We are more or less in the middle. But that would be an advantage for me if not everything is over-regulated. #00:28:24-0#
61	Interviewer: Ok. You said that fits in well with your business. Overall, in philosophy. So, the topic FinTechs, digitisation. Would you also see this as a marketing effect because the funding is being uploaded? There is a crowd there, there are people who can look at it
62	Interviewee3: Absolute. That would have been one of my next thoughts. Because such a thing can certainly also be part of our approach, we always have to think in equity story. Which messages do you give out? What is positive for the company? And that is certainly positive for the company. Because it simply corresponds to the spirit of times a bit. The evolution. And something like that has more positive aspects for the brand side. #00:28:45-9#
63	Interviewer: Could, of course. So, you are now financially well, but if you upload a funding and trying to get funds and you do not get the funds. Then maybe that can have a negative message. So that you get a stamp, ok they did not get any money. But as I understand it now, you are financially well off and you would be overweighting the positive effects of marketing. #00:29:12-5#

64	Interviewee3: Yes, I would overweight that. Well, that is how self-confident you are. You can guess for yourself, at least a little bit, how the chances would stand then. I have to make the decision in advance. If I knew in advance that this could turn out bad, then maybe I should rather refrain from it. But you get in advance a certain sense of it. #00:30:11-4#
65	Interviewer: That is the way you upload the funding, the investors see it, but there is also the risk of a copy of the idea. So, if you have a great idea now. That is shown there, means the competitors can see it, other competitors can see it. How would that scare you back? #00:30:33-6#
66	Interviewee3: Actually, not so much because the ideas are only the knowledge, when we approach new projects, that is in our heads in the minds of engineers or software developers. So far, you would not transport that to the outside. That it would be critical to knowledge that you give to the outside. So, there you would still dare to venture. Then I see no problem. #00:31:04-7#
67	Interviewer: We just talked about crowdlending. How about crowdinvesting? That would be virtually the same principle. But it is mezzanine instruments. How would you finance it, or under what circumstances would you ask for funding? #00:31:26-7#
68	Interviewee3: The decisive thing for me is the topic with the conditions again. How is that designed. There are probably the same varieties as in conventional mezzanine financing and it really depends on the individual case that it is a form of financing that suits us best, the project we wanted to finance with it. That would be the criterion for me. #00:31:59-0#
69	Interviewer: Earlier, at the beginning of the conversation, you said that you would prefer mezzanine to a bank loan. Would that also be the case that you would prefer crowdinvesting before you would do crowdlending? #00:32:16-9#
70	Interviewee3: Yes, as I said we are not in the situation yet. But today, I would prefer crowdinvesting to crowdlending a bit. #00:32:25-4#
71	Interviewer: Ok. Because these are the mezzanine instruments. The other is... #00:32:31-6#
72	Interviewee3: Yes exactly. This is related to balance sheet structures and depending on which one can be flexibly extended in the direction of debt or in the direction of equity. I think I have more creative freedom here than with the other form. #00:32:45-4#
73	Interviewer: And would you then, the next step, before you would take a normal bank loan, would you prefer crowdinvesting? So, mezzanine means that the conditions are a bit higher but it is more flexible. In the balance sheet, you have more creative freedom. But would you consider crowdinvesting as an alternative to a bank loan? #00:33:19-5#
74	Interviewee3: I agree. It is at least an equivalent alternative, if not a bit preferred alternative. But if it were up to us then it is probably more state of the art today. As a company, it is important for us to keep up with the times and then we should do that on the financing side as well. That would be my credo. #00:33:49-7#
75	Interviewer: You have already considered mezzanine back then. I have already said a little bit about crowdinvesting. I know it is hard to evaluate because you do not have the experience. But would you see some pros and cons of crowdinvesting compared to normal mezzanine capital? So, to a normal mezzanine financing, let us say so. #00:34:22-1#

76	Interviewee3: Yeah, if that is what you said earlier in crowdlending as a potential downside that the topic will be published. Bank financing is more likely to take place in the backyard. Here I am completely open and transparent. That might be a disadvantage, but I believe that the advantages outweigh. From my personal point of view that one just goes with the time that fits to the company, the way of financing. That outweighs then for me the other theoretical disadvantages. That is what I would see today. When that happens, perhaps other perspectives or arguments will be included. But so today from afar, in quotes, that outweighs. #00:35:15-9#
77	Interviewer: Now there is one more point. Crowdlending and crowdinvesting is currently limited in volume to 2.5 million. This is little attractive for larger companies. But related to funding: You could also upload several funding. Is that negative for you or does it not scare you back? #00:35:40-9#
78	Interviewee3: Actually, that would not scare me. If I have, say, more need and I can portray this over several fundings. Because I am not so much in the topic, is there also a limit for the number of funding running? #00:35:57-4#
79	Interviewer: No, I did not see that. #00:36:00-6#
80	Interviewee3: No, that would not scare me because this one-time effort is certainly there to read this topic but then the 2nd, 3rd and 4th is an exchange. A copy paste may be too short. But the first step is much bigger than the follow ups. So that would not deter me now. #00:36:27-1#
81	Interviewer: Then I would go to the next topic. As I heard it out, I think you have not used this financing instrument yet. Factoring. Or have you used it in the past? #00:36:42-2#
82	Interviewee3: No, that is right. We were in the lucky situation that we not needed it, either from the cash flow situation or other criteria. I knew it partly. We have acquired a few companies in the last five years, and they had it in part. The subsidiaries. But since they belong to our group, they did not do it anymore. Because we ourselves have taken over appropriate financing functions from the point of view of the parent company and there was no longer the cash flow argument which is often the main argument, was then no longer there. In this respect, I know that more from the transition phase and today we no longer use it. #00:37:25-6#
83	Interviewer: Because there are also factoring platforms. That is the same principle. You can register there and then you can upload an account receivable online. And there are a few different matching variants. That the platform even finances itself or even through an auction. Now, suppose you would want to use factoring, how or under what circumstances would you try a factoring platform? #00:38:04-1#
84	Interviewee3: Well, factoring you have partially to disclose in the annual report. I might have a little bit of inhibition if we would do that and via a platform. Because now I do not know how public that will be but probably already. That would indirectly signal some cash flow problems to the outside. That would put me off at the point a bit. Whether this is a K.O. criterion, I do not think so. But it would be such a disadvantage that I would take a closer look at it. #00:38:48-0#
85	Interviewer: So, where the platform decides and refinances itself, it will not be published. I cannot say that 100% honestly. But then I understood, if you have to refinance a claim you would then try to refinance it by other means, perhaps through a bank loan or other factoring, where there is no danger of publicity due to the negative signal to the market. #00:39:21-3#

86	Interviewee3: I agree. That would be such an argument or a theoretical disadvantage for me. Whether that would be an exclusion criterion, I do not think so. But that is what I would to think about. #00:39:37-9#
87	Interviewer: That is relatively flexible in terms. So, you upload individual invoices and you are flexible. On the other hand, if you were to sell receivables on a regular basis, you would like to sell a whole portfolio. In the beginning, relatively bureaucratic but then unbureaucratic. Would that be an advantage if you had the flexibility, or would that be a disadvantage because if you needed it on a regular basis because it would be too bureaucratic for you? #00:40:27-5#
88	Interviewee3: No, that does not sound too bureaucratic. I believe and without concluding that I can judge that in traditional factoring. I have often heard as an auditor of clients that it is bureaucratically. And that sounds a bit less bureaucratically. In this respect I go with what you said. To the other forms of financing less administrative effort would be a clear advantage for me. In that sense, I would perhaps prefer this from. #00:41:15-0#
89	Interviewer: Then we come to the end. Is there something I did not ask in this context, but what you expected? #00:41:22-1#
90	Interviewee3: What we have just looked at a bit and that is part of the FinTech area are alternative providers of payment transactions. So, from payment processing tools. In fact, we are looking at both euro-based and, above all, foreign-currency issues because we imagine the prices that the banks offer us have huge spreads. And there are now FinTechs which are attractive in mass transactions especially from the conditions. And that is a topic which we are actually looking at. So, payment processing FinTechs. And there are some. I do not want to say that they sprout up like mushrooms but there are some by now and they are well-known and have a brand history. And that is a topic that we are looking at from this FinTech area. This is not a funding topic but a FinTech topic. #00:42:23-3#
91	Interviewer: I have to say honestly, I started with the dissertation and there you always think, you consider a lot of things. Initially, I wanted to consider all FinTech or FinTechs in general. And then I get deeper in there and have noticed that is not in my scope unfortunately. #00:42:39-9#
92	Interviewee3: Then you also like to get bogged down. #00:42:41-1#
93	Interviewer: Yes exactly. And that is why I had to focus and that is why I focused on these financing FinTechs. That is why I cannot give you any ... #00:42:52-1#
94	Interviewee3: No, no problem. But we are looking at this and as I said, sometimes I know the topics also, not from my own but from indirect experience and that was quite exciting what the colleagues had often reported. #00:43:05-4#
95	Interviewer: I mean, you can also try it on the other side as an investor, if you have money where you say you want to invest it differently. It is also interesting; you can look at different projects and fundings and invest. #00:43:16-8#
96	Interviewee3: Yes. No, that was also very informative and very educational for me. That is why I really wanted to make the appointment. Even though it was a bit difficult today with these provisional numbers, we have done that now. #00:43:33-6#
97	Interviewer: Yes, I have to thank you again. Thank you for taking the time because I know that it is natural. #00:43:47-5#

98	Interviewee3: Yes gladly. What is the response from other CFOs? Is it difficult to get appointments? #00:43:49-7#
99	Interviewer: It works. I find it surprisingly good because it may be a more popular subject and companies that are more innovative are also more open. But I also look at companies that are a bit more traditional. Then, I have a good comparison. They have already been available. Well it works but I get a lot of rejections. #00:44:16-9#
100	Interviewee3: Yes, well, of course. There are enough companies in southern Bavaria or in Bavaria. The selection is great. How did you come to us, if I may ask?
101	Interviewer: I searched the Internet, googled and then came to you and saw, innovative, Industry 4.0 and the numbers I could see directly which was great. Because then I knew, perfect, fits exactly into my investigations. #00:44:28-5#
102	Interviewee3: I did not know X before. Is a B2B area. Is not a brand that you know somehow anyway. Often one speaks of the hidden champions although I would not consider ourselves now as a hidden champion but already as a company that is already market leader in its field in Germany or Europe if the brand is narrow enough. And I did not know the company before. And there are quite a lot in Bavaria that you do not know that way. #00:45:25-0#
103	Interviewer: But that may change in the future with the growth. #00:45:29-5#
104	Interviewee3: That is true. Since the IPO has already contributed a lot. You can confirm that in any case. #00:45:36-5#

Transcript: Interview 4

- 1 Interviewer: So, you have 800 employees and you have a turnover of about 300 mn €. You are represented in 26 locations and have existed for a long time. Founded in 1878, I have seen. You offer logistics systems and connection elements. On the one hand, as I understood as wholesaler, but at the same time as a service provider in which you offer the system. #00:00:52-3#
- 2 Interviewee4: I agree. That is pretty well described. So maybe to explain the business model. The conventional approach used to be that in this range of C-parts. We distinguish this in an A-B-C classification. Each customer defines the parts a bit differently, but, in any case, they are the least valuable parts. The boundaries are flowing. It can be described as screw, nuts, washers, all possible modifications. This goes to industrial parts, so any hydraulic parts. Everything that is not too expensive. I say so in Ikea it would be the bag with the screws. These are the C-parts. And the conventional procurement was such that one, I say now that you had in such a factory then 500 or 1000 different parts. And they were then disposed of conventionally. This means that you have made an inquiry about a certain amount. You could not order too less because otherwise the price per piece were quite high. You also have to order a certain minimum amount and then made a call for tenders. And then you took all at once time or on several occasions which in turn led to a disposition. At the workplace, the worker then actually took care of himself in this customer warehouse, then left the workplace and filled up his inventory there. Of course, when chatting with the warehouse staff he kept talking and was then more or less short or longer away from his workplace. The new process is going on so that there is really only, I say so, only one tender which often runs over several years. Two, three years are usual periods. It is then practically negotiated the very rough amount. A price is defined. It is the case that we go directly to the workplace with the various logistics systems, the simplest of which is the two-container system. Either directly to the workplace or at least in a hall directly near the workplace set up a two-container system. The operator removes from the front container, when empty the container is either scanned and thrown into a box where RFID tag is automatically scanned more or less, the passive one. Or there are also containers that are only rotated. And turning triggers the ordering process. And that will automatically happen in our IT system. If an order is the only manual action, then in the warehouse is the picking and delivery. What is saving the customer? Here I say the keyword total costs of ownership: At the customer the result is that there is no regular tender anymore, the complete disposition, the warehouse, the inventory, so that the capital tie up, the warehouse staff, and in the end the customer has his screws and his hardware where he needs them without all the process costs that have made him quite a lot of work before. Because the disposition of a small part is not, I say now, not easier than a disposition of an expensive large part. That is just how it is. And that is the business model. #00:04:38-3#
- 3 Interviewer: Ok, I understood that so far. Then perhaps very briefly to your role. You are managing director since 2008 and responsible for purchasing, finance, and IT. #00:04:49-6#
- 4 Interviewee4: That is right. In the past, I was also responsible for the warehouse, but a colleague who has also been managing director since the beginning of this fiscal year, who also planned this warehouse, has taken over the job and it is in very good hands. That fits. #00:05:06-3#
- 5 Interviewer: I just prepared a few questions. I would just go through it. #00:05:09-7#
- 6 Interviewee4: Gladly. #00:05:12-7#

7	Interviewer: Then I would go directly to the subject. You also mentioned briefly that you currently have financing with an interest rate of 0.6% to 1%. #00:05:21-1#
8	Interviewee4: Yes, that is the range. #00:05:21-1#
9	Interviewer: My question would be. What financing instruments do you currently use? #00:05:28-2#
10	Interviewee4: Ok. I am going from long term to short term. Of course, in the long term we have, I say, when I look at the group and I also take the real estate company to finance the real estate in the long term through mortgages. Then, of course, a very large factor is the working capital requirement. I see that mainly in stocks and accounts receivable. So, working capital as you say it. We have stocks in the order of more than 100 million €. We have receivables in the order of 40 million €. Everything has to be financed. And there is, I say now, at the level of the sales GmbH then medium-term financing and when I speak of level of GmbH, I always speak of no collateral. Mid-term financing in the range of 3-5 years and then of course there are also the very short-term which are usually covered by money market loans with the term of 1-3 months. And, of course, there is the situation where a three-year financing or a five-year financing sometimes falls under three years. That means I have between 3 months and 3 years, of course, I have the foothills more or less in it. This is the classic financing mix and factoring is also an issue for us. We do factoring for two reasons. Once liquidity and secondly also hedge. Because behind factoring, when I sold a claim, there is no default risk anymore. And then I do not need my own credit insurance. Of course, I could cover that separately in a two-contract model. Both has advantages and disadvantages. We decided for the one-contract model. There is, let us say quite classic, a real factoring so a real sale of the claim so that it is out of the balance sheet, sold to a factor. And that makes the credit insurance in the background. #00:07:49-1#
11	Interviewer: So, you have one general contract. And I think, you also wrote me that you have about 350,000 receivables. Do you sell all accounts receivable directly? #00:08:04-2#
12	Interviewee4: No, we have selected debtors that we sell. We proceed according to the following two criteria: On the one hand payment term. I do not need to sell anything that has a fortnightly payment term. Does not make any sense because until I sold it is the receipt of payment there. And of course, the volume. That is, even if one hundred-and eighty-days payment term and there are only 2000 euros on the account because I need no factoring, because it is not worth it. Since the effort is not worth it. So, we do factoring for those with high balances and high payment terms. And in the combination. There are certain minimum balances, even if you have a long payment term. We do not include them all. Where there is really meat behind it, you can see on the balance mainly, is factoring used. #00:09:03-5#
13	Interviewer: Can you say something about the conditions? #00:09:06-5#
14	Interviewee4: Yes, I say, I can specify a range. And our model is designed to be relatively flexible. For example, I sell 30 million in claims. Of these 30 million, there is also a retention. At the end, there are maybe 25 million available because something is rejected because a limit does not fit or whatever. No matter. So, I could get 25 million. However, I only have to finance an annual average of 8 million. However, I sold the rest and I also have credit insurance. But I am so flexible that I only have to take over these 8 million or take on average and only for these 8 million or it can sometimes be 10 or 12 million. And only then, I pay an all-in margin. An interest margin more or less. EURIBOR plus an interest margin. And in this all-in margin, the interest for financing

	and the risk costs, i.e. the cost of credit insurance which operates the factor in the background is covered. And the terms I am not telling you exactly what I have now. I cannot do this. But I will tell you what the market is here in this area. The all-in margin is currently somewhere between 1.2 and 1.5 percentage points what we pay at the current EURIBOR. So, I have virtually a financing, I say, between 1.2 and 1.5 percent pa. For this financing including the credit insurance. #00:11:14-3#
15	Interviewer: Ok. And that is pa. So, per anno. #00:11:20-0#
16	Interviewee4: Yes, exactly. And I have got that. That is why I wrote that too. I believe that these systems cannot handle things in this scale. I cannot imagine that there is anyone who invests there. But I mean, that always depends on the credit rating. I know people who pay three times for factoring. #00:11:44-9#
17	Interviewer: And again, very briefly on the medium-term financing. Are these bank loans? #00:11:52-2#
18	Interviewee4: Yes, without collateral. #00:11:53-2#
19	Interviewer: Without collateral. And you have not used mezzanine yet. Or did you use it? #00:11:58-3#
20	Interviewee4: No, we have not used mezzanine yet. I have been working on it but that was ten years ago. Promissory note we had once. That was relatively expensive back then. We had only done that once. Was not in an interest phase as now. Ten years ago, that looked a bit different. But at that time compared to the conditions we get now, even if I extrapolate to that time, promissory note loans were more expensive and not cheap. #00:12:37-9#
21	Interviewer: Assuming you have to make an investment now, do you have a certain preference, which form of financing you would use? #00:12:47-3#
22	Interviewee4: That depends on what you mean by investment. I am talking about investing in buildings or operating equipment, i.e. storage rack or investing in an equity investment. Of course, that varies, depending on what you need it for. #00:13:06-1#
23	Interviewer: Let us say for a building or another asset, like a storage rack. #00:13:16-0#
24	Interviewee4: So, we would try to mortgage the thing according to our approach. Over a period of at least ten, if possible fifteen years. #00:13:31-5#
25	Interviewer: Ok. #00:13:34-1#
26	Interviewee4: And when it comes to an acquisition. For example, I mean there is no, there must be in the end the bank which provides a credit rating. Then it will be a little more expensive. You would have to negotiate individually with the bank. It would definitely be a bank loan as a rule. Whereby I would expect the interest, I say, with a two before the decimal point. #00:14:00-2#
27	Interviewer: And regarding internal financing, would you first try to finance it as much as possible? #00:14:04-9#
28	Interviewee4: That is always the question of liquidity, so say what is the company providing in liquidity. There is more liquidity if I put less in the current assets at the storage or less in receivables. Where the storage is always the main factor. Of course, profit which is there which is not distributed, of course, is used first. But since we are relatively capital-intensive because of the high inventory we have to hold; credit is always more or less. Because that does not matter. If I use the liquidity left over as

	repayment of loans on the back side, I have to put back in the front, if I want to make an investment. #00:14:58-0#
29	Interviewer: Ok. Yes, I have understood that. So, this is capital intensive and you would prefer the internal financing first. But if that is almost tight you would access external debt like a bank loan and as you mentioned mezzanine is more in the back because you used it once and the conditions were relatively high. #00:15:24-5#
30	Interviewee4: Yes, we had a promissory note. We did not have mezzanine. Mezzanine is such a mixture of debt, where e.g. rather silent business partners are behind it. At least that is how it was then. Maybe that has meanwhile changed in the last ten years. You may know more about what models look like now. I cannot say that. #00:15:42-7#
31	Interviewer: There are also different models. There are subordinated loans. Then subordinated loans with participation that you get in addition an interest rate that depends on the turnover or even the profit. Or also participates in the company value increase. Or also, as you mentioned, a silent participation or certification rights. And they have a relatively flexible scope. But maybe then to the next question. You also said you have banks. Do you also have one or more longer relationships with a house bank? #00:16:28-4#
32	Interviewee4: Yes, of course. Almost all the banks we work with. We have been working with them for a long time. I have been in the company for 24 years now. Most of them we already have had. Some came 10, 12 years ago and one came half a year ago. One is eliminated for that. After all, there are also very long-standing relationships. And of course, it is one of those things, you do not believe is that way but even nowadays there is a certain amount of seriousness and trust in the business. And on both sides. It goes to the point that I do not change the banks like the shirts only because someone offers two tenths cheaper. But one tries to build up a long-standing business relationship. Because, I say the bank wants that because of course they want to have a good customer loyalty. And we want that because, of course, we attach importance to the fact that not when the tiniest wind comes up the escape here leave the house. And that is why we have never taken in foreign banks. The Austrians came once, then they left again. At the moment they are coming back. That is a bit too close to us. Yes, that does not help. Then you have the work again to change. They also cook with water. We know what the market price is and we get that from our house banks too. #00:18:04-8#
33	Interviewer: Ok, I understood that. You certainly see advantages through a relationship with a house bank. That would be e.g. as you know each other, a kind of trust. And that availability is also there, so when things do not go so well that you can rely on getting a loan because the bank knows you. #00:18:25-9#
34	Interviewee4: Not always. If it is not bad, bankers are not crazy. They also have to justify. If the banker does have such a good relationship with me, he will not say 10 million more but we know you are going bad soon. So far love does not go. But there is not always only black and white, but there is also a grey area. #00:18:45-1#
35	Interviewer: It goes in the direction. So, you feel more like you have a higher availability. #00:18:49-4#
36	Interviewee4: Yeah, there you are, of course. If I need a little more then I will call that and then it will check it and after two minutes I will have some information and everything will be fine. #00:19:01-4#
37	Interviewer: So, also the speed. #00:19:04-2#

38	Interviewee4: Exactly. #00:19:05-9#
39	Interviewer: And concerning the conditions, you said, there was already one or the other bank which then tried to come in with better conditions. But that is not so important to you but rather you want the reliability. #00:19:26-0#
40	Interviewee4: Yes, you have to see that. Everything moves then in the tenth of a percent range. That is not the case that it is two percent cheaper because it would not work. That would be negative. But everything moves in the low single-digit range. And if one goes in with a competitive price of 3 or 4 tenths than the market, one knows for sure that he cannot keep that after a year. That is about the same when you change the gas supplier. Since you get great conditions at the beginning and after one year you are at the same price as the other. #00:20:06-8#
41	Interviewer: Yes, that is the business model. Only cheap try to come in and then raise prices. #00:20:13-2#
42	Interviewee4: Yes, logically, taking advantage of the inertia and saying the first year I did not make money but now I can earn. Then there is just that, you can handle that by changing every year, but that is not what you always want to do. It is not a big effort, but the human being is sluggish. #00:20:38-2#
43	Interviewer: And regarding the collateral. Because you also said that they are unsecured. Then you also have an advantage. Because the house bank has known you for a long time. It knows your business model. It knows your cash flows, more or less naturally. That could be an advantage. #00:20:57-3#
44	Interviewee4: Of course. I do not know now, how others would react when I say that I would like to have 10 million € from you without collateral. Those who do not know us might look at the balance and say ok. But I do not know because we have not tried it yet and therefore cannot make any statements. #00:21:21-0#
45	Interviewer: Do you see any disadvantages through a house bank relationship? #00:21:24-3#
46	Interviewee4: What could be disadvantages? Yes, well, of course, since I do not know the other systems so well. I do not know how they work. Sure, if you say now that is a pure FinTech which is internet-based and I have my shares there and eventually comes the money. Works also, sure. But that is probably also a generation issue. I am in my mid-50s and I have no problem with communication. Since the younger generation, maybe if they do not do it by What's App has more of a problem. So, I do not know. For me, there is no disadvantage in having to communicate. #00:22:24-7#
47	Interviewer: So, to make regular appointments and maybe to fulfil certain requirements. So, I do not know if you have such kind of covenants even if you do not have to deposit any collateral. And if you have to comply with certain ratios? #00:22:44-3#
48	Interviewee4: Yes. In some loan agreements but rather not in the mass. We always reject that if one wants to have one. Simply with the justification of equal treatment. The others do not have it, so you do not get it. Works mostly. Actually, works at all or has to work, otherwise I have a problem with everyone. So far. Where it is different if I have an individual financing of a project in the building sector. There was some funding where there were some covenants. But they have expired so far. But we do not have any problems there. I mean in some way want the new providers a certain security? Or how is it with this crowdfunding? Or what is there. Is there no collateral? Or put someone else against assignment of any amount? #00:23:56-5#

- 49 Interviewer: Then I would go to the next topic very briefly. Namely to crowdlending and crowdinvesting. And maybe just tell something about it. There is the generic term crowdfunding. This is when money is collected from investors and given to borrowers for a particular project. That is basically crowdfunding. And it can be differentiated again in crowdfunding with financial return for the investors and once without. That is the donation-based and reward-based crowdfunding and that is donation based or you get another reward but no interest rate in this sense. And crowdfunding with interest rates can also be divided into two areas again. In crowdlending and crowdinvesting. Crowdlending is a kind of credit. So, you have a fixed rate and a fixed term. Both works in principle like that. You go to a platform on the internet, create a funding there for a specific topic, for a project, for an investment and upload it to the platform. Investors can then invest in the funding and you will get the money. That is the same for both. And in crowdlending, it is some kind of credit, like fixed rate and fixed maturity. And there are also various mechanisms in which investors and borrowers come together. Once it is like that. You create a funding, then the platform makes a creditworthiness check and determines what the interest rate is. And then investors can invest. The second variant is: You upload the funding and an auction defines the interest rate. And the third variant is that the platform itself decides whether you get the loan or not. Also, at a fixed rate because the platform has a contract with professional investors. Then, if the platform gives you feedback and defines a fixed rate, then the funding will still be uploaded to the platform for five days, then investors can invest and if the amount is not fully met, it will cover that through the contract with the professional investors. And currently, crowdlending rates are between 2.49% and 16.6%. Currently, for all platforms except at a platform with the auction a personal guarantee is necessary. Of course, this is for a company, a limited liability company, if you are a manager, let us say an employee, of course that could be difficult. #00:27:15-0#
- 50 Interviewee4: Certainly yes. And I have the alternative. I do not even pay half the interest on the best price and have no collateral. Three times you can guess what I choose. #00:27:24-3#
- 51 Interviewer: Yes, I can think so too. Now my question would be. Under what circumstances would you make funding through crowdlending? #00:27:37-3#
- 52 Interviewee4: Yes, I say the conditions must be better. So, under conditions are clearly the hard facts for me. That means interest rate and collateral should be the same, so none. I mean that is the classic. Money is the same everywhere. And the repayment structure, etc. But I think that would probably be flexible. But the topic is actually the interest rate and the price. If you have a homogeneous product, then the price is natural, I say 90% decisive. And then come in soft facts where you say, what is the effort with the whole thing. And the effort is probably even higher over the internet. Because I have to upload the thing, otherwise I just have a relaxed conversation with my banker. He already knows me anyway. He then summarises the most important things and talks to his credit man. This will probably mean less work for me than the whole thing, let us say our business model, discussing our intention with the network community there. I could imagine. I do not know. #00:29:07-1#
- 53 Interviewer: Well, of course, you have to create a funding, and that is certainly more effort the first time. Maybe a bit less if you do it more often and of course more experienced. But it is probably already associated with a certain effort. You do not have to make a physical meeting with a banker but you would have to upload business numbers. And you have the effort to create the funding and upload it. Then I would interpret it that way, even if the interest rate and terms were even the same you would

	tend to keep it running normally over the bank because you actually see it as less effort in a conversation with the adviser. #00:29:50-4#
54	Interviewee4: And I would like data privacy at the bank. Sure, is nothing. But I am talking to the bankers and I know that will work. If I upload that to the internet. I do not know who is sitting on the other side of the bank. And I do not know where my data goes there. I have to undress a bit in quotation marks. Of course, also towards the bank. There is no essential difference. But there I know where it goes and on the internet I do not know. #00:30:24-0#
55	Interviewer: Regarding banks, you probably know, there are some regulations like Basel, MiFiD and everything else that the banks have to meet. In the case of crowdlending platforms or crowdinvesting platforms, such rules do not have to be met. In the case of crowdlending platforms, it would be the case that the loan is also provided by a bank because in Germany only the bank may grant a loan that has a banking license. The platform would collect the funds from the investors and then give it to a bank. The bank grants the loan and then the bank resells the whole thing in partial claims to the investors. There are a lot of transactions behind it, but things are automated as much as possible. But would that scare you off? That it is less regulated because you do not know exactly how the data will be used. #00:31:24-3#
56	Interviewee4: Yes, correctly. I mean, I do not know exactly what is going on in the background of the bank. I cannot say that. But maybe it is just a feeling, maybe because you do not know it. I would not rule out that. But because it is so regulated, a certain security is there that not all the data appear somewhere where they should not appear. Because I am on a platform to access the diverse audience, I upload my sensitive data, such as business plans, etc. #00:32:03-8#
57	Interviewer: You also have concerns about a copy of the idea. Because you publish the funding. It depends on what you need the money for. Would you be sceptical about the topic? #00:32:21-8#
58	Interviewee4: As in our industry rather not because what do I need money for? For a warehouse finance, I need money for a building or for an operating device. As long as I do not have to publish the exact technical plans of the conveyor technology there, I would not have any concerns now. If I were a manufacturer, I would have to justify financing for a product that is relatively new and represents a new idea. And I would have to disclose that I have a problem. Not in my industry. #00:33:01-8#
59	Interviewer: Ok, understand. Would you then perhaps see it as a marketing effect? So, in the positive direction because the funding will be published there and the company will be presented. #00:33:15-5#
60	Interviewee4: Yeah that is a thing now. Do I really want to have my funding published? Is this advertising? Do not I want to control my advertising separately and publish completely different things? I would rather see it in that direction. What will be published. If I want this effect, I have to set up my documents quite differently like normal financing documents. Then I really have a funding, so it is also called and let the marketing department move up and say that is particularly positive there. Maybe this is when I build a new central warehouse in our industry, then I can say that is so and so big and so many places and everything really great. But if I finance my storage, well then. That is not very sexy, yes. #00:34:16-0#
61	Interviewer: Ok. I understand. Then to the next question. There is still a point. The whole thing is actually limited, so in terms of volume. That is per funding. You can also upload multiple funding, but the maximum volume is € 2.5 million. #00:34:45-6#

62	Interviewee4: So, our last warehouse expansion cost 10 times that. That means that would probably be too low. But I think so, I also learnt in our conversation. As I understand it, I can only imagine that as a reasonable alternative for a smaller middle class. A smaller middle class may also have worse conditions at the banks. With the factoring companies and may also be willing to, just owner-managed, because he must also provide personal guarantee to the bank and for which is an interest rate of 2, 5% or 3.5% very interesting. Because he gets nothing better at the bank. So, the personal guarantee issue would not be as important for them as it is for us. And the interest rate would not be so bad for him. The amount limit would not be bad for him. That is probably enough. I could imagine it. I think the thing should work in small medium-sized companies. To SMEs as you say. I do not know where the border is right now, but I will say 50 million and below. That could be interesting for them. #00:36:21-5#
63	Interviewer: There are different SME definitions. According to the SME institute here in Germany, the limit is exactly 50 million. But there are also other definitions, now also from banks or other institutions. And some of them also have other definitions, even up to 500 million. And my focus is precisely on the higher middle class, where you also fit in optimally. Because I am looking closely at how it might or might not be an alternative for these companies. Because currently it is already so, they already focus more on, as the indicators look like, on the smaller companies. #00:37:10-6#
64	Interviewee4: Yes, the chance of success is higher. #00:37:13-6#
65	Interviewer: Yes, exactly. But my investigation is: There is this model, Christensen's disruptive innovation model. This is a Harvard professor. Maybe you know the model. He says that exactly these companies, so the new providers, come in such a market, first serve a small niche. The customers are not attractive to the established. Because small businesses are not attractive to big companies. Like banks and small businesses. Since the banks do not earn money with the little companies. And then they improve, change their business models and then serve large customers relatively quick. And then it is often too late for the established companies to react in time. I would like to look exactly here, to what extent that is perhaps attractive for larger companies or which K.O. criteria already exist, where to say, ok that is very difficult. #00:38:31-6#
66	Interviewee4: Yes. Amazon did the same thing. Grown up in the B2C business. First with the books. Then in the complete B2C area. And now it is also in the B2B area. At least with standardized item delivery is very vulnerable. In the end, that goes in the same direction. So, in summary, one can say that for us a security criterion would be the personal guarantee. Another serious criterion would be the amount of the funding and the work involved. For 2.5 million, I make a call and hold a five-minute conversation. Then I have 2.5 million. I do not need a published funding. I do not need anything. The issue is done. This is also a convenience factor. #00:39:23-1#
67	Interviewer: Maybe then briefly to crowdinvesting. There is then no bank loan but mezzanine financing. These are those loans with an additional interest rate which is participated in the profit or to the company value increase. Certification rights or silent participations. But as I would interpret it because you would put mezzanine back on the funding preference, you would not even tend to try it. #00:40:08-9#
68	Interviewee4: I know that, of course, that cannot be very favourable from the point of view of classification. And, of course, it will be a high effort from the structuring. Because it is just a mixture of equity and debt capital. And for me it would be only a case if I would get no capital outside. Because in times of need the devil learns to fly. #00:40:38-1#

69	Interviewer: But then I understood that. Let us say you would not get a bank loan; would you like to try crowdlending? #00:40:45-8#
70	Interviewee4: Yes, of course that would be a possibility. And I say, if I did not get anything from the bank, then there are also no interest rates of 1%. You do not get more. That depends on the credit rating. And then, of course, it is interesting for the others again. I think that one is much higher in the pricing of such loans. #00:41:15-3#
71	Interviewer: And then there are also factoring platforms. That is right, you already read that. You upload the account receivable. And there are also different mechanisms. This can also be sold through an auction. Or the platform itself finances that and makes the decision whether or not it finances it. As I understood, that would be out of the question for you purely procedurally. Because you want to have a standard contract in which all is regulated and the claim is automatically assigned. #00:42:05-7#
72	Interviewee4: Yes, exactly. Just to understand the system with this platform. Is it then an open factoring? This must then be communicated to the customer. So, in other words, does the debtor pay the person who acquired the account receivable? Or will he still pay us and we will pass on the payments? #00:42:27-0#
73	Interviewer: So, I have identified a total of 12 platforms that meet certain quality criteria. I have looked at all of them and more or less they are all relatively flexible. One platform offers that, the other this. But there are both. There are recourse and there is non-recourse factoring. And there is notification and non-notification factoring. And some also offer a specific service. So, in that respect it is already very flexible. But you upload the accounts receivable individually and it is refinanced individually. #00:43:14-1#
74	Interviewee4: That does not work for us. Because of the small business. Because every single screw box is calculated individually. Because it is just an automated process. I have about 10,000 accounts receivable a month. And there is maybe an average of 40-50 euros each. #00:43:42-4#
75	Interviewer: Yes, I understood that. So, if you want to do some sort of FinTech, then that would have to be automated and the terms should be exactly like where you have it right now. #00:44:02-6#
76	Interviewee4: Yes, from my point of view, I believe that it would be technically very expensive for us. And now we really have a very simple system. We download the open items twice a week from our SAP system via a programmed export. I mean, they also get the individual items. That is also the case. But the platform is based on the fact that I pluck lots of individuals out of it. And then I probably get my money from thirty different people. So that will be no option. Over my dead body. I am scared to death, to be honest. I understand if smaller SMEs do it which have some big bills. It puts in twenty bills, for example á 80,000 euros, then this can be handled but not with my structure. #00:45:07-9#
77	Interviewee4: No, it went completely in the direction that I was expecting, and I have become a bit smarter, too, what is there. That was also the key stimulus for me. That for me, at least during this time, was 90% to me. There were still some uncertainties because I still could not judge. But I have learned a lot about where the journey goes. #00:45:13-2#
78	Interviewer: I understood that. Then I would already have to go to the end. #00:45:13-2#
79	Interviewee4: We are full in time. #00:45:16-2#

- 80 Interviewer: Have you one or more questions that you have expected in this context but which I did not ask? #00:45:22-1#
- 81 Interviewee4: No, it went completely in the direction that I was expecting, and I have become a bit smarter, too, what is there. That was also the key stimulus for me. That for me it is no option, at least during this time, was to 90% clear to me. There were still some uncertainties which I could not judge. But I have learned a lot about where the journey goes. #00:46:01-1#

Transcript: Interview 5

1	Interviewer: What financing instruments do you currently use? #00:00:16-6#
2	Interviewee5: The situation to the equity ratio once again. This is actually more dramatic than I have just described because we have a very high cash position next to the equity financing and little debt. So that is a bit crazy. Not just a bit. It is completely. But that is very much the case, as you have already seen, we have stopped projects, have not really invested heavily in the past 18 months, but we have got a lot of depreciation on projects of the past. And that is a tax issue. We have a low tax rate and so we are collecting money right now. #00:00:55-7#
3	Interviewer: And the high internal-financing. Does that have specific reasons? #00:00:58-7#
4	Interviewee5: Yes. The main shareholder wants to be independent of banks. He does not want to limit his scope of action through external partners. That is why he does not want to go public. So, he would never go public because he does not want to give a quarterly statement and then explain to anyone else why he should do anything. This is a topic of perceived freedom. #00:01:28-2#
5	Interviewer: Is there no bank loan? Maybe for short-term liquidity? #00:01:33-2#
6	Interviewee5: There are short-term, so we have just turned off for 31.5., our balance sheet date, and there we have delivered. There our goods are gone. So, in principle it is the case that we normally, at present it is not a normal case, but normally we have then relatively quick 50 - 60 million euros loans. Because we always have to pre-finance our half-yearly sales. And if you have 400 million euros in sales, there are 200 million. Then there are goods that value between 60, 70 or 80 million euros. We usually have to pre-finance it. Currently not at all due to our cash position. And then actually have a financing issue during the year. But, for example, if we buy a property here and then build something for seven or eight million, we will do it with our own funds. #00:02:30-6#
7	Interviewer: And there are no other financing instruments either? For example, leasing? #00:02:33-0#
8	Interviewee5: Leasing. We use leasing but not from the idea of financing. But rather from the allocation options. So, what I want to say. For example, we have 180 cars. We lease that. But not because we cannot buy them but we lease them, so that after three years we can give the thing back and take a new one. So, we have three people in our fleet that manage our fleet and if we buy, and we have 180 cars, then we have to sell between 30 and 50 annually. The effort, so we think the effort would be higher. But for financial reasons, I would not finance it but for handling reasons. #00:03:30-3#
9	Interviewer: Ok. For process, administrative reasons. #00:03:34-3#
10	Interviewee5: There are so blatant topics. X did that. They sold their brand and leased it back. Such a sale and lease-back process. You do that when you stand financially from your cash flow with your back against the wall. Does not matter. But we have another topic. In times of negative interest, such a cash flow does not really help you much. #00:04:08-2#
11	Interviewer: Ok, I understood that. Due to the high liquidity you have never used factoring in the past? #00:04:16-7#
12	Interviewee5: Yes. Partly we have done factoring, but then the reason was that we have recognised that we cannot continue with our medium-sized instruments of our

company. But that was not a financing idea, but that was a handling idea. Because we just thought, ok, if we sell the receivables, for example, for 60 or 70 percent, it is faster for us to get more money and less effort than if we deal with it for 2 or 3 years and get money from the Greeks. So, it is not so much funding. So, many are doing this to favour their cash flow and simply to improve their working capital. That was not our topic so far. #00:05:01-9#

13 Interviewer: Those are more the process or procedural costs behind it. #00:05:05-2#

14 Interviewee5: Exactly. #00:05:06-5#

15 Interviewer: That you have no administrative costs. #00:05:07-9#

16 Interviewee5: Actually, as we now talk, we wanted to say that it tends to be process simplification in the business. If that is always true, let us just ignore it, but it is the same with us. #00:05:20-3#

17 Interviewer: Ok. Regarding mezzanine, have you used mezzanine capital, yet? #00:05:25-0#

18 Interviewee5: There was simple, sometimes just spoken, never a reason. So, X has always valued his growth potential well and if we have ever discussed an IPO or if an investment banker approached us, Y always asked an essential question, what am I doing with the money? And that is really a question. If somebody gave us 100 million today, what would you do with the 100 million. Now you could say, ok, we are looking for even better managers or even better designers. A theme. But we already have enough money today. The next question is we would invest in a logistics centre or invest in SAP? Or we go brutally to a country like the United States and have a marketing campaign with 30 or 40 million and hang half of the US with our posters full. You realize right now, I just do not know where we should spend the money and even what I would not do, even if I had the money, logistics and SAP at the same time, I would not do synonymous because we as an organisation could not cope. So, the only topic that would really make sense in the end, would be to conquer a market, if I had to put a lot of marketing power behind it. Otherwise I just cannot do it with the imagination. Now we could say that we can buy the market companion. But we have excluded that in the company. I think I could not say we buy X. But even that makes little sense in our market because we are very much brand-driven and a small brand or other brand is of no use to us. Actually, it does not help much. #00:07:18-6#

19 Interviewer: If you had to make an investment now. Let us say a bit smaller. Let us not say the big sums. Due to the high liquidity that you have there, would you prefer in the first case, the internal financing? If it could be covered by the internal financing. #00:07:34-2#

20 Interviewee5: Yes, that is the way it is. When we have received offers of cheap loans in the past. For example, a loan for the photo studio. I believe 5 million for half a percent. I would have liked to take it, but it makes no sense to take it and pay negative interest on the other side. So, the current situation is strange for the one who currently has these resources. By the way, I have to add one more thing. Of course, it has something to do with the fact that we do not distribute everything we have on cash. We could also have a shareholder who says, I pull all the cash that I have, I pull out and that at the personal level and do that in private assets. He has not done so far. #00:08:24-1#

21 Interviewer: So, he distributes, I partly think of something, but a large part he always leaves in there as internal financing. For operations and also for investments. #00:08:33-5#

22	Interviewee5: Exactly. So far, we have never financed the dividends, which is common in other companies. So great do that. They say then, ok I distribute now and finance it with three percent because I know that my return is over three percent. We do not do it. #00:08:59-8#
23	Interviewer: And let us say, hypothetically, the money would not be enough for an investment. The liquid funds you have. Which instrument would you prefer? So, for example, a bank loan or mezzanine? #00:09:10-5#
24	Interviewee5: So, we would access a bank in a classic way. Because we get such loans because of our creditworthiness and the current situation on such good terms that I would keep it simple. And you can demand almost everything in the negotiations with the banks. With special cancellations. Actually, in the current situation, you realise that they are happy to give money to someone with a good credit rating because we have money. Because they have the same problem with the negative interest. #00:09:55-6#
25	Interviewer: Yes, the situation is ... #00:09:58-6#
26	Interviewee5: Yes, that is why the interview can be a bit strange. But it is not difficult to get money right now with a good credit rating. #00:10:07-3#
27	Interviewer: You already said that they offered you a loan. Or you could use a loan with a good interest rate. Is that with a house bank that you have longer? #00:10:20-1#
28	Interviewee5: From our banking structure we work together with UniCredit and with Sparkasse. Meanwhile, the DZ-Bank has come as well. The logic is, we have house banks. A mix of an international bank, this is the UniCredit. But we also have a local bank on the other side. This is the savings bank. Because we have different interests, of course. And in fact, when we get a loan, UniCredit sometimes cannot compete. But sometimes vice versa. So, just how it is set up. So, we had the basic idea earlier. Two, just three house banks with which we work relatively close together. But they cover different topics. If we want to change payments in Hong Kong, I do not have to talk to the Sparkasse here. They could somehow but the one from UniCredit I meet locally and says gentlemen we do that. Back to the lending. Of course, we still do it so that our house banks stay the same. We have once a year. This is mostly after our board meeting in January. There we publish and discuss outlook for the next three years. We are doing a banker's day. Every banker who works with us is invited. There are usually seven or eight people sitting around the table and we imagine how we want to continue working in the next two or three years, and then they all have the same information and can then ask if they did not understand something. Then everyone has the same information. That certainly helps us in such discussions because we are very transparent. It does not exist that we say something to one bank and the other bank we say a little bit differently and vice versa. But they have the same information. #00:12:20-7#
29	Interviewer: And can you say whether the house bank, so one of the house banks, offers better conditions, for example, than another bank? #00:12:31-4#
30	Interviewee5: Yes, that is indeed the case. Because there is one bank or another that would like to become a house bank. So, there are already highly competitive prices. So, if you finance the photo studio like now and you play that out, you actually get better conditions than at another bank. In fact, we sometimes use that to bring it to the bank. We do not say who is a fellow player. We say, you want to stick to these issues. Normally, it is not that we, by the way, is not that it is one percent better. They are already on a low level. That is almost impossible. But we already had the case when we played within this triumvirate. For example, a UniCredit said at the beginning, we are

	out there. We will not come with you. And the DZ Bank has still been able to deliver or vice versa. #00:13:31-4#
31	Interviewer: But then this is a bank, which then tries to gain a foothold? #00:13:37-8#
32	Interviewee5: There is. But, of course, they have to increase after a period like after 2 years, 18 months. That is how DZ-Bank came in. Already seven years ago, the DZ-Bank recognized early on that when it approaches our main shareholder with very good conditions that it can place itself. And in the end, it is the mix. For example, our forward foreign exchange transactions, if we then get these terms and conditions, they would like to make this business with us. But you only do that from a certain size. That is about 50 million euros a year for us. And, of course, they make profit. I am aware. #00:14:29-3#
33	Interviewer: And do you see any more benefits in a house bank relationship? #00:14:31-3#
34	Interviewee5: Actually, I do not see any advantages in a house bank relationship because the very critical thing we have never experienced here is when you do not have a good credit rating anymore and you have to negotiate with the banks that they keep up your line of credit, then you realise relatively quick, how strong the house banks are. And I have experienced quite exciting things in my earlier time. So, what I want to say. Today, all that is good, if you have 70 million and you ask for 100 million again, you get it relatively easy. It is different if you are already at -20 and you want to have 100 million more. Who else will go with you? #00:15:22-8#
35	Interviewer: Ok, I understood. You mean a house bank relationship is good only as long as my credit rating is good and if my credit rating is worse and I actually need the funds that then the bank is not there although you would actually think from a long relationship, they know the company and just then available in worse times. #00:15:41-4#
36	Interviewee5: That is the interesting thing about the Sparkasse and the Volksbank because they are more interested in the region. We probably have 800 employees here and 1,000 on the retail side. And if someone says he turns off the light, then he also knows that he probably has 50, 60, or 70 home financings which he also has in his books. He also turns off the light of them. May not be so bad in Y right now because you can use them differently. But is certainly different in Erfurt or Halle. That is why it is also a mixture of a major bank or international bank but also a regional bank. #00:16:24-6#
37	Interviewer: Ok. I understand. So, you would see the advantage in a regional bank because they are simply interested in regional issues. That the region is stable because of the broad funding. And that is why you also see the advantage of a higher availability. #00:16:40-5#
38	Interviewee5: Yes, that is the logic. #00:16:43-3#
39	Interviewer: And regarding speed. So, I mean your house bank knows you. And there is also a bankers meeting, so it knows the numbers. Then maybe a decision-making process on a loan goes faster? #00:16:58-0#
40	Interviewee5: Yes, that is indeed the case. You cannot compare that to having a bank in Hamburg. It is also so on very big issues. We had such a theme. We prepared in advance that something could occur and we work out the financing concept before the issue has even occurred. And if it does not occur, then it may be more work, but we are very transparent. And that is really true. This has something to do with speed. What is

it about? What am I talking about? It is about the audit risk. We have such a residual risk. It is very small, but if the small risk occurs, it will be a high volume. We could not cover that even with our 70 million cash. But we also talked about whether we would get 60, 50, 70 or 80 million more. That was very easy. But that has something to do with the special situation with us. Even with our still strong operating cash flow, we come into the situation that I described earlier. #00:18:11-5#

41 Interviewer: And do you see any other disadvantages with a house bank relationship? #00:18:15-7#

42 Interviewee5: I believe a house bank relationship is always, we are a regional player. We have a shareholder who is rooted here with his family. Everyone knows him here. He himself is a very conservative person and as he is seen, this is projected on us. And that makes it very easy for us to negotiate with banks. I am just going to another scenario for a moment. The main shareholder would be known to be very jumpy. His financing on his personal level is not under control. Much money would pull out here. That would certainly complicate the situation with the house banks. So that is why it is. I have just so much positive tailwind. Successful company, conservative, operating cash flow, very high equity, so more is almost impossible. And in addition, we have a high cash balance. And I keep going up to them and say 20 million, half a percent. That is natural, if you ask me that is absolute luxury. And of course, that, of course, I know from my earlier years, that can change very quickly. And then these structures can be different at once. #00:21:17-7#

43 Interviewer: And maybe a disadvantage, maybe in general and not just by a house bank but generally by bank financing. So, covenants. You just said the X does not have to justify itself somewhere or somehow have to disclose something. And banks already have so-called covenants, so they get regular report from you, that they say you have to keep certain key figures or you have to keep certain assets especially because they are deposited as collateral. #00:20:18-8#

44 Interviewee5: That does not burden us. The more critical the bank would be to us and the more effort that would mean for us. Of course, at that moment, so if I melted that away from the benefit, of course, other forms of financing would be relevant to put it simply. And today it is so, so it goes in this direction, we have not had that in the last 5, 6, 7 years. But that has to do with high transparency and very high performance. #00:21:01-4#

45 Interviewer: Ok. And appointments with banks. You said you bring the bankers here once a year. Do you find that rather disadvantageous or do you find that rather positively, that one exchanges regularly? #00:21:17-7#

46 Interviewee5: So, the basic idea on our side is that we want to have a high degree of transparency and that we want to ensure that we want the same information. That is why it is very positive for me because we set up the day or the three hours. That is why we took the initiative. So, it is not like they say ok now tell us but we will talk about it. So that also means we are in the lead and we can show what is important to us and can also show what a challenge is and where we might need help. #00:21:51-4#

47 Interviewer: Yes, that is right. On your side is the initiative. You definitely only see advantages. #00:21:58-5#

48 Interviewee5: Yes. And of course, it would be something completely different if we were on the stock exchange. For example, as an alternative. The effort would, of course, be dramatically higher. So, with quarterly reports, everything with IPO, I do not mean the IPO but the completed IPO and what happens then. And I also know one or

	the other, who are dealing with a delisting process because of the operationally benefit. So, if you are in a stable business and your stock market price, I say go up or down three percent. You just have to think about how many people do you need to prepare all the regulations. You have to think twice; do I need that? #00:22:50-9#
49	Interviewer: Yes, I know someone there too. Tesla. #00:22:55-8#
50	Interviewee5: Yes, exactly. That is a wonderful example. #00:22:58-0#
51	Interviewer: Good. Then I would go to the next topic and briefly say something about my investigation. So, I actually have three essential steps. First, I looked at the financing FinTechs. This means crowdlending, crowdinvesting and factoring. I can say something more about that later. So, what is the business model of them. Then, in a second step, I conduct interviews with CFOs of larger mid-sized companies to find out how financing FinTechs are an alternative to traditional banking. And third, I discuss a strategic model. This is the Christensen model. The disruptive innovation model. I do not know if you have ever heard of it? #00:23:43-4#
52	Interviewee5: No. #00:23:43-4#
53	Interviewer: This theory states that quasi new companies come in an established market, first serve the lower segment which is not interesting for the main players and is not attractive, so they will not look down there. They serve their main customers and rather the upper segment and are geared to their needs. And then the lower ones develop pretty quickly. Adjust their business models and then come pretty fast and pretty quickly pull main customers away from the established ones. And then disruption can happen. #00:24:22-1#
54	Interviewee5: Amazon would be a good example. #00:24:22-2#
55	Interviewer: Exactly, Amazon is a typical example. These are the essential three steps for me. First, I would ask, do you know crowdlending or crowdinvesting? Or maybe you already have experience with it? #00:24:35-5#
56	Interviewee5: Yes, but I have no experience. Except that I read it in the newspaper. But those were rather very sharp topics. Less for I finance my business but more I finance a venture. I started planning a traffic island. Who wants to spend 10 cents, 20 cents or maybe 1 euro or 5 euros? Up to expeditions or we help a children's village in Africa. That is how I know it, not furthermore. #00:25:05-9#
57	Interviewer: Then I would just say something for a moment. So, crowdfunding is an umbrella term and means I collect money from many smaller investors. A borrower who can use it for any project or funding. There are usually two distinctions. First, crowdfunding with financial return for investors and second, without. Without is donation-based or there is a return in another way. I am focusing on those with financial return. And there is crowdlending and crowdinvesting. Crowdlending is like a normal loan. There is a fixed rate and a fixed term. Both work in principle: A company can create a funding that is uploaded to the platform. There, investors can screen the funding, invest, the borrower gets the money and in the end the money is paid back. Crowdlending is a normal loan with a fixed term and a fixed interest rate. And there are three different matching mechanisms. Once, the funding is uploaded, the platform sets an interest rate and then investors can invest. The second option is, an interest rate is determined by an auction. And the third variant is that the platform itself decides whether or not to provide the loan. And the platform has a contract with professional investors, so to speak, if the amount cannot be fully funded by other investors, which can then be covered by the professional investors. And crowdinvesting is like

	mezzanine instruments. Subordinated loan or a subordinated loan with a participation in turnover, profits or company value increase. Participation rights or silent participations. Now I would just ask that assuming you had to make an investment, under what circumstances and conditions would you request a funding through a crowdlending platform? #00:27:21-3#
58	Interviewee5: Only if the relationship bank could not keep up. Pure from today's point of view. So here in the company, so as the board of X. #00:27:26-9#
59	Interviewer: So, you have internal financing anyway. If you now say the internal financing is exhausted, then you would definitely prefer the house bank. Then you would possibly search for other alternatives. I think I understood that, for example, on the hypothesis that the interest rates are the same, I think you would continue like this. If the interest rate were lower on a crowdlending platform? #00:28:02-0#
60	Interviewee5: Today it should be much lower. Why? Today I know my house bank, I know my contact person and that is the same contact person for 10 years. And they have proven to be very reliable. For that reason, purely in terms of relevance, if there was not a significant improvement in funding, there could be two levels. Either the interest is significantly lower or the amount is significantly higher, I would still remain in the concept. So that means it is actually about the terms. Because I would indeed get involved in something unknown from my current perspective. From point one, two or three but from today it is unknown. And today, I am just call Mr. X, who is the head of the bank, and say, look at that, please. But it could suddenly become more complicated, at least for me. #00:29:13-5#
61	Interviewer: And if that would be relatively popular? If you were a little more familiar with it. In principle, would you be open to it? #00:29:22-8#
62	Interviewee5: It was exactly the two topics. Once unusual. If I were more informed, if I had already experienced the business model and if I then knew someone else as a person, i.e. a contact person no machine, then that would be different. It is so. Yes. #00:29:47-0#
63	Interviewer: Maybe because these platforms are less regulated. The loan would eventually be provided through a bank. In crowdlending, it is the case that you need a banking license in Germany in order to be able to grant a loan. And it would be that the platform gets the money from the investors, then it gives that to the bank, the bank provides the loan and resells it in partial claims to the investors. But otherwise it is not as regulated as a bank. Would that deter you? Or would you rather see it as positive? #00:30:24-2#
64	Interviewee5: No. I would even rather see it as positive. Because in the environment in which we move, I find that over regulated. #00:30:36-0#
65	Interviewer: Then you could upload it there. Many investors see that. Would you see the marketing effect positively? #00:30:43-8#
66	Interviewee5: So, in our industry, such a topic is not perceived as a positive marketing effect. That may be different in other industries. But I already have such a high brand awareness here. I do not have to get known. But that is another special case. I understand the argument quite well and in other companies, especially when I start, it can be completely different in our industry as well. So, if I want to draw attention to myself, that could be a model. #00:31:21-7#
67	Interviewer: Of course, it is like that, if you try it through such a platform and let us say you did not get any bank loan and you try it through a platform and there you will not

	get it. That is a sign, a stamp no money received. How would you rate that as critical? #00:31:39-9#
68	Interviewee5: Alright. So, on the other hand, if your house bank does not give you any money and then the platform does not give you any money, then you at least have the security you will not receive any money. Then you are already burned anyway. So that is why I would not say that I would not go there because then it would be a negative image. The banks would only say, I have already said that. I have no other option. I would not see that as a negative. Because I am already branded negative. Well it would be confirmed. #00:32:17-1#
69	Interviewer: And would you consider something for idea copy if you uploaded? #00:32:22-3#
70	Interviewee5: No. The question with us, so in our case, is always, that is why I put this first previously. If I could take a bigger amount, no matter from whom. A larger amount is 50 to 100 million euros with us. Then I need an idea what I am doing with it. Would not go without attention in our industry. If I build a logistics centre for 90 million over there, as X did, everyone knows it. So that is because you meant idea reproduction. This is very difficult in our industry because you are under surveillance anyway. If we rent 10 flagship stores in the US, we would do it too. So, there we are very transparent. And they would ask themselves, what are they doing with the money? #00:33:19-7#
71	Interviewer: Ok. I mean, I looked at all the platforms. And it is true that they are focusing more on smaller companies. I am just interested to what extent this would be an alternative for larger medium-sized companies. It is just that they have a limit of 2.5 million euros per funding. So, you could upload multiple fundings. I think you just mentioned a few buzzes, that would be too low for you. As I understood it. #00:33:51-3#
72	Interviewee5: Yes, it would be too low. But on the other hand, it is natural to look at a company's lifecycle. If two or three guys meet and say I want to make the best X in the world and nobody will believe it. But they have expertise and an idea, only someone who finances them the first-round need. Then I think that is an interesting model. #00:34:15-9#
73	Interviewer: Exactly. There are also platforms for start-ups. In part, these platforms, which I have also looked at, also provide loans for start-ups. There are some that are only for start-ups. That is another point. For all, they do not demand assets as collateral but a personal guarantee. And, of course, if you are now employed as a CFO, I think that would be critical for you. Or how would you see that? #00:34:50-0#
74	Interviewee5: Sure, of course. So, I would say to our main shareholder, yes, like to give a security, but I am not part of it. Incidentally, we have the same principle in our franchise agreements. So, I understand the model. I do not want to have a contract with the limited liability company but with the person. Quite understandable. #00:35:14-0#
75	Interviewer: And would you consider that in principle easier to create and upload a funding? So, it is unknown, you said earlier, but would it deter you from the first tendency? #00:35:24-2#
76	Interviewee5: I think it is not easier. If you have people who have accompanied you for 10, 20 years. You know X and I would go to those today. Sparkasse. And I say, listen, I need 10 million euros because we are building three new flagship stores in the Belgian market. I would not have to explain that to them. He would know us; he would also

know the country results. He knows if this is critical or less critical. Sure, if I told nonsense, e.g. If we wanted to go into quite a stupid country, he would say we will not go there. But as long as that is out of his understanding because he accompanied us for a very long time, we have the money very straightforward with us. That is what I meant. If I had to explain to someone first, I need that for that. He has no plan who we are. The next would be, in the worst case, there are still questions. But because of what you said earlier with speed, which we also cultivate in our relationship management, that is precisely what counts. And there it is not at all, if the interest rate is good, but he looks at it and says yes because we already wondered, why you do that or yes, I understand, strategically an interesting approach. We carry it with us or we do not carry it with us. So, we have not only a bank but also someone who can check against if that makes sense. #00:37:00-1#

77 Interviewer: You would have investors in a funding. So, they look at that too in what they invest their money. In addition, you might have feedback about the product or the idea. #00:37:14-5#

78 Interviewee5: So, that is right. That may sound brutally arrogant now. I think that is a bit on the market. Even if I do not hear recommendations from consultants who have known us for a long time. For example, that we should make X or good Y. We would never do that. We cannot do that and we do not want to. In our case, since everyone thinks he can have a say in X and that is even more important to us, in brand building and brand architecture. They rarely help, the inputs from the outside. Well, there are people with whom I would like to talk about the future and other measures and issues. But they are not that many. #00:38:19-4#

79 Interviewer: And at the banks? #00:38:23-7#

80 Interviewee5: Similar. So, at the banks it is also interesting. It has more to do with care now. There is actually a good caregiver per bank who knows our history, knows our balance sheets. He can talk about financing issues. However, this cannot be the case with designs or realignments, e.g. do we want to change X and Y and do X? What market opportunities does X has? They are not there. There is also the savings bank director and UniCredit boss not there. Because then you actually need the investment banker, who is interested in X and has a taste. So, what I mean by that, the expertise from outside, sounds arrogant, is sometimes overrated. I believe that you need expertise, also from the outside. But I would not buy it from an investor who happens to have just any money, and he just happened to find X interesting. Now he talks to me. I do not think so. Just as if you were a sports car manufacturer and anyone who can pay one million euros explains how the new sports car should look like because he has already bought it once before. So that is why I do not value the expertise from the outside so much and have no meaning for me anymore. That would be irrelevant. #00:39:52-1#

81 Interviewer: Ok. I understood that. Then maybe briefly to the next topic. To crowdfunding. But I think that is pretty clear, too. You said yes, you would only try crowdlending if you did not get a bank loan. Now mezzanine capital is still a bit sharper than a normal bank loan. Would you first try crowdlending and then crowdfunding? Or the other way around? #00:40:21-2#

82 Interviewee5: Well, I would not even accept the variant from my current perspective. I would look for a wealthy person who knows that he has money. There are a few in our industry. And I would ask him if he would like to join us. Because with that I get a certain expertise and also get contacts because, for example, landlord knows that are important for the store. I would like to address a topic. He is relatively well known in

our industry. Mr. X. He is also chairman of the board at Y. He should do that well. That is easy because he wants to sit in Z. And of course, the X has contacts due to his other activities that Y could not get anywhere. So, if someone from Y wants to meet with the board of the German bank then that is by phone. In other words, now I turn it all over again, before I would go down with strangers on a bidding process or a platform, I would rather search for a person who has high liquid stocks, who has a certain personality. And about the personality and the history of certain contacts that I need. Because that feels more tradable for me at least subjectively. The basic idea, however, I think is already correct. So that somebody buys somewhere and for example if you do not want to have a fixed interest rate but you are more value-added or fundamentally more entrepreneurial, I tend to find it better. #00:42:24-3#

- 83 Interviewer: Ok. Let us say you do not have this contact and you would not find any contact and it would be the last option. #00:42:30-4#
- 84 Interviewee5: Then I would prefer that. #00:42:29-8#
- 85 Interviewer: That with mezzanine involvement where one is entrepreneurially involved. #00:42:33-3#
- 86 Interviewee5: Yes, but I have to say, always with a symmetry of opportunity and risk. #00:42:44-5#
- 87 Interviewer: Ok. So that must be in proportion. #00:42:44-5#
- 88 Interviewee5: Yes. Otherwise it makes no sense. An entrepreneur who is only an entrepreneur if things go well, I do not need that as an entrepreneur. So, I would take a certain amount of risk from the money. #00:43:01-9#
- 89 Interviewer: That he is not just liable for the amount he invested but maybe even beyond. #00:43:11-6#
- 90 Interviewee5: We can do it relatively easy. As one says, ok I provide 3 million. I need a guarantee of 3 million against it. We fix a minimum funding of 4% and an entrepreneurial component and I get the 4% in any case. Then I would not need it. #00:43:32-9#
- 91 Interviewer: If you say 3 million, no security. This is mezzanine capital, so first you have to serve debt, then mezzanine and then equity. #00:43:42-9#
- 92 Interviewee5: Absolutely ok. #00:43:44-8#
- 93 Interviewer: Ok. Then to the next topic factoring. There are also factoring platforms. You can register, upload accounts receivable, and then either sell it through an auction or the platform refinance it by itself. You said you have used factoring once. Would that be an alternative for you or under what circumstances would you use it? #00:44:13-5#
- 94 Interviewee5: In our process of accounts receivable, in claims where we cannot get ahead. It is still an alternative. But it is much more like the other topics, we are at the end of our competence and our process and then somebody gives us something that is very valuable to us, factoring plays a role. So, we have 85% of our customers as discount payers. So that is why it is different with us. But you can change that. You could also achieve something completely different. I save my internal departments and it is important for me that I receive the money quickly. The whole process is straightforward, factoring already plays a role. Whether that runs on platforms, as you just said. Not really because then I would just look for someone who handles the process for me. When could that be an issue for me? Maybe with a high account receivable where we cannot get further. And in other cases, if we have a 30 million

	account receivable, I would not take the risk because the risk is too high for me. #00:45:42-0#
95	Interviewer: Ok, I understood. So, if you would use factoring, then you would do it by a framework contract which takes over the whole process and then you have no more procedural effort. This is then automatically transferred. You get your money within a few days. 70% of it or whatever. And then you have nothing more to do with it. #00:46:03-9#
96	Interviewee5: That is how it was in the past when we used factoring. #00:46:07-5#
97	Interviewer: And otherwise such a platform only if a relatively high sum that you cannot pass on through a framework contract and you want the money for it, then you would try it on such a platform. #00:46:21-9#
98	Interviewee5: Exactly. #00:46:23-0#
99	Interviewer: Ok. Then we will come to the end. Is there any topic or question that I did not ask but you expected? #00:46:38-3#
100	Interviewee5: So, there is no. For a very simple reason because I had no expectations. It would be interesting, out from this conversation, another question. Which questions are offered as such due to our conversation in the current situation? And on the models, you have been talking about, I do not even go from the financing side, but I am going from the investor side. So, people have money. And at the moment they can think about it, they buy cars, watches, land. So, I am going from the other side now. That is what we just did not discuss. To what extent would be a platform for us with the cash we have and with the know-how that we have, for example, if there were platforms that finance young companies in our area, then that would be very interesting for us. If we notice we have 5 million for investments in potential affiliates. Then, for God's sake, we do not want any subsidiaries, but we want to be in contact with young people entering the industry. Now I come from what you have said before, in this dreg, which we do not perceive. How can we get to such people? Then that would be very interesting for us. Because we can come to other ideas and innovation with relatively manageable resources. This is a different direction now and so the conversation was not established. But that would actually be interesting to us, as we come up with manageable resources in technologies and people and contacts that we would not find so easily. And if there were such a thing, so there would be start-ups in the X sector or in Y or with Z, then it will be interesting for us. #00:49:08-0#

Transcript: Interview 6

1	Interviewer: First of all, I would like to repeat some information about your company and your role. I have informed myself in advance and if you want to complete or correct, you can do that. So, you build X. The company was founded in XX and has existed for six generations. You have three managing directors who are also shareholders. You are one managing director. The company has 1,600 employees. Make about a turnover of 160 million euros and has about 1,500 plants annually which you produce. #00:01:10-1#
2	Interviewee6: Correct. There are a few updates. We are four owners, managing director meanwhile. The sixth generation is correct. This is me. Annual production is 1,600 plants, employees are 1,800. Turnover is more towards 180 million. We have to update that on the homepage. But I think it has no meaning for you now. #00:01:44-1#
3	Interviewer: Ok. Maybe another question about the equity ratio. How is that about? #00:01:50-8#
4	Interviewee6: When you see it, we advertise with zero bank debt. So that is 100 percent. #00:02:00-7#
5	Interviewer: Alright at 100 percent. Then I would go directly to the next question. Among the financial instruments you currently use. I have read that you have no bank loan at the moment. But perhaps you have other financing instruments such as mezzanine which is recognized as equity or factoring or even leasing? #00:02:26-5#
6	Interviewee6: That is why it will be a very slim phone call for you. No. No. No. So, the only thing you could think of as bank credit is contract performance guarantees which we issue under our contracts and then bring back. #00:02:41-2#
7	Interviewer: Ok. But everything else 100 percent financed internally? #00:02:48-0#
8	Interviewee6: Yes. #00:02:49-9#
9	Interviewer: Ok. If you were going to make an investment and you would need some funding that you could not cover with internal funds, would you have a certain preference which financing instruments you would then use? #00:03:12-9#
10	Interviewee6: Yes, then we would take a classic loan at our house bank. Why? If you want to know reasons. We advertise our brand for just these zero bank liabilities, so that we can act completely independently entrepreneurial. That is why we would not publicly seek platforms for funding. #00:03:39-2#
11	Interviewer: Ok. But you would then prefer a bank loan as a first step. For example, mezzanine instruments would you consider as a second stage? #00:03:53-6#
12	Interviewee6: Correct. We would deal with that, if only then more details are needed. #00:03:58-8#
13	Interviewer: And because you already said about bank relationship. So, you have one or more banking relationships? #00:04:06-5#
14	Interviewee6: Exactly. We have house banks. But from the point of view that we have our liquid funds there and work together with them on this topic. #00:04:19-3#
15	Interviewer: What advantages do you see of a house bank relationship? #00:04:25-7#

16	Interviewee6: We have long-standing relationships. Background is the reliability that results from it. You have a contact person and know each other. #00:04:42-4#
17	Interviewer: Ok. #00:04:47-3#
18	Interviewee6: And the house bank is normally available tomorrow. I do not know that from the platforms. #00:04:54-0#
19	Interviewer: Ok. Because you meant reliability. You have never had a loan so far, as I understand you. Or have you had a short-term loan in the past? #00:05:09-3#
20	Interviewee6: In my knowledge not. But I cannot exclude that we may have taken a loan in the context of real estate purchases. Because it makes sense from an entrepreneurial point of view. Actually no. All construction projects known to me come completely from internal financing. #00:05:32-8#
21	Interviewer: Ok. And because of reliability. Maybe you can describe it a little more precisely? #00:05:38-8#
22	Interviewee6: Well, reliability I called it. I understand that in the traditional sense. I have a contact person, I can judge that. I know the person will do what they tell me. Simply because the person is also interested in a long-term partnership. #00:05:59-7#
23	Interviewer: Ok. I mean only in that respect because you did not need credit so far. Often it is also like having a house bank, that one says, ok, if the business is getting worse, then maybe you need a loan. It is often the case that the banks go back and say it is too risky for them. And in that sense, you could also interpret reliability as meaning that when it matters and you need a loan, the bank will be there too. #00:06:32-2#
24	Interviewee6: That is also a point. I have looked at your questions in advance which also speaks for me as a house bank as sparring partner. That when I present a project, the partner bindingly says we are going with you or not and gives feedback that this is a meaningful project. #00:06:56-8#
25	Interviewer: So, you mean the bank's expertise that they are watching it, whether it is profitable or not. #00:07:04-9#
26	Interviewee6: I could imagine that. #00:07:09-5#
27	Interviewer: Do you also see any disadvantages in a house bank relationship? #00:07:14-9#
28	Interviewee6: I have some points listed for you regarding crowdlending. I could imagine, as I said before, that there is some form of crowd intelligence in terms of investment. So that companies that are not specialists in a traditional sector like us, young companies, perhaps they find their partners while a house bank traditionally says, because maybe they are not directly familiar with the new technologies, no we do not. #00:07:52-7#
29	Interviewer: Ok. Before we turn to the topics crowdlending and crowdinvesting: Maybe again very briefly to the house bank relationship. Do you think physical appointments with the bank that e.g. the adviser comes to your place, as negative? #00:08:09-1#
30	Interviewee6: No. I see that as relationship maintenance. #00:08:17-1#
31	Interviewer: Then I would just talk about crowdfunding, crowdinvesting and crowdlending. So, I looked at all the platforms that offer crowdlending and

crowdfunding for mid-sized companies. Crowdfunding is an umbrella term, i.e., just that I collect money from many investors and then use it for a specific project. There are two different categories. Once with financial return and once without financial return. That without financial return is donation-based or you get another kind of return. And with financial return for the investors is crowdlending and crowdfunding. Crowdlending is that you create a funding as a company. Upload the funding to the platform and there you will find investors who then give some kind of loan. You have a fixed interest and a fixed term. In crowdfunding, it is not a loan in that sense but it is mezzanine capital, where then the investors are partly participated in the turnover, profits or in the company value increase. There are also different matching mechanisms. So, in crowdlending, there are three different matching mechanisms as investors come together with the SME. The first option is to create a funding as a company, upload it and then the platform looks at the funding, does a risk assessment, defines an interest rate and then you can find investors who then invest within a certain time. The second option is to upload the funding and the interest rate will be fixed by an auction. And the third option is, the funding gets uploaded, the platform decides directly whether or not it finances the project and also at a certain interest rate because the platform has a contract with professional investors and then you would put the funding on the platform and if there were not enough investors then that would be covered by the professional investors. That is how rough the three matching mechanisms are. The interest rate currently amounts between 2.5 and 16.6 percent for the crowdlending platforms. And are currently demanding personal guarantee. These are of course topics that are more focused on smaller medium-sized companies. And that is why it is interesting for me just like it is for larger medium-sized companies. Because the limit is also at all at 2.5 million euros per funding. So, you can upload multiple fundings but the single funding is limited to 2.5 million. Now my question would be. We just said that you would prefer the internal financing. Let us say the internal financing is not enough and you would need additional funds. Under what circumstances would you apply for a loan through a crowdlending platform? #00:11:55-7#

- 32 Interviewee6: If you want to get an insight into large medium-sized companies, family-run companies, then the answer is, then everything else would have gone down the drain. Then our core strategy would have gone awry if I resorted to these means. And if you say the limit is 2.5 million per project, if I understand you correctly, you have to imagine as a large medium-sized company, I spent this in the morning for machines of the training workshop. By that I mean, so that you would not be able to act we would have to finance ourselves in this way from our point of view. #00:12:39-6#
- 33 Interviewer: So, you would definitely try it in advance at a bank, even if the interest rate would be lower over the funding than at a bank. Would you perhaps, so you can create a funding, you can also create multiple fundings, then you would perhaps still try on such a platform? #00:13:03-5#
- 34 Interviewee6: The answer is no. I would damage the core content of our brand. #00:13:07-7#
- 35 Interviewer: Ok. Regarding the image because the crowd and investors would see that your business needs money through such a platform, and you would see that as a loss of image. #00:13:26-3#
- 36 Interviewee6: We would record that because we have always stood for different values and for reliability. We are active in the construction industry. There are many that exist today but they will not exist tomorrow. Our brand core is a completely

	different one. It is precisely that we are very successful in the market since XX and that would be a huge burden. #00:13:52-9#
37	Interviewer: Ok. I understand it. A key point you have concerns about it is that you think they will come and go again, relatively quick because it is a dynamic environment. Would you also consider it negative that they are less regulated than a bank? #00:14:13-7#
38	Interviewee6: If so, yes. Then there would be another point for us. We are, compliance is sure to tell you something. We handle it here very strictly. So, I would not know 100% about our partners. Well, there are problems with banks too. That would, of course, also be a point to be able to assess the partner correctly. #00:14:39-1#
39	Interviewer: So, they are already less regulated. That is the way it is, ultimately, at the crowdlending platform, the loan is also provided by a bank because to lend a loan in Germany, you need a banking license. And it would indeed be the case that the platform collects the money from the investors and provide it to a bank. The bank provides the loan and the bank resells that as partial claims to the investors. But otherwise it is not regulated further. There is no banking license and all the regulations like Basel 3 etc. are not available otherwise. And so, it is just less regulated. Maybe if I can ask another question. If you have any concerns about the risk of copying an idea. Because the funding will be uploaded. It depends, of course, on what kind of funding you have. But if you were sceptical about it first. #00:15:39-5#
40	Interviewee6: Of course, yes. In the field of innovations this is a very close market for us. And we have already been copied, of course. #00:15:55-5#
41	Interviewer: Ok. You can see that the other way around too. You upload the funding and it is a kind of marketing effect. #00:16:09-2#
42	Interviewee6: I understand, yes. #00:16:11-7#
43	Interviewer: As I understand it, you would not see it as a marketing effect, but a) you have the risk of having a negative image to the outside since I have to ask for funding and b) you see the risk of idea copy. #00:16:26-2#
44	Interviewee6: Exactly. And to understand it correctly. This is my personal view as a business entrepreneur of just this company. So, if I would have a start-up and would have to market the ideas I would, of course, see it differently. #00:16:42-6#
45	Interviewer: Ok. I think then, if we go one step further. So, from crowdlending to crowdinvesting, where even mezzanine capital is used. That is a number sharper again. I think here you would be even more critical of the whole thing? #00:17:11-8#
46	Interviewee6: There are additional points to me, as I understand it. Based on your documents, as I said I have dealt with it. I do not know who as a silent partner also join me. So, for me that would be a step in a direction that does not suit us. #00:17:28-9#
47	Interviewer: So, it is like that. They have no voting right. It is mezzanine capital. Mezzanine capital is between equity and debt. But they have no voting rights and also have no direct participation in the profit or turnover, but there is an additional interest rate which is then capped usually when the turnover, for example, has reached a certain point. Then the investor gets again a certain additional interest

	which is also capped. But then I understood that so far. Maybe you have had some touching points with factoring yet? #00:18:34-1#
48	Interviewee6: Well, I am a lawyer and factoring is a concept I know. We have had considered once or was part of our considerations. We solve it differently. Very successful. We have various accounting and lawyers in-house and they are specialists and pursue our accounts receivable. Therefore, there is currently no reason for us to sell. #00:18:58-9#
49	Interviewer: Ok. There are factoring platforms. There you can upload individual accounts receivable and they can then either be auctioned or the platform finances that directly themselves. But then I would assume that this would be out of the question for you. #00:19:21-0#
50	Interviewee6: No, that would be the case described earlier. Then our liquidity cover would have to be so low that we worry about such things. Then we would have completely different problems. #00:19:37-0#
51	Interviewer: And if you would try factoring. If you say you want to do factoring, then you would rather do it via such a traditional factoring provider as e.g. a bank or would you be more open to a platform if it was not public? #00:19:57-2#
52	Interviewee6: Feeling that, of course, traditional factoring, I have to take a closer look at what is going on there. What would be the commercial conditions on the platform? #00:20:19-4#
53	Interviewer: So, you would fix it on the terms? #00:20:26-0#
54	Interviewee6: If the partner is reliable and assured and if confidentiality is ensured then I would think about it. #00:20:42-4#
55	Interviewer: Yeah, as you said, it is going to be a relatively short interview because you are 100 percent self-financing. I am almost finished with my questions. My final question is, have you expected a question in this context which I did not ask? #00:21:06-0#
56	Interviewee6: If you ask me, no. So, I understood what the shape of your investigation is and that you cover up with your questions. My question to you would be, what about the other large medium-sized companies? Have you already dealt with it? #00:21:29-6#
57	Interviewer: Yes, so you are now the sixth interview I had. It is different. I have not analysed it yet because you first collect the data and then you have to transcribe it and then you go deep into the analysis. But it is different from what I have heard about so far. But many companies tend to be like you. So, you are already quite far, I say, that you would not try it. Then there are some who are a bit more open and would try it. And then there are some that are really very open. But these are companies, such as a company that has gone public and they are pretty much Industry 4.0 and they are very technologized and they would already see that as quite positive and also as a positive image. They consider that as an equity story and also to customers, etc. would see that positive and use that as well. Of course, only if the conditions are equal. But many companies out of the six were not likely to be so. But I conduct the interviews and apply the model of Christensen. This is a strategic model disruptive innovation. Maybe you know that? #00:23:21-8#
58	Interviewee6: No, I do not know. #00:23:21-8#

59	Interviewer: That is a Harvard professor. And he is saying that such a disruptive innovation takes place when new players come in and first serve a customer segment that is not attractive to the main players, i.e., the established companies. And the established companies ignore them and then the business model of the new players develops relatively quick. They optimize the business model and then pull off main customers. And when that happens, it is often too late for established companies to act in time. This platform, as I have already told you with the limitation of 2.5 million, then the conditions and also the personal guarantee, these are of course all topics that are not attractive for large SMEs. Rather so for small businesses, where to say that just get no loan at the bank or only by very high interest rates. And now it is just the question if they would change a few things. And as you also said would not come and go right away but really establish, then maybe it would be the case of disruptive innovation. #00:24:57-3#
60	Interviewee6: Yes. Exciting thing. My first feeling, if you want to know, it depends on the size of the company, at least in the first step and also on the industry. #00:25:08-4#
61	Interviewer: Yes. I think so too. #00:25:08-4#
62	Interviewee6: But we would like to call again in ten years. I am curious. #00:25:15-2#
63	Interviewer: Yes. I am curious too. I have scheduled more interviews. I am also curious what is coming out. But what a point is, quite a lot of financing is through internal financing. As long as this is preferred, other instruments are not interesting. #00:25:35-8#
64	Interviewee6: Yes. Correctly. That is right. Then I wish you a lot of success. Thank you very much for the interesting phone call. #00:26:24-7#
65	Interviewer: Wonderful. Thank you for taking the time. Thank you. #00:26:30-1#

Transcript: Interview 7

1	Interviewer: Maybe I will say something in advance about myself and my background. I gained professional experience after completing my studies. I was at HVB for several years. Among others in inhouse consulting as senior consulting. The whole thing for five years. Afterwards I went to Marc'o Polo in Stephanskirchen where I reported to the CFO and was responsible for the project management office there. Have already started a dissertation parallel. The dissertation is a PhD and takes place in Scotland as well as in Hamburg. #00:00:48-3#
2	Interviewee7: Very nice. And at which university in Scotland? #00:00:49-0#
3	Interviewer: At the University of the West of Scotland, Glasgow. #00:00:54-2#
4	Interviewee7: In Glasgow. I was in Scotland this summer. That is very nice, the university in Glasgow. We looked there around. Exactly. An old wall. #00:01:02-7#
5	Interviewer: Yes, exactly. There are a few more universities, but yes, there it is very nice. #00:01:08-8#
6	Interviewee7: We have already considered whether to send our son there to study. He thought it was ok too. #00:01:12-9#
7	Interviewer: Scotland is also very nice. Of course, the weather is sometimes a bit. #00:01:21-7#
8	Interviewee7: We were lucky. Two weeks of nice weather. #00:01:22-2#
9	Interviewer: Yes, I think so too. Very pleasant. Now I am investigating how FinTechs are influencing traditional SME banking and how they are a threat to traditional banking. And for this I have taken different steps. The first step is, I have looked at all financing FinTechs. I did a qualitative content analysis to understand how the business model works. The second step is, I conduct interviews with CFOs of medium-sized companies. The third step is. There is this model by Christensen a Harvard professor. The Disruptive Innovation Model. This is such a strategic model that says how new and younger companies entering such a market are first serving a niche but then replacing established players as well. There are different criteria for how to do that. And that is what I would like to say about how this has a strategic impact. These are my steps. I have prepared a questionnaire. I would just go through that if that is okay with you. #00:02:49-5#
10	Interviewee7: Gladly. Only one question in advance. How did you find us? #00:02:50-4#
11	Interviewer: I have searched for different companies through different websites. Once on different job portals. And I think that is what I came up with. I have to say honestly that I did not know you before. #00:03:15-1#
12	Interviewee7: That does not surprise me. We only provide X. That means we only have one B-to-B business and no B-to-C business. That means we are relatively unknown. #00:03:28-7#
13	Interviewer: I think I came to you through a job portal. Of course, I looked at the website. Looked at how big your company is, how many employees you have and in which industry you are. Yes, and that fits into my examination very well. And then I wrote to you. I also appreciate that you take the time. #00:03:45-1#
14	Interviewee7: With pleasure, gladly. Then shoot off. #00:03:48-3#

15	Interviewer: Exactly. Maybe shortly to your company. What you offer I understood so far. Maybe again very briefly to the key figures. So, in terms of turnover you have about 90 million and in terms of employees you have about 130. And in 2007 you were founded and you are a managing director for financing and commercial topics. #00:04:18-3#
16	Interviewee7: We were founded in 2007 but we existed before. Since we were part of the Y. But then, due to legal requirements, we had to outsource our business area there and pack it into our own company. The business is much longer, what we do here. But us as X has been existed for eleven years. #00:04:43-4#
17	Interviewer: Ok. Then I would go directly into the technical questions. My first question would be what financing instruments do you currently use. #00:04:56-0#
18	Interviewee7: We are totally bored. We have classic bank loans. In some cases, simply just individual loans with individual banks and a syndicated loan were taken up in 2016 two years ago to finance larger projects. We do nothing else. Just classic bank loans. #00:05:16-3#
19	Interviewer: Ok. Classic bank loans. Then I also think internal financing. So, you try as far as possible to finance your business. #00:05:25-0#
20	Interviewee7: Sure, what we can invest ourselves or what we can invest from our cash flow. Of course, we do that as far as possible. We still have a loan from our mother of Y. That is what I believe 12 million, if I have it right in my head. I just do not know exactly. For liquidity protection. #00:05:52-5#
21	Interviewer: Do you use factoring? #00:05:54-3#
22	Interviewee7: No, it does not matter to us at all. We have a relatively small customer base. This is not a mass business we do. So, what we market are X. Someone gets the right to use Y, so to speak. Whether he does that or not we do not care. He just pays. These are wholesalers. These are not private customers, so we have only a small circle of customers and the billing process runs smoothly with us. Factoring does not matter at all. So, it does not interest us. #00:06:26-0#
23	Interviewer: Ok. Then I saw that you carried out a capital increase. #00:06:30-3#
24	Interviewee7: Exactly. #00:06:32-3#
25	Interviewer: What was the cause? Or how did that happen? #00:06:36-4#
26	Interviewee7: Historically, we were founded with very little equity. That is because, as I said earlier, we are a spin-off. We already existed. So, our mother Y is the majority shareholder. And that has spun us out and transferred all the property, plant and equipment to us at a book value that was already very much depreciated at the time. As a result, we had very little equity. Now, for the first time in our history, since 2016, we have taken up a major bank loan. And the banks have said that with this equity capitalisation this is too thin for us. You have to go up significantly. And that is why we then made an equity increase in the course. I believe of 138 million and in the course of two new shareholders have joined us. So, two shareholders of Y have participated directly with us. On the one hand the X and on the other hand the Z. Ultimately, it was about bringing our equity ratio to a reasonable level. So, the banks that provided us with a syndicated loan allow us to sleep well. #00:07:43-1#
27	Interviewer: Ok. I understand. The equity ratio is currently approximate, I have looked at the balance sheet, at 55%. #00:07:50-2#

28	Interviewee7: Yes, that should be about. However, we have not yet fully called the syndicated loan. So, it will go down a bit but not dramatically anymore. #00:08:01-7#
29	Interviewer: Ok, I understood that. You have carried out the capital increase to increase the equity ratio to receive external debt ... #00:08:16-9#
30	Interviewee7: Before, we had an equity ratio of about 10%. Is not critical in our industry. But for the banks, for the internal processes required that we get the credit approval. #00:08:25-5#
31	Interviewer: Ok. And if you need financing for an investment. What kind of funding would you prefer first? #00:08:34-0#
32	Interviewee7: Bank. Very classic. We are extremely conservative. We know banks. I have to explain to you how our business model actually works. So, we are one hundred percent regulated. That means the following. The X, which is our regulator, tells us every year how much revenue we can generate. Exactly this amount is also achieved through sales. In other words, we are doing our capacity. When we calculate the unit price per unit, we say ok what is the X to us what we are allowed to achieve in revenue, divide this by the expected market capacities. That is how I get the unit price. With that I start the business year, so to speak. At the end of the financial year, I calculate and see if it has fit. Of course, a forecast is always wrong. So, either I have got too much. Then I have to give back what I have overpaid in the next year to the customers. If I did not earn enough, then over the next few years, I will get a mark from my clients that will give me exactly the amount I can get. This amount, which is determined, which I may achieve, determines the X and just looks what costs we have. What operating costs. The operating costs you deserve. Operating costs include financing costs. That means the financing costs I get over the market over and over again. Actually, I do not have to intensify my search for the cheapest financial instrument because I say no matter how I finance myself. Of course, I am not allowed to do any fancy stuff that would be incredibly expensive because at some point the X says that is uneconomical what you do. That cannot be at the expense of your customers. But as long as I am in a normal range and a classic bank financing instrument is of course unassailable. I stop the competition and see what conditions I get. So long, I have no incentive to finance as cheaply as possible because that does not improve the result for me as a company. So, if I finance myself very well, my sales revenues would be correspondingly lower than they admit. That is our weird system. #00:10:41-5#
33	Interviewer: Ok. But then I understood it that way. You make a certain turnover. The profit is given. #00:10:51-5#
34	Interviewee7: Not the profit, the turnover is given. #00:10:53-3#
35	Interviewer: The turnover is given. #00:10:55-5#
36	Interviewee7: Yes. #00:10:56-4#
37	Interviewer: This results in the fixed price for the customers. I wonder if you might prefer the internal financing over the external. What does that mean? Because you first start with internal financing and then you access the loans. #00:11:26-6#
38	Interviewee7: Yeah, yes. The internal financing costs me nothing. For this I do not get anything from X, I do not get it refunded. And external financing I get 1:1 over the external proceeds refunded. A small restriction. Quite simply, the world is not. But you are not a professional in this topic. There is still the so-called efficiency value. The X keeps looking at how efficient the network operators are. Efficiency is always the

question of input output. Input is practically the cost that I have, where also the financing costs are relevant. Output is quite strange things; I do not need to explain. Are so specific and completely wrong in my opinion but that make the X. And then we are compared with other so-called Y operators. There are Y of them in Germany. This is our market we are compared to. And if we say, the ratio cost is equal to input to output, these are four different parameters and then the best is chosen which gets 100 percent. And the others, who are worse off in comparison, then have a lower efficiency value and we are then intensified to reduce these inefficiencies over a regulatory period of five years. The revenues we get are then slowly melting away around these inefficiencies. So, to speak, I already indirectly have a lever, where I say, since then financing costs may be relevant. However, financing costs are more of a marginal factor in our overall business. So, I do not win a flowerpot. But there would be at least a starting point for optimising the financing costs. #00:13:13-3#

39 Interviewer: Then to my next question. You also said that you have bank loans. Do you have one or more longer bank relationships? #00:13:23-9#

40 Interviewee7: Yes. For historical reasons, we have had relatively long banking relationship with Bayerische Landesbank. They took over a lot in our spin-off. Some of them are already finished, some of them are still running for a few years. We already stopped; how should I say. Since our foundation, Bayerische Landesbank has always been our financing bank. For the first time through the syndicated loan from 2016, we have expanded the banking sector a bit. You can still see how it goes on with the banks. I believe we have completed a 15-year financing there. We will definitely stay in business with the banks for 15 years. That is certainly true. #00:14:06-9#

41 Interviewer: And do you see any advantages through a house bank relationship? #00:14:10-2#

42 Interviewee7: It makes some things easier. Especially in our business. Because our business is so special. Such a classical approach like revenue, expenses, profit does not work so easy with us. Each bank must first understand our business model. They also need to know where the risks are with us. And the risks are almost zero with us. That is why I am not keen on getting new banks on board because I always have to tell the same story to explain how our business model actually works. Of course, that makes things easier when I say that the bank just got it. The employee understands it easily and can assess the case correctly. #00:14:45-6#

43 Interviewer: Ok. You also think that it is actually associated with no risk. Do you still feel that the availability of a house bank is higher? #00:15:00-2#

44 Interviewee7: Availability for what? #00:15:00-2#

45 Interviewer: The availability e.g. for a loan? #00:15:01-2#

46 Interviewee7: To be honest, from the point of view of the bank, I cannot comment on this because we have never had the problem. You have never tried it. So, when we look for loans, back in syndicated loan, we realised that the banks are running into us because we are a risk-free borrower with a secure return. So, a dream for a bank. Thus, we have no problem finding a bank at any time. #00:15:29-5#

47 Interviewer: Ok, do you see a difference in terms and conditions? #00:15:33-6#

48 Interviewee7: Not that I know now. I am just considering how the process was. I think there was our long-standing bank, the Bayern LB, was not the cheapest. I recently closed an interest rate swap as an interest rate hedge. We always invite the banks to do so. There was the Bayern LB, which is our long-standing house bank, not the

	cheapest bank. Since the others were cheaper. Actually, I do not see such an advantage. #00:16:03-8#
49	Interviewer: Ok. And you may also see any disadvantages? #00:16:06-4#
50	Interviewee7: Honestly, no. I am thinking right now. I would not think of anything spontaneously. No. #00:16:20-3#
51	Interviewer: Maybe disadvantages overall by bank financing? #00:16:23-6#
52	Interviewee7: Well, of course, there are other financial instruments that may be more interesting in economic terms if I purely look at interest margins. From my previous life, I know that, of course, the requirements are different. So, I do not get the better business as a gift, but then I have other requirements to fulfil, where I say well, I do not think so exciting. So now we have only one financial covenant in our loan agreement which is not a problem. It is also clear. The lower the margin, the more pressure I get from my financing provider, whoever that may be. A bank or somebody else. In this sense, it is always an overall balance. Our cost pressure is not so high, I prefer to take the simple, maybe the little bit more expensive bank financing. But I have a simpler system for that. #00:17:11-0#
53	Interviewer: What alternatives would you have considered? #00:17:16-8#
54	Interviewee7: What was the order of magnitude, that was a 150 million loan at that time if I have it right in my head. A debenture bond also considered in terms of the size. That would have been the biggest thing. I would not do a corporate bond. That would have been too much effort for me again. So only a syndicated loan and, if necessary, a promissory note loan. The only thing you could think of, and still make a classic loan but to take a different kind of financing provider. Not a bank, but an institutional investor. Our industry in particular, i.e. infrastructure in the broadest sense, is very popular with institutional investors. So, say the big insurance companies, pension funds, pension insurance or the like. Since you would certainly get attractive offers of those. Maybe more attractive than the banks do. But we have not tried it yet. #00:18:12-8#
55	Interviewer: There you think the covenants are stricter than ... #00:18:19-4#
56	Interviewee7: Yes, I would guess. #00:18:19-4#
57	Interviewer: Then my next question would be, do you know about crowdlending and crowdinvesting or crowdfunding in general? #00:18:29-6#
58	Interviewee7: From the newspaper, yes. Exactly what one reads from time to time. #00:18:34-3#
59	Interviewer: Then I would just say a few words if that is okay for you. #00:18:38-8#
60	Interviewee7: Yeah, that is nice. #00:18:38-7#
61	Interviewer: So, crowdfunding is an umbrella term. And crowdfunding can also be split into where the investors get a return and once where they get no return. Where they do not get a return is donation based, so donation based or where they get another thing in return. That they are the first to buy the product or get the product or a service out of the company. And then there is crowdfunding with financial return. The investors get a return and this can be subdivided into crowdlending and crowdinvesting. Crowdlending is where a company or privately can create a funding for a project where it needs money. Then upload it to a platform and find investors there. They then give the money with a fixed interest rate and a fixed term. So, it is a

bit like a bank loan with fixed interest and fixed maturity. In crowdfunding, these are mezzanine instruments. There is also a fixed interest rate agreed and yet an additional interest which is linked to how the revenue develops and the profit develops or a company value participation. So much for that. Now I just ask you openly, even if you do not have much experience or no experience with it. Suppose you want to invest; under what circumstances would you apply for such a crowdlending platform? #00:20:23-1#

62 Interviewee7: No realistic. My perception is that crowdfunding is currently being used by start-ups in particular which may have problems getting a classic bank loan on attractive terms. Because banks are simply struggling due to the risk structure at start-ups. It is clear. That is their business model. Then there are the other financiers who jump around and say I finance ten and hope that one of those becomes a success. Maybe you do not like it or you will not have access there either. So, for me, this crowdfunding always seems to be a solution for those that have no alternatives. That is my perception of newspapers. I do not know more. After it is not an issue at all with us. So, the banks overrun us. They call me regularly and ask, if you need more money. That is why I have never dealt with it, and I cannot imagine that it really matters to us in the future. #00:21:17-6#

63 Interviewer: Ok. And you have the impression mainly through the press. #00:21:22-0#

64 Interviewee7: So, I do not know anybody who did crowdfunding in practice. It is not like I am running around asking. But it never happened to run into anybody. #00:21:31-8#

65 Interviewer: Right now, the interest rates are very low. The banks must also pay penalty interest. Let us say if the whole thing gets more difficult. So, if you had problems with the bank, would you think about doing something like that through a crowdlending platform? #00:21:56-4#

66 Interviewee7: Yes, exactly. I will always get money from the bank. It is always a question of price. Because of the system, the price is not that insanely important. That is just such a stupid system. That is why I would hardly think. I am not so sure; I have never tried it if the conditions are really better with crowdlending. These are always some who say I give away my money for a certain risk and the return I get for it should also be somehow risk-adequate. That I now have any people who find it fancy because then you get the product is not an option with us. So, I am not an Apple or comparable. I have totally boring products that are completely irrelevant to consumers. Can anyone actually lend me a money that says I am doing business with it. This is a business model for me. So, he has to make a risk assessment. And then I do not know if the then, no matter how the banking market develops, as economically would be more attractive than the bank. #00:22:49-0#

67 Interviewer: Yes, that is the condition right now. I have checked all financing FinTechs. The conditions are just, when you compare it with the conditions of medium-sized companies what they get from the bank, the terms are already higher. I have looked at all of them and the current interest rates published there for crowdlending vary between 2.5% and 16.6%. But that is the current state. I do not want to be too focused on that. That is, I say, more in the early stages and that can still develop. That is why I would be interested, let us say, assuming the interest rates are the same. So, if you would get a loan on a crowdlending platform and the interest rate is the same as a bank loan, I am assuming that you would not do it. #00:23:50-3#

68	Interviewee7: No, because the banking processes I have just integrated in the house. We know how that works. We know what reporting we have. We know which financial indicators the banks want to see. That is all established. In crowdlending I first have to understand what they need. It may be necessary to establish new processes here in our house, where I say, I would, if only then, if I had a substantial economic advantage on the other side. Only then I would think about it. If it is a zero sum, economically speaking, I do not see any need. #00:24:18-0#
69	Interviewer: I mean, you do not have meetings there. It is not like you have physical meetings. It is handled purely online. That could be an advantage. #00:24:30-7#
70	Interviewee7: Yeah, but then I have to send something too. With us in the normal credit relationship, it is not always the case that one constantly meets physically. We just have our reporting obligations. The reports are previously agreed with the banks. These are the standard things. They get them sent and then maybe call them again if they did not understand something. Then it has usually done already. It becomes critical when I get a problem as a borrower and say, yes, the interest rates are a bit high, I cannot get it. And then of course I need a physical meeting and of course I do not want to exchange emails with anyone. I want that sitting at my table and looks me in the eye and says I have a problem that we must now discuss. So, there is a bank employee who knows me a bit longer and says ok, I know the company. For 10, 15 years I accompanied this. I can estimate approximately. No problem, we can stretch that. This helps longer business relationships. The anonymity of crowdlending is a bit more difficult. #00:25:26-1#
71	Interviewer: And even if the interest rate is not so crucial in the business model. Let us say the interest rate would actually be lower on such a crowdlending platform. Would you possibly consider that? #00:25:40-3#
72	Interviewee7: Yes, then I would think about everything, sure. You just have to do an analysis again. In other words, what is extra work for me compared to the current system. What do I gain economically for this? That is just a trade-off. Does that make sense to me? Yes or no. Then I would also think wider. Then I would not only consider classic corporate finance but also corporate bonds, promissory notes, other investor circles. So as already mentioned, I would then appeal to other investors. I have huge platforms. Since I can then look at everything and see who offers the economically most attractive offer for me. #00:26:14-1#
73	Interviewer: On the platforms, it is so that it is published and then many investors see it. You do not have a B-to-C business now. A B-to-B and it is less published at press. It may be more for other companies but it is a marketing effect. At least it could be. It is even more public. Would you rate that as positive? #00:26:40-5#
74	Interviewee7: That is completely irrelevant in our business. We are a monopolist. We do not have to advertise. Who wants to have service X? He has no alternatives. And so, advertising brings me nothing at the point. #00:26:56-6#
75	Interviewer: It would work like that. Ultimately, who wants to provide a loan in Germany needs a banking license. The platform collects the money from the investors. The platform gives the money to a bank, the bank provides the loan and again resells that in partial claims to the investors. But otherwise it is not regulated anymore. Banks have, may you know, for example Basel 3. There are many regulations that banks have to comply with. Would you see it negatively that it is less regulated or would you see it more positively? #00:27:38-2#

76	Interviewee7: I do not really care about that right now. Because I am a borrower. That means the risk that something has happened on the bank side and not on my side. I have the problem with Basel whenever I give my money. If they have my money and I say that I want my money back and say oh I am sorry we do not have that anymore. This is cheered and our bank is broke. That is why it does not really matter on the borrower side. I am just wondering what else would happen in the worst case if it is not regulated. Who is actually my contract partner in the construct? The bank or the investors? #00:28:12-3#
77	Interviewer: Contracting party is the bank. Would have to be the bank. #00:28:23-7#
78	Interviewee7: Because I do not want to have to talk to 15 people, of course. I want a contact person who is my contract partner. #00:28:28-9#
79	Interviewer: Yeah, no, it is the bank. #00:28:37-8#
80	Interviewee7: Then that is actually a pure refinancing model for banks. I have another refinancing opportunity and I am collecting money in the market somewhere. If you say, it will be published on the platform. That means that if I were an investor I would check and say ok, if I provide the company X 100,000 euros and I participate with 100,000 euros, I get the following interest rate. Of the interest rate, but the FinTech has to do a business and the bank has to do business. So, compared to the classic banking business, it has to be more expensive. How else would the bank refinance? Either through their deposits, through their clients' deposits or, more likely, through loans for bank financing or to get money from the ECB. #00:29:32-5#
81	Interviewer: Yes, again. There are different matching mechanisms. So, if you upload the platform, then there is a mechanism where that takes place between the investors through an auction. So, then the interest rate is set. So, everyone offers. A kind of bidding process and if it is enough the best interest rate is set. Then there is the second mechanism. That is that the platform will set an interest rate and then provide that to the investors. And the third mechanism is that the platform directly defines an interest rate and says directly whether they do it or not because they have a contract with institutional investors who provide the money when not enough money from other investors came in. And, it is the platform has its normal fee and the bank wants a fee. #00:30:50-6#
82	Interviewee7: But the question is, who bears the risk of a borrower default on the whole construct? Who stays on the money? Is that the bank, FinTech or the investors? #00:30:58-9#
83	Interviewer: No, the investors. #00:31:00-7#
84	Interviewee7: The investors have the risk. #00:31:02-2#
85	Interviewer: The investors end up with the risk. And that is of course already the case, that then for the investors adequate risk / interest ratio must be available. #00:31:21-1#
86	Interviewee7: How do I assess the risk as a potential investor? #00:31:25-7#
87	Interviewer: I mean, that is difficult, of course. That is why some platforms have changed. So that they set the interest rate and not the investors. Because in the beginning it was more like that. That the investors decided that. But then it often did not seem like the right assessment because investors often did not get their money and then of course it is also a negative image for the platforms. They also want successful fundings. And that is why they publish fundings with a better credit rating

and set the interest rate at the same time. A bank has certain transformation mechanisms but they are no longer there. So, if a bank says it takes the loan on the book, refinances it and provides the loan, it has a kind of risk transformation. And it has a maturity transformation because it refinances at short term and provides long term loans. You do not have that there anymore. The investor is agreed directly with the borrower. Therefore, theoretically, if there was a proper risk calculation, the interest rate could be lower because the bank in between who has that on the book would lose its margin. #00:32:55-6#

88 Interviewee7: Yes, the risk premium. But if I say at the end of the day is the risk with the investors, then I actually have to say as an investor, I would like to have a direct relationship with the borrower. Because if the borrower is really going to go bankrupt, then I want to file my bankruptcy claims and not have to hope somehow that the FinTech or the bank will do it properly. So, I would think as an investor. The FinTech takes a management fee, so has no risk. The bank also takes a fee and has no risk. #00:33:22-5#

89 Interviewer: Exactly. #00:33:26-3#

90 Interviewee7: The FinTechs and the bank certainly need a license, not as a bank, but as a financial services provider. This is a consulting business what they do. Then I get such a thing for so much and so much for the company, then you would have to get the license as a financial service provider? #00:33:41-5#

91 Interviewer: Yes, exactly. In crowdlending definitely. Crowdfunding does not require a license. You do not necessarily need a license as a financial service provider because they seem to mediate directly. As with factoring. They do not need a license either. #00:34:15-6#

92 Interviewee7: Yes, factoring requires a license. If I remember correctly. We had a case like that. I used to be a lawyer, that is why. #00:34:26-8#

93 Interviewer: Well, they definitely do not have a banking license. There are different licenses, they do not necessarily need it. And it is so, the BaFin looked at it and it always depends on the business model. You cannot say that in a general way. #00:34:49-8#

94 Interviewee7: But you see, when I think about it that way, I say as a borrower, I do not care. I receive money from someone and it is his problem to receive it back. I get an interest rate. Either variable or fixed. So, I do not care. But the more I think about it, the more I say, the whole construct behind it is somehow. There are many involved and everyone wants to earn something. There are many contractual relationships. If I want to deal with the fact that I simply understand, who is actually the one who could hurt me, so that I can judge, if I can enter into a business relationship. At a bank, it is relatively simple. There is the bank that I know or do not know. But I just have a very simple 1:1 relationship and the rest is none of my business. So, with the FinTech I would ask if I really want to deal with it, to first understand how it actually works. Then the business would have to be much better than with a bank, that I would do the whole mess then. Just so I understand who is actually interested in the whole game. #00:35:50-9#

95 Interviewer: Ok. I understood that. There are more parties involved and you have to see through it first. You have to understand the business model. There are different stakeholders. There could be different risks at certain corners. #00:36:08-0#

96 Interviewee7: That is right. #00:36:09-5#

97	Interviewer: That was crowdlending now, where there is still a bank involved. There are also crowdinvesting and these are mezzanine instruments and there is no bank involved. Do you see that as farther away, or would you perhaps consider it? #00:36:29-5#
98	Interviewee7: That will be even more difficult to see who is actually in a legal relationship with whom. What is the interest? Who carries what risk? That would be very interesting economically, that I say, I invest the time and the energy to understand this and to make a personal assessment for myself, whether the whole thing is economically worthwhile. Maybe over time, once you have seen that and maybe others are reporting it. But reporting is always very difficult. The one who reported, really understood it? I am always applying the approach, I want to understand it myself before I do something like that. Otherwise I cannot really judge if that makes sense to me or not. #00:37:13-8#
99	Interviewer: Ok. Then I understood that so far. You have carried out the equity increase through your mother company in order to increase your equity. I mean, you can do that through some kind of mezzanine instruments, if it were allocated to equity. Now, if you would say again that you would like to have such a mezzanine instrument, then you would consider other mezzanine instruments through other ways in relation to crowdinvesting. Or would you put the crowdinvesting at first or would you first look at the traditional mezzanine options? #00:38:05-2#
100	Interviewee7: Yes, we have already looked at mezzanine in the course of the last equity increase. But that is relatively difficult for us. Because mezzanine, says the X, we as a company cannot optimize ourselves at that side. This does not work for us out of regulatory reasons. If we make a capital increase, it will be a classic equity increase. Anything else does not work for us. But this is a special case with the regulation. I have no advantage in that. #00:38:33-6#
101	Interviewer: Ok. I understood that. You do not have factoring. #00:38:41-0#
102	Interviewee7: No, that does not matter to us. Totally uninteresting for us. #00:38:42-9#
103	Interviewer: Maybe I will just tell you something about it. There are factoring platforms. There you can register and upload accounts receivable. There are also different mechanisms there. This account receivable could also be auctioned or refinanced directly via the platform. Is more transaction based. This is not like traditional factoring, where you have a framework agreement and then constantly refinance the accounts receivable automatically. But that is more individual. There are also various options for factoring. For example, factoring with recourse or non-recourse, and notification or non-notification factoring. And there are also different variants. There are many different platforms. I think I analysed twelve platforms. They offer different variants. Do you have an opinion about that? #00:39:46-6#
104	Interviewee7: Does not matter to us. It may certainly be interesting for large companies with a lot of customer business, where maybe I have relatively small amounts and say that is a huge effort. But there too, think about the business model. The factoring provider calculates so that it is a relatively reduced risk for him, later makes a discount and then he still has his own administrative burden. Just as an example, if I now take the Y, which are also involved in us, who have a huge mass business. The effort to the customer who does not want to pay is always the same for both. The only advantage an outsider may have is that he says he is not Y. I do not have to pay attention to the customer relationship. He may then be able to fight with

some harder bandages than the Y, who want to have a lasting customer relationship. They might say that we cannot handle that so hard. Maybe that may be a bit of an increase in efficiency. But I do not think so. Because at the end of the day, it falls back to the original contractor. He cannot hide. So, I do not know factoring. I have never experienced that in practice, so I lack the experience of how it is in practice. Does it make sense or does it make economic sense? I would be rather sceptical to be honest. Factoring, because you think as a company then, if I get no more bank financing. Then I start thinking about factoring. No, that is not right. Clear that. There is the modern version, which says, I just do not want to put on the shoe to run bills afterwards. I do not want to build the infrastructure and I am saving the effort and it is worth having somebody else take care of it. #00:41:32-5#

105 Interviewer: I mean, I have already interviewed several companies. Some of them already do factoring. I believe a) it is a cash flow thing in some companies, but in some companies, it is a procedural thing. They say ok we have a lot of small amounts and they often have effort to still get the money, so they just take it off right then and also have no administrative effort. And it is firmly calculable. You always get that amount. #00:42:04-2#

106 Interviewee7: Cash flow is an important aspect. That is true. But is not an issue for us. We are just a monopolist. We also prepare our accounts receivable in advance. We want to have an amount before. As a result, we never had a liquidity issue and if we had one, X is no longer provided. There we sit at the longer lever. He has no alternative. #00:42:21-9#

107 Interviewer: Ok. #00:42:23-4#

108 Interviewee7: That is the advantage of a de facto monopoly. #00:42:26-5#

109 Interviewer: Ok, I understood that. Probably that would not be so attractive, if you look at the whole time from the other side. From the investor side. As I said, it is a two-sided business model. On the one hand the borrowers and on the other hand the lenders. And for some of the companies I have interviewed, I have heard that they find it interesting on the investor side. For example, just to get know-how from smaller, perhaps more innovative companies. Since I do not know now, if this fits into your business model? #00:43:05-0#

110 Interviewee7: Not at all. Since we had to build a business branch and this would probably do my mother company. So, if that would be interesting then they would do it themselves. Then they do not need us for it now. So, no, that is not something we would look at. #00:43:17-7#

111 Interviewer: Ok. Then I would come to my final questions. Is there perhaps something that I may not have asked in this context but what you have expected. #00:43:35-2#

112 Interviewee7: To be honest, I did not think much about it. I thought, I will see what he will ask. No, I cannot think of anything. #00:43:52-9#

113 Interviewer: Or maybe something else? Maybe what you still want to provide me? #00:43:57-9#

114 Interviewee7: FinTech is actually part of this big industry that works with digitisation. This is the case in all company levels, where I always ask myself the question, is it really the case of reality or is it a hype? And so, I always have the impression as an interested newspaper reader, that is my source, because I always have the impression that there is a lot of hype. But if you think about it a bit, I just do not understand it. Where I ask myself, where is the business purpose really? Where does the added

value come from that really justifies such market values? I often get the impression that this is speculation on something. Probably on stock market developments. Not at corporate values. I can also go to the casino in Monte Carlo. That is similar. Such is my subjective impression and I am doubtful even with the FinTechs. I know a FinTech a bit about a friend. And when she talks a bit, I wonder if that will work out well in the long run. Because they get a risk in the house and I am not so sure if they understand the risk so well. And if then sometime like a pyramid the house collapses. Of course, it does not matter to the borrowers. This is more an issue for investors. An investor is an institutional investor. They have to know for themselves what they are doing. I have no sympathy now. Sometimes I am not so sure if that can really work that way. So I have my doubts. #00:45:40-7#

115 Interviewer: Ok. Yes, I mean FinTechs is of course a big topic. There are financing FinTechs but of course there are also payment system FinTechs. There are FinTechs who work on the asset side or insurance. Or as a consulting service provider. That is a big spectrum. I think one or the other business model is associated with more or less risks. But of course, it is a direction in digitisation. Some FinTechs already have, in any case, from my first insides, disruptive potential there. That might already be in danger and some other FinTechs it is more of a hype than really ... #00:46:52-8#

116 Interviewee7: When I look at financing FinTechs and say the competition is the classic banking business I wonder what makes a FinTech better than a bank? As a rule, a bank has been on the road for a few years now and may be specialized. So, I know now that individual consultants are specialized in individual industries. They have developed a certain feeling over the years, such as the individual risks in the individual sectors are to be assessed. I say this is an asset that I have to build up over years. I cannot read that. Since I really have long accompanied an industry and have accompanied individual companies to get a reliable feeling. What banks have certainly is a giant machine, where I can say as FinTech, instead of 100 people, I only need 10. The rest makes a computer or let me completely under the table. Because I say there is some potential savings in it. The question is, is that enough to build a more interesting business model overall? Where I say, I am just slimmer, faster on the go and therefore, can I offer more favourable conditions than a bank? Whether there will be a business case out of it? #00:47:59-6#

117 Interviewer: Yes, for example, a scenario. Imagine. You can quickly and easily create a funding. Then you can upload it to a platform. Investors can be found there very quickly and within five days you will have your money without big bureaucracy and maybe a really good risk assessment with new methods like Big Data, where you consider a lot of different data. #00:48:34-2#

118 Interviewee7: About which size do we speak? #00:48:34-9#

119 Interviewer: You mean the volume? Of the loan volume? So of course, it is currently the case that they are limited. So, it is relatively unattractive for larger mid-sized companies because the limit is 2.5 million. But per funding. You can also upload multiple fundings. But now if you make a turnover of 90 million, you probably have larger volumes when you make major investments. #00:49:07-1#

120 Interviewee7: We need millions. We cannot get very far with 2.5 million. #00:49:12-5#

121 Interviewer: You are not getting very far. The point is you have to otherwise create a prospectus and then it will be costly. And that is why it is currently limited to 2.5 million. And I see that too. There are definitely a few hurdles left. I definitely see that.

Once with the volume, which is limited. The second point is that I have not mentioned yet. It is difficult, especially for larger medium-sized companies, where managers are also employees. Maybe you still have stakes in it. But crowdlending platforms require a personal guarantee. This is not a problem for smaller companies like start-ups. They may be personally liable. They do not want any other collateral. But of course, that is a point, if you want to enter this market. That is difficult. #00:50:23-2#

122 Interviewee7: I would never do that. I would be stupid. #00:50:23-2#

123 Interviewer: And these are two points where I say that are just K.O. criteria. But who knows? Christensen's strategic model is called disruptive innovation. They say that there are well-established players in the market, and then smaller, newer companies come into the market, serving a segment that is not attractive to established companies. And these are the small companies. They have a higher risk. They have a small loan volume. The bank does not earn much from that. They are not that attractive. But if they are then served and then it is like that, then if they improve their business model then relatively quick enter the higher market. In the mainstream market. And then it is often too late for the established players to react. And that is just the question of how this could happen here? To what extent could their business model still change, and then serve a higher segment. #00:51:23-3#

124 Interviewee7: Sure, I can imagine, if I have such a mass business with small businesses, such craftsmen who says 2.5 million is exactly my volume. Then yes, that can be done with my personal liability but I would be careful. And say this is just a mass business. If 10 percent fail but the remaining 90 percent works, the interest rate is accordingly higher. Then that is all in balance. In other words, the business model actually lives off the ground, so I diversify the risk in the crowd. But if I now insist that a few of them actually grow. I cannot assume that one hundred percent is suddenly growing. Then the mass gets less. The individual volumes become larger. In other words, my overall risk as an investor increase. So, if one out of a thousand fails, I say that gets lost in the noise. If one out of ten fails and they are all bigger, then it hurts me accordingly. That corresponds to ten percent. Before that, I had a volume of 1 tenth of a percent, now 1 percent. And then the business model looks very different. Then I can no longer say, I need a personal liability because I know something good for 100,000 euros. Maybe that would be good in private but for 10 million it did not. And I am already wondering how that should work? This is clear when I have a business relationship with and grow with the company because I then finance the larger if that is allowed by the regulator. Or anyway, when the hurdles are all eliminated. Then I ask myself how they act? What is their business model? Whether they say then, we just keep it up or if they then tilt towards the bank and say personal safety is no longer enough. Now somehow, I need assets as security. What is the bank's advantage then? Then it cannot be cheaper because the apparatus is slimmer. I have less administrative costs and that is why I can deduct you 20 basis points from the margin. Ok then I can think it over. Then it becomes very similar to a bank. #00:53:26-1#

125 Interviewer: It is also true that banks can be replaced but not banking, I say. And banking is a model that is likely to remain. The question is, how does it happen? Does that take place in a different way or does it stay more traditional? But also, the banks, I think so, there is also the maturity transformation and risk transformation. So, the bank gets the deposits of different people and can then grant a loan in different volumes and sizes and takes over the risk and the maturity. I can withdraw my money from the bank at any time but they give out a loan for 10 years. And that already has a reasoning of existence, otherwise one would say, ok, if the financial markets do not

work directly with each other, then a bank comes and that is why a bank was originally founded. And now I am investigating whether the whole thing is almost reversed. But, of course, it is questionable because it already has its right to exist. #00:54:50-8#

126 Interviewee7: Yes. A bank exists and that has reasons. One did not invent that because one did not think of anything and was boring but they already have a function to and to keep the risks under control. Sometimes more, sometimes less successful. #00:55:07-7#

127 Interviewer: Very good, then we are already at the end. #00:55:12-9#

128 Interviewee7: Great, then we are curious what comes out of it. #00:55:20-7#

Transcript: Interview 8

- 1 Interviewee8: I am CFO of X, I am 48, I am also from the area of Munich. So, I also have a long Munich history. First, after my vocational training, I studied at Y. Also worked the first 15 years of my career at Y in pretty much all financing areas and in corporate M&A. Then I switched to Z in 2007. Was then for Z two years in China. There as CFO. And I was back from China in 2010 and then I had the task of selling a division of Z to an American private equity firm. I also took the chance to go with the deal and since 2013 I have been working as CFO in the private equity investment company. Especially now here at X. I have been working here as CFO for three years now, and the focus here is clearly on leading the classic traditional family business into the capital markets, and at different levels I say private equity funding. At the same time also an exciting story because here in the three years we have made 10 additional acquisitions in order to continue to grow inorganically with different forms of financing. So, from this side also a really exciting environment. Well, I like to listen to you now. #00:02:06-5#
- 2 Interviewer: Maybe as a first question. Or maybe I could say some numbers from X. Maybe you could then complete or correct them. I found numbers from 2016. Since you have made a turnover of 430 million. Employees 2300 and the year of foundation is X. #00:02:42-5#
- 3 Interviewee8: That is right. In X the family business was founded. By 2018, we will get close to 620 US dollars / 550 million euros annual revenue with 2600 employees. And currently represented in 220 countries. #00:03:21-8#
- 4 Interviewer: Ok. Then maybe to the financing instruments. Maybe you can tell a little bit about what financing instrument do you currently use? #00:03:31-4#
- 5 Interviewee8: So right now, we have three financing instruments roughly. So, we have a classic private equity financing. This private equity has increased capital through a capital injection. First, to create a certain foundation. This is quite classic that a private equity has acquired shares and from this side capital is going to the company. That is the first step. Actually, more that the shareholders distribute the shares. #00:04:19-1#
- 6 Interviewer: Is this equity or are these also mezzanine instruments? #00:04:23-4#
- 7 Interviewee8: That is both. At the moment we have equity capital. In the same breath, part of the purchase price was externally financed. So, we also have a credit line that has been provided in America by private equity in addition to the equity increase. Classically that private equity pledges a part of the company and then in addition to its equity increase, a substantial credit line is available. So that is the one variation or these are the two variants we have from owners. Then there is the second variant right now that we have various loan options. Since we have three variants. We have a kind of delay draw. That means we have a line of credit with a promised interest rate over a certain scope that we can call. Which of course can be very interesting in the low-interest phase. That in the long term, over two years, we have assured a credit line of no insignificant amount. There is a bank consortium behind it which can call up variable and pay back variable. And there is, in principle, I still say classic short-term loans that we use for disposition but actually only to an insignificant extent. That is one topic and then there are quite classic long-term forms of bank financing. These are the main topics. Although we also have a global framework for the syndicate of banks as well as a regional framework with different banks. #00:06:54-3#

8	Interviewer: Ok. Can you also say something about the volume that you have? What you said, the two years are fixed and you can access them anytime. #00:07:08-5#
9	Interviewee8: About the delay draw, that is to say about the interest rate hedge we have over several years, we can already count on a volume of more than 100 million euros. #00:07:24-8#
10	Interviewer: Ok. And what is currently the equity ratio? #00:07:31-1#
11	Interviewee8: The equity ratio is now nearly 50%. #00:07:36-9#
12	Interviewer: 50% ok. And perhaps you also use factoring for the operative business. #00:07:48-7#
13	Interviewee8: No, we do not use. We are lucky on the one hand, relatively speaking I say that we are in a high phase and morale has improved. We do not do anything like this right now. But it is basically an option that we have to think through. #00:08:12-3#
14	Interviewer: Ok. And if you were to finance a certain investment now, do you have a specific preference which funds to use first? #00:08:26-1#
15	Interviewee8: I say that we have a strong banking driven concept. Let us say you basically take what is the most attractive interest rate. It is a bit of a difference. There is still a second expression. This is the covenant of the individual financing agreements which of course defines a certain say of the banks from a certain level of financing. Of course, it is clear if you make long-term bank financing in the 100 million range that the banks first have a say in organisational or business changes in the company. Of course, you try to exclude this as a company as far as possible or I say times to keep away. And from this side, I say we try rather first to exhaust the loan, which would bring as little voice of the banks with it. This is quite classic for the interest rate hedging clause that I mentioned earlier, the delay draw. At the end of the day, the rights of the banks to speak are relatively low because they are only granted over a certain short period of time. Of course, if you take advantage of a long-term framework, banks are already trying very hard to intervene in operational controls. #00:10:12-7#
16	Interviewer: Ok. So, you would also finance a part with a relatively short-term credit line, even if the investment is a bit longer in order to reduce banks' covenants. #00:10:31-1#
17	Interviewee8: Exactly, if that is still in a tolerance range with regard to the interest charge. #00:10:41-8#
18	Interviewer: And would you try to firstly finance it internally through sales? #00:10:43-4#
19	Interviewee8: Yes, definitely. I say, you have to differentiate. There are many of the family or medium-sized companies in Germany. If one assumes, with the good economic utilisation at the moment. It looks like it may not grow that much in 2019 but at least it will remain stable. With full employment and well-filled order books, many companies have the chance to finance themselves through self-financing and sales. Clearly. That would have to be one, I say in the boom phase to make it strategically independent over either shareholders or banks. That is premise one. Of course, then just big strategic actions such as M&A activities simply cannot be financed by own funds. #00:11:51-2#

20	Interviewer: Ok. And then you would access loans. And then another like mezzanine capital? #00:12:00-8#
21	Interviewee8: Difficult. At the moment, let me tell you, once you commit yourself, speaking from an entrepreneurial point of view. If you decide to build on a banking syndicate that will be difficult. Then you are quite heavily involved in a credit structure because, of course, you have to sign hedging and settlement statements which you basically then, I say, limit very much other forms of financing. #00:12:34-9#
22	Interviewer: Ok. #00:12:37-0#
23	Interviewee8: That may be the disadvantage. To reflect that at the end of the day. The easy way is, of course, if you have a larger bank syndicate behind you and the financing is relatively easy in administration and settlement. It can be planned. It is good. But it will give away some flexibility over the period. #00:13:01-9#
24	Interviewer: Ok. How many house bank relationships do you currently have? #00:13:11-3#
25	Interviewee8: Right now, we have two banks primarily. We have a house bank with which we handle all operational issues. This also means the whole topic of treasury and cash worldwide. This is more the house bank character in that sense. Really everything operational. We have a lead bank in the bank syndicate that is not the house bank that coordinates all the funding for us. #00:13:50-0#
26	Interviewer: But do you work with them for a long time? #00:13:50-6#
27	Interviewee8: Yes, yes. So now almost two and a half years. #00:13:55-0#
28	Interviewer: Ok. Now my question would be. Do you see certain advantages and disadvantages in a house bank relationship? Let us start with the advantages. #00:14:09-5#
29	Interviewee8: So, the benefits are certainly, you have to distinguish something. A mid-sized business that is purely regionally organised may not have as many benefits from a house bank relationship. The advantage for me is rather, if you act internationally, the advantage is even greater that the whole treasury, my transparency, my money laundering controls, my control elements is all through a bank. I think there are a lot of synergy effects that the banks do the risk assessment of countries, etc. provides much more information and not only the transactions or the bank transaction. But also provides information content. From this side, I say, now and also from compliance side that is a big topic and a huge advantage. Another advantage is that most major banks today cover all major countries. From this side, it is not like ten or twenty years ago. But from this side you can cover that today with the banking network. Also, from the software side that is well feasible. Another advantage is that you have a corporate key account manager at the bank's side with whom you can often discuss meticulous topics which you can develop further. Another advantage in my opinion is that you basically do not have a financing framework that you cannot balance between the financing framework and the banking activity. That is always the problem, from my point of view, I had that before, that a house bank was also the financing partner. In my view, this has developed unfavourably because risk management on the financing side has paralysed operational development in the first place. And that is decoupled. For me personally it is an advantage that it is decoupled. Disadvantage is of course already, I say now, that you may not be the interesting business partner for a house bank, of course, the money is more likely to have a financial framework, as the day-to-day operations. A

	trade-off. You may not be that interesting partner but at the same time it makes perfect sense. #00:16:47-7#
30	Interviewer: Ok. You mean that the financing costs are not higher at a non-house bank? Because I mean, a house bank that does the operational business and there is a long relationship, of course, then you know each other. Maybe the risk can be assessed differently. That could be a reason that financing costs would be lower at a house bank? #00:17:11-3#
31	Interviewee8: Well, my experience is that the market for smaller volumes or for smaller companies, where the financing volumes are not particularly high, I agree with you. As a financing through a house bank can be equivalent or attractive in the financing conditions. The moment you go up in the 100 million range, they will be eliminated anyway. That was also the reason why we chose a bank consortium with a lead bank which has tendered the financing at the end. So, at the end we had five offers from five different world banks on the table. And then it is easy again because a traditional middle-class house bank system cannot keep up anymore. #00:18:08-6#
32	Interviewer: And I think you have no problems with availability now. So, to get loans from banks. This availability could be higher at a house bank. In that respect, do not you think it is critical that you are financing with the non-house bank? #00:18:31-3#
33	Interviewee8: No, that is why we deliberately chose a bank syndicate with a lead bank on top. Fully aware. Where we just staked two frames. Namely exactly with an interest rate hedging clause rather the medium-term financing option and a long-term financing, so that we can say that we first staked out a relatively large framework that will surely lead us through one, two, three years. Of course, you can negotiate that at some point. And I say, if the business grows and, in the end, we make a very classic acquisition, business acquisition on a larger scale, then you have to inform the bank syndicate anyway. Because of the covenants. At the same time, you can also, if that is so big that you need additional financing needs, you can discuss that relatively well with them. Because at the end of the day, they have already done a risk assessment for you and if you say, well the strategic direction says I need now 50 million more and have a reasonable business case, then that is relatively fast actually. I think that having the big banks as partners behind you is as good as having a traditional house bank. You might need to spend more time on contract law. That is very clear. #00:20:05-5#
34	Interviewer: Ok. That would be for example the next point meaning disadvantages. #00:20:11-8#
35	Interviewee8: Exactly. So, I think the covenant itself is a disadvantage in the big bank. Since the house bank certainly has an advantage. To compare it like this. Regarding the interest rate, the major bank is usually more attractive than the house bank. The house bank has the advantage that it is closer to the business, the understanding, the assessment than the big bank. The big bank has the advantage that it covers rather a strategically long-term framework which does the small or the house bank generally not do. The main difference at the end of the day is the contractual expenses and also the tax law. If you work with a bank syndicate, you have global tax issues, you have money laundering issues, you have an immense contractual effort to operate with. That is the disadvantage of a major bank. You do not have that at a house bank either. These are the essential topics at the end of the day. #00:21:31-7#
36	Interviewer: Ok. Then I would come to the next topics. To crowdlending and crowdinvesting. #00:21:37-3#

37	Interviewee8: Yes. #00:21:37-3#
38	Interviewer: My first question would be now. Have you ever heard of or even gained experience with it? #00:21:44-4#
39	Interviewee8: I had a little bit in my previous job. Currently not in the current task. #00:21:55-3#
40	Interviewer: Ok. Then I would just say something about it, if that is okay for you. #00:21:57-7#
41	Interviewee8: Yes, sure. #00:21:59-2#
42	Interviewer: There is crowdfunding. That is an umbrella term. This means that many investors provide money for a project or investing object. There is crowdfunding without financial return for the investors. This is donation based or another compensation exists. And then there is crowdfunding with financial return for the investors. And there you can differentiate between crowdlending and crowdinvesting. Crowdlending is a kind of loan. So, the investors give money and then a fixed term and a fixed interest rate is defined. And then the borrower gets it, can invest for his project, and then classically pays it back to investors in an annuity loan. Here it is also the case that in Germany these platforms do not have a banking license. But to be able to grant a loan in Germany you need a banking license. And finally, crowdlending would also run so that the money is given to a bank. The bank provides the loan to the borrower and then the bank in turn resells that back as a partial claim to the investors. And so, the bank would be out again. It would then only be a white label bank to use the banking license. Then there is crowdinvesting on the other side. That is where the investors get a return. However, these are mezzanine instruments. Especially subordinated loans plus an additional variable component such as participation in profits, turnover or company value increases. It can also be silent partnerships or profit participation rights. Both works so that a company, e.g. a medium-sized company created a funding. The funding is uploaded and then there are also different matching mechanisms, how they work together with the investors. A mechanism is e.g., the platform decides directly whether it finances it because the platform in turn has an agreement with institutional investors. Then there is a mechanism where it will be auctioned off. An interest rate is set by offers from investors. And the third is that the platform define an interest rate and then they search for investors. Now my question would be open, even if you have no experience with it. Suppose you want to make an investment. Under what circumstances would you make a request via a crowdlending platform? It is like some kind of loan. #00:24:58-3#
43	Interviewee8: I would say. So, my personal assessment now, because I already worked with some middle-class companies that had financing needs. I would make a difference. I think it is certainly an interesting alternative for larger start-up companies that are growing to get their money and not necessarily go the classic way of financing. Larger companies, I am more inclined to crowdinvesting because of their character rather. As a larger company, you have more of a problem working with so many parties. Larger companies usually seek one to five strategic partners. Two or three different strategic partners in the ownership structure. And then, in principle, they may have one or two funding partners who play an active or passive role at the end of the day. That comes a little bit closer to my personal experience as well. So, the classic private equity model. At the end of the day, PE (private equity) does nothing but rally a host of sub-investors, strategically or whatever, whether it is pension funds or whatever. In principle, they want to benefit exactly from a

guaranteed minimum return plus, of course, a participation in the corporate value increase. In my opinion, this has the greater charm for larger companies because it is easier to manage and more institutional. Crowdfunding I am more inclined which is certainly questionable for larger companies, whether it is the right alternative. #00:27:28-8#

44 Interviewer: Ok. Maybe very briefly. Of course, there are quite a lot of transactions behind the stage. But also, in crowdinvesting. Smaller investors can also invest there. But the company does not have to transfer every single transaction, but that is what makes the platform. There are also different forms. But the platform coordinates that. #00:28:05-5#

45 Interviewee8: Exactly. This is more convenient and a little more transparent on the corner. #00:28:08-7#

46 Interviewer: What disadvantages would you still see in crowdfunding? #00:28:18-9#

47 Interviewee8: So crowdfunding I do not really have much experience. I have to admit that. I think it is certainly more flexible and faster. Disadvantage may be for me. That is always the question of which platform I come at the end of the day. The disadvantage is of course always, if I have too many smaller lenders. But that is difficult. That always depends on the individual case. I am struggling to do a general assessment now and say one thing is better than the other. It probably depends on the life cycle and the needs of each company. #00:29:19-7#

48 Interviewer: Well I understood that you definitely see it as a disadvantage when there are many transactions. It is that they are not that much regulated. Such a platform does not have a banking license. The loan would run through the bank, but otherwise there are no other regulations. Do you think this is more of a disadvantage, or even an advantage because it involves less bureaucracy than, for example, with a bank? #00:29:49-2#

49 Interviewee8: So basically, as a growing company or as a younger company I see that as an advantage. To regulate less. And if I am already in a more mature stage and I say, as a mid-sized company I am planning to go IPO to take the next big step. Or at the end of the day, I want to sell my company in a timely manner, then one should rather, I can say, demonstrate more transparent and stable structures. That helps immensely in such a process. #00:30:35-3#

50 Interviewer: Maybe another point. If you create such a funding, it will be made available to investors on the platform. The investors see the funding. Do you see this as a positive marketing effect or would you rather see this as a negative marketing effect? #00:30:55-8#

51 Interviewee8: It depends on the industry, to be honest. In some industries, I say, very promising are a positive marketing effect. In traditional industries like engineering, etc., it may be viewed rather negatively. So, I think that I would not condemn it generally but because the industries are very different. If you are going into very innovative and development-intensive areas today, there is something positive about setting up the right funding. If today's corporate strategy is more in a classic mechanical engineering environment, that can be interpreted rather negatively. #00:31:54-3#

52 Interviewer: Because the image can be outward that the company now needs funding over such a crowd. This could be a negative image by implicitly saying that another financing, e.g. would not work through a bank. #00:32:11-0#

53	Interviewee8: Yes, exactly. That is the whole point. I believe from a certain company size, if you introduce yourself in Germany. You are a large corporation or SE or stock corporation and you would need to publish your figures semi-annually on a quarterly basis. Even as a large GmbH you have to do that. And so, everyone can read on the market how they are funded and structured. And if there are crowdfunded and not institutional, then it may be very negative. That is why I say, in my view, it is very dependent on the size of the company and also the industry. #00:32:58-6#
54	Interviewer: And then, if you upload the funding and then, let us say, in this case, you cannot find any investors, it will also send a bad signal to the other investors or the market that you have not received any funding. #00:33:19-0#
55	Interviewee8: Exactly. Yes. And that is one of the main reasons, I think. I am also in some founder forums. Sure, in the founders' forums are a lot of young start-ups who are dependent on quickly to get money. Not necessarily to deposit one hundred percent collateral. They like to go into crowdfunding. But if you go into more stable companies, the reluctance is already relatively large. Since the German market is still very conservative on the corner. #00:34:05-5#
56	Interviewer: What do you mean by that, that the market is still so conservative? #00:34:11-6#
57	Interviewee8: So, I think these are two topics. For one thing, I think Germany is still very traditional. So, if you look at Germany for the last 30 years. So, innovation, start-up, entrepreneurship which really came only the last 10-15 years. Since we are very late. The same is true, these forms of financing actually become common many years later than in Asia or America. And I think it is very traditional, according to the motto, either you finance yourself or you go to a bank. That was also drummed into our heads for decades. And then there was also the wave of the 90s and 2000s according to the motto, with the stock market crash and the economic crisis, I prefer to stay with a bank. I think that there is still a lot of traditional and high risk or I say risk assessment is still a big issue for many. And they often do not approach the subject emotionally. Because maybe they do not know the content. #00:35:39-4#
58	Interviewer: Would you also rate the risk high or low by creating such a funding and investors see the funding stealing the idea? #00:35:55-4#
59	Interviewee8: I do not think so, no. Personally, I do not believe that. It is a potential risk. But at some point, I have to take a risk. Let me tell you, if I publish the funding or if I publish it all, or if I will be at any innovation fairs or conferences and place myself in the market. The risk of followers or copying is always there. But I think you have to say rather, we go immediately out and we do it. #00:36:46-0#
60	Interviewer: So, what I took with me was that if you wanted to make an investment. You would first try it through internal, so the internal financing. Then you would rather try a classic bank. And if it does not work out on a bank, let us say, purely hypothetical, then you would rather access crowdinvesting, as I understand it, and not crowdlending. #00:37:21-1#
61	Interviewee8: Yes, that is right. #00:37:19-5#
62	Interviewer: Ok. Then maybe if you turn the whole thing around. Of course, it always takes investors on the other side that the borrowers get appropriate funds. Would that be interesting for you on the investor side? That you might spend money on a loan or perhaps on a mezzanine instrument? #00:37:43-1#

63	Interviewee8: Now for us personally no. For us it is more like that, I will say, I will go to the other side as an entrepreneur. Now I have some capital at my disposal, which I can invest. At the moment, it is clear that in many sectors, the market is currently consolidating, in many sectors of traditional industry. That means both customers and suppliers consolidate. Today, I believe it is very important to exploit the strength of the market in order to strategically position itself. And I believe many companies, as well as we are currently investing more in strategic acquisitions or strategic investments and less crowd topics. Once it is the strategic component to expand the market position. If not now, when then. And the money is relatively cheap or there is a low interest. So, I can easily finance another company with a high multiple effect. From the side we are more inclined to expand the market position. #00:39:09-5#
64	Interviewer: Ok, I understood that. So, you would rather from a strategic point of view, so that you acquire long-term companies or somehow strategically involved and not just temporarily on a crowdlending or crowdinvesting contract which then in 5 to 10 years in any case expires. #00:39:29-5#
65	Interviewee8: That is exactly how it is, yes. #00:39:30-0#
66	Interviewer: And wherever you have influence on the management or on the operational business. #00:39:38-6#
67	Interviewee8: Exactly. #00:39:41-0#
68	Interviewer: Then briefly on factoring. You said that you currently do not use factoring. But maybe even consider it. There are also factoring platforms. But there it is that most of it is based on individual accounts receivable. That means you can upload accounts receivable as a company and then finance them there via a factoring platform. There are also different models. Once it is auctioned off with other investors or even where the platforms finance that themselves. Again, with agreements with institutional investors. How would you use it? #00:40:32-2#
69	Interviewee8: I would not rule it out in principle, I have to say very clearly. At some point here, too, I will say. There are industries where factoring is not an issue at all. That is normally there. There are industries that are more traditional. If you go into the classic German mechanical engineering middle class today and you are doing factoring then you have a bad market reputation. This is also very dependent on the industry. If you go into the high technology today, factoring is normal and given at the end of the day. It just depends on the industry. So that is an issue. The other is, of course, how the economic situation is. And if it is good, I will say, you have little payment default and can even enforce relatively good payment terms in the market due to capacity shortages, then the need for factoring is not that big. #00:41:39-2#
70	Interviewer: Ok. So, for you, if factoring would come into question. There are different reasons. Once from a cash flow perspective, then perhaps from a procedural point of view. That one says, I often have the failure and what is behind, it is the account receivable dunning and collecting. What would be the point that you use factoring? Or for what reasons? #00:42:11-5#
71	Interviewee8: Difficult. Hard to answer, I have to say quite honestly. Or to answer fair. It just depends on the situation. Personally, as a CFO, I am often inclined to do factoring again and again in order to optimise my own cash situation. But this is purely the CFO glasses and my colleagues in the management are rather negative voted. They say that you cannot do that because at the end of the day we have the problem that it is seen as if you were bankrupt and you do not want to publish it. #00:43:14-2#

72	Interviewer: Ok. I understood that. But that means if you decide and you want to do factoring. You would also try it through a platform or not just through a traditional provider like banks or other factoring providers. #00:43:27-8#
73	Interviewee8: Yes, that is right. #00:43:35-2#
74	Interviewer: Well, then we are already at the end. I have two final questions. Is there something that I did not ask in this context but what you expected as a question? #00:43:51-4#
75	Interviewee8: No. I will say what keeps coming up for me. If you go a bit more into the start-up scene. That is the end of the day. There are also other financings. There are also operational funding elements. Such a kind of incubator. The real enterprise or high-finance business groups join forces and provide whole innovation part that bring both infrastructure and maybe some funding elements. This is something that you see relatively little in Germany at the moment or not yet. If you go to the Baltics today, there is a lot going on and given. That is also something where I say, I get to know this. Y has set up the centre of innovation and incubator at the airport in Munich, where it provides certain start-up companies with high-quality office space at relatively low prices and then evaluates whether they are entering into a strategic partnership with them or even longer term financed. That was only from a company point of view. What I see now is e.g. in the Baltics, to the university campus, really set up some sort of incubators or innovation miles, where really financial investors say, I am now investing a million. There is a committee. This is similar to crowdfunding at the end of the day. There is a committee that finances young innovative ideas and then secures shares of 10-20%. That is an issue that has charm, but, in my view, has not really arrived in Germany. #00:46:18-4#
76	Interviewer: Ok. Is there any other point or anything you would like to include in the context of the interview or the topic? #00:46:34-3#
77	Interviewee8: No, that is it. There is no more in my head now. #00:46:49-8#
78	Interviewer: Then thank you for taking the time. #00:46:48-3#
79	Interviewee8: Thank you, thank you very much. I wish you success for your work and I am curious what comes out. #00:46:54-7#
80	Interviewer: Yes, thank you. #00:46:59-0#
81	Interviewee8: All the best. #00:47:01-0#

Transcript: Interview 9

1	Interviewer: Maybe you could say something about your role first, and about your company? #00:00:24-1#
2	Interviewee9: I am here at X since 2005, the treasurer. So responsible for both the financing side, and so for the investment side. This also means short-term liquidity planning and long-term liquidity planning. These are the main things, e-banking and everything that goes with it. So, the normal tasks of the treasurer. We are very credit-driven. We have a lot of financing. And of all that, this is the main task. I brought you here the annual report from last year. Here you can see a bit of our key figures. It is relatively extensive. You could then look for what you need. So, we had 205 million in 2016, from 288 million. The business is always so we have a very different business both even and odd years. In even years more business takes place than in the odd years. That is why, as you can see, sales are even higher in even years. And in 2017, that was an extremely weak year because all 12 years pause events. That means, there comes the odd year and then the pause of some big events. And that means, 2017 was one of those extremely weak years. Now we are back on track. That was also the best. Despite this bad odd year, it was still the best odd year in the company's history. #00:02:13-4#
3	Interviewer: Ok. I also see your equity ratio is a bit below 50%. #00:02:20-4#
4	Interviewee9: Exactly. #00:02:20-4#
5	Interviewer: I also saw at the number of employees, that was just over 900 in 2016. #00:02:24-#
6	Interviewee9: Yes, that is roughly how it is. That is all in the brochure. #00:03:13-1#
7	Interviewer: Maybe you could say something about your current financing instruments? So, what instruments do you have? #00:03:23-5#
8	Interviewee9: So, we are financed by equity. Very classic. Y and Z are the main shareholders. And they also provide us with fresh equity at regular intervals. So capital increases. That was also in the last year and this year got a capital increase. So, they provide us with that. Of course, we also take profits and depreciation as financing instruments. Debt, we are financed only by bank loans. So, we do not have promissory notes yet, no other types of financing. So right now, it is just in quotes, bank loans. So, loans for long-term investments and current account for the short-term as working capital. So very slim so far. #00:04:21-8#
9	Interviewer: What is the volume of the long-term loans? #00:04:24-4#
10	Interviewee9: 100 million. It also varies. So, we paid back a lot but now come new construction measures. It will rise again peu á peu. That was always 150 million before. We had some redeemed now. So, it is fluctuating but it is going to rise again in the next few years. #00:04:40-5#
11	Interviewer: Ok. And the duration is about how long? #00:04:43-2#
12	Interviewee9: The term, we assume that we say in these halls 10-15 years. If we say a high-quality office building now, we would go into a longer financing. #00:04:55-2#
13	Interviewer: Ok. And can you also say something about the interest rate? #00:04:58-6#

14	Interviewee9: Only that we are very margin sensitive and get very good conditions. #00:05:08-9#
15	Interviewer: Ok. I mean, you also have an equity structure that maybe strengthens that, too. #00:05:13-7#
16	Interviewee9: Yes, and partner in the background. So, from there. We are very focused on the margin. And we give no collateral. #00:05:27-8#
17	Interviewer: Ok. So, if you are financing a loan, so the property is not given as collateral. #00:05:38-1#
18	Interviewee9: No. A site here is a special property and because the effort would be too high, maybe even sharing the terrain for these things would be far more expensive. That is, the credit is given based on our cash flow, our equity situation, and our business model. We always have relatively long-term economic planning, and we always stick to it, which is why it is more about cash flow than collateral. Because the exploitation of a hall with us is not that exciting. #00:06:05-6#
19	Interviewer: Yes, I understand that. And do you have covenants? #00:06:10-7#
20	Interviewee9: Negative only, that we do not make anybody better but not financial covenants. #00:06:17-7#
21	Interviewer: Ok. And otherwise just normal that you have to provide information regularly? #00:06:22-7#
22	Interviewee9: Yes, exactly the information and that the shareholders stay. But the information is necessary for the KWG anyway. So that is nothing out of the ordinary and the shareholder in the background persists. But they are no financial covenants now. #00:06:43-6#
23	Interviewer: And you do not have other instruments? So, mezzanine. #00:06:50-4#
24	Interviewee9: No, not mezzanine because it is just too expensive. And there is no need right now. We had thought about promissory notes. So, we will try it out because that is where the contract, the transaction is very simple. This is also offered by many institutions and the demand to sign the note is very large. That is why we will do that as the next step if we need something. #00:07:22-6#
25	Interviewer: Ok. In what volume about? #00:07:25-2#
26	Interviewee9: I think 50 million like that. That will be it, so it pays off. So that the fees and everything or that is profitable for the bank and that absorbs at all. #00:07:42-7#
27	Interviewer: Alright. And I also think factoring does not fit into your business model? #00:07:47-2#
28	Interviewee9: Factoring does not fit. We also do not need it because we have no accounts receivable in this sense. Yes, because if someone wants to come, he pays the fee. So, we have nothing there. #00:08:03-3#
29	Interviewer: Ok. Then I assume, if you had preferences for the financing instruments now. You have now carried out an equity increase. I think first you prefer the internal financing through the turnover. Then you have now carried out a capital increase. And then you would fall back on the classic bank loan. #00:08:22-0#
30	Interviewee9: That is right. And we had, too, clearly the classic bank loans. The bank refinances again via KfW or LfA. Or energy efficiency. The halls have a very high

	energy standard. Then there are also public loans, where you receive very cheap loans, which are then also very attractive from the interest rate. #00:08:47-9#
31	Interviewer: Do you also have one or more longer house bank relationships? #00:08:54-9#
32	Interviewee9: Yes. We have that for years. Where I say house bank, where to turn for every little thing because something does not fit. But strangely it has no funding. There we have one. And we can say three or four banks or five banks that are in favour of financing. Where there are two or one which cannot take so large volumes. That is why I would say four big and one with which we like to work together for smaller volumes. #00:09:34-2#
33	Interviewer: Ok. And have you had them longer? #00:09:36-5#
34	Interviewee9: Yes. #00:09:38-6#
35	Interviewer: How many years about? From ... to? #00:09:39-6#
36	Interviewee9: I say ten years or more. #00:09:46-3#
37	Interviewer: Ok. What advantages do you see through such a longer banking relationship? #00:09:54-2#
38	Interviewee9: Well of course there is an uncanny trust there. It is a quick fix if anything is up. So yes, there are the annual accounts. It is the whole history. There are the business plans, the new things. That is, if I have anything, yes, it is known here, how we do it. So, the construction projects. That they were on schedule. That they stayed in budget. That they are accepted and the utilisation is there. Therefore, this is really fast for us and the volume can be controlled. Because it is not always the case with us that it is said to be a small volume but it gets higher. And that is where we need efficient banks that can invest in larger amounts. So that is the advantage. Also, that one says then, ok as I had mentioned before. These public loans or these refinancing loans give the banks a better standing and better refinancing and then pass on the terms and conditions. #00:10:55-1#
39	Interviewer: Ok. So, if I can summarize it a bit. Once the trust, the personal contact, and already the long history. You know each other. Things are going faster, too. #00:11:11-0#
40	Interviewee9: So, it feels faster. But it is very fast. So, the decisions are very fast. #00:11:16-0#
41	Interviewer: The banks also have some expertise, such as a refinancing via the KfW. And so, you come to favourable conditions. Do you have the feeling that, even now, irrespective of the KfW loan, the conditions are also better than if you were to working with a new bank? #00:11:49-9#
42	Interviewee9: Working together with a bank, no, because we are a relatively attractive address. If new offers came, they would certainly be just as cheap. Our rating is indeed in the investment grade. So, that is why the difference is not that big anymore. Even if the evaluations come then, the PD (Probability Default). It is relatively the same. That means there is not much room left. They are about the same. #00:12:23-5#
43	Interviewer: And regarding the collateral. Because so far you did not have to give any collateral. If you have a new bank now. #00:12:32-7#

44	Interviewee9: Let us say that we do not provide a collateral. And that is known from the start and accepted that way. Otherwise we would not do it. I cannot treat the others more unfavourable. #00:12:46-4#
45	Interviewer: And do you also see any disadvantages in traditional financing through a bank? #00:12:55-8#
46	Interviewee9: I do not really have any disadvantages now because I think with such long credit periods. These are advantages for us. It could certainly be somewhere that one says, yes, one could talk about FinTechs or some sort of financing like a promissory note. You save up the credit lines. That is, if you would come from the volume of loan at the very top, maybe a promissory note or something like that which protects the credit line. That would perhaps be a disadvantage now, if you now very strong would expand or go very heavily into the debt purely. That one says, one could keep open the banking lines with it. That would be the disadvantage of the house banks. If you say, if you are looking for a different type of financing, such as the promissory note or even a FinTech and put it publicly, that I then lift up my line of credit and there is the advantage. So that is the only thing I could say if you take credit limits somewhere. #00:14:13-4#
47	Interviewer: Ok. I do not know if you have regular appointments with the banks. I assume. Do you see that as a disadvantage? So that there are physical or other kind of appointments? #00:14:23-6#
48	Interviewee9: If it is time consuming, then yes. But I do not really see it as a disadvantage. In general, once it is a rating meeting and that is initiated by me. And I think it is good to see the trend of the banks where it goes. As the changes of the rating are and sometimes to see one or the other comment. You get then at some institutions like a traffic light, that you see the value has now deteriorated or has become better. Or suggestions for it. I do not think that is annoying right now, I have to say that now. Sure, then things will come, just from the succession to the balance sheet. Yes, you have to look for something. But I think that is always in the frame. I want something for that. Well, I do not think so now, maybe it would be easier otherwise. But I do not see that as necessarily negative. #00:15:24-4#
49	Interviewer: Ok. Or maybe the availability. Maybe again as an advantage. If you have a long relationship now over ten years and the business would not go so well and the rating would not be so good either. Would you then feel that by a longer house bank relationship that knows your business model that would then rather give a loan? I mean, if you work with a new bank and the rating is not that good, it would probably be more difficult. But do you feel that there is a trust there? #00:15:58-2#
50	Interviewee9: Yes, the trust is there. That was also the first point I said. So, the trust and the personal relationship. Definitely. #00:16:06-2#
51	Interviewer: Then I would just like to come to the next question. I would like to ask you; if you know about crowdlending and crowdinvesting or if you could even gain experience with it? #00:16:18-8#
52	Interviewee9: So, it was something spontaneous. That was a financing. It would have been called a public bond in the direction, maybe for marketing reasons, etc. But the administrative effort would have been far too big. Then all the legal restrictions, the documentation requirement. And then the costs, not only for the bond itself but also those that would have to be paid as interest. So, it would have been absolutely unprofitable for us with the many small units. That is how it was done as a first step. So, these platforms in the private sector have arrived because there is a real estate

developer in X who is very active there. He also has some construction projects in the area and also has a very good reputation and creditworthiness so far. And it makes the interim financing on such FinTech platforms. Something has arrived in the private sector. So that one says, ok for the interim financing you get here still 4% or 5% interest which is already outside the market what you do with banks. Yes, and everyone must know the risk for themselves, but it is still a manageable deal somewhere. That is one thing. Business we have no experience. So now we had the first contact with Loanbox but not more. #00:18:10-3#

53 Interviewer: Then maybe I would tell you something, if it is right for you. #00:18:15-7#

54 Interviewee9: Gladly. #00:18:15-7#

55 Interviewer: So, there is crowdfunding. This is an umbrella term, so to speak that I collect money from many different investors and use it for a project. There are two differences. Once crowdfunding with returns for investors and once without. Without is so donation-based or another type of return, such as a product or right of first buying a product or whatever. And then there is crowdfunding with financial return for the investors. And then there is crowdlending and crowdinvesting. Crowdlending is a kind of loan. You have a fixed interest; you have a fixed term and there is also the process actually so that it still runs through a bank. In order to be able to grant a loan in Germany you need a banking license. In that case, the company creates a funding, uploads it and then investors can invest in the funding. When enough money has accumulated, then a bank that cooperates with the platform provides the loan and sells that in part to the investors. Then there is crowdinvesting. These are mezzanine instruments, i.e. subordinate loans, even silent partnerships or participation rights as well. There is no bank involved. Sometimes a payment service provider is switched in between who then has a separate account for the processing of payment transactions. But otherwise the contract is exactly between the parties. And there are mezzanine instruments. There are also various matching mechanisms as investors and borrowers come together. Crowdlending has three different mechanisms. Once you create a funding, the platform sets an interest rate and then investors can invest at that particular interest rate. Then there is another variant. Then you upload the funding and then the interest rate is set by an auction. And the third option is that the platform sets an interest rate and decides within 24 hours if the funding is funded or not. Because the platform, in turn, has a deal with institutional investors who will give the money when not enough people from the crowd finance the funding. That means the platform would agree, then the funding will be published. Then private investors can invest. If not enough money has been collected, it is collected through institutional investors. That is exactly the principle behind it. And now I would just ask openly. Suppose you would like to make an investment, under what circumstances would you want to make a request for crowdlending. #00:21:39-5#

56 Interviewee9: First only by the amount. The one says, well ok, the amount would be in the frame. #00:21:48-1#

57 Interviewer: Amount, you mean the volume? #00:21:48-9#

58 Interviewee9: Yes, the volume. Good the interest rate anyway. Then the question is, how big is the effort because that has to be relatively small-scale. Would that be in relation to how we need it. And I think you will not find anyone for a long-term financing. That would be more of a bridging loan. And then I come into the problem of overdraft. That the banks now have to pay this 0.4% negative interest. Of course, bank overdrafts go out with zero or a very small margin. So, for what I could take it,

that means I need at short notice, I need these huge volumes I probably cannot do with the effort and the conditions at the moment. But for that I would say that would be a good option now, if I would not have a huge sum, as working capital loans, as interim financing for the construction project, I would give it a try. But as I said at the moment by the conditions that is limited, I am sure. #00:22:59-0#

- 59 Interviewer: Ok, I understood. So not for long term anyway. And for the short-term not now, too, due to the low interest rate level and the banks with the negative interest, because that is naturally more comfortable for you, more comfortable. #00:23:20-1#
- 60 Interviewee9: Yes, rather spend the money to zero than pay 0.4. #00:23:21-1#
- 61 Interviewer: Okay. But let us just say, if the interest level were higher and let us say the interest rates for the loan are the same, would you possibly try it? #00:23:32-8#
- 62 Interviewee9: Yes, I would give it a try. Under the condition the project fits. I will say something for a maximum of two years or three years. Really something like energy efficiency when the lighting needs replacing. Really to make such a project, where one says, one has now everywhere LED lights or one has now a new heating system. Something like this with a short term for a specific project. I could imagine it then. #00:24:04-8#
- 63 Interviewer: And what would be the main driver for you to try? What would interest you most? #00:24:06-7#
- 64 Interviewee9: Well, that the funding is slightly diversified. #00:24:16-3#
- 65 Interviewer: Ok. And you have said just before, marketing effect. Would you see that as a marketing effect? #00:24:23-2#
- 66 Interviewee9: Yes, right. You can see that here in the neighbourhood as well. And because we have many events, you get, except as a local, you often cannot imagine, what our service includes. And of course, it would be nice if you say something that makes you public. I would then take it as this instrument. #00:24:46-1#
- 67 Interviewer: Ok. I mean, you have a good credit rating and a good rating now. Therefore, I think, you also assume that you get a financing there as well. But to what extent do you perhaps consider not getting any funding there, and that then it may be a negative external effect? Think of it as a risk. #00:25:07-8#
- 68 Interviewee9: No, I do not see the risk to get no financing at all and not in the next few years. Also, that I say, the protection of credit lines. The supply of credit lines is much more there, what I need. But now I say, we have to put it back because that costs the banks too. They have to hold equity. And if you know, in case I do not draw that line, then this is a business that is not fun for both and it should not be like that. And that is why I do not have any in the direction of saying the capital structure or diversifying the financing structure. That one says, that one has different times of the term and of the kind. That would be the only one. #00:25:55-4#
- 69 Interviewer: Ok. I think there probably will not be such a big risk here that the idea could be copied. Because there are other business models where you have a project that you want to finance. And that is a great business idea, you might think it is being copied. But I think you have no problem with that in that sense. This market is less regulated. It is then through a bank, but ultimately the platform has no license and there are not as many regulations, as Basel 3. Do you see this as an advantage or rather as a disadvantage? #00:26:41-7#

70	Interviewee9: Yes, for me, if I get the money, it is of course an advantage. If I am the investor from the other side. Invest money, if I had, I would not. #00:26:58-6#
71	Interviewer: Alright. #00:26:58-6#
72	Interviewee9: Well as a company. Because then yes to explain to the board of Supervisors, well we would otherwise have received no interest or would have to pay negative interest. Now we receive an interest, but we did not get the capital out of it. That does not work for us. So, I think now in our company, it would be the security. #00:27:25-1#
73	Interviewer: Ok. On the platforms I always need the investors on the one hand, otherwise there is no money for the borrowers. So, you would not see it for that? #00:27:37-1#
74	Interviewee9: Very limited. So that might be the company which is also communal, like energy supplier or something. Where to say the risk is not there or zero. There it would be a possibility, but now, no, I would not do it. #00:27:57-1#
75	Interviewer: Ok. Maybe you could say a bit more. You said, smaller volumes with shorter terms. What are those volumes? #00:28:09-6#
76	Interviewee9: So, I would say between 1-5 million. I would have to say yes, for what purpose it needs and then just could take something like energy efficiency. Because the others, the construction projects are much more expensive. I do not yet see these platforms for that. Maybe from tomorrow on. #00:28:32-0#
77	Interviewer: Yeah, it is actually as well that platforms like crowdlending are all limited to 2.5 million. The fundings currently. Because it is so, you would otherwise have to create a prospectus and that is complicated as a company. Since you have a lot of effort. Thus, the limit. The regulator says 2.5 million is the limit. Until then, you do not have to create a prospectus. That is why large companies or larger medium-sized companies ask for larger volumes. You can sometimes run two fundings at the same time, but that also varies depending on the platform. And would you consider that as an advantage that you would not have to go to the bank? So, you create a funding, upload it and everything is done online through the platform. #00:29:44-7#
78	Interviewee9: Supposedly, it is the way it is sold, absolutely easy. This is supposed to be very transparent and then you have directly the offer comparison. So that is so propagated. I can only say that from theory. You would not have any procurement costs etc. and it would be safe. So that sounds good. #00:30:12-1#
79	Interviewer: Ok. #00:30:13-8#
80	Interviewee9: But as I said from practice, I have no experience. #00:30:16-8#
81	Interviewer: Where did you get the information from? Or where the impression that it is easy? #00:30:28-6#
82	Interviewee9: Well, these are the FinTechs, where I once informed myself. Or the banks that have subsidiaries there and who are just making it public, how the whole thing works. And the impression is that everything is really simple, fast. #00:30:47-6#
83	Interviewer: Then you would definitely find it as comfortable if that is really easy online. #00:30:54-1#
84	Interviewee9: Yes, if that is as I said and you have a direct offer comparison. You come right on. There are no or very low purchase costs. #00:31:09-7#

85	Interviewer: Then perhaps on the subject of crowdfunding. So, with the kind of mezzanine instruments. Under what circumstances would you request such funding? #00:31:20-2#
86	Interviewee9: Okay, we do not need it for our equity ratio, plus or minus 50%, because it just gets too expensive then. And it no longer has the effect on balance sheet ratios, rating or whatever. Whether we have 50% or 50% plus x now does not matter. Therefore, this is not a possibility for us because it is too expensive, too small and too cumbersome. That does not pay off. #00:31:48-2#
87	Interviewer: Yes, ok. These mezzanine instruments have different components. Partially a fixed interest rate of e.g. one percent and then another component, such as turnover, profit or company value increase participation. But that would not be an option for you. #00:32:15-5#
88	Interviewee9: No. #00:32:17-9#
89	Interviewer: And have you gained experience with mezzanine instruments yet? #00:32:19-0#
90	Interviewee9: No. #00:32:20-9#
91	Interviewer: Never. #00:32:22-2#
92	Interviewee9: No. By the equity base, by the shareholders. It was only once considered as a financing alternative. Bayern Invest or something. There have been just inquiries. What sum, what term and what conditions. But that was absolutely uninteresting. #00:32:40-1#
93	Interviewer: Ok. You do not use factoring either. Does not make sense here. Then that it is. Do you have another question that I have not asked in this context but which you expected? #00:33:12-8#
94	Interviewee9: No. It would be a request only if you then have your result. Because it is interesting for me. The result, if you could give us an info in this context. I also think that is something that will increasingly gain in the future. I am pretty sure about it. And as I said, tomorrow I also get such an idea of the thing tailored to our company. Then maybe I can tell more, that I say of the theory, it is just as I imagined or how it works. #00:33:57-1#
95	Interviewer: Ok, yes, I like to do it. If I then have the results, I can gladly make something available to you. Do you have anything else that you might want to share with me in the context of the interview? #00:34:10-2#
96	Interviewee9: Yes, as I said, so that in the private sector that is pretty much now with us, so in the circle of friends. You are welcome to take this with you. That would be the interest component which is passed on over the company X. So, there it is handled briskly. There the runtime is often shorter than announced at the beginning. This is partly repaid earlier because the construction works quite well. In the private sector it is already running. Others have other things but I do not know that now. But in the business sector because we have such low margins, it is all too expensive right now. #00:35:13-9#
97	Interviewer: Yes, I understand too. I have looked at all the platforms that meet certain criteria and offer that for medium-sized companies. And interest rates on crowdlending are between 2.49% - 16.6%. #00:35:33-8#

98	Interviewee9: The risk premium has to be in there. That is also clear and that is fine too. #00:35:36-8#
99	Interviewer: And there are a few more points on the platforms I have looked at which indicates that the focus is more on small businesses. As the volume of 2.5 million, then the interest rates are currently relatively high for good companies with good credit rating too high. And crowdlending has now demanded personal guarantee. So, in companies like yours too and the managing directors are employees and you are not just owners like start-ups. #00:36:24-4#
100	Interviewee9: Start-ups, yes. #00:36:24-4#
101	Interviewer: For start-ups, this is still a structure that fits in there. Of course, personal guarantee is difficult for larger companies. The theory that I am currently looking at by Christensen is that it is precisely that one who enters the segment that is not of interest to the established companies. And as traditional bank you are more likely interested in larger companies, larger mid-sized companies, where the volume is higher. Because the fixed cost rate is the same and if the volume is higher, of course I make more money. And also with good credit rating. And the smaller ones, where the credit rating is worse, are not that much in the focus of traditional banks. The question is to what extent the companies improve here, adapt the business model and then enter this market. #00:37:24-2#
102	Interviewee9: I think that will certainly. Or if I say now, we would not be so real estate-based and we have machines or something as fixed assets, I think, then it makes sense again. Then it is a nice thing too. Then it is to finance, to a security transfer, it is manageable. This is a volume where I can imagine it. Then it is also competition for the banks. That is how I see it. Because it might be easier, even if I am already an established company. #00:37:58-9#
103	Interviewer: Ok. Otherwise, I already asked, as an investment site, you would not see it. #00:38:09-5#
104	Interviewee9: But this also has to do with our shareholder background that we are absolutely focused on security. So, if I also do an interest rate hedge or a derivative, I need the underlying deal. Therefore, there are very strict rules, and thus this would not fit in here. #00:38:33-4#
105	Interviewer: Ok. But if the equity structure were not so. #00:38:40-5#
106	Interviewee9: That is why I say, if that is private, so if you have money left then to say, ok that is a manageable amount, then we would get involved. But as I said, the regulation is too strict for us. And usually we have no balance left. We avoid this. #00:39:07-4#
107	Interviewer: Yes, ok. Very well. Do you have more topics? #00:39:13-4#
108	Interviewee9: No. #00:39:13-4#
109	Interviewer: Thank you. #00:39:13-4#

Transcript: Interview 10

1	Interviewer: Then I would say a few words to myself and to my research project. #00:00:08-0#
2	Interviewee10: Gladly. #00:00:08-0#
3	Interviewer: Well, after my studies, I worked at the head office of HVB. Was working there for almost five years. Among other things, as a senior consultant in the internal management consultancy and have managed various projects. After that I worked for Marc O'Polo in Stephanskirchen at the headquarter. So, I changed the industry a bit from the bank to the textile industry. I reported to the CFO there and was responsible for the project management office. I then started a dissertation in parallel. Right now, I am not working at Marc O'Polo anymore because I want to focus on my PhD. At least this year. Next year, I am going to take on a new challenge, but for half a year, I wanted to completely focus on the PhD. That is a PhD I am doing. This is a cooperation between Hamburg and Scotland. That is why I am often in Scotland and also in Hamburg but otherwise it is over distance. I live in Chiemgau, in Traunstein. In my research, I want to find out how financing FinTechs have a strategic impact on traditional SME banking in Germany. And there I have different steps. I first looked at all financing FinTechs, i.e., crowdlending, crowdinvesting and factoring platforms offering services to mid-sized companies. I analysed the business model. The second step is that I conduct interviews with CFOs or CEOs of SMEs. And the third step is by discussing the strategic model from Christensen, a Harvard professor. So, I want to find out how financing FinTechs are a disruptive innovation, in other words, how it could be a threat to traditional banking and could take business away. Exactly, these are the three steps. I prepared a questionnaire for the interview. I would just go through that. My first question would be whether you could first talk about your business and your role? #00:02:52-7#
4	Interviewee10: Exactly. There is also a question back. We are a group that consists of two areas. This is the logistics area and we have a second area with real estate. Now, my question is, should I refer the answers to the whole group or e.g. only on the logistics area? #00:03:19-2#
5	Interviewer: Actually, both areas would be interesting. So, if there are different opinions, if you say once from the logistics sector it would be like that and once from the real estate sector, then this is interesting for my investigation. #00:03:34-1#
6	Interviewee10: Ok. Then I will tell you about both. Today we have 900 employees in logistics and about 90 million euros in turnover. In X we decided to build up a second foothold. A real estate development and property management activity. This means that on the one hand, we cannot quite compare it to a real estate developer, we develop real estate and, according to our strategy, we keep these properties. Today, all that we have developed are in our ownership. But in future, the possibility should also be given to sell real estate even after-development. One reason, perhaps that is interesting for you, is also that basically the real estate sector should offer greater independence from financing companies, so that in case of changes in interest rates, credit ratings, etc., we are not dependent on banks that we retain our decision-making authority. We have, I say, a considerable part of the capital earned in the last 50 years invested in own real estate since X. The much larger company and the older company is the logistics sector. There we work in three divisions. This is the contract logistics. Here we carry out warehouse management. Maintain logistics centre. Perform assembly activities. This means that we complete and assemble, for example, exhaust systems for the automotive industry but also complete seat mechanisms for

the automotive industry. We handle logistics projects in contract logistics which means we basically play UPS or mail on our customer's campus. Pick up the goods there, distribute them, pick them up again after a certain refinement or change and redistribute or ship them. This is the area of contract logistics. The second business area or field of competence in logistics is transport logistics. That means we are not a forwarding company. That means we are hardly in the general cargo sector for a large number of customers. What do we do? We operate almost exclusively for the industrial and commercial sectors, where we take over complete vehicle fleets, where we exclusively carry out the entire distribution of their goods, and thus create a certain unique selling point and competitive advantages for our customers' customers. The third area is the digital logistics sector, where we develop the IT in our company in the field of logistics. That goes all the way to own software. We have two products. This is called motors warehouse and motors inplant. An engine inplant is a factory logistics software that gives our customers the opportunity to see where their goods are currently located. The customer can decide if he has an urgent package or a normal package. Of course, then there are different transport prices behind it. He sees how long the throughput times have lasted. Throughput times are defined. This software is also used by an external logistician. Whether the logistics company is late for delivery or not. And he has 100 percent traceability. That means he knows exactly who has moved the goods, when it has moved and where it has moved because there are partly moved goods moving in the six-digit range, sorry seven-digit range. Second software product, motors warehouse, where we developed our own software that developed warehousing solutions for our customers. Exactly, these are the three divisions in logistics. In real estate we have two areas. On the one hand, this is real estate development. In other words, we basically develop our properties by ourselves. We also have clear differentiation criteria here from our competitors. We want to develop highly innovative buildings in the outskirts of X. A project is already as I said from X, not so old. Since the old real estate are bundled. But the new ones have already been developed and the new ones are under the premise of developing highly innovative buildings that give our tenants a very special experience. Such a thing is usually only known in the big cities in the high-end locations. And we want to develop something like that in the outskirts of our big city. The second area is the administration of the real estate, so the tenant support, also there in the exclusive area. We now understand this as a kind of concierge service, indeed also where we take over changes and conversions for our customers and really look after the entire rental cycle of the customer from A to Z there. #00:11:43-6#

7	Interviewer: Ok. And that is both under a holding? #00:11:45-3#
8	Interviewee10: Both run under a holding. And the companies are completely self-contained in their own right and do not have any capital-law links. So, of course, about the holding company but no ties at the same level. #00:12:14-7#
9	Interviewer: Ok. Maybe you can still say something about the financing instruments? So, what financing instruments do you use, both for the logistics and the real estate sector? #00:12:22-4#
10	Interviewee10: Credit line, credit line for working capital reasons, classic fleet financing based on purchase and buy-back, leasing for the fleet and car sector, and classic real estate financing. #00:12:48-4#
11	Interviewer: Ok. Is that financed by a traditional bank? #00:12:54-1#
12	Interviewee10: This is financed by, I do not know what you define as traditional banks, so leasing is very common in the automotive industry. The leasing of material

	handling equipment, i.e. forklifts, etc. also runs mostly through the manufacturer. Often in the context of debt service contracts. And the other things are classic banking, i.e. credit line or working capital loans. #00:13:35-1#
13	Interviewer: Ok. So, you do not use mezzanine instruments? #00:13:39-5#
14	Interviewee10: No. #00:13:41-8#
15	Interviewer: And factoring? Do you use that? #00:13:44-7#
16	Interviewee10: No. #00:13:44-7#
17	Interviewer: No, ok. If you want to make an investment now, do you have certain preferences which forms of financing you will use first? #00:14:03-6#
18	Interviewee10: Yes. For real estate, classic real estate financing. For industrial trucks, floor service leasing. For cars, these are products offered by the automotive industry. But because quite interesting, that you cannot speak of manufacturer financing. We have here for example a leasing model from Daimler Benz Bank and our fleet are probably 80 percent BMW vehicles. So, they are brand independent today. And they finance this just brand independent. In the fleet sector, truck financing is classic manufacturer financing. Actually, from the respective manufacturers which also takes the vehicles after the usage time which usually takes an average of three years through a buy-back procedure and residual value guarantees. In the equipment area of vehicles, that is semi-trailers, trailers, swap bodies and swap bodies, classic bank financing is often used. Then on production sites where welding robots are used, these are classic working capital loans that are financed by banks. And our daily business is covered by a buffer over the range of variation across the entire company via credit lines. #00:15:55-5#
19	Interviewer: Ok. As I understand, you finance the real estate mainly through bank loans but at the same time the cash flow from the real estate on the other side it is supposed to be more independent of the banks. #00:16:12-2#
20	Interviewee10: Yes, so say, if today a bank would say, see 2007 banking crisis. What was the saying back then, those who need the loans do not get any and those who do not need it would get one. And if it would just be on the one hand on the market or in your own company, to have the independence to say, if the bank says, very difficult and only under very specific conditions, that we are always in the situation to finance certain volumes by ourselves. So basically, we want to be the second player inside, and sometimes there is the situation, it can happen inside the logistics too because we have an equity ratio of around 65 percent which means we also do financing and cross-check, say ask the bank and make offers. If the whole thing is difficult and uninteresting and the framework does not fit, that we say no that we finance from our own cash flow. But that is not exhausted to the last, so we say then, no in the case that really makes sense. The framework fits all, interest rate fits. We finance at the bank, protect our liquidity reserves, and thus have an escalation level which is just at the last end to the real estate sector, just to ensure independence of the banks. And a partnership cooperation. That should not sound negative now. We work very cooperatively with our banks, but it should stay with a partnership and not an intense dependency. #00:18:39-4#
21	Interviewer: Ok. Maybe again very briefly to the equity ratio of 65 percent. Was this only related to logistics or holding level? #00:18:54-8#
22	Interviewee10: That is at the logistics level. So, the exact numbers, I would have to look now. At holding level, it is a little bit higher. #00:19:12-0#

23	Interviewer: About? Maybe you just know it. #00:19:18-0#
24	Interviewee10: So, in the real estate sector is the debt ... The problem that is always with us. This is the third financing instrument or what I had not mentioned yet which is relatively important for us as service provider, are liabilities from delivery and services. And that makes up a very significant share. If you take away the trade accounts payable today, that does not mean that this is being actively managed, but these are the classic payment terms of 14 days and 4 weeks, but if you cover relatively high volume of service internally then at 80 million sales a relatively large position. If you count out the pure bank financing which will be in logistics at about ten percent and in the real estate sector currently between ten and twenty percent. #00:20:30-5#
25	Interviewer: Ok. I understood that. #00:20:32-1#
26	Interviewee10: And trade payables are the difference in logistics. So, they are somewhere at 25 percent and that is much smaller in the real estate sector. And this results in a slightly higher equity ratio on a holding basis. I guess that somewhere, I am not sure about 70 percent and if you expect the deliveries and services out, then it will be somewhere at 90 percent at the overall level. #00:21:08-6#
27	Interviewer: Ok. Then I understood that so far. And you already said that you work with banks. I assume that you have one or more long banking relationships. #00:21:23-5#
28	Interviewee10: Right. #00:21:23-5#
29	Interviewer: How many do you have there? #00:21:25-5#
30	Interviewee10: How many banks? #00:21:29-9#
31	Interviewer: Exactly how many banking relationships? #00:21:31-3#
32	Interviewee10: Four. #00:21:41-0#
33	Interviewer: Ok. And you have been working together with them for a longer period? #00:21:41-0#
34	Interviewee10: Right. #00:21:41-0#
35	Interviewer: Ok. And I have already heard, what you may see as a disadvantage is, when times become a bit more difficult, as in the crisis of 2007, when markets collapse a bit, and then banks are no longer willing to lend. #00:22:05-8#
36	Interviewee10: Right. #00:22:05-8#
37	Interviewer: Do you still see other disadvantages? #00:22:13-6#
38	Interviewee10: Good question. I have shown you five different financing instruments previously. All in all, we find out that the banks and I now list all five financing providers including manufacturers' banks, such as a Daimler bank or Mercedes bank, such as Linde, which makes its trucks via a full-service leasing. There we find a high degree of flexibility. Say, we would go to Deutsche Bank now and say we would like to finance a Mercedes-Benz truck via a buy-back, of course we have no flexibility. If we go to the Mercedes bank and say finance a Mercedes truck or a BMW car then we have there perfectly tailored solutions. Just as it is in real estate, where a Mercedes bank says, so I cannot do anything where we get perfectly tailor-made solutions from the banks. So, we created ourselves a portfolio with the banks in the market and by that, I mean not only cooperative banks, savings banks and the big banks, but by that

I mean also manufacturers banks etc. And I have to say definitely the disadvantages are very low because they have highly individualised solutions, when I envision the financing world we have just discussed, we have highly flexible solutions here, but as I said, difficult to exchange among each other. So, say Deutsche Bank and forklift financing is far from being as flexible as the manufacturer maybe makes it because the latter consider it as sale instrument. And also knows the problems of its customers. He knows how his own product works. That means he can buy it back again. He has his own instruments in the house of such products. And I say we are individually highly flexible with this portfolio. #00:25:26-8#

- 39 Interviewer: Ok. Do you have certain covenants from the banks where you have to comply with certain key figures? #00:25:35-9#
- 40 Interviewee10: Yes, we have. #00:25:37-2#
- 41 Interviewer: Do you see any disadvantages there? #00:25:43-8#
- 42 Interviewee10: Do I have to say, as you know, the banks have come under pressure. From what you analyse like FinTechs and the market framework factors since 2007. And that means the willingness of service providers massively increased. The same applies to covenants. There you are very cooperative with each other and we see no disadvantages. That is legitimate. Perhaps this is a special position for us because we are very keen to enter into a partnership relationship with our banks and not build up any major dependencies. In other words, we would really be seen as a customer and not as financing for a restructuring process. So, for example, it is true that we have called these four banks, was frankly not entirely correct. We have two in Germany, one in France, and one in Austria. But we have classic sales financing. Or no sales financing, we would almost be in factoring. In the field from the point of view of the manufacturer financier, e.g. with a Mercedes bank etc. or with Linde, for example in the forklift area, we have other financiers. Excuse me, now I have lost the thread. Your question was? #00:27:57-2#
- 43 Interviewer: Originally the question was with the covenants and the disadvantages. #00:28:02-0#
- 44 Interviewee10: So, as I said in the case of the covenants, this is very cooperative. As an example, the bank says, great we finance that in logistics. We have two house banks in Germany and one has been working with us for twenty years. We unfortunately had to change the second house bank because they merged and the classic lending business is no longer part of their core business. That was a smaller bank. We have changed and are now at Commerzbank. At the beginning there were the aspirations, yes, we finance everything. All assets are considered as collateral for the entire group and we said no. Every legal entity has to act independently for itself, and thus be independent. And it also has to be evaluated independently by the banks. If there is financing in the logistics sector today, then the logistics sector must be assessed independently regardless of the real estate. There was just the house bank, where we have no problems for twenty years. With the new one there was an explanation at the beginning what that means. We say we need it separately. If not, cooperation is difficult or even impossible. Then you analyse the company, then see the numbers and then ready for a very cooperative solution. So, no unpleasant things from where we say covenants, we have to deliver this and that. A huge bureaucratic effort, intertwining with private assets etc. No, that is all strictly separated. But it is definitely, I believe not in the collegial and nice attitude of the financiers but in the corporate policy and how we are positioned. #00:30:51-6#

45	Interviewer: Ok. And do you think that by a longer relationship, so if you have been working together with a bank for several years, then perhaps even with the covenants, perhaps also with collateral or with the interest rates, so with the terms are more accommodating? #00:31:09-8#
46	Interviewee10: Yes, definitely. The partnership relationship becomes better every year, from year to year and decade to decade. You get to know your customer. The scepticism, the model works is quite another. There is an example. We had production finance in France right at the start of the business. We opened a checking account with the French bank, discussed everything with it and then wanted to finance it. Then there was nothing at all. We then said that it is not a problem. We asked at our German bank. They said no problem, even in France, and immediately financed it. Today it looks like the French bank is approaching us and say when can we finance something for you again? We know you by now. We know your requirements. We can better respond. So, this relationship of trust and knowing the service portfolio and the product with us definitely leads to an increasingly easier collaboration. We are partial today, such as to settle a seven-digit financing within eight to nine days with Deutsche Bank. From the request to the payment. #00:32:54-4#
47	Interviewer: Ok. I understood that. As a longer house bank relationship, it is all faster. #00:33:04-1#
48	Interviewee10: Right. Because you have confidence in the company and give the statements more credibility. Also, of course, numbers can read better. The company understands better and knows how it works. #00:33:20-8#
49	Interviewer: How do you consider regular appointments with banks as negative? #00:33:28-7#
50	Interviewee10: On the contrary. We even ask them. At least once a year, there is a complete report on the company in person. And we report to the banks on a quarterly basis, so we are moving forward very proactively about our quarterly figures. And again, they are not required. Of course, one says meanwhile, if one knows that and one makes a new financing, one says yes and then one writes perhaps once again in covenants purely quarterly reporting. This is not a problem for us in partnership. We say that we do, of course, because we have and want it anyway. There they are informed on a quarterly basis and once a year in person about the annual report which is very detailed and lasts about two hours with the bank, reviewing the entire year and answering all the bank's questions. We do not want to pursue secrecy here because transparency leads us to build trust and I hope that it will be easier in difficult conditions. Not easier as with the good conditions but will be easier as in the poor conditions. #00:35:15-5#
51	Interviewer: Then I understood that so far. I would then move on to the next question. Do you know about crowdlending or crowdinvesting and maybe you have already gained experience with it? #00:35:19-7#
52	Interviewee10: I have no experience. I can roughly imagine what it is. What I know a bit but even just reading from the newspaper is crowdfunding, where basically about people who are interested in having a product from a business here are ready to provide capital. But details, how this is differentiated from crowdlending, I am not well informed. #00:36:18-2#
53	Interviewer: Ok. Then I would just say something about it, if that is okay for you. #00:36:20-4#

54	Interviewee10: Yes, with pleasure. #00:36:20-4#
55	Interviewer: So, there is crowdfunding, as you already said. That is an umbrella term. This means that I collect money from many different investors via a platform and use that for a project or something else. There are two differences now. Once with returns for investors and once without returns for investors. #00:36:44-8#
56	Interviewee10: Ok. Crowdlending without? #00:36:44-8#
57	Interviewer: No. #00:36:49-3#
58	Interviewee10: Ok. #00:36:49-3#
59	Interviewer: There is donation-based and reward-based crowdfunding. There is no return. This is really just a donation or that the investors get another kind of compensation, e.g. a right of first buy the product or the product itself in return. And then there is crowdfunding, where investors get a return. This is crowdlending and crowdinvesting. And the difference between the two is that crowdlending is like a normal loan. So, you have a fixed rate and a fixed term. And it is also true that the loan is actually granted through a bank because in Germany a loan may only be issued with a banking license. This works so that you as a medium-sized company can create a funding, upload them to the platform, there you will find investors and if enough investors have found or enough money, then a bank provides the loan and resells the claims in partial claims to the investors. Thus, the bank is then out again. That is crowdlending. Crowdinvesting has mezzanine instruments. There it is the same. You upload a funding and find investors. But then there is no bank in between but also directly the contracts between the investors and the borrower. These are subordinated loans and also silent partnerships or participation rights. And then, in part, you have a fixed interest rate plus a stake. So, an interest rate that depends on how the turnover, the profit developed or a company value increase participation. There are also many different variants. There is a lot of room for mezzanine instruments. You have not had any experience with it but I would like to ask you simply and openly, assuming you would like to make an investment, under what circumstances would you make a request for a crowdlending platform? #00:39:16-7#
60	Interviewee10: So, from what I have heard from you and what I have read so far, I would not start any. Under no circumstances. Why? Everything that has to do with investing, maybe we are also an untypical company. Maybe also an information. Also, what we do in logistics and what we do in the real estate sector, we always try to establish ourselves like a manufactory. In other words, we want to provide exceptional services for our customers which are very individual and very strongly tailored to the customer. Which bring added value to the customers. And the more complex a task, the better it is. That is my basic principle. For us, it is not about fast growth in the area that we say we want to become a global player in logistics and provide complete connectivity worldwide that we can offer to our customers. Often these are also complex services. Therefore, because they are offered globally but, in the microcosm, if you look at the service as such it is relatively easy. So, let me give you an example. Transporting a package today via a freight forwarding company is relatively easy. Transporting, packaging, and final unpackaging a large aircraft component is very complex and much more demanding. If you were not very happy with a forwarding in the classical sense. That means we will be very much in the future, what do I call that now. That is where the era changes. When I say, manageable growth. Since 2008 we have grown about 145 percent. We have somewhere between 5 and 15 percent growth per year. That may be less at the present time, but we always have continuous growth. Our aim is not to become a

global player, as we have said, where very high financial investments are necessary at one go. Since I could imagine such a thing very well, that companies with a high capital demand, get faster money. As I said, with the intention of an absolute specialist, our growth is good but not huge. But that is not our goal. Of course, we want to make good money with it but not in the sense of multiplier effects that we say a fifty percent growth is more important to us than a ten percent. So, in comparison, as we had eight to ten percent. We want to grow. We want to develop further. Intensively even further develop what concerns digitisation. But this extremely fast growth is not part of the strategy and is not necessary for our service. But on the contrary. In the event of extreme growth, we find that we cannot maintain quality levels. And that is why I say this is on the one hand, as described just unattractive. But we also have certain advantages. That means we have a decent return on sales, if you exclude this year, the past ten years, the return on turnover was about twice as high as the market level. And as I said, there are just two strategies that you can drive. That one says, maybe a slightly lower return on sales but with mass to reach the absolute number. And for us, rather, the return on turnover is very important to achieve a high return on turnover for our industry. The same applies to the real estate market. We are about 30, 40 percent above market level but through normal growth, let us call it, we do not have this high funding requirement, and now it comes along with our philosophy of not being influenced from other stakeholders, except our customers, to let talk into our business models. We are very self-confident and want to run our business model and not represent the interests of others. That is why it would not make sense for us. Above all, if I understand it correctly, crowdfunding, where you can participate in profits or even equity. Then you simply have more stakeholders involved in the conversation, change strategies and we have a very clear view of innovation. So, our slogan in logistics is passion for solutions. Our vision has important core issues such as competence, commitment, and commitment of our customers and our performance. #00:46:17-3#

- 61 Interviewer: Ok. So, regarding mezzanine instruments, I have looked at all the platforms, no has a say in such a way but an information right and the participation is already dependent on the profit and turnover. Of course, depending on the contractual arrangement, they are entitled to it. #00:46:33-4#
- 62 Interviewee10: That and the second topic is of course the crisis vulnerability. This means that something is changing in the market again, something is not going so fast and it needs a follow-up financing and no one is available anymore. These are all things on the one, yes now I have to be careful when I say a conservative company. So, we are highly innovative and extremely creative in our processes. Offer things where our competitors would find it difficult to offer such services. So, I give you an example. In our industry is the reliability, the delivery reliability may be, if you have the process well under control at 90-95 percent. Our customer complains when we reach 99.75 percent. We are close to 100 percent and every deviation is seen as undesirable by us and the customer. #00:47:57-4#
- 63 Interviewer: Ok. #00:47:58-9#
- 64 Interviewee10: When Amazon comes on Amazon Prime Now an hour later or 10 minutes later, it does not interest you but when in the automotive industry comes something 10 minutes late you have a huge problem. #00:48:13-6#
- 65 Interviewer: Ok. I understood that. You see it already, in terms of crowdfunding and crowdlending, riskier, because you are not like a house bank, where you have a longer relationship, when the times become more difficult it can be problem with follow-up financing for crowdfunding and crowdlending. #00:48:40-2#

66	Interviewee10: Right. Because that depends very much on market trends. But as I said, I take not only the new financial instruments in the boat but also the banks. That is why I say the stable setup in-house, to make the own way as independent as possible from third parties. To take those but in a balanced portfolio, so basically a risk diversification. #00:49:11-8#
67	Interviewer: And would you perhaps also see it as a positive marketing effect? You upload something there and then different investors see it. Can be perceived positively but also negatively. #00:49:34-0#
68	Interviewee10: So that our customers find it positive when using modern financial instruments? Or did I misunderstand you there? #00:49:44-5#
69	Interviewer: Exactly. So, if you are using a modern financial instrument, such as crowdfunding and crowdlending. And also, if you can present your company there? #00:50:00-3#
70	Interviewee10: I did not understand it. So, it does not really matter to our customers how we finance ourselves. Of course, you are also interested in whether we are solidly positioned. So, I have to disclose company data but nowadays subject to disclosure. As an advertising instrument I now see it positively neither towards employee in the sense of an employer branding nor towards customers. So, I would say in the IT field, as I said we have our own IT company which develops the logistics products, I could imagine, because the very IT technology people and such FinTechs are often based on IT technologies that could be of interest to the employees in terms of employer branding. #00:51:31-1#
71	Interviewer: Ok. The crowdlending or crowdfunding process is completely online. So, you do not need physical meetings, you can do it all through the website or the platform. Maybe another question in this regard. There are less regulations. Crowdlending involves a bank but the platform does not have a license. Crowdfunding also not. Would you rather shy away from that, that it is less regulated than the banks? #00:52:10-1#
72	Interviewee10: Yes, because that is exactly how I see the vulnerability of such a system. I think the whole thing will have an important future but we saw completely unregulated markets in 2007 which is what the Americans, who are a big proponent of unregulated markets, can mean in the context of globalisation. From that point of view, I am generally for unregulated markets which may in a way work for a while and also serve the advancement. But as it is so typical, human and his needs come into play, as well as aspirations for more and then come here and there the negative effects. Definitely that makes me sceptical. But again, I am not a classically conservative person. That means we are very open to new technologies. We also see that positively. This is part of a development but also scepticism is part of it. That is, such instruments will increasingly gain acceptance if certain people are not ripped off. Because crowdfunding is also the domain of small investors. We saw the whole thing in the US housing market. Small investors are being pulled over the table as well. In other words, things like that work well for a while and are good for certain companies that handle it properly. But there are other companies that do not handle it properly and then smaller people are being ripped off again. And that requires in my opinion then in the course of time a reasonable and manageable regulation. So, no regulatory anger, as we like to have in Germany. #00:54:58-9#
73	Interviewer: Ok. You said that you would not currently making a financing request, e.g. at crowdlending. I assume that if the interest rate is the same. But if conditions

	on a crowdlending platform were even better, would you possibly try it? #00:55:21-5#
74	Interviewee10: To be honest, this is a somewhat difficult question. Currently no, because today we have financing in the working capital which is less than two percent. The topic will certainly be interesting when the interest level generally rises and there may also be some distortions. So, the distortions do not have to come from these areas but exactly the other way around. The classic market has distortions and then you react with such FinTechs against it, for example. And then, of course, it can be much more interesting if you get funding here for eight percent and get there for five percent. But there you have to look behind the scenes regarding influence, profit sharing, and reliability in the sense of follow-up financing. Because I also know that banks today, etc. think in the future according to the motto, if the customer gets no follow-up financing on a FinTech for some reason, he comes back to us to the bank. So, I rely very much on a partnership and trustful cooperation. But that can also work through such a system. I mean credit card systems, PayPal or ApplePay are FinTech instruments and ultimately there is a trust. So, as I said, it is a little bit difficult to answer this question. I would like to see that in detail. I would not say, no in general. #00:57:38-0#
75	Interviewer: Ok. And would you rather tend to crowdlending or crowdinvesting? The second would be with the mezzanine instruments. #00:57:47-5#
76	Interviewee10: Crowdlending. #00:57:56-5#
77	Interviewer: Crowdlending. Like a bank loan, so to speak. #00:57:59-4#
78	Interviewee10: Right. #00:57:59-4#
79	Interviewer: Because of what background? #00:58:06-8#
80	Interviewee10: Yes, because we would like to keep our results of our business activities in our house as long as we are able. We know what we can and, as said, no compulsion to participate in it. What is the reason? That is certainly selfish. But then you better take it yourself. Or it is an arithmetic example that I say pay out profit sharing is cheaper on the bottom line. That is a calculating example. #00:59:00-4#
81	Interviewer: If you use a mezzanine instrument. You have a fixed rate of one percent and the rest is linked to turnover. Then you would be less risky in that regard. If you say the investor only gets another interest rate of five percent when the turnover threshold is reached. #00:59:23-3#
82	Interviewee10: Yes, although there are business models or projects in both directions as turnover is increasing, return is declining. Or turnover increase and as it should be classical in the doctrine, should also increase the return. Can also go in the other direction in practice. So, on the subject of risk-free is the question of whether a revenue-oriented interest is actually risk-free. #00:59:57-8#
83	Interviewer: Of course, you are right. So, you can also link it to the EBIT. That would also be a possibility that it may involve even less risk. #01:00:06-8#
84	Interviewee10: Yeah, but that is a calculation where you say you make a comparison between the two methods. How much does the interest rate get better if you link it to the EBIT and does its scenarios? That is a purely mathematical decision. #01:00:36-6#
85	Interviewer: You do not use factoring. Maybe shortly as info for you. Maybe you are interested too. There are also factoring platforms. There you can register and upload

individual claims and refinance them, let us say. Either through investors, where you can then auction it or other ways, where then the platform is financed in a collaboration with institutional investors. I mean you do not use factoring now but maybe you would want to use factoring, could you imagine that? #01:01:27-5#

86 Interviewee10: I can basically imagine it. I always have a question mark behind the systematics. If I upload something like that and sell my account receivable. Who knows the account receivable better than the entrepreneur himself? So, as I said there is a certain amount of scepticism to find any people. Sounds good now. Account receivable as a fundamental issue is done. But why do you do that? I do not see the meaning behind it. To get the money from the customer or to get the money from the investor? It can only be another way of financing that the customer says, I will only pay you after three months. #01:02:38-5#

87 Interviewer: It is a cash flow story, so you are more likely to get the money. But it can also be a risk issue. You are kicking it off, but that is the point that I actually know my client better than an investor. So, if I give it up, then maybe it is already a sign. #01:02:59-#

88 Interviewee10: Then I am looking for a stupid who takes it from me. #01:02:59-6#

89 Interviewer: Yes, but for some companies it is already a cash flow issue to get cash. To maybe increase the equity ratio. #01:03:07-7#

90 Interviewee10: Yes, right. #01:03:07-7#

91 Interviewer: Well, if you make a balance sheet reduction and reduce liabilities, you could increase the equity ratio. And it may also be a procedural issue. I have already heard of companies who then said that they do not carry out the entire receivables management and that is why they do it purely procedurally. Because the effort behind it seems to be relatively high for some companies. #01:03:33-9#

92 Interviewee10: Yes, but there is the question again. If it gets high, then the investor has an interest in it because then he has the job. Because if he has to warn the customers regularly, so that he gets his money. Ultimately, someday you have to pay. That may not be very innovative, what I am saying now. Maybe I am too easy to knit. This is a huge complication and one is always the stupid at the table. And in general, but ok that is perhaps more like father of thought. In Germany, the payment terms are neat, but if I look at Italy or Spain then that is a disaster. But if I look at the national economies, that is kind of analogous. So, say, to finance on payment terms, I think it is nonsense economically, and thus a lot of bumbling is driven. And as an entrepreneur, I also see something as a responsibility to do everything, at least what is in my power, not to give it a boost. That is why I am a bit critical of such things because there is always a stupid guy sitting around the table somewhere. That is also the scepticism of the banks because the banks have noticed the write-downs, they were the stupid at the table. And then you are always critical. At some point crowdfunding or factoring, ok crowdfunding may be a bad example, but in factoring, the framework must fit really well for it to work. But if it fits, I ask myself again where is the meaningfulness. If I want to risk-off, then I am looking for someone who takes my risk. And maybe a little stupid. I may still see default risks in terms of insurance. That would be more sensible. That said the average default risk is three percent. Of course, this is reduced by a large portfolio. This distributes the risk to everyone. I find that very sensible. But in general, I do not want to risk-off that I cannot get my money and look for a fool who takes it and pack it nicely, so I am more of a critic. #01:06:37-4#

93	Interviewer: Ok. Where then, a return is there, which is not so low. The investor does not take the risk without a corresponding return. #01:06:48-7#
94	Interviewee10: Right. And then, from our point of view, it does not make economic sense again. Then we are back in the model where you grow extremely fast and where you have huge capital needs that you cannot cover yourself anymore. We were in the happy situation, if that was so happy, I do not know, but it has been developed strategically by ourselves. #01:07:19-1#
95	Interviewer: Ok. Then I got that. Perhaps you have another question that I did not ask in the interview but which you might have expected? #01:07:33-6#
96	Interviewee10: Now I am thinking about financing, where we have difficulties. No, I cannot think of anything right now. #01:08:00-3#
97	Interviewer: Or maybe you have something else in this context, what you might to provide me? #01:08:11-2#
98	Interviewee10: We briefly mentioned that in the context just before, that instruments always work, if, as I said earlier, if there are no idiots at the table. We saw this in the real estate crisis in 2007 and 2008. There were stupid looking for. That was then the end customer who then had the securitised papers in his rent or wherever. Therefore, it is very important for such issues as regulation to build mechanisms that are not based on stakeholder ignorance, thereby generating an advantage for individuals or competitive advantage for individuals. So, you really have to see that all stakeholders in the process are treated equally fair. And by that, I mean above all in the sense of crowdfunding. The people who do not deal with it so intensely. Otherwise, such systems will be quickly regulated or disappear from the market. These things always look like very short legs. As I said in 2007 and 2008, we saw it. But the black swan always comes from somewhere else. And the next crisis will come back somewhere else. But for all things that you develop, that sounds very moral now, but in my opinion, it is not moral but in terms of the longevity of a business model, it is important that all stakeholders and those who have too little knowledge. And that are there participate, such as if somebody gives his money and does not even know what he is giving it, but only for a great story, but does not know the details, that care is taken that this cannot be abused. Otherwise, such instruments will not work in the long run. And those who assert themselves will always prevail because they treat all stakeholders fairly, and then these instruments will be successful too. #01:11:31-1#
99	Interviewer: Yes. That is interesting as you say. I see it that way too. You have a two-side business model here. You have the investors on one side. The borrowers on the other side. And there you need each other. It is true that most platforms have changed it so they set the interest rate by themselves. Before that, it was even more that the interest rate has been set through auctions or investors have set interest rates. They said ok, see the risk like that and I want this interest rate. And that does not seem to have gone so well because they have changed it, so the platforms will do a credit check and then fix the interest rate. Because investors seem to have never received adequate interest for the corresponding risk. I also think that in the long term, there is definitely an adequate risk assessment required that the investors who give their money in the long term get their money back and also a corresponding return depending on the risk. #01:12:42-7#
100	Interviewee10: Exactly. But as I said the interest rate does not regulate everything. Because if you only get an interest rate in the short term. They have a high interest rate. You get eight percent but your claim still fails. You only get something from him

if he runs for twenty years. But if he only runs for three years then you have a problem. That is why it is always important. But such instruments are then taken for many other things. I say only commercial loans is such a good example that have fallen into huge disrepute. Where synthetic papers have been designed. That is exactly what you have to pay attention to. The basis for such financial instruments is mostly good and honest and very intelligent. But that is then taken to extremes with derivatives or with synthetic themes, where one suddenly reaches the point that one no longer has an overview. Not transparent, only believes. And then they also suffer, and that is the bad thing about it, the honest dealings among them because the methods are fundamentally a good idea in principle. Just as in currency hedging, etc., meaningful structures are behind it. It is problematic if then as I said there is no business behind it. But only the speculation. And, of course, anyone who develops something like that has to be careful that he or she, especially if he does not want to be regulated by the state, supplies the framework factors for it and that his model cannot possibly be abused. And human, simply tends to, I am just saying Cum Cum or Cum Ex deals. This is amazing how creative people are. And that is where the FinTech industry should be concerned, for the good will of leaving out certain market participants. #01:15:40-9#

101 Interviewer: Maybe you are still interested. I just do not always say that during the interview because that might influence opinion. It is a bit regulated. The current limits are also at crowdlending as well as crowdinvesting at 2.5 million euros. So, it may not be interesting for larger medium-sized companies. #01:16:11-4#

102 Interviewee10: Yes, but you still have to see one thing. I see this not only from an entrepreneurial point of view, but also from the point of view of the one who gives the money. Right, I will say, if the little man suddenly can take part in something like that. Human is a player. One more, the other less. But somewhere the game seems to be very important to humans. And then you have people with a level of education who approach this topic with a certain naivety and then gamble away 5000 or 10000 euros which is enormously important to them. And looking at all the stakeholders in the whole is important. As I have gotten so with smaller investors can participate in something and so you have to look. Do you know the following problem arises from the fact that systems get into disrepute? Currency transactions, if they were not so established, would increasingly fall into disrepute or have fallen into disrepute because they have just been abused. And then it is just that then suddenly the little man does not spend any more on such a thing and certain systems may not work anymore, even though the basic idea was very good. And that is why you have to, I say, in the case of the knowledge does not have protection mechanisms for the dispose. And there just 5000 or 10000 Euro can make a lot. #01:18:02-4#

103 Interviewer: Yes, that is the limit. The legislature has also determined there to a maximum of 10000 euros for individual investors who are not professional. #01:18:16-2#

104 Interviewee10: Yes, but then you see it is regulated. #01:18:19-8#

105 Interviewer: Yes. #01:18:21-1#

106 Interviewee10: Often rightly so. #01:18:24-2#

107 Interviewer: Yes. Well, then I would like to thank you in any case. I really appreciate that you took your time. #01:18:37-2#

108 Interviewee10: Gladly. #01:18:38-3#

109 Interviewer: I would then send you the transcript for your information. #01:18:53-3#

110 Interviewee10: Very much. Good luck then. See you. #01:18:59-2#

111 Interviewer: Thank you. Bye. #01:19:00-0#